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Title of Thesis: Towards an understanding of the vision-mission statements of higher education institutions in Zimbabwe and the extent they foster a technological society for sustainable development

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Dedication with extreme affection and gratitude to

My wife Jenipher Mnkandla and the children,

The late Professor Lindela R Ndlovu,

And

The Higher Education fraternity

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Abstract

The objective of the Thesis was to investigate the professional rationale for the adoption of the vision-mission philosophy by higher education institutions in Zimbabwe. The visions of excellence, technopreneurship, premier, world class seek to stimulate the market model to foster the technological society objective for sustainable development. The study built the footprints conceptual model based on the statements of 34 tertiary institutions. In driving the mandates, the brands seek to promote the constituency servicing, governance, quality assurance, comportment, and evaluation footprints in line with opportunities for continuous improvement to match globally renowned examples. Specifically, the statements inspire the infinite manpower pool of thinkers, builders, improvers and providers to meet demand for infinite production, consumption, growth and development. However, the evidence was inconclusive to justify the statements as the default policy yardstick inducing sufficient strength, motivation and fit in the delivery of the mandates, failing which they are the classical model of intellectual dependency, leading to the principles and attitudes of copy-write. Steered through the post-positivist paradigm and using the mixed method, drawing data from document sources, a diversity survey and interviews, the study interrogated the multiple-case study of four science and technology universities. Enumerative content analysis and the QCA program were used in the presentation and analysis of the data by method of verification per footprint. From the empirical evidence, the philosophy was justified as an all-purpose purpose vehicle inspiring the core deliverables of excellence, research-innovation-entrepreneurship, the leadership-committee system, moral efficiency, and sustainable development. The predominant average mean rating of 2.4 meant that the statements were rated 'normal/adequate' rather than the aspired 'exceptional/world class', revealing evidentialism the missing link at adoption. The study accepted the proposition that the statements fail to inject the aspired technopreneurial-sustainable development revolution in sync with the potential learning product. Instead, they emerge as a realistic novelty and fantasy. The rigid macro-bureaucracy, coupled with diverse stakeholder interests, resource constraints and external pressures emasculated the academic-administrative infrastructures jeopardising the aspired continuous improvement and reducing the statements to a *fait accompli*. The constrained sustainable development escalated the challenges of technological imperialism and the vicious cycle of *Homo simplex*. The study recommended a personalised mission model anchored on a practice-theory curriculum fusion to fashion out much more functional skills befitting local conditions.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

4Es	-	entrepreneurship, employability, equal opportunity & employment creation
AAU	-	Association of African Universities
AAUP	-	American Association of University Professors
AHEEA	-	African Higher Education Excellence Award
AI	-	artificial intelligence
BD	-	bureaucracy dictionary
BRICS	-	Brazil, Russia, India, China and South Africa
B TTC	-	Belvedere Technical Teachers' College
BUSE	-	Bindura University of Science Education
CISDL	-	Centre for International Sustainable Development Law
CUT	-	Chinhoyi University of Technology
CUZ	-	Catholic University of Zimbabwe
EIAA	-	empowerment, indigenisation, affirmative action
EI	-	emotional intelligence
E/W	-	exceptional/world class
F/C	-	functional/commendable
GDP	-	Gross Domestic Product
GEEP	-	Graduate Entrepreneurship and Employment Programme
GMO	-	genetically modified organism
GRIN	-	genetics, robotics, information technology, and nanotechnology
GRI	-	Global Reporting Initiative
GSIF	-	Global Sustainability Initiative Framework
HDI	-	Human Development Index
HIT	-	Harare Institute of Technology
HIV and AIDS-	-	Human Immunodeficiency Virus & Acquired ImmunoDeficiency Syndrome
HR	-	human resources
IDS	-	Institute of Development Studies, NUST
I/S	-	inadequate/substandard

ICT	-	Information communication technology
IIAG	-	Ibrahim Index of African Governance
ISCED	-	International Standard Classification of Education
ISO	-	International Organization for Standardization
LPA	-	Lagos Plan of Action
LPI	-	Legatum Prosperity Index
MDGs	-	Millennium Development Goals
MHTE&STD-		Ministry of Higher & Tertiary Education & Science & Technology Development
MoU/A	-	Memorandum of Understanding/Agreement
MPI	-	Multidimensional Poverty Index
N/A	-	normal/adequate
NEPAD	-	New Economic Partnership for Africa's Development
NGO	-	non-governmental organization
NUST	-	National University of Science and Technology
OECD	-	Organization of Economic Cooperation and Development
P-AIUG	-	Pan-African Institute of University Governance
PESTEL	-	political, economic, social, technological, environmental, legal
PhD	-	Doctor of Philosophy
QA	-	quality assurance
QCA	-	Qualitative Comparative Analysis program
QCHE	-	Quality Code for Higher Education
REI	-	right to education index
RPI	-	research performance index
SADC	-	Southern African Development Community
SARUA	-	Southern African Regional Universities Association
SDGs	-	Sustainable Development Goals
SIRDC	-	Scientific and Industrial Research and Development Centre
SMEs	-	Small and Medium Enterprises
SRC	-	Student Representative Council
STEM	-	science, technology, engineering and mathematics education
SUAS	-	Senior University Administrators Association

SUV	-	Sport Utility Vehicle
SWOT	-	strength, weaknesses, opportunities and threats
THES	-	Times Higher Education Supplement
UCE	-	United College of Education
U/J	-	unable to judge
UKZN	-	University of KwaZulu-Natal
UNESCO	-	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
UK	-	United Kingdom
USA	-	United States of America
UZ	-	University of Zimbabwe
VAE	-	value-added-per-employee
VU	-	Vincennes University
VUCA	-	volatility/vulnerability, uncertainty, change and ambiguity
WTO	-	World Trade Organization
Zim-Asset	-	Zimbabwe Agenda for Sustainable Socio-economic Transformation
ZIMCHE	-	Zimbabwe Council for Higher Education
Zimind	-	<i>Zimbabwe Independent</i>

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CHAPTER I

1.0 BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

1.1 Introduction

In line with the rationale of the knowledge aim: to interrogate the professional role of the philosophy of vision-mission statements among higher education institutions, this chapter configures the interconnecting and interrelating multi-structural elements shaping the problem, and whether by engaging the philosophy the institutions emerge pragmatically stronger academically, administratively, technologically and environmentally. First, among the controversial encounters to trigger interest was the vision-mission debate at the 2011 National University of Science and Technology (NUST) Senior University Administrators Seminar (SUAS 8) followed by events at the 'Manager's Toolkit' seminar also in 2011, and at the 2012 Lupane State University stakeholder breakfast meeting.

The Manager's Toolkit seminar asked whether or not, as participants, we were working in tandem with the NUST vision-mission. I remarked that, having grown up under waves of sanctions, I was not sure what 'a world class centre of excellence' was or looks like. No immediate answer was offered, while at the Lupane State University stakeholder meeting so much controversy surrounded the wording of the statements, raising the *Cartesian doubt* (to mean a philosophical doubt) whether the higher education vision-mission statements do rally and propel the institutional momentum for development excellence.

From its origin in the business world the philosophy of vision-mission statements now inundates the higher education markets. Vision-mission posters decorate rooms and corridors and, like sentries, greet entry into offices, with numerous publications and websites inundated with the same: a definitive assurance of a dynamic game changer. Accordingly, as the study enzymes will illustrate, the different chapters elaborate the multiple facets of the philosophy's political economy and its bearing on the potential learning product or, as now popularly defined, human resources development, ultimately to promote a scholarly intellection of the knowledge aim which is an understanding of the role the statements play in fostering the technological society for sustainable development.

1.2 The problem context and setting

Throughout history philosophy has played a pivotal role in the idealization and rationalisation of human endeavours (Russell, 1996). Biblical, political, scientific and economic personalities, both past and present, adored as men and women of great vision-mission, ushered enormous changes in the lives of people. Today, through globalization's transnational networks, coupled with developments in business and public choice research and strategic studies, the vision-mission philosophy plays a dominant role across socio-economic enterprises to drive mandates (MacMillan, 2011; Morpew and Hartley, 2006). Through reductionism, it has converted into a market and non-market commodity advancing the causes and interests of corporations, government, organizations, and most markedly, the complex role higher education plays in the development agenda.

Morpew and Hartley (2006) sum up the strength of the philosophy as lying in its 'all-purpose purpose' role. In other words, the institutions use the vision statements to confront the vast world of education, among many determinants, to cover all eventualities, in particular to harness and manage the curriculum to grow the infinite human resources (HR) while stemming leakages; to position themselves in the institutional ladder; for competition for survival; and to fervently get to grips with the corporate mandates to address the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) and consolidate constituency aspirations. On closer look, the statements express the philosophy of continuous improvement, or 'perpetual betterising' (Chulu, 2016a), or the technology exponential syndrome which is the very essence and goal of the mandates. The contention then is why they do not take advantage of the 'one' statement approach to visualize the mandates as the alternative of three statements renders misrepresentations and contradictions more likely with unintended and unexpected outcomes and consequences?

Hence, events constantly trigger reservations and scepticism whether, from the valued and privileged visions, and against all expectations, the philosophy definitively guarantees the much-acclaimed economies of scale subtended to the potential learning product – the simultaneous match between supply and demand, as well as product massification and quality assurance. Otherwise, as Morpew and Hartley (2006, p.456) state, it is part of the long list of "unanalysed broad and ambiguous abstractions...clothed with threadbare anecdotal evidence" which work on paper, but with massive arcane opportunity costs

(Kwaramba, 2016). In answer to the 'so what' question, the study interrogated the vision-mission phenomenon through science and technology education to find out whether its adoption was sustainable, enabling the institutions to duly realise the dream to foster the technological society, the backbone to sustainable development.

We illustrate the academic character of the philosophy that underpins vision statements by a few relevant examples drawn from universities in different countries. The mission of Vincennes University (VU), Indiana, USA, states that it "is the State's premier transfer institution and leader in innovative career programming. The VU community ensures educational access, delivers proven associate and baccalaureate programs, and offers cultural opportunities and community services in a diverse, student-centred, collegiate environment." In turn, the vision "is a premier learning institution, widely recognised for leadership in innovation and delivery of successful educational experiences. A broad range of program offerings and a commitment to superior service ensure the University's role as an important link in Indiana's economic and cultural vitality." The tacit values indicate that "VU is a diverse community whose members all share responsibility for supporting the University mission and are respected for their contributions" (vinu.edu).

The mission of the University of Illinois (USA) states that it "will transform lives and serve society by educating, creating knowledge and putting knowledge to work on a large scale and with excellence." In turn, the vision "is to create a brilliant future for the University of Illinois in which the students, faculty and staff thrive and the citizens of Illinois, the nation and the world benefit, a future in which the University of Illinois is the recognised leader among public research universities in: teaching, scholarship and service; engagement and public service; economic development; arts and culture; global reach; and athletics." In terms of guiding values, the university will: "aim high; strive to control our destiny; be accountable for our actions and exercise responsible stewardship; be inclusive, treat each other with dignity and respect and promote citizenship; value excellence, quality and service; foster innovation and creativity" (uillinois.edu).

Closer to Zimbabwe, the vision of the University of Zambia states that it "will be a leader in the provision of higher education in the region, celebrated for providing comprehensive and rigorous teaching-learning, research and scholarly programmes that are responsive to the

needs of the individual, industry and society.” In turn, the mission recognises the university as “a centre of excellence in higher education for individuals, industry and society through the provision of quality education, research and scholarly programmes for strategic human resource development, in order to promote national and regional development, through relevant and appropriate partnerships.” “Excellence, equity, accountability, transparency, social justice, integrity, search for new knowledge, inclusiveness, critical thinking, academic freedom, innovativeness, service” constitute the values (unza.zm).

The vision of the University of Lagos (UniLag.), Nigeria, is “to be a top-class institution for the pursuit of excellence in knowledge through learning and research as well as in character and service to humanity.” In turn, the mission is “to provide a conducive teaching, learning, research and development environment where staff and students can interact and compete effectively with their counterparts both nationally and internationally in terms of intellectual competence and zeal to add value to the world” (unilag.edu.ng). The values are subsumed in the two statements.

Last, the vision of the University of KwaZulu-Natal (UKZN), South Africa, is “to be the premier university of African scholarship”, while the mission is to be “a truly South African university that is academically excellent, innovative in research, critically engaged with society and demographically representative, redressing the disadvantages, inequities and imbalances of the past.” The seven statements of ‘GOALS’ centred on African-led Globalization, Responsible Community Engagement, Pre-Eminence in Research, Excellence in Teaching and Learning, Institution of Choice for Learners / Staff, and Efficient and Effective Management sum up the seven elaborate statements of ‘Principles and Core Values’ covering numerous bread and butter issues (UKZN, 2013). The same goes for the University of Cape Town (UCT) in its elaborate ‘Statement of Values’ which is symbolic of ‘vision, mission, and core values’ statements.

Logically, the Zimbabwean higher education institutions have absorbed the global experience with arrays of vision-mission-core values statements forming the basis of their internal and external communications to market their mandates, relationships, futures and all. For example, the vision of the Bindura University of Science Education (BUSE, 2013) states that

the University is “to be a hub of knowledge and a beacon of excellence in teaching, research and extension services.” Correspondingly, the mission is

to contribute to the advancement of knowledge and its practical application to social, economic, technological, cultural and scientific challenges; to produce innovative, highly acclaimed graduates equipped with research, entrepreneurial, social and technical skills for the benefit of the nation and the international community.

The core values embrace ‘Knowledge acquisition and sharing, teamwork and diversity, integrity, student centeredness, innovation and excellence, commitment and discipline.’

Likewise, the vision of the Westgate Industrial Training College (WITC, 2012), Bulawayo, is “preferred and leader in high quality skills up-grading and training through innovative use of existing and new knowledge, attitudes and resources.” Its mission is “to provide systematic skills upgrading and increased utilization of technologies in order to improve industrial productivity and the quality of life in the society”, with the accompanying *Goal* “to produce a highly skilled workforce capable of effecting economic and social transformation and ensure global competitiveness.” Last, the values of ‘patriotism, integrity/*Ubuntu/hunhu*, professionalism, entrepreneurship, honesty and industry’ cement the socio-scientific thrust.

The cited examples are not empty rhetoric or merely futuristic glossaries. The institutions define a new operational format matching global market standards. As a sign of the times, this is the way to go to ‘operationalize objectives’ to buoy ‘goal-directed employee behaviour’ to enhance the ‘performance of the institution’ leading to its continued ‘survival’ (Smith, Heady, Carson, and Carson, 2002, p.2). In other words, over and above endogenous improvements, the philosophy represents a new illumination on immediate and long term wishes and strategies with regard to practical professionalism, profit generation, reputation and other market niches.

The fervour is to attain the potential learning product, i.e., to culture the *educated class* in order to access the *technological infinite*: that is, infinite growth, infinite production, infinite development, and infinite consumption (Verhelst, 1990); or, according to McCarthy (2012) to attain autarky, or competitiveness (Campbell, 2006). Beneath the surface is the inescapable power of globalization with the statements providing the tool-kit to manage the multiple activities: clusters of curricula, social values, beliefs, meanings, experiences, patterns of behaviour, transnational networks and governance technologies the social actors exhibit and

interact with in their daily activities for successful delivery of the best products, goods and services at the disposal of business, the nation and beyond (BUSE, 2013; MacMillan, 2011).

Accordingly, the vision statements are treasured as policy blueprints *par excellence* so much that the distinction between pluralism and prescription has become blurred. Whether Western or African, the differences are relatively marginal – more lexical than substantial. In the process, they have not only superseded the traditional philosophy of the Golden Rule and institutional credos, but are even antecedent to goals, aims and objectives. As a result, the higher education market has caught the wave, with common catchy brags like ‘proudly BUSE; genuine graduates apply to... NUST or UCT’; I did it with Harvard, MIT or Oxford.’ The Thesis sought to answer the question whether such catchy axioms are a reflection of stereotyping or of supply matching demand, or both. Indeed, given the difficulties involved in realizing the technological infinite, the vision-mission statements seem to fulfil the role of critical milestones to rally and propel the institutional momentum forward for sustainable development. All this is buoyed by the philosophical thought which recognises that while education does not develop the world, humanity cannot transform without it (Cross, Mungandi, and Rouhani, 2000).

In favour of the adoption, Opiyo-Newa (2010) argues that popular understanding is that the philosophy addresses the basic need for definition and direction, and in particular issues of purpose, values and ethical principles by which the members aspire to work and live. Buttressing the viewpoint, Darbi (2012) also argues that, far from the fly-on-the-wall, there is tremendous scope behind the wall hangings going beyond prestige and the desire to be felt or heard. From this angle, the philosophy is a key component of the leaderships’ policy arsenal, providing the jet propulsion fuel guiding and directing workforce and client behaviour in line with the expected standard. Given such a powerful role, it is mandatory for the institutions to have the statements to clarify purpose/aspirations (Education World, 2011; MacMillan, 2011; Zimbabwe Council for Higher Education (ZIMCHE), 2011).

Overall, the statements embody issues of ontology, epistemology, methodology, and normative ideals. Ontologically they indicate how the reality is perceived, constructed and concretized; epistemologically, they sum up the philosophy of the curriculum or forms and fields of knowledge and belief systems, defined in terms of the best understanding of the

human motor at that point in time; methodologically, they sum up the beliefs on the best way to acquire the knowledge; and normatively, they act as a guide to deliberation, discourse and decision making. All this is within the context of practical reasoning and assurance of standards, notwithstanding the dilemma of broad, ambiguous, unanalysed abstractions and the arcane knowledge that they tend to hide (Clark, 1986). Accordingly, the philosophy's enthusiasts find it unprofessional, if not outright illegal to operate without the statements (MacMillan, 2011; ZIMCHE, 2011). The institutions use the vision-mission statements in the perspective of a paradigm to define the commonality of 'purpose' that binds the academic community to work together, figuring out where and how professionally, academically, technically or spiritually it is going and it will get there. Indeed, the language approximates the 'wanted state' and the drive to be where 'we want to be'. Operationally, it is fitting then that they constantly question their strategies and the wisdom to maintain, adopt and adapt particular philosophies, worldviews, practices and experiences.

1.3 Crystallization of the problem

Typical of social enquiry, a problem was created where none existed before to find out whether, institutionally, the vision-mission statements live up to the pronounced hype, particularly, in line with trends, technocapitalism. It was then deemed that rather than *the* default policy yardstick driving the delivery of higher education mandates, as a self-indulgent theory, the philosophy misdirected the institutions exposing them to uncertainty and other pathologies. That they would unleash prosperity is more an exciting myth that ignores tough challenges related to chasing perfection, reflecting the tendency by policy experts to think alike even in the face of contradictory evidence.

Also, as the Pan-African Institute of University Governance (P-AIUG) (2010, para.3) contends, the statements are but part of the continuing trends of the 'classical models of cooperation in which the "expertise" of the North are transmitted to "addressee" and "consignee" of the South, ingraining the principles and attitudes of copy-write.' This is intimating that Africa's institutions have copied and seem destined to carbon-copy global trends as if it is their ultimate right, hence, continuing the tragic irony and fallacy of the false dawns reigning supreme across the continental scapes (Kagame, 2015; Ngwenya, 2016; Nyathi, 2015; Sharara, 2015).

Evidence from the literature further supported the events that triggered the *Cartesian doubt* – being reference to the wilful suspension of all interpretations of experience that are not absolutely certain: used as a method of deriving, by elimination of such uncertainties, axioms upon which to base theories. In a study on the institutionalization of visions and missions, a position echoed by Opiyo-Newa (2010) and Travis (2015), Darbi (2012) found out that the general assumption is always that once in place, everybody understands, believes and knows what to do with them. As he notes, nothing could be farther from the truth. According to Hill (1999, p.4), always allowed to lapse are the common drivers of institutional inefficiency, namely, the “rational ignorance effect, the special interest effect, and the short-sightedness effect” which raises potential for both forced and unforced errors. The combined impact is the adoption of policies with either elusive or concentrated benefits as a result of poorly informed inputs compounding transparency issues, with costs either hard to identify or clearly outweighing the benefits. Hence, given market pathologies, especially self-interest and the dilemma of “individual rationality to sabotage the efforts to reach group objectives” (Hill, p.2), what Chulu (2016b) calls ‘invisible entrepreneuring’, numerous primary and secondary tensions marked by differences, misunderstandings, confusions and corruption regarding the interpretation and application of the statements abound and, with them, lip-service, doubt, angst, resistance or defiance.

Furthermore, critics from the left and sceptics argue that there is more to the statements than meets the eye. If anything, the philosophy is part of the Western agenda to refine and domesticate capitalism natively (Broch-Due and Schroeder, 2002; Tandon, 2008). Nwagbara (2011) argues strongly that the social constructions are symptomatic of the theory of ‘Learned Helplessness’ with the institutions trapped under the ‘jackboot of colonialism’, barely addressing endogenous perspectives, but happily romanticising with capitalism and staying buoyant from narratives and initiatives set by others to boost their egos. To Sachs (1992) they amount to ‘fascination with myopia’. Pipim (2013) uses the analogy of the ‘Elephant-in-the-zoo’ and the ‘African chicken’ to describe the challenge. In the former, the people are unable to free themselves even when the technology to do so exists. In the latter, they pretend to be eagles flying high in the sky when the truth is that, like chickens, they can barely fly. In the process, the societies continue to incur open and hidden social costs escalating poverty, vulnerability and other VUCA variables.

On the other hand, to Mabhena (2016b) such philosophies are further evidence of the ‘Western university in Africa’, while to Morley (2003, p.6) the construct reflects the “moral panic over standards, the massification of higher education, wealth creation, and globalization” gripping higher education, generating socio-political discomfort in the South. Ironically, as Nyathi (2014) argues, the ensuing Aristotelian education only churns out ‘technically incompetent intellectuals’ well-schooled in Western accepted norms or creeds but with limited capacity for alternative local, socio-economic interventions or work ethos. Marking their level of busyness are routine maintenance functions: teaching, marking, basic research, consumption, prescribing, conferences, ceremonies, contacts and the like, and rarely, technological making or building. Legendary is the way the vision-mission pronouncements, as Olivier (2010, p.33) posits, simply contradict the reality on the ground. Indeed, how plausible is such

progress (*premier, world class, knowledge hub*) in an underdeveloped environment where economic conditions are generally backward, where rampant poverty prevails, where communication infrastructures are primitive and even non-existent, where educational standards are lagging, where good governance and the rule of law least prevail, where primary needs still dominate, where cooperative interdependence is limited, and where societal security is under constant threat? (*Emphasis added*)

Pipim (2013) refers to the growing volumes of ‘*nillionnaires*’ and ‘*illionnaires*’: being reference to the poverty stricken and sick African masses, respectively – summing up the skewed *Homo simplex-Homo technologicus* relationship. Hence, Sharara (2015) asks the rhetorical question ‘When will Africa’s time come?’ while Dube (2014) argues that, for Zimbabwe, achieving the MDGs by 2015 remains a pipe dream. Many indicators are either marginally stable or are declining, given the rising levels of ‘insecurity and vulnerability’ in health, employment, education, poverty, and government (Ngwenya, 2016). Weak aggregate demand complements the challenges of de-industrialization and deflation as the bulk of the workforce earns far below the Total Consumption Poverty Line. Meanwhile, the institutional products are caught in the plight of deepening psychosocial stressors with the people and institutions physically, mentally, emotionally and environmentally exhausted (Burgis, 2015; Chulu, 2014; Dube, 2014; Mkanachi, 2013).

The challenges bespeak the trials and tribulations besetting the potential learning product. The philosophy paints a picture of a social expediency or gimmick for public appearance and internal gratification rather than a highly-spirited force for development excellence. Viewed

this way, it is a non-event, essentially nothing more than a myth or fad of little substance and import, simply pushing the dictates of globalization and the agendas of politicians and transnational companies (Morley, 2003). Given the available evidence, the study sought to show that the socio-environmental challenges facing the people of Zimbabwe cannot be camouflaged by ‘world class centre, global hub, premier, leading institution’ and other catchy forms of corporatism the vision-mission statements espouse. Hence, the study contends that the popularity of the philosophy lacks scholarly rationalisation of its pulse, only to resemble an *ipse dixit* or dogmatic statement whose legitimacy rests on the authority of its pronouncers.

Morphew and Hartley (2006) and Darbi (2012) also discuss criticisms that describe the vision-mission statements as a *fait accompli*. This is to say they are a mere formality, signifying the desire to be felt and heard and nothing more. While in some instances audits accompanied pre-adoption, in others it is the hand of outright official fiat or imposition, yet the institutions pride themselves as strong advocates of ‘evidentialism’. Like rarefied air, the statements are of little substance and import in the daily business of the institutions. Yet, in today’s policy environment, formulations that lack constructed support and validated proofs face problems of acceptance which renders them controversial cauldrons of unproductive tensions and conflicts (Darbi, 2012; Kapfunde, 1997).

The impetus to this work was driven by these observations: to undertake a philosophical exposé of the inner dynamics of vision-mission statements to fulfil, in line with Scott and Usher (1999, p.26) “the goal of research which is that of providing interpretations of human actions and social practices within the context of meaningful, culturally specific arrangements.” Consequently, within the context of the field responses, the study was able to verify and build events and phenomena in order to better understand the social dimensions of the vision-mission statements. It is hoped that the intellection will enhance levels of pragmatism to generate edifying curriculum-management renaissances.

1.4 Definitions and conceptual perspectives

In line with Muzondo (2012), there are a few studies (if any) in Zimbabwe which have been carried out to determine whether the vision-mission statements accurately depict and portray the organisational reality. Taking after the global hype for rapid emancipation of the human motor, the institutions have imported the same approach without as much as conduct pilot

studies to ascertain its efficacy. In the process, they have inadvertently incurred known and unknown social costs likely to escalate people misery rather than abate it. The study, therefore, identified and set out to fill this gap.

To open up the discourse and explore the philosophy further, it was critical to briefly highlight the dimensions of some key protocols. First is the status of the topic or knowledge aim, followed by the concepts of higher education, vision, mission and values and, last, the technological society. Other variables are defined as the text progresses.

Basing on Jansen's (2010) analysis of the knowledge aim, the 'understanding' constituted the material object and, therefore, the study stimulus; the vision-mission-values statements, the formal object or focal target; and the fostering of the technological society for sustainable development, the empirical domain. Higher education in general and the science and technology universities in particular constituted the social space to be investigated. Through rigorous aggregation-disaggregation the material object stimulated scrutiny of the formal object and its epistemological and ontological inroads the higher education social spaces. Constantly analysing and synthesising, moving back and forth, smoothing and unravelling, it subjected it to creative inquiry, studious rationalisation and holistic integration to crystalize its role to stimulate the empirical domain to address the need and demand for the technological infinite against the vagaries of the false infinite. Notionally, both the material object and the formal object articulated 'diversity' as the dominant concept which influenced the breakdown of the norms of thought of the problem which was largely qualitative since diversity is a qualitative rather than a quantitative paradigm.

The term construct was employed to denote the philosophical and ideological dimensions of the vision-mission statements and their potential to interrogate institutional processes and practices. As a usual appendage 'statement' expresses their everydayness whereas construct underscores capacity for scientific and philosophical rigour with a strong connection to research theory and policy formulation. Hence, in addition to reducing the pedestrian undertones associated with 'statements', construct is used to connote the collective voice of the statements so that a more empirical rationale is achieved. Moving forward, the terms are used in the most appropriate contexts.

According to the International Standard Classification of Education (ISCED – 2011) higher education refers to post-secondary/high school education (levels 6, 7 and 8) offered by universities and colleges, and in professional and specialised schools like the law, theology, medicine, business and technology institutes at the end of which a degree, diploma, or certificate is awarded for the prescribed course of study. It is called Further Education when it extends to post-graduate studies like Masters and Doctoral degrees. The education comprises specialised fields with a strong, complex, professionally-inclined, theoretical component leading to the high calibre qualifications recognised throughout the world representing multiple expertise and skills that employers and entrepreneurs require (ISCED, 2011). It is undergoing tumultuous change which leaves it groping for visions and missions as *the* instruments to progress forward.

Each of vision, mission and values has several meanings. Kantabutra and Avery (2010) argue, though, that the definition of vision cannot be standardized as it is an *in-situ* reflection according to the leadership's conceptualization of things. However, generally, vision shares meaning with terms like dream, fantasy, perception, idealistic and fortitude. Hence Darbi (2012, p.96) defines it as "meant to evoke powerful and compelling mental images of the desired future state of the organization." Like business, higher education conceptualises the vision as the aspirational description of the better state it would like to be both the mid- and long-term future, hence, serving and providing a clear guide for choosing a specific mission or courses of action. Institutionally, it is described by robust terms like premier, world/top class, excellence, leading college or university, with special focus on several parameters pivotal to the mandate.

For example, the focus of the NUST is '...excellence in teaching, research, innovation and entrepreneurship for sustainable development'; the University of Zimbabwe (UZ) '...prosperity, peace and dignity in Zimbabwe and beyond'; the Bulawayo Polytechnic '...leading provider of technical and vocational training nationally and internationally'; the Chinhoyi University of Technology (CUT) 'technological innovation and entrepreneurship'; and the Zimbabwe Republic Police Staff College '...leading centre of training, development and academic excellence in management and policing, pursued through commitment, diligence and teamwork'. In each and every case, to carve that special niche, focus is to inform the market that the institution will serve it competently and professionally. This is

important, since, as Taylor and Braddock (2008) point out, unlike public security and correction services which are always in the market radar and can operate without such statements, the higher education institutions need them as what they offer is neither always in the public eye nor of interest to everyone.

Smith, et al. (2002, p.2) define the mission as “a broadly defined and enduring statement of purpose that distinguishes the organization from others of its type and identifies the scope of its operations in product (service) and market terms.” Darbi (2012, p.96) sums it as “a broad, overarching framework around which other strategic concerns like vision, strategic intent and capabilities, goals, objectives, core values, behavioural standards, business models, etc. evolve.” Last, Rafael Mattos Deus Rosane Aparecida Gomes Battistelle Gustavo Henrique Ribeiro da Silva (2016, p. 404) observe that, “as a strategic tool for organizations, the mission statement gives a unity of direction, creates common values, reflects the institution’s reality, provides direction and purpose, promotes shared hope and affirms the commitment of the organization to survive and grow.” Like business, institutions use the mission statements to announce their purpose and strategy – that is, what they do and why they exist, or their products, services, goals and culture to all and sundry. Therefore, not only does the mission capture the institution’s *uniqueness*, it anchors the behaviour standard edifying the complexity of the mandate.

The mission is couched through terms like ‘contribute, provide, enable and empower’ whose implication is doing so more extraordinarily than has been the case before. It means exalting the mandate with more torque pressure, hence, edifyingly culturing a ‘prime’ institution that is markedly a cut above the rest. The University of Illinois best apes the animated zeal in its claim that it ‘will transform lives and serve society by educating, creating knowledge and putting knowledge to work on a large scale and with excellence.’

Likewise, the mission of the UZ is to ‘assist clients and customers make meaningful contributions to sustainable development in Zimbabwe through high quality education, training and advisory services, guaranteed through teaching, learning, research, and community service excellence.’ Equally, the NUST advances its purpose as ‘contributing to positive advancement of humanity through knowledge-based solutions to scientific, technological, economic and social challenges’, while the CUT avers to ‘produce innovative

graduates, enhance entrepreneurship, create knowledge, and provide community service through quality teaching, training and technologically-oriented research.’ In each and every case there is an emphatic declaration of the institution’s bounden duty to the people and the nation. In a sense, each is saying: ‘trust us; we are here to make things work for you and test us for it’. Given that globally renowned universities have successfully achieved such aspirational elevations inspired by their visions, a lower throughput would not only be uncharacteristic but very disingenuous.

Darbi (2012, p.96) defines the core values as “the enduring principles, ideologies and worldviews that the founding fathers of an organization hold in high esteem.” According to Muzondo (2012) values pronounce the emotional, moral and ethical rationales and behaviours, including issues of belief, disbelief and withdrawal of judgment. As worldviews, they serve to connect with the targeted clients, in particular on the right way to treat people, the right way to behave in society, and the correct way to approach duty. The proselytizing entails shaping both physical appetites and social longings to consolidate the expected and anticipated life-skills talking of which Kwaramba (2016, p.2) would advance “good relationships, ethical business conduct, fairness, reason, understanding and professionalism.” Due to their enduring nature, values are also called the organizational vision or core ideologies (Darbi, 2012).

Both descriptive and normative terms are the norm expressed through a host of indicators that resemble a shopping list, as the list from the University of Zambia has shown. The local higher education institutions display a similar constellation of terms with ‘excellence, leadership, integrity, equity, honesty, innovation, entrepreneurship, professionalism, hard work, commitment, discipline, Christlikeness, spiritual maturity, democracy, *ubuntu/hunhu*, multicultural tolerance, dynamism, human beings as stewards of God’s environment, social and environmental responsibility’ and many more part of the conversation. Here, the institutions are spoiled for choice, albeit with some common, uniform markers. If, on one hand, the workforce and, on the other, the end-products (graduates) display distinctive qualities enshrined in the values, then the institution has more than successfully acquitted its mandate. All the stakeholders – students, the institution and the market – are more than assured of the requisite ideals and progress in the advancement of humanity. Hence, of the three variables making up the construct, the values envelop is the most loaded made up of

largely normative terms compatible with the desire to culture the technological society as the very prime seed towards the yield of best products and services.

The technological society is the collective definition of technologically-endowed *Homo sapiens* founded on the covenant between science, technology and society. According to Lienhard (2004, para.3), the term technology is derived from the Greek word 'technē' (pronounced techne) which describes the art and skill in making things. "Technē is the work of a toolmaker, or a builder, or a composer. *Ology* is the study or the lore of something. Technology is the knowledge of making things." Beyond the traditional handyman and his heterogeneous tools and materials, skilled to use whatever is available, and able to invent pragmatic solutions to practical situations, is the advent of the technocapitalist, according to Suarez-Villa (n.d. para.1), reflecting the "evolution of market capitalism that is rooted in rapid technological evolution" with socio-economic impacts never seen before. Its objective is to produce intelligent humans, adept at exploiting all those mental faculties of creativity, work capacity, intrinsic motivation and other abilities relevant for developing new technologies and mobilising artificial intelligence (AI). Hence, the ability to exploit the intangibles of creativity, new knowledge, intellectual property (IP), AI, as well as new networking and technological infrastructures into more and better instrumentally useful, culturally-transmissible innovations, goods and services leading to higher exergy and consumability values, has become the locus of the education (Bostrom, 2009).

This is inevitable given technology's role as "the key determinant of the ground rules within which the games of human civilization get played out" (Bostrom, 2009, p.4) which makes *Homo technologicus* (or they-who-use-technology, especially design technology) the basis for technocapitalist trending to mobilise the ramifications of the technological society against the vagaries of *Homo simplex*. The latter are the disadvantaged segments of society that fail or are excluded from the social benefits enjoyed by *Homo technologicus*, yet their survival requires the know-how and culture of the latter (Geisler, 2001). *Homo simplex* is a living reality across the African landscape given the crises of poverty and disadvantage as a result of the inability to access science and technology resources. The ultimate target is a practitioner whose ideas and artisanship skills translate into proficient psycho-technics for high quality theoretically practicable throughput.

Techno-progressivism, technopreneurship, and tech-corporation are part of the language defining the technocapitalist trending and its strong roots in new technology sectors, in the power of corporations, and in new networks and forms of organizational behaviour (Suarez-Villa, n.d.). Significantly, the trending pits the two intelligence hubs of unqualified and qualified intelligence. In line with Bostrom (2009), the superintelligence of the former equates with conscious competence – the rational, scientific, innovative and consummate decision making and problem solving skills based on scholarly intellection and quality emotional intelligence, crowned with the capacity to create, analyse, organize, strategize, and produce goods and services for the market. In contrast, qualified intelligence is characteristically superficial and flawed from lack of transparency and depth so much that it constantly requires defence against incessant complaints and attacks. It equates with mixed conscious/unconscious competence and/or incompetence, or MacCoun's (1998) rational ignorance or mental economy, extending to agnotology to mean purposefully cultured/constructed ignorance to exploit the weak and disadvantaged. The ultimate institutional-national benefit is the tangible 'cumulative, linear progression from ignorance to knowledge and modern life, the steady inexorable movement away from *Homo simplex* to *Homo technicus* and, ultimately, to posthumanity' (Sachs, 1992, p.15).

Accordingly, the technological society reflects this converging-cum-forward advancement of humanity and technology enshrined in the philosophy of transhumanism: the theory that human beings are in a state of transition as they seek to transcend themselves beyond what they are, only delayed by their biological make up which technology will definitely set right (Hook, 2013; Rivera, 2010). Through the science and technology education enterprise: the trans-disciplinary field of study concerned with the teaching and learning, generation and application of theoretical and practical ideas, information, industrial and commercial arts in the solution of social, political, economic, cultural and environmental problems, the culturing of a technological society will materialise pushing forward a more and better human nature.

The technocapitalist drive is the homogenization workshop to usher immense capacity for upward mobility for the state, the economy and the people, with robotic efficiency– to mean endless, flawless, sophisticated product and service delivery and, therefore, a well fulfilled potential learning product – the ultimate target. Culturally, this means a supremely intelligent society comprising technocratically superior and free people, governing and living in self-

contained habitats, nurtured on self-sustaining footprints, engineered and fulfilled through the scientific calculus. Geisler (2001, p.5) provides the most appropriate definition of such a society as the “combination of the outcomes and benefits accrued from science and technology including the unique environment the outcomes have engendered characteristically complex, complicated and sophisticated.” Although the institutions do not openly say so, the technology exponential syndrome nurturing posthumanity, in reference to the state of advanced humanity over and above the original human nature, is the ultimate vision of the vision-mission statements. At this stage, the nation is well empowered to address and redress the vagaries of vulnerability, uncertainty, change and ambiguity (VUCA) confronting the economy and the people. The choice of science and technology as the field of reference, therefore, arose from its overwhelming role to endow the people with the right skills and render them more culture participant than before. This is despite the dilemma of reducing the life world of individuals and communities into an oppressive uniformity through the imposition of scientific categories.

Experimentalism defined in terms of conversion efficiency is the hub of the technological society – to use both tangible and intangible gifts to transform or change materials, energy, data and information, and networks into useful products and services to meet the needs and demands of modernity. This is the cornerstone of the relationship between modern society and science and technology: science develops individual thought processes into instruments of adjustment to the environment to validate the truth and meaning of ideas through utilising them (Chiwome and Gambahaya, 1998; Russell, 1996). In addition to the BUSE, NUST and CUT, the Harare Institute of Technology (HIT) cements the technological society mandate eloquently through its vision of being ‘the stimulant of scholarship in innovation’; and its mission: first, the ‘*Cause* – to cultivate commitment towards technopreneurial leadership’ and, second, the ‘*Calling* – to commercialise the technology through professionalism rooted in integrity’, anchored on the values of ‘innovation, leadership, integrity, commitment, and professionalism’. The robust construct inspires the right spirit and right mind frames against all forms of mental gridlock.

In pursuing sustainable development, the technological society franchise seeks to optimise a balanced ‘academic-productivity-humanitarian’ interface as a new nature that has never been witnessed before to sustain future niches and related complex psychosocial scapes.

Hence, the language is clearly one of active, mind-on-hands-on learning experiences inducing capacity to convert new knowledge into practice or to implement what the learner formulates, which must proceed to inject reform in research, curricula, pedagogy and practice for a more innovative, state-of-the-art, entrepreneurship education (Wilson, Holloway, and Gandhi, 2014). Indeed, the world belongs to those who understand ‘singularity’: to those with the technology who will then spell out in no uncertain terms their visions and missions; to those who have transformed the technocracy into a ‘technogarchy’ utilizing the power of technology for ‘actual’ or ‘virtual’ government across the entire fabric of the economy, society and the world. (Geisler, 2001; McCarthy, 2012).

Technically, the science-technology bidding reflects in programmes like science, technology, engineering and mathematics education, popularly known as STEM, with emphasis on technology and engineering from the (high) school level, rising to genetics, robotics, information technology and nanotechnology or GRIN technologies and other branches like Science, Health and Technology (SHT), and predictive analytics (or Big Data) at university level (Bostrom, 2005), ideally, to culture superintelligent beings with the proper psycho-technics plus matching artificial intelligences. No doubt, politically and ideologically, the science and technology discipline leverages an overwhelming socio-economic influence in Zimbabwe’s modernization cultural drive: it is the vanguard of the nation’s autarky drive.

Hence, as Clark (1986, p.232) long indicated “exhortations and reminders engulfing and saturating speeches, studies, discussions and debates” about the African university or college make it clear that, in justifying its existence, it has to “be demonstrably relevant for and totally committed to national development.” The Mission of the University of Botswana captures the essence of the message eloquently: ‘to improve economic and social conditions for the Nation while advancing itself as a distinctively African university with a regional and international outlook’ (ub.wb). And many go by this maxim.

Accordingly, the vision-mission statements play the judicious role energising science and technology to guarantee the higher education institutions and their benefactors total achievement of the right outcomes and goals by what Haden (2012) calls a remarkable workforce leading to the alleviation of people misery. According to the Rostow model of development, *Homo simplex* and *human misery* are not permanent states but passing

phases humanity must triumph against, and the vision-mission statements propel the take-off. In the footsteps of Vision 2000 and Vision 2020, the resolute statements promise the great visionary leap to the technological infinite, notwithstanding the explosive implications for both the institutions and the wider market. It is the duty of the science and technology institutions to assist the constituents adopt, adapt and align their own visions and missions to correspond with the national dream for a broader technological culture.

This, then, is the substance and import of the vision-mission construct whose normative strength lies in its capacity to reduce the supernatural or paranormal into tangible markers. Naturally, several aspects worth noting emerge, most of which are elaborated in the next chapter. First, the statements vary in length, depth and order of emphasis, and, therefore, how much detail is proclaimed. Most apparent is the influence of the classical Campbell and Yeung's (1991) Ashridge Mission model and its four elements of purpose, strategy, standards and behaviours, and values. Brief visions are characteristic, (for example, UniLag., the BUSE and the University of Zambia) accompanied by fairly long missions and values in others (BUSE, UKZN, University of Illinois,), while there are no core values at all in others (UniLag.) and so on depending on how the institution perceives its life-business. Last, the arrangement of terms suggests some priority order. For example, for the BUSE, knowledge acquisition and sharing followed by teamwork and diversity are the top most values, with commitment and discipline further down the ladder.

Second, some presentations begin with the mission statement followed by the vision (for example, VU and UZ), while in others it is vice versa (for example, the NUST), or everything is contained in one statement, usually the mission. In line with the Ashridge Mission model, the mission statement is considered enough since it expresses both the vision and values and, also, because it is measurable unlike the vision statement which is too hypothetical. But the fact that no organization is stationary and all of them dream big, vision statements set the pace towards the ultimate goal, hence, their popularity. Meanwhile, some institutions put more emphasis on the mission and/or core values rather than the vision (e.g., the Catholic University of Zimbabwe (CUZ) and Morgan Zintec College) and all talk about the core values. To enhance audibility, flowery and fiery energy terms are the norm to aggrandise the institution on the momentous push and commitment to the 'Cause and Calling' (the HIT) and

other social and workplace aspirations. Trends and patterns are, therefore, quite flexible with no hard and fast rules reflecting the originality verve.

Of immediate interest is why the statements enjoy so much appeal at the expense of institutional diversity. What is behind institutional interest to vest so much in them which the methodologies of Acts, Charters and Ordinances fail to do? Or is it nothing more than just a change of tune on the same old song? Sharing on the debate, Darbi (2012, p.95) observes that the statements are said to “motivate, shape behaviours, cultivate high levels of commitment and ultimately impact positively employee performance.” In business language, they enhance the human motor in terms of value-added-per-employee (VAE) measure, while from a Public Choice perspective, they represent “the application of the rational choice model to non-market decision-making” (Hill, 1999, p.1). Continuing the conditions of labour since the Industrial Revolution, they induce and seduce exceptional labour power to optimise combinations of industrial-socio-economic activities for viable productive-social ideals, as well as reconcile formal rationality (the institutional rules and procedures) with substantive rationality (the informal workforce-students’ conducts and behaviours), hence, diluting and ameliorating the restrictions of the bureaucracy.

Thirdly, as the basis of rebranding, the construct nourishes the desire to be the top and unique institution ranked among the pre-eminent both nationally and globally (Opiyo-Newa, 2010). The institutions are able to envision hitherto unparalleled progress to generate ideas, concrete practices and solutions with positive impact human enterprise. In short, the construct serves as the catalytic, persuasive symbol galvanising operations to elevate the most cherished philosophies and/or ideologies be it idealism, existentialism, globalisation, progressivism, legalism, or strategic choice, with all converging on entrepreneurialism for sustainable development. Institutional sovereignty means rejection of further delay to arrive at what they want to be recognised and well known by.

In a nutshell, comprehensively foresighted and farsighted statements articulating the right strength, motivation and fit (Bradt, 2012) must be engendered to uplift product expertise and national livelihoods. More inspirational than inquisitorial or adversarial, the philosophy has become a powerful part of the policy arsenal, ushering organizational limelight through which the institutions express both their ‘visibility’ and the capacity to deal with psychosocial

challenges. In turn, the market says 'now we both see and understand you'. Spoiled for choice, and as part of the structural criticism, they throw in everything to reflect scholarly passion in the innovation, in some cases with the terminology bordering on 'flowery/unintelligible clichés, technical jargon and complex expressions' as Professor Lindela Ndlovu lamented (personal communication, 22 August, 2015).

But, as Morley (2003, p.6) would argue, more importantly, the contention is whether the statements are "a forceful response to existing conditions and problems, or else a discourse in which both problems and solutions are created." In short, as an alternative to what has come before, is the philosophy destined to produce more and better results, specifically, helping to uplift the national poverty to greener pastures? Or else, as the problem exposition has shown, it is just one of the countless, uncanny copy-writes, theoretically impressive, but practically faulted, with the envisaged workforce competitiveness hard to fathom. As the old adage says: the proof of the pudding is in the tongue.

1.5 The footprints conceptual framework

Ngulube, Mathipa and Gumbo (2014a, p.7) indicate that, as critical elements of research, both the conceptual and the theoretical frameworks are developed basically "to account for or describe abstract phenomena that occur under similar conditions." The choice of either depends upon the nature of the study, with common practice tending to combine or show elements of both. Accordingly, a search of the literature was undertaken for foundational models or theories for a framework to follow. No model was readily available since the subject matter of this work is not widely explored in higher education. The study relied on substitute models from the business sector: the classical Ashridge Mission model, together with public choice and the Adizes' Corporate Lifecycle model (2015), as well as study constructions by Morphew and Hartley (2006), Wang, Gibson...Slate (2007) and Opiyo-Newa (2010) which were the basis of the modelling detailed in the next chapter. Alongside are additional support models and critiques from the multiple reference sources.

Through content analysis as employed by Morphew and Hartley (2006) to determine the 'elements' of 300 mission statements of universities in the US, the study built the pre-structured footprints conceptual model based on the survey of vision and mission statements of 34 randomly selected public and private institutions – universities, colleges, institutes,

schools, academies and centres – drawn from the Zimbabwe Universities Directory 2012. In line with Ngulube, et al. (2014b) through open and selective coding, or thematic synthesis, “the diversity to be studied was defined beforehand (pre-structured)” and the aim of the formal inquiry was “then to see which and how the predefined characteristics exist empirically in the population under study” (Jansen, 2010, p.2).

The enumeration analysed the statements into single words and/or phrases in sync with the context in which they occurred. Table 1.1 shows the multiple indicators articulating the behaviour norms and performance standards from which was aggregated the five context codes, or themes, or realisation factors dubbed the ‘model footprints’, namely, constituency servicing, governance, quality assurance, comportment and evaluation. Together, they constitute the ideal building blocks of each and every set of statements. This was cognisant of the realisation factors of ‘scholarship and innovation, capacity and capability, branding capability, and cultured citizenship’ by one of the study institutions which fitted with the quality assurance footprint.

By definition, the footprints are the core vision-mission pillars, dimensions and categories, exhibiting diverse processes, practices and resource levies that induce unique socio-environmental results and effects critical in product and service delivery. The choice of the term footprint, therefore, reflects the ecosystem nature of the institutions to define the sum total of the envisioned material, energy and information inputs and the sum of outputs plus changes in stock. The relationships are summed up in Figure 2.1, Chapter 2.

Briefly, the indicators of teaching, research, extension services, creative activity, knowledge-based solutions, leadership, enterprising, etc. resonated with constituency servicing; leadership, identity, corporate governance, recruitment, full semesterization echoed with governance; excellence, highly acclaimed, premier, and world class matched with quality assurance; and leadership, integrity, innovativeness, equity and discipline corresponded with comportment and so on. Altogether, strict categorization was undertaken to avoid unnecessary repetitions and overlaps. It progressed smoothly with hardly any indicators demanding intense negotiation. Given variations in contexts, and based on original classifications, some indicators appear in more than one footprint as what, for instance, constitutes leadership in one context is not what it means in another.

Table 1.1 The model footprints and specifiable indicators

Model Footprints	Specifiable Indicators articulating the standard of behaviour
Constituency servicing	teaching; extension services; knowledge-based solutions; research; identity; creative activity; leadership; enterprising; service humanity; quality of life; people empowerment; development; strategic partnerships; technologically-oriented research; cultural enrichment; prosperity, peace and dignity; whole person; highly skilled personnel in management and information technology; holistic education; generation, dissemination and application of knowledge; problem solving; learning environment
Governance	source of identity; corporate governance; recruitment, motivation and retention of staff in an environment of a caring institution; full semesterization
Quality Assurance (QA)	excellence (academic, professional); highly acclaimed; premier; world class; freedom; efficiency; effectiveness; creativity; scholarship and innovation; capacity and capability, entrepreneurship; intellectual/ academic technical skills; registration; accreditation; branding capability; cultured citizenship
Comportment	leadership; integrity; innovativeness; equity; professionalism; research; social and environmental responsibility; <i>ubuntu/hunhu</i> ; discipline; commitment; honesty; hard work; care for others; spiritual maturity; multicultural tolerance; transparency; industry; diligence; accountability; sensitivity to the dignity of every human being; needs of the disadvantaged; human beings as stewards of God's environment; African culture; Christlikeness; holiness; love; creation; service; fairness
Evaluation	excellence; world class; grading; holistic education; by 2015; by 2025

(Source: Generated from 34 Institutional visions and missions, 2012)

Defined, constituency servicing is the reciprocal relationship between the institution and its hinterland involving mutual support and exchange of resources for sustainable development. As Table 1.1 shows, it is the most dominant footprint. Governance is the whole spectrum of oversight roles reflecting the way authority is exercised, especially the co-process of faculty governance-administration and the related capacity to direct-manage effectively. Compared to the other footprints, it was relatively thin in the sampled vision-mission statements.

According to Materu (2007), quality assurance (QA) is guaranteeing that the higher education offered meets strict and acceptable local and international standards, free of market distortions, while also rich in practical professionalism. Hence, as a high-profile yardstick, a

highly irresistible quality assurance is the most sought after and cherished variable. Comportment is the totality of skills, attitudes, behaviours, personality profiles and humanely-related practices expected of the products and stakeholders. Overall, it resonated with quality constituency servicing and was the most loaded and diverse. Last, evaluation is the systematic acquisition and assessment of information, products and services to provide useful feedback on the efficacy of the visions and missions (Trochim, 2006). Unlike the other footprints, evaluation was silent but was deducible through indicators like excellence, grading and forecast dates. As Ngulube, et al. (2014, p.15) indicate, theoretical saturation was reached when no new footprints were being generated.

Being reflected is how the vision-mission statements are justified on the grounds of reviving prospective rationality within the institutional collective: uplifting constituency servicing and inspiring dynamic governance, ensuring premium QA and a superlative comportment, while engendering robust evaluations, culminating in befitting infrastructural and behaviour transformations and standards, cognitive change and other vital proprietary targets. In line with Ngulube, et al. (2014a), as the basis for the designation of the formal object, the literature review, the research design and data manipulation, the footprints model provided the appropriate scaffolding for the selection and prioritization of the indicator variables which enhanced explicitness and self-audit, as well as coherence between empirical observations and conceptual inferences and conclusions. Naturally, the aggregation-disaggregation exploded with elements of STEPED covering social, technological, economic, political, environmental and demographic critiques; SWOT analysis, exposing the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats behind the visions and missions; and other studious enquiry techniques to achieve the desired understanding of the diverse inroads the formal object plays in institutional affairs.

1.6 Proposition

From the onset, it was observed that the vision-mission statements were workplace models seeking to leverage the 'From...To' strategic imperatives which, therefore, translates into capacity to fire up mandates and portfolios to optimize the science-technology ideal, failing which it would be pointless having them. But, the study proposition was that the evidence was inconclusive to justify and sustain the notion that the statements are the default policy yardstick driving the institutional mandates to foster the technological culture to achieve the

highly sought expert services for sustainable development. The problem context was, therefore, profiled in the ambit of this debate.

1.6.1 Main research question

How does the rationale for the vision-mission statements galvanise the institutional mandates to foster the technological society for sustainable development?

1.6.2 Sub-research questions

In pursuit of the main question, the following sub-questions were formulated:

- a) What was/is the justification for adopting the vision-mission statements by higher education institutions in Zimbabwe?
- b) What practical steps enhance the productivity of the construct?
- c) How do stakeholder views portray the marketability of the construct?
- d) What role do the vision-mission statements play in the science and technology transformation agenda?

1.6.3 Study objectives

Corollarily, the study was guided by the following objectives:

- a) To interrogate the justification for adopting the vision-mission policy blueprint by higher education institutions in Zimbabwe.
- b) To evaluate the practical steps to enhance the productivity of the vision-mission initiative.
- c) To solicit stakeholder views on the viability of the philosophy of vision-mission statements.
- d) To scrutinize the role the vision-mission statements play in the science and technology transformation agenda.

1.7 Delimitation

While the construct's formless generalities rendered strict delimitation difficult, the four science and technology universities in the country comprised the research island. Focus centred on the footprints and how issues of productivity, curricular strength, marketability and the transformative role of the statements, the very heart of the market model, as perceived across the infrastructure sources and by the multiple staff categories, played out without

going into details on individual systems nor perceptions by specific individual participants or groups unless to highlight issues. Hence, the study was neither a system-wide institutional audit, nor was it about each and every statement or the entire educational processes and practices there in, or each and every initiative and the impact of such initiatives, although complementary of these. Focus was restricted to the statements' inherent capacity to inject curriculum and management strength, motivation and fit to address the theory of change over and above the endogenous psycho-technical changes.

1.8 Limitations

Some limitations envisaged at the proposal stage were actually encountered both during and post the fieldwork. The usual non-idiographic limitation of the case study design aside, most apparent were participant limitations: decline by one key institution and the non-respondent error and failure to respond timeously to questionnaires and requests. The delayed response rate was explained on the basis that the participants were 'too busy'. On the other hand, it was likely that many forgot or lost interest while some claimed non-receipt of the instruments, or they were electronically challenged, or wanted payment. Ironically, it also implied that the vision statements mattered least to them. The slow response rate created bothersome follow-ups and constant reminders. But that the study had to resort to hard copy was a tough omen on the status of institutional programmes like e-learning.

Next was the problem of instrumentation which required originality, compounded by lack of specific tests or procedures for validating non-market instruments. The limitation was off-set through investigator triangulation, while on a more positive note, the originality worked to the advantage of the study.

Also, subjecting the adoption of the construct to further questions and criticism was the dearth of local studies for back-up. The subject of vision-mission statements has attracted scant research, except strategic planning and accreditation audits. Africa's philosophers have failed to come up with a vibrant Negroid philosophy exposing the systems to the rubble of the Western philosophy earthquake. Equally, the criticism that the study was using 'flowery' and difficult language revealed not only the limited experiences most people had with the statements, but the dilemma surrounding the philosophy and its style of communication and

marketing. Stakeholders were and are certainly, and most likely, operating at discordant wavelengths posing the audibility challenge for successful endeavours.

Limitations of omissions, stereotype observations, social desirability and extreme acquiescence rarely surfaced as previously feared (Mamabolo, 2009). So, too, was the risk of substitute participants and the challenge of different characteristics which renders such participants less useful or even irrelevant to the issues at hand (Archer, 2007).

1.9 Significance

Kapfunde (1997) observes that policy matters require constructed support and validated proofs to justify the investment. While a non-commissioned study, practitioners in curriculum and education management should find it a worthwhile read and test ground for some of the popularly held ideas and philosophies. Accordingly, the study sought to contribute to the building of empirical literature on the subject of vision-mission-core values statements in order to enhance institutional capacities across the wide spectrum of curriculum and management endeavours. Currently, such studies are rare and largely unknown. More specifically, focus was to build capacity for explanatory insights into higher education curriculum and management issues and challenges; to measure and account for the results of public policies and programmes; to stimulate and strengthen the culture of introspection; and to understand and strengthen the dynamics of culturing praxis-articulate products well versed in practical judgment and action, balanced measurement and functionality to shape situations for the betterment of the institutions and wider society.

Together with spin-off papers, the research will yield more organizational and personal benefits, providing a useful read for the academic and personal development of students, teachers, administrators and those in development work and other fields. Staff development and training should also find it an invaluable companion in its work.

1.10 Study assumptions

Best and Kahn (2007) define assumptions as the way the truth can be ultimately derived and/or ascertained notwithstanding the lack of proof. They reveal the necessary conditions and/or the attended risks for the study to succeed. The main assumption was that the vision-mission philosophy is fully understood by the wider population in higher education to

influence positive values and attitudes to yield a credible outcome to strengthen institutional endeavours. Two, was the assumption that communication technologies were readily available for the participants to use when responding to enquiries. Three, that organizations survive on truths and myths causing stakeholders to think alike even in the face of contradictory evidence. The last assumption was that Zimbabwe's economy will continue to improve to reduce cumulative frustrations with everything blamed on it.

1.11 Operational definitions

According to the World Wildlife Fund (2015), **ecological footprint** is the amount of the environment necessary to produce the goods and services necessary to support a particular lifestyle. In the study, it is the core vision-mission pillars exhibiting diverse processes and practices that induce unique professional results critical in product and service delivery, ultimately, reflecting the impact of the philosophy at the given time.

Compartment is the sum total of formal and informal skills, attitudes, behaviours, conduct, and personality profiles expected of the institutional products and stakeholders.

The **technological society** is the combination of the outcomes and benefits accrued from science and technology including the unique environment the outcomes have engendered characteristically complex, complicated and sophisticated (Geisler, 2001). Technology evolutionists distinguish the levels of human motor between *Homo Technologicus*, or *Homo technicus*, or *Techno sapiens* and its opposite, *Homo simplex*, being reference to those that survive inside and outside modern science and technology, respectively.

Product is the education and training services offered by the institution. Varying with contexts, it embraces either the 'learning output' (the students), or the 'learning process' (the pedagogy), or the 'education programme' or 'training programme', or all the four (Van den Berghe, 1998).

The **vision-mission-core values construct/philosophy** is the foresighted and farsighted Messianic narrative symbolising appropriate strength, motivation and fit to address the power-profit-uncertainty spectrum to approximate the envisaged dream (after Habley, 2011). It is the basis of institutional epistemology and strategy.

1.12 Organization of the study

Chapter 1 is the background to the problem. Chapter 2 is the review of the literature and related theoretical and conceptual frameworks, while Chapter 3 further interrogates the political economy of the philosophy from the perspective of the model footprints. Chapter 4 is the research methodology and how the data were collected, including the preliminary analyses and issues of credibility and ethics. Chapter 5 is the data presentation, analysis and interpretation of the field evidence, while Chapter 6 discusses opportunities and challenges from the emerging meta-deliverables. Chapter 5 is the summary, conclusions and recommendations. Last, are the references and appendices.

1.13 Summary

The chapter outlined the source stimulus to the *Cartesian doubt* with regard to the philosophy of vision-mission-core values statements. Using global and local examples, it configured and crystallised the problem context, followed by exploratory definitions and perspectives of the philosophy as *the* default policy yardstick driving the institutional mandates, with special focus on science and technology education. The reductionist, fiery, earth-shaking statements induce a panorama of management and curriculum processes and practices grounded in the uncompromising optimization imperative in the exploitation of technological creativity and new knowledge to foster most significant changes befitting the power of the corporations. Drawing from the conceptual perspectives, it constructed the footprints conceptual model as the basis for interrogating the problem. Last, is the rest of the conventional research rubric comprising the proposition, delimitation, significance and assumptions, concluded with operational definitions and the chapter schedule. From the preliminary evidence, the philosophy is both the boon and bane of institutional endeavours, saying what they do mean and/or meaning what they do not do. The next chapter reviews the role of the literature in the justification of the construct and significance to the study.

CHAPTER II

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

This chapter undertakes an in-depth literary review of both published and unpublished materials to provide answers on the state of knowledge or theoretical and policy issues and debates surrounding the subject of vision-mission statements. As a key component of research, as summed up by Ary, Jacobs and Razavieh (2009), the multifold purpose of the literature review includes: to enable the research to define the frontiers of its field; to be positioned in its proper perspective; to facilitate the interpretation of the results and explanation of any emerging contradictions; to verify methodology and thus develop sophistication in the knowledge about educational research and, finally, to justify the study to stakeholders and readers. Through the qualitative systematic review or qualitative evidence synthesis (among the many genres of literature review), this chapter sought to unpack the political economy of the vision-mission construct, more so its professional rationale and material influence as the basis for institutional branding or reform to attain the most cherished ideals from evidence from the literature.

To sharpen the review, the following questions were raised: what is the nature and scope of the vision-mission philosophy which justifies the high attention price? How much is the strength and motivation of the processes and practices going on in higher education? Does it fire up the demand for technical skills for sustainable development? To answer the questions and more, the chapter developed the literature concept map, Figure 2.1, which then directed the aggregation and disaggregation of the wide spectrum of primary and secondary sources for related themes or constructs to explicate the multiple parameters and variables involved and, ultimately, from the mustered detail, the implications of the philosophy for the study as a whole.

2.2 The nature and scope of the vision-mission-values construct

Figure 2.1 sums up the nature and scope of the vision-mission construct. Briefly, the conceptual dimensions espouse structure and related institutionalization processes which determine the construct's interface with, and role in, the science and technology education—

sustainable development imperatives and, therefore, how it either promotes or discounts the mandates. Most significant is its pronounced role and influence strongly orchestrated through the footprints of constituency servicing, governance, quality assurance, compoment, and evaluation driving the envisaged opportunities and benefits against the embedded challenges and consequences higher education has to grapple with. Last, is the outcome and impact of a new and diverse science and technology culture (or technocapitalism to be more exact) and the attended personnel windfall of Thinkers, Builders, Improvers and Providers. As always, the evaluation footprint is the constant check mechanism to ensure that feedback and other relationships are kept well-oiled, knit and compact for more and better results and impacts. Through sharing worldviews, the literature enriched the study with frameworks and critiques to reconcile the theory-practice continuum.

Figure 2.1 The Vision-Mission flow map (Source: Author, 2015)

2.2.1 Background

The vision-mission philosophy reverberates with different epochs in history symbolic of the Great Design, The Renaissance, the Period of Enlightenment, the American dream and the

Third World Revolutionary Independence Waves to overthrow colonialism and dictatorship and usher a new life-work rationale. Each epoch has been a moment of great visionary insights bringing about profound developments that have directed or misdirected human history in different and multiple ways. Today it is identifiable with the African dream (NEPAD, 2001) and, above all, the *techno sapiens* dream (Hook, 2013). With renewed vigour and enthusiasm, people continue to look forward to the sunshine uplands for a more gratifying future for themselves and their offspring, in spite of the mixed blessings.

In Zimbabwe, the 1980s and 1990s were decades of visions of Growth with Equity, Vision 2020, Health for all by the Year 2000, the Economic Structural Adjustment Programme, building up to the 2001 MDGs. Today Zim-Asset (2013) is the macro-vision supported by micro institutional visions and missions. Across the board, the drive is to use such forceful assertions to clarify 'purpose', articulated as the benchmark propelling Sachs' (1992) uncompromising optimization imperative to scale the goals of empowerment, emancipation, indigenization, entrepreneurship and, ultimately, the technological society.

Behind the scenes is the influence of the globalization agenda to appropriately convey and align the mandates with the source philosophies of continuous improvement for global parity and equity. Unlike the erstwhile Golden Rule, credos, aims and objectives, the vision statements inject greater verve in the translation of these philosophies. The high level promissory spirit and self-indulgence readily endear the construct to all and sundry to stake their futures on compared to the rigidity of the other maxims which leaves little room for manoeuvre. Of particular interest is bringing the fragmented curriculum units and stakeholder interests together. Hence, driven by fatigue with old maxims and the need for greater capacity to adapt, the construct offers the chance to experiment with the inconstant variety of innovations and strategies for more and better modelling (ZIMCHE, 2011).

While the different maxims are neither mutually exclusive nor totally distinct, with some visions as precise as a goal or as compelling as a credo, aim or objective, between them they are potentially apart (Habley, 2011). Hence, in an attempt to close the communication gap, institutions often resort to using all of them together to express their mandates. Confusion then reigns when an institution feels that, alone, its vision-mission statements are inadequate and fail to bring out more succinctly the totality of its mandate. They must be

supported by goals, or the core purpose and/or objectives and/or principles to aid the communication. One side effect is the undue repetition and duplication, generating confusions in the process, let alone confusion between the vision and the mission and rules and examples abound across institutions (Kwaramba, 2016).

The moral persuasion behind visions and missions is that local institutions are taking after household names like McDonalds, Harvard University, Manchester Institute of Technology and the NUST to capitalise on the philosophy to build and earn much higher and better statuses and prestige. The future is in the hands of each institution and is subject to how it is interpreted and projected today to arrive as planned tomorrow. Clark (1986) argues that the developments signal the powerful influence of the expanding range of interests and rising expectations from the vast student market with the various symbols of technocapitalism bolstering the endeavours.

2.2.2 Vision-mission modelling

Clark (2003) defines modelling as a representation of some aspects of reality, selected and brought together to show certain of its properties, and providing a working hypothesis against which reality can be tested. Iconic, textual, analogue, symbolic and digital models are the cornerstone of the process, either to raise or to lower the level of abstraction into a controllable (usually diagrammatic) image, map, signal or theory for purposes of knowledge generation, utilization, decision making and commercialization. As such it has become a popular research tool to manipulate interaction among variables to formulate, explain or produce a phenomenon.

The Campbell and Yeung (1991) Ashridge Mission model is the vision-mission modelling standard. It consists of the four components of 'purpose, strategy, standards and behaviours, and values' – well biased towards business as Figure 2.2 shows. According to Smith, et al. (2003), each component answers to some critical question about the enterprise or institution. For *purpose* the question is: why does it exist? For *strategy*: how does it pursue its strategic objectives, or what is its commercial rationale? For *standards and behaviours*: how does it act or behave in terms of the articulated values (ethically, morally, aggressively, honestly, professionally, win/achieve, improvement-oriented, empower, adapt/respond, innovate)? Last, *values*: what does it believe in or what is its moral rationale (philosophical priorities,

basic beliefs and aspirations – learning/training/development, dedication, social/civic responsibility, etc.)? Naturally, answers will be as diverse as the players in the game.

Figure 2.2 The Ashridge Mission Model

Purpose and strategy are referred to as the hardware elements and standards and behaviours and values, the software elements (Muzondo, 2012). The test of the construct is the extent it includes both elements. It is excellent if it complies with all the four components; good when both hardware and one software elements appear; average when at least one hardware and both software elements are reflected; and poor and very poor when only the software elements or no elements are shown, respectively. The qualitatively definitive statements are, therefore, the trademark of the indulgence, separating and differentiating institutions from their competitors.

The vision-mission construct is created in many ways. Procedurally, participants review the existing documents, or respond to proposals, or react to collated ideas, in most cases, the organisational credo (Travis, 2015), or to ‘realization factors’ or benchmarks that aid “in communicating it; in aligning organizational processes and systems to suit it; in empowering others to act to achieve it; and in motivating staff” (Kantabutra and Avery, 2010, p.39). Likewise, MacMillan (2011) talks of incorporation of full descriptions of the target market, geographic domain, concern for survival, growth and profitability, philosophy, and the desired public image. Conferences, seminars and workshops involving the stakeholders are then held to consolidate the portfolio although, always controversial, is the number of representatives which is never enough, especially with big organizations like universities.

Debate then surrounds the issues of content and breadth. Generally, institutions go by different maxims: 'less is more/beautiful' whereby clarity and brevity prevail (11-22 words or ten lines), or 'more is better', or 'cover all bases' where verbosity and detail prevail, for example, Illinois University, UKZN and Mlezu College; or simply long enough to reach the target audience. Hence, as Darbi (2012) advises, while the construct must be comprehensible and, therefore, short and concise enough for staff and interested parties to commit to memory, or to share within a short time, it should avoid undue brevity to be mistaken for a motto or being lofty and meaningless. So, in addition to being clearly comprehensible, relevant, flexible and enduring, the construct must be current, adaptable and ambitious enough to incite and encourage commitment from the target audience towards its long-term fulfilment.

The assumption, then, is that the statements sufficiently spark and articulate the prime goal and values, which the stakeholders must not only understand and follow in their day-to-day and future activities, but must be emboldened by the prospects. Kantabutra and Avery further argue that stronger organizational performance reflects powerful visions and the institutional ability to live the construct, whereas weak visions indicate the opposite, which brings into question the force behind it all between the visionary persona or the system, as the statements become a boardroom affair.

2.2.3 Integrating vision-mission-values

The institutions work with three separate statements depicting the vision, mission and values whose relationship inspires robust communication and action with theory and practice supposedly fitting in the entire exercise. According to Habley (2011, para.8) the

foresight and imagination suggests that we must imagine what would define us if we were 'being all that we could be'. We must focus on the answers to the questions: How do we want to be remembered? What is the ultimate compliment that could be paid to us? What do we aspire to deliver? What contributions do we want to make to the lives of our students? To the success of our institutions?

First to draw from the above observation is the vision or visionary to mean marked by foresight and imagination to culture a robust future state. This entails harnessing the existing practices and processes, fantasies and dreams into plausible and genuine images of the future state that is the pride of the institution. Habley's further exhortation (para.8) notes that, as the most robust and effective vehicle to the future state, the vision reflects that "rare and

exhilarating opportunity to imagine, to create, and to visualize” as the institution approximates everything it wants to be. The following examples illustrate the epistemology:

- (i) The vision statement of the Ministry of Higher and Tertiary Education, Science and Technology Development (MHTE&STD) is Guarantee Zimbabwe as a leader in the creation and use of new and existing knowledge, skills, attitudes and resources through the local mobilisation and provision of quality higher and tertiary education.
- (ii) The vision statement of the University of Zimbabwe (UZ) is to be (and be recognised by others as) a leading University working for prosperity, peace and dignity in Zimbabwe and beyond.
- (iii) The vision statement of the Catholic University of Zimbabwe (CUZ) is for Holistic Education for the Whole Person Imbued with Christian Values.
- (iv) The vision statement of the Belvedere Technical Teachers’ College (BTTC) is to ‘produce highly professional, competent and committed secondary school teachers in Academic and Vocational/Technical disciplines.
- (v) The vision statement of the United College of Education (UCE) is to be the centre of excellence in the production of highly qualified primary and specialist teachers for the country, region and the world.

The celebrated aspirations vary as well as differ in format, pattern, length and tone, but the target is the same finish line whose equilibrium is the gold standard with regard potential for success, reputation, quality and market competition expressed through terms like premier, leader, leading, centre of excellence, producer of highly..., and Holistic Education. As the top target, the vision is the imagined, visualized, creative, superior image shared by all, although visions like ‘leader’ beg the question why it is important to be a leader rather than something else. In line with Habley, the vision champions the messages of purpose/identity, standards and values in a manner never witnessed before while articulating the mental image of the desired and chosen future state as a realistic, credible and attractive goal that is much better in all respects than obtains now. The From...To... injects spark into the life of the institution, adiabatically jump-starting processes, events and phenomena when chips begin to go down. It offers the future strategic direction and energizes the institution to strive for success at a new level of performance. As the HIT (2015, p.4) sums it, the design plan is to strategize the “future unconstrained, before working towards the impossible”, if not even the improbable.

Second, the mission statement serves to execute and uplift the vision which is why it is also referred to as the creed, purpose, or statement of corporate philosophy and values (Darbi, 2012). It details what the institution does, for whom and how with respect to its products, services and workflows to achieve the vision. According to MacMillan (2011, para.15), at a minimum, the mission statement should answer the questions: (1) what are the opportunities or needs the organization addresses? (2) What does the organization do to address those needs? and (3) What principles and values guide the organization? Alternatively, according to Habley, it addresses the questions: who should we serve? What should they receive? What is the ultimate result we seek? In short, as the *modus operandi* and centre of gravity, the mission brings the vision to the ground to walk the talk. The following examples illustrate the paradigm:-

- (i) The mission statement of the MHTE&STD is to provide an effective system for the production of patriotic and competent high level manpower through the provision and accreditation of higher and tertiary education programmes and institutions for sustainability and global competitiveness.
- (ii) The mission statement of the UZ is enabling our clients and customers to make meaningful contributions to sustainable development in Zimbabwe. To this end we provide high quality education, training and advisory services on a needs oriented basis. We guarantee the above by maintaining excellence in Teaching, Learning, Research and Service to the Community.
- (iii) The mission statement of the CUZ states that as a University in a multi-cultural society, the Catholic University in Zimbabwe provides wholesome education in its teaching, research and service programmes and fosters commitment, service, moral uprightness and academic excellence.
- (iv) The mission statement of the BTTC is to produce students with high level technical entrepreneurial skills as to be gainfully employed in industry or successfully embark on business enterprises.
- (v) The mission statement of the UCE is to satisfy national educational needs by producing competitive primary and specialist teachers capable of adding educational value in socio-economic development and global competitiveness.

Across the board, 'provision' is the centre of equilibrium and constant refrain – to mean an all-out, forceful drive targeting a future whose philosophy is boundless success of the highest

standard over all cherished accomplishments. The implied 'uncompromising optimization imperative' must deliver distinctive products and services second to none. Paramount is delivery of patriotic and competent high level manpower or socio-technical entrepreneurs critical for globally sustainable competitiveness. From the above examples, only the CUZ is openly concerned with moral standards, while fascination with myopia is the doing and undoing of most of the missions.

In pursuit of the 'Prime' stage goal, institutions have embarked on exceptionally powerful and highly distinctive educational journeys (From...To), the ultimate in epistemology and pedagogy to realise the climax of all conceivable human endeavours. Heralding the 'gold standard' or 'robotic efficiency', the journeys inspire the stakeholders to probe and solve academic and administrative matters and portfolios, extending to the marketplace. The absence of challenges and hardships indicates how these are considered conquered and out of harm's way, with the 'very best, acme, sublime, leading, world class' the premium behaviour standard. Purpose has never been so definitively defined.

Last, the core values define the esteemed and highly cherished life skills that epitomise the vision and mission. They define the principles and standards or unspoiled knowledge, skills, behaviour, conduct and attitude profiles at the very centre of product and stakeholder character over which there is no compromise. They are the perfect, pacific concert of the overriding morality guiding the individuals and the institution against the opposite of unacceptable and harmful forces and vices. Among the most notable are the Seven Nolan Principles of Public Life, namely, selflessness, integrity, objectivity, openness, honesty, accountability, and leadership and Clark's (1986) eco-social justice, liberty, competence and loyalty. Institutionally cogent is Manktelow and Carlson's (2012, p.1) framework comprising the values of 'being accountable; making a difference; focusing on detail; delivering quality; being completely honest; keeping promises; being reliable; being positive; meeting deadlines; helping others; being a great team member; respecting company policy and rules, and respecting others; and showing tolerance.' Underlying all these are Olson and Stewart's (2011) micro-traits of focus, maturity, awareness of personal strengths and limitations, assertiveness, courteousness, proper exercise of authority, confidence, diplomacy plus service and incorruption.

As Kwaramba (2016, p.2) sums it, “values are the soul of the organization so much that its operations are anchored on them.” In short, values finally aggregate the substance and import of the entire construct as the following examples illustrate: -

- (i) The core values of the MHTE,STD comprise: patriotism, creativity, integrity/*hunhu/ubuntu*, entrepreneurship, professionalism, innovativeness, industry, multicultural tolerance
- (ii) The core values (or pillar outcomes) of the UZ comprise knowledge, diligence, integrity
- (iii) The core values of the CUZ comprise: Christian principles: academic excellence; highly skilled personnel in management and information technology; honesty and openness of mind; individual responsibility for personal development; sensitivity to the dignity of every human being; and human beings as stewards over God’s environment
- (iv) The core value of the BTTC is to produce a body of young professionals ingrained with attitudes, values and interests compatible with the socio-economic environment
- (v) The core values of the United College of Education comprise: transparency, patriotism, *ubuntu/hunhu*, creativity, entrepreneurship, innovativeness, integrity

The values interface the ‘soft’ skills of patriotism, integrity, morality with the ‘hard’ skills of technology, highly skilled personnel, industry (or psycho-technics), hence, anchoring the drive to achieve greater self-mobilization. Inasmuch as the terminology varies with institutional philosophy, the overall difference is razor thin, reflecting the character mix of the institutions and efforts to deal with the constant opposites from the push and pull of overlapping goals and interests. The total number of values varies from zero to a rare minimum of three (UZ), through the standard six (NUST), to maximum nine/ten values in the majority of cases. The more secular terms are common with public institutions while terms with religious (mainly Christian) undertones dominate the private institutions. In contrast, American examples are relatively more realistic (extropian) while local samples are highly aspirational and Utopian signifying differences in experience, perception and conceptualisation of the local realities. With multiculturalism and other exchange programmes, the values envelop keeps growing creating a governance nightmare.

The complexity in institutional types and tasks, coupled with the expanding demands of the diversified market contribute to the diversity of values. In particular, as Lewis (2007) observes, is the influence of business where the student-institution relationship is understood in 'consumer-supplier, or willing buyer-willing seller, or customer-service provider' terms channelled through strong market related bonds ingeminating both appetites and longings whose sharpness dictates the calibre of the engineered products. Technically and socially, the bandwidth depicts the drive for healthier levels of service delivery to mould proper products, services and workflows to close psychosocial gaps and counter endemic socio-environmental pressures and challenges. Hence, institutions emphasise different sets of values more than others, while omissions are seemingly compensated through the 'collective responsibility' exercised by each on behalf of all.

Reflecting the aspired psychosocial changes, according to Gert (2011), the ideal is to cement values related to leadership, productivity, entrepreneurship, accepting God's authority and championing peace, justice and liberty and giving precedence to integrity, honour, love, purity and sanctity, while avoiding and preventing unhealthy appetites – usually short-term cravings driven by self-interests. As microcosms of their constituents, the institutions must inculcate the lifelong values (or the affective domain) critical in fostering the desired socio-economic transformations to successfully promote as well as hold the nation or sections of it together against possible fracturing or unforeseen calamity.

Notwithstanding errors of omission and commission, such is the nature and aspirations of the values envelop. They are central to lifestyles and workflows and constitute the critical formalization and informality in the governance metric, whose target focus is the reciprocal state-action-psychosocial relationship, which translates into successful delivery of the uncompromising optimisation imperative ethos. Therefore, whatever models serve as sources, the values envelop has become quite overbearing to pose selection challenges. Apart from the deliberate exclusion of the thorny and contradictory in favour of the more conservative values, from a Public Choice perspective, non-market values play a secondary role to the values of self-interest. In the final analysis, in the drive for self-mobilization to raise the flag and create a healthy technology-humanitarian nature and culture, the values mosaic has become a complex affair full of diverse assumptions and interpretations that are as clear to some as they are fuzzy to others.

Ultimately, the target is to instil the discipline to execute strategy perspectives with high integrity and dependability or according to the ideals of the Pareto optimality and, therefore, free of personal, group or extra interests. Socially, the personnel and products must never compromise public interest in terms of both truth conflicts and conflicts of interests, howsoever the psycho-economic pressures. Whatever the biases, decision making and problem solving must be transparent and solely based on merit with regard duty to care, accountability and exemplary behaviour. In support of this view, Morley (2003) argues that, rather than plain knowledge, a work-aspirations-institutional goals nexus has become the norm indicating how a flexible attitude and disposition responsive to change has assumed a more dominant role rather than knowledge *per se*.

Epistemologically, whichever model is followed, the action or journey (mission) must lead to the desired state (vision) or the desired state (vision) must guide the action or journey (mission) to the vision, ultimately synthesised in the core values or life's credits the products must learn and proceed to work and live by. The reciprocal state-action-psychosocial relationship is the heart of the epistemology, which translates into successful delivery of the Prime ethos, whereby the products have learned and can use and transfer the relationship clinically free of distortions. This, then, means that the products must prevail against all manner of uncertainty as the proverbial concrete pillars to support and firm national socio-economic aspirations, whatever and however difficult the odds.

To sum up, as Morphey and Hartley (2006) put it, the vision-mission statements inundate the market, gravitating stakeholders from both within and outside the institution around the fact that the institution-constituency essentials are well articulated to guarantee effective and efficient oversight or graded performance befitting the potential learning product. Varying interests and complexities aside, and whether excellent, average or poor and, therefore, highly selective than inclusive in communications, the final outcome must be sound statements that appropriately reflect the institutional terrain: that inject the appropriate indulgence or requisite fire power to stimulate a well marshalled education clinical in the technological and cultural homogenization of the nation and other related aspirations. The graded performance satisfactorily meets all manner of requirements for and by end-users, stakeholders, shareholders, workers, students, employers and other markets, extending to

policy stipulations. The close equivalents are bees which, when they make honey, they are the best; or ants which, when they construct or destroy a structure, it is an act of exceptional engineering. So too the institutions through the vision-mission statements as they set out to do what they know and can do best – cleanly, precisely and flawlessly. The University of Illinois model closely replicates much of what is being raised, ensuring a comprehensive construct that is robust, inclusive and edifying.

2.3 Institutionalization models

The installation of the construct is a varied experience that undergoes both slow and rapid changes, progressively reaching the correct or sublime level of world class, premier and leader or some such aspirations. Among institutionalization models in place are business models, on one hand, and research studies, on the other, in reciprocal relationships. Among the former, the study utilised elements of Public Choice and the Adizes' Corporate Lifecycle model, complemented with research studies by Morphew and Hartley (2006), Wang, et al. (2007) and Opiyo-Newa (2010) with further critiques by Jaffee (2008), Darbi (2012) and Rafael, et al. (2016) among several others.

2.3.1 Public choice and business models

From the Public Choice perspective, the vision-mission statements enter institutional space to duplicate, emulate or catapult the efficiency of the market model in non-market exchanges in sync with the thinking that “government is simply a mechanism that would do the right thing if given enough resources and information” (Hill, 1999, p.2). Given the lack of a positive governance theory analogous to the theory of the market for the institutions to follow, the application of catallactics, or the science of exchanges, has become a close substitution (Buchanan, n.d.). Hence, as one of the core tenets of the bureaucracy, the statements constitute “formal and informal networks that connect the organizational personnel to one another through flows of information and patterns of cooperation” so the workforce lives and works together under mutually acceptable behaviour norms and standards (Tiorean and Bratucu, 2009, p.245). In that vein, the statements assist the bureaucracy pursue power in the same manner the market pursues profit, necessitating target procedural rules to ensure total employee empowerment so the system runs smoothly and with excellence. As indicated in Chapter 1, while the introduction of the construct is meant to ensure practicable

compatibility, it also has to contend with antagonistic cleavages, failing which it serves an obscure purpose.

As an economic model, the Corporate Lifecycle model elucidates the implications of the public choice perspective. Figure 2.3 shows the key stages corporations go through during their lifetime. The initial stages of ‘Infancy and Go-Go’ along the left limb signify organization flourish, boom and optima culminating in the ‘Prime’ stage, the climax of the vision-mission metric whereby all the footprints are practically fulfilled. Although so much happens in-between, at this point the corporate offers the best products, services and workflows ever, making it the envy of the rest.

Figure 2.3 The Corporate Lifecycle Model (Source: Adizes', 2015)

From ‘The Fall’ stage (or late prime / stable) at the top of the curve, the right limb signals descent through the problematic ‘Aristocracy and Recrimination’ stages to the ‘Bureaucracy and Death’ stages. Largely dogged by aging, the stages are cauldrons of pathologies – staleness, witch-hunts, rigidity, reactions and client neglect, culminating in failure to pursue and sustain long-term opportunities, especially the corporation’s upper hand in the market. Emphasis is on causes and sources of problems rather than what to do with them. As it slowly loses its flexibility and vitality, the corporate is rendered “largely incapable of generating sufficient resources for self-sustenance. It justifies its existence by the simple fact that the organization serves a purpose that is of interest to another political and business entity willing to support it” (Adizes’). It has reached the level of artificial life support as rebirth or sustainable

development becomes extremely hard unless by artificial means. At the 'Death' stage no one is committed to sustaining the corporate anymore, causing to it to physically close down.

As corporations, the institutions do reveal these stages, in particular the vision-mission drive to attain the Prime stage (or full technocapitalism) versus the reality of the Bureaucracy stage they find themselves embroiled in, which ushers the 'principal–agency' problem, whether mandates will be fulfilled as agreed or unprocedural trends will break the rules and usher entropy. Evidence largely points towards the rulebook basking in both the representative bureaucracy and the punishment-centred bureaucracy. Formal rules and procedures affecting all stakeholders constitute the former, in addition to which are the imposed, coercive rules of the latter. Resembling a bank account ravaged by stratospheric inflation, but whose survival rests on more bearer cheques stocking more inflammation, the punishment-centred bureaucracy has assumed the upper hand packaged through the constant refrain to 'punish offenders severely'. The intensity of systems and rules to police the rules breeds tension between the formal rules and the informal, normative ways of the students-workforce, ultimately, rendering operations tense and terse, suffocating initiatives.

Since many institutions border on fully-fledged bureaucracies, they are, in many respects, steeped in the chronic breeding of malfunctions, rituals, red tape and defence walls, or bureau-pathology for short. According to the Lifecycle Model, at this point, the organization finds itself reeling under many systems and rules, run and ravaged by ritual and less reason amid leadership disconnect. Unbridled policy monopoly creates buffers to reduce disruptions from the external environment, forcing customers to develop elaborate approaches to bypass the roadblocks. The Lifecycle model cautions that "monopolies and government agencies that are quarantined from competitive pressure and provide a large employment base, often live long and very expensive artificially prolonged lives." Hence, with the corporatization atypically at a standstill, the faulted continuous improvement or causal ups and downs make some brands renowned while others remain unknown in spite of their statements, giving the impression that some bureaus are good at interpreting their visions while others are less able to do so, courting mediocrity.

According to Jaffee (2008), McDonaldization's strict regimen, involving the principles of "efficiency, calculability, predictability, control", signifies corporatization inroads into higher

education, paving way for technocapitalism to permeate the institutional metric. Efficiency is reflected in the well set and well planned curricula designs, departmentation, the 80:20 rule, semesterization, online registration and dispensing results and awards; calculability on the *number* of points at entry, of courses to be taken, of credits to graduate, of learning hours and lessons to be taught, and of allowable semester grades; predictability on the standardized degree programmes, fixed syllabi and course outlines, lecture delivery, and examinations; and, control, on the budgetary allocations and payment plans, course choices, requirements and prerequisites, timetables, class registers and compulsory attendance, and the physical design and normative order of the classroom. Complementing the metric are the quality assurance yardsticks from responsible agencies as outlined in the next chapter.

In a nutshell, the corporatism means full transformation of the institutional bureaucracy according to world class business standards exemplified by McDonalds fast-food outlet and other equivalent corporations. Ultimately, technocapitalism is the standard and way to go if the nation is to catch up with the rising rest. However, as the discussion further illustrates, typical of high tech solutions, other critical issues are overlooked with both tame and wicked problems enlarging (Jaffee).

2.3.2 Research models

Table 2.1 sums up studies by Morphew and Hartley (2006), Wang, et al. (2007) and Opiyo-Newa (2010) based on different text rules. Using content analysis, Morphew and Hartley emerged with 13 core categories of *Elements* classifying the 300 mission statements they studied from private and public four-year universities and colleges across the United States. Using content analysis and the student *t*-test Wang, et al. emerged with 15 *Themes* in their comparative analysis of Thematic Differences in Mission Statements between Four-Year Public Institutions and Two-Year Colleges in Texas. Last, using focus group discussions and interviews Opiyo-Newa emerged with four *Core Outcomes* in the case study of the United States International University, East Africa. In spite of the pluralism, the elements/themes/outcomes underscore the variability of diversity as a concept and the capacity of the construct to integrate phenomena, which explains the striking commonalities in the structure of the vision-mission components.

By and large 'sameness' is the operating standard in concurrence with the conclusion by Morphew and Hartley (2006, p.464) that, while "no two institutions had precisely the same

configuration of elements...striking commonalities existed across the groups.” This signifies the greater convergence rather than divergence around the corporate philosophy and core ideologies resulting in slender differences. Morphew and Hartley (2006, p.469) then surmise that it is such convergence which invites criticisms of ‘meaningless, self-aggrandizing, vapid statements’, although, as they argue further, the criticisms appear to ignore the complexities surrounding purpose and, therefore, the fact that the statements serve a lot more than as mere ‘signals and symbols’ or plain determinants. Rather, the institutions use them “to communicate their utility and willingness to serve in terms that are both normative and politically apt.” In short, the construct’s curricula dexterity induces sensitivity to the multiple undertakings and stakeholders.

Table 2.1 The vision-mission statements macro-goals

Elements	Themes	Outcomes
serves local area; liberal arts; commitment to diversity; prepare for world; religious affiliation; civic duty/service; values; student development; teaching centred; access; a sense of community; leadership. (Source: Morphew & Hartley, 2006)	leadership; citizenship; cultural diversity; life-long learning; excellence in teaching & research; creativity; academic achievement; critical thinking; collaboration and partnership; academic readiness and skill development; vocational and technical skills; access to higher education; student services; community focus; technology. (Source : Wang, et al. 2007)	higher order thinking; global understanding and multicultural perspective; literacy; preparedness for career and community service (Source: Opiyo-Newa, 2010)

The study developed the footprints conceptual model which was compared with and standardised against the three studies in Table 2.1. Except for the evaluation footprint without clearly matching indicators, the rest of the elements/themes/outcomes matched with the different footprints. For example, ‘serves local area, civic duty, student development, community focus, leadership, life-long learning, literacy, vocational and technical skills, preparedness for career and community service, and global understanding and multicultural perspective’ converged with constituency servicing, while ‘access (to higher education), student services, leadership, collaboration and partnership’ resonated with governance. Relationally, the footprints model was the basis for healthy divergence and convergence, or

'cross-vergence' (as Nwagbara would put it), providing sufficient latitude and longitude to join forces and share information and ideas.

Operationally, the statements cascade to different units – divisions, faculties, departments and sections. For example, the vision of the BUSE Research and Postgraduate Centre is to be the core provider of resources that support the teaching, learning, research and community service activities undertaken at BUSE. Its mission is to provide current, relevant and expert support to research as a major activity as well as provide information on postgraduate issues in accordance with the International University Standards in fulfilment of its role to facilitate teaching, learning, research and community service at BUSE. Last, competence, teamwork and professionalism make up the core values.

Similarly, the vision of the UZ's Human Resources (HR) Department is "to be a leader in the delivery of high quality and value driven human resources management services and be recognised as such by our internal and external clients." In turn, the mission is "enhancing the quality of service delivery through hiring of highly qualified human resources at all levels and through retaining and optimally utilizing those already serving." To this end, the Department's position is that the University should "recognise and reward hard work and achievement as well as provide fair and effective human resources policies relating to recruitment, remuneration, promotion, advancement and disciplinary procedures which encourage justice, transparency, fairness, stability of tenure and trust." As the examples illustrate, the lower level statements become more incisive (the governance footprint in both cases) with the potential to enlarge the legitimate disorder. Unless to illustrate issues, they were discussed under the main statements.

In conclusion, the vision-mission-core values construct reflects the prevailing philosophical mandate to direct the ideal state or desired outcome (the vision); the default journey or operations and activities (the mission); and the values and behaviour standards anchoring the mandate (the values). Notwithstanding differences in wording and related challenges, the branding is basically convergent. Theoretically, the construct pushes the mobilisation of manpower thresholds as the *nerve centre* of institutional growth, competitiveness and recharged stakeholder equity – amidst the challenge as to who actually inspires: the visionary or the statements; or is it both? Before venturing further, it is important to analyse the other

component of the knowledge aim – the technological society-sustainable dividend and what both mean to humanity in general, the Zimbabwean scape included.

2.4 The technological society franchise

The technological society is the hub of the vision-mission statements with all institutions, in one way or the other, typically mandated to achieve it or, if not, to provide the requisite support. In significance, it is the 3rd generation creative force after the theories of evolution and the great design (Creation) whose miracle is not a result of random forces, but an outcome of one of the greatest developments in human history outside the universe. The psycho-technics endowments are the mainstay of the material production and innovations to realise the much-sought paradigm of sustainable development.

Reduced to the premium language of the University of Illinois, the holistic package espouses a brilliant future in which the students and the institutions thrive and the citizens, the nation and the world benefit; a future of well renowned leaders among public-private institutions: transforming lives and serving society by educating, creating knowledge and, with excellence, putting the knowledge to work in economic development and other spheres. None lie outside this rationale, only they are more utopian than extropian.

Hence, excellence and world class and their equivalents form the heart of the statements, signifying the quest for top class, unsurpassable products, goods and services beyond the current level of human endeavour. By description, like gold, such products, goods or services are highly priced; are unique, exceptional and matchless; are one of a kind; and, are *the* real mark for *singularity* – the key to the technology exponential syndrome, or superintelligent beings and creations, or technocapitalism – now the backbone to human advancement.

By definition, singularity is a point at which, over space and time, a function takes on an exponential value. Outside its numerous mathematical functions and from the research perspective, it means an infinite human resource value exceeding balance across all odd-even indicators. The HR *infinite* is: innumerable in number; immense in diversity; liberal in knowledge, skills and values; inexhaustible in creations, ideas, inventions and innovations; robotic in efficiency; emotionally intelligent; prodigious in productivity/entrepreneurship; illimitable mass consumption; democratic in governance; is a theocratic/ecumenical

commonwealth; and is transitionally renewable *ad infinitum*. Therefore, as the basis for capitalist fertility, singularity's core tenets are the only way to sustain a robust market niche capable to address the psychosocial complexities surrounding the profit-power-uncertainty momentum and other relationships.

In the article "The end of evolution", FairfaxDigital, citing Professor Alan Goldstein (2003, para.2), posits that the nanotechnology revolution is behind it all. Through the fusion of flesh or biology and technology, a new creature called '*Homo Technologicus*': a creature with so many modifications and materially so smart that it "won't see like us, breed like us, feed like us or need like us" is being created. The singularity hypothesis avers that, given the rapid evolution of humanity and technology towards each other, transhumanism will occur within the next few decades producing the perfect condition of posthumanity marked by a new and better creation never seen before. Rivera (2012, para.1) posits that *Techno sapiens*, which he defines as the "new intelligent species resulting from Homo sapiens' integration with technology" is the inevitable outcome of the extremely rapid technological developments being witnessed today.

The biomechanically modified being or *Homo Technologicus* is the genetically and physically metamorphosed new sapiens different in body chemistry and lifestyles from *Homo sapiens*. With enhanced abilities and senses, it is engaged in activities driven by the very engines of its ingenuity, inventing and being reinvented by its own inventions – tools, machines, and other forms of intellectual property, that not only inspire human minds, but inspire themselves as well. Lienhard (2004, para.5) cites the microcomputer and its invention as an example of this process, and how the machine literary invented itself, as "at each point in its evolution the machine revealed more and more of its potential to us. At each stage, it exposed one more step that this or that person recognised and leaped to complete" without anybody actually claiming to have invented it.

Summing up the literature, Bostrom (2005, para.4&5) observes that the radical spectacular advances in technology hold promise for either the Heaven or the Hell future scenarios, or if mishandled, a combination of both. The "GRIN technologies" herald immense "prospects for superintelligent machines, non-aging bodies, direct connections between human brains or between brain and computer, fully realistic virtual reality, and the reanimation of patients in

cryonic suspension”, but equally “at an accelerating pace, with environmental brutalities almost unimaginably destroying large chunks of the human race or the biosphere.” He further observes how the Heaven Scenario displays the unstoppable

curve of exponentially increasing technological change, leading, before 2030, to the creation of greater-than-human intelligence, which proceeds to improve itself at such a rate as to exceed comprehension. Almost unimaginably good things...including the conquering of disease and poverty, but also an increase in beauty, wisdom, love, truth and peace are happening pretty much on their own accord, without deliberate steering.

Similarly, debating at the 5th Science and Technology and the Future of Humankind Conference, Japan, Furukawa (2008, p.1) observes that, in the face of global challenges and threats, new theories to support continued human affluence must be born. He recommends the “Fusion of Knowledge” involving adopting technological innovations that, among other things, ensure ‘Innovative clean energy in harmony with Earth’s environment; Information devices with no age barrier or devices which can “read” peoples’ feelings; Stress-free, accident-free driving or operation of industrial and transport systems; and, Security-assured, human-error free information systems’. Such high-tech installations will render industry capable to ‘preserve Earth’s environment as well as achieve a comfortable information society and a life-long healthy society – that is, a society where industry and consumer appliances are gentle on humans’. This calls for proper and accurate ‘fusion of society’s needs and its citizens’ needs’, and even further still, a “fusion between policies and regulatory and systemic reforms” on a global scale to lead the process’.

Characteristically, as Rivera (2011, para.5) observes, singularity is the domain – i.e., the human capacity to “re-invent their own natures into states of being low-tech approaches of self-discipline, hard work and patience could never really make possible.” At the heart of singularity is the “law of accelerating returns, which manifests itself as exponential technological progress” (Bostrom, 2009, p.18). Its total import is that science works; it makes things work; it is talents and wisdom that produce practical results and products; things are done right and rightly, correctly and precisely for maximum resource appropriations. Scientific and technological planning and production mean robotic efficiency across the economy. This blends well with Chiwome and Gambahaya’s (1998) description of science and technology as the most vital instrument behind human endeavour and adjustment to the environment, validating in practical ways the truth and meaning of ideas and assertions that affect human interests and purposes – the very essence of technocapitalism.

Through the combination of space exploration with atmospheric, oceanic and the earth sciences, humanity continues to enlarge his capacity to accelerate, control and transform the biotic, abiotic and other socio-environmental forces, patterns and processes to his advantage. The increasing defiance of adverse physical conditions and limitations, coupled with the capacity to combat extremities like plagues and diseases continues to foster more and better wellbeing which will, ultimately, culminate in the total elimination of the myriad socio-environmental challenges, especially poverty and related rampant inhuman practices, predictably, as the economies of scale and opportunity costs level each other out (Bostrom, 2009; McCarthy, 2012).

Pushing the techno-progress and cutting into *Homo simplex* numbers, is the vast array of self-medication drugs, self-health tracking devices and implants, artificial transplants and inseminations, Anti-Retroviral drugs to fight the Human Immunodeficiency Virus and the Acquired ImmunoDeficiency Syndrome (HIV and AIDS), genetically modified organisms (GMO) to support the burgeoning populations and soon, human operating systems (HOPs), to name a few. Through eliminating cell damage, cryonics will successfully freeze human bodies to be raised later when the disease they suffer from can be cured, extending to preservation of brains for future transplants. As Hook (2013, p.1) observes, HOPs (the doctors inside the body) applications will

include devices that would: (1) develop and implement new tissue to heal arthritic joints and torn ligaments, (2) Los plaque in heart and brain blood vessels, (3) manufacture and deliver certain medicines in the body, such as insulin; and (4) replace or repair damaged brain cells in people with diseases like Parkinson's disease (liver included).

Meanwhile, many previously dreaded diseases the likes of small pox, polio, diphtheria and even HIV and AIDS no longer pose chronic and acute threats any more. Future spin-offs will even witness decline in doctor-patient ratios and demand for hospitalization as more people take greater control and care of their own health. The totality of biological or cybernetic immortality will mean the total elimination of aging, illness, diseases, death and many of society's ills (poverty, crime, social class), going beyond better health practices and the preservation of life (Rivera, 2010; Roy, 1999).

Likewise, as a result of total control of the biochemical processes of human senescence,

uploading (neuroscience and information technology) continues to revolutionise lives and occupations through access to more and better communication, learning, research, exchange, and innovation. For instance, as Hook (2013, p.2) observes, direct neural interfacing with computer systems means that humans have “entered the computer and now live in it. At last, the human brain, embedded in a computer, has been released from weak mortal flesh...It is in control of their own destiny, housed in indestructible lattices of silicone, and no longer restricted in their many years...such a life will live forever.” The developments in artificial intelligence are already proving highly attractive to people with disabilities and those who need access to vast sources of information.

In-keeping with demand for higher exergy and consumability values, as Wadhaw (2014) observes, the digital transformation is driving technology and business to re-align and invest in new models like additive manufacturing and IP technology infrastructures for maximum useful work extractable from systems as they reversibly come into equilibrium. Robotics, coupled with limitless energy opportunities from magnetism will continue the production shift from scarce to abundantly cheap manufactures and services, relying on far fewer workers. Indeed, by 2030 computers and robots would have replaced hosts of jobs, including the professions, by up to 35%. According to Bostrom (2009) and McCarthy (2012), projects like the ‘hybrid habitat’ will translate all manner of environments across the universe into ‘survival and liveability’ making very viable the settlement of other planets or outer space, creating virtual settlements as the states spread away from each other to exercise more autarky.

Philosophers like Isaac Newton (1642-1727), August Comte (1798–1857), Albert Einstein (1879-1955), John Dewey (1859–1952), Stephen Hawking and many more, coupled with science fiction writers like Jules Verne (1828–1905), Isaac Asimov (1920–92), Robert Heinlein (1907–88), and George Lucas (of the Star Wars fame) are credited the Prophets and Fathers of modern science. They have inspired countless scientists both past and present leading to the colossal technological leap and other scientific advances. Resultantly, the likes of positivism and Instrumentalism have progressively co-joined capital and technology together, giving birth to diverse philosophical views on science and technology and its role in the development agenda. As noted, technocapitalism is both the notable beneficiary and Frankenstein monster. In the not too distant future, singularity is likely to be a new science discipline in its own right. However, in much of Africa, the absence of such a

powerful science tradition is a big poser to the envisaged science revolution, leading to a lukewarm science culture of limited substance and import, ironically, dependent on and deriving inspiration from technological imperialisms.

From its interactive influence with the state, market and capital, science and technology has assumed a compelling primacy and universal validity among non-Western nations eager to develop and modernise their economies and societies. Technological homogenization is the way to go; it is the future, which fits well with the desire to foster the sustainable development goal for a technological cybermarket away from the tag of poor developing countries torn apart by crude capitalism. The target is to nurture the best professional or scholarly minds that are a cut above the rest, endowed with psycho-technics and the capacity to sustain powerful mandates anchored on techno-environmental responsibility platforms. A higher science and technology throughput is, therefore, totally ingenuous whereas a lower one is the opposite and a burden to humanity.

2.4.1 The technological society challenge: enfranchising versus disenfranchising

Geisler's 'paradox of progress' sums up the franchising-disenfranchising challenge behind the science-technology drive: to enhance more scientific 'growth and prosperity' and, in the process, celebrate greater creativity and enlightenment versus strong fears of rising turmoil and social unrest from its development and applications (Rivera, 2010). This is to mean that the technological society must contend with its opposite, *Homo simplex*, who are the disadvantaged segments of society that lack access to the social benefits enjoyed by the technological society. Yet their survival requires the know-how and culture of the latter. As discussed so far, *Homo simplex* is a living reality across the African landscape given the deep levels of poverty and disadvantaged societies.

There are two scenarios to the paradox of progress. The first view says that, given the malleability of physical laws as the source of consciousness, and that the results of such laws are computable, it will be no surprise that the GRIN technologies will completely overwhelm humanity. Naturally, neo-Luddites are uncomfortable with the technological dictatorship as safe, proper usage will be harder to control and abuse much harder to prevent with rising chances of enslavement among the uninitiated. Indeed, as Hook (2013, p.4) amply

puts it, “a quick look at the history of technology shows that for almost all the technical “fix”, myriad other problems arise” and worse if they are irreversible.

Consequently, Geisler (2001) argues that the challenge is whether or not to accept the technological change versus the fear and anxiety that go with accepting and venturing into the unknown: whether to invest in open science or to impose controls and restrictions on its generation, conduct and implementation. The question then arises, between the two, which scenario is responsible for perpetuating the uneasy technological society—*Homo simplex* gap? Meanwhile, to realize the Heaven scenario, humanity must scale the crossroad or else it will find itself consumed by the Hell scenario, torn by the multiple existential risks related to *Homo simplex* stigmatization, climate change, stripping harvests, political polarisation, nuclear weapons, designer pathogens, high-energy particle colliders and accretion disk flooding (Geisler, 2001; Bostrom, 2009). The dilemma is testimony on how the anti-technology crusade is only matched by the syndrome of learned helplessness, with both groups having resigned fate and destiny to the unstoppable advances of science and technology, evidently with both conditions posing a big challenge.

The other scenario is that, whether born out of the technological gap or not, *Homo simplex* is the burning reality, now the Achilles heel of the technological society and where lies the problem? According to Geisler (2001, p.2), *Homo simplex* raises technical, social and “ethical issues with regard the applications and adoption of scientific and technological innovations in the economy and society.” He cites as the technology drawbacks:

...understanding of the role that science and technology play in the economy and society; awareness of the trends of science and technology and the necessity of participating in the environment they create; utilizing the science and technology in all facets of life, including work, learning, social intercourse; and understanding of the diverse consequences of not participating in the science and technology-driven economy and society (Geisler, p.6).

The terrain is distinctly one of crude development (or proxy capitalism) riddled with negative exponential growths and chronic downgrade processes revealing a widening and deepening multidimensional poverty index (MPI) the technological society has to grapple with. Spanning the numerous intrigues surrounding the science-technology journey are chronic disease epidemics and pandemics; distorted demographics, hunger and poverty; chronic stubborn illiteracy rates, inequality and inequity; chronic racism/tribalism; chronic resource wars;

infinite dictatorship and oppression; and the infinite lack of innovativeness leading to gross dependency and other crossroads (Olivier, 2010). The human development measures point towards rising and widening disenfranchisement and all the trappings of the Hell scenario that is rapidly consuming much of society creating large chunks of poor and vulnerable individuals and groups.

According to the culture-fit theory, science and technology is a product and attribute of a particular culture and, therefore, is never universal as claimed. Its internal imperialism is the source and cause of the problem. It has failed to blend harmoniously with the indigenous conditions: to take root with the same force and power as it has done in Western culture. Instead, it is a tool for control and subjugation by the West, now driving the stealthiest and much more sinister of imperialisms – technological imperialism (Roy, 1999). It has become a colossal burden on other cultures that are yet to design their own science and technology. Rather than help people meet modern challenges, the science has tended to denigrate and supplant their vernacular cultures creating cultural confusions. Rather than represent growth prospects, as Verhelst (1990) argues, the singularity breeds the *false infinite* (false productivity, false consumption, false growth, false development) generating the ‘paradox of consumption’ by mixed societies that produce what they do not consume and consume what they do not produce. The 2008–10 collapse of the free-market philosophy is sufficient evidence of the vulnerability of the science and technology rhetoric.

On the other hand, the universal-fit theory argues that, just like any other discipline, science and technology is a social tool at the disposal of every learner to use or apply its principles and tenets freely to solve whatever challenges and problems confronting them (Geisler, 2001; Rivera, 2010). As Sachs (1992, p.229) notes, what makes science and technology even more universal is that it is said to be impartial and objective: “is above emotion, caste, community, language, religion and is international.” Hence, the more investment there is the greater the prospects for growth and other opportunities. According to Roy (1999), it is the misappropriation reflected through improper utilization of products and results which is responsible for the paradox of progress and the massive costs human and environmental conditions. The earlier contradictions return showing how the utilization of science and technology is cause for both celebration and concern given the diverse implications for society and the environment.

The most obvious is the fact that science and technology only makes sense among scientists and technologists while those lacking the skills, power and money to buy it barely participate in much of its domains. Arguably, according to Sachs (1992, p.299), this is the very paradox with science and technology in that

planning, science and technology have become the principal means for usurping the people's rights to the domains of knowledge and production, for extinguishing and dismissing the people's right to create knowledge, and diminishing their right to intervene in matters of public interest or affecting their own subsistence and survival.

Reviewing the debate, Mnkandla (2006, p.60) observes how, overall, science and technology uses universalism and objectivity precisely to energise itself as well as deny, rob and enslave the uninitiated across different scapes, now standing above the interests of all and enforceable on all. The people have lost the right to function as competent human beings unless indoctrinated in science. They are deficient as human beings and have to be recreated through science. For the majority of humankind, therefore, the psychosocial changes have been seductive and traumatic, disembedding and alienating. Furthermore, not only has the scientific culture proved difficult to access in the face of the rigidity of *ubuntuism* and neo-patrimonialism (the hybrid Western-African leadership-management genre), the scientific dividend has neither succeeded to counter the scorching effects of global warming, neo-liberalism, radical Islamization and global inequity nor the vagaries of unstable interest rates, unfriendly tax regimes, the debt burden, and the destabilizing transfer of wealth from the poor to the rich. Meanwhile, poverty and climate change are dividing the global community with the offenders and victims trading accusations of all sorts some of which intensify opposition to science (Tandon, 2008; Cop 21, 2015).

Furthermore, is the dilemma related to the way techno-sapiens invests according to its consumptive demands and that of its offspring versus the basic needs of the poor and disadvantaged. Since he will not invest where there are no returns, the world is witnessing the diversion of scarce resources away from very pressing needs, especially social safety nets, towards scientific investments that produce luxury goods and services with minimal spread effects (for example, more weaponry or holidaying in outer space). In addition, some science applications like GMOs, cloning, and electronic gadgets invite strong resentment and, therefore, opposition to science. The controversy on the health effects of GMOs rages

on with some countries like Zimbabwe resisting growing such crops but importing the food, while cloning poses the risk of demeaning human procreation and even threatens to eliminate it, a condition many fraternities are extremely jittery about. UNESCO, as cited by Mnkandla (2006, p.63) forecasts that

ethnic discrimination using gene sequences of human reproduction threatens to dispossess humanity of many of its rights and liberties, including the right to reproduction, leading to increased subjugation to science and technology, while on the other, the bio-ethnic effects of chemicalised and genetically modified food is beginning to manifest itself through higher incidences of illnesses, cancers, diseases, disorders and deaths especially among non-Western peoples. Ethnic societies with lower tolerance levels face the possibility of reduction of their populations, if not outright extinction.

Adding to the debate, Bostrom's (2009) four families of scenarios on humanity's future discusses technology as an existential risk either driving his extinction, or phases of recurrent collapse, or on a more positive scale, driving the higher levels of the plateau of existence or posthumanity. Also, Owen (2009, Prediction Two, para.10) echoes the argument noting how in the event "the rich and powerful keep the artificial-selection technology to themselves, then the split between the upper-class, dominant population and the lower-class, genetically oppressed population" is practicable.

Equally, while electronic gadgets support and promote myriad life services, others like ICT gadgets and social media devices also promote corruption, offensive intrusions and invasions like prying into people privacy, spying and cyber-attacks or espionage in the interest of power and security (for example, the USA's National Security Agency (NSA) 2013 spy scam on world leaders and the threats to South Africa's banking and finance system in 2015). McCarthy (2012, p.1) further argues that the scientific prospects gained from molecular nanotechnology (MNT) are shrouded in fear of the dangers the technology is likely to bring about:

...dangers, hard to visualize at this point, but all stemming from the radical power of this new tool. Whether super weapons of unspeakable destructiveness or home-made attempts at genocide, at least some of the potential products of an advanced molecular manufacturing ability give us pause, making us wonder if the heralded "Age of Nanotechnology" will be nothing more than a finely engineered disaster.

Already tied to such concerns is the fear of robots not only taking over jobs, but of killer robots refusing to obey human commands or issuing their own commands, leading to human harm or massacres of immense proportions. In short, in the event of program-failure leading to

failure to avert the collapse of the laws of robots, robot rebellion is an unavoidable reality with grim consequences humanity.

Summed up, the technological society debate is a complex affair that is as desirable as it is contestable. Geisler (2001) and Bostrom (2009) note how the implementation of science and technology is a paradox of opportunity versus loss of opportunity, of growth prospects versus foreclosure brakes, and of good versus evil. Implemented well, it is a 'great equalizer' able to pull more people out of *Homo simplex* into the ranks of a modern society resulting in economies of scale (hence, the lavish praise of STEM education). But in-between are brakes, driven by the desire to curtail illegal practices and the challenges of misuse, abuse and recklessness. Yet, as humanity's most celebrated construction and, therefore, the most effective and efficient tool to create value and benefits to the economy and society, there is no alternative to singularity, except more and better domestication of science and technology. Fear and idealization and, therefore, increased control of science and technology is not the solution, but "provision of adequate conditions that will allow it to progress at its own rate, while maintaining a balance between incentives and boundaries – based on the analysis of benefits and risks" (Geisler, 2001, p.10).

Without fail, in pushing science's positives the techno-progressivism must consciously embrace the fact that "human progress should not only focus on technical and scientific measures, but also on ethical and social ones" as well, as technology is as technical as it is social in its influence (Rivera, 2010, para.15). Transhumanism is here and now and visions of 'advancement of humanity' through STEM education mean that the developing countries are well steeped in it. The only choice is to embrace science and be members of the high technology league. On this front, the Republic of Rwanda's education and rural agriculture IT programmes reflect how well it understands this philosophy, enabling producers and the market to talk business and progress together.

In essence, what the institutional vision-mission statements are emphatically proclaiming is that progress towards the technological society is no longer a mere feasibility, but a practical reality at the fingertips of the institutions. Specifically and essentially, no job is undoable nor beyond the VAE measure which is a mistake if Zimbabwe is not doing so already. The vehicle for the voyage now exists from the exquisitely crafted vision-mission statements, simply

waiting uploading, and the end is both bright and certain. It does not matter that individuals are turned into (production) machines or gadgets and global commodities first (human resources) and human beings last to address the demands of capitalist fertility (Broch-Due and Schroeder, 2002). Such are the predicaments of the technocapitalist springboard and the extent it has colonised education with the latter receiving it with open arms.

2.5 The sustainable development climax

The 1987 Brundtland Report defines sustainable development as the ability to meet the needs of the present without compromising the needs of future generations. The Principles of International Law for Sustainable Development (ILSD, slides 21-23) define it as the duty of the state to ensure: (1) sustainable use of natural resources; (2) equity and the eradication of poverty; (3) common but differentiated obligations; (4) precautionary approach to human health, natural resources, and ecosystems; (5) public participation and access to information and justice; (6) good governance; and (7) integration and interrelationship, particularly in relation to human rights and social, economic, and environmental objectives. Last, summatively, Sachs (1992, p.15) defines it as “the cumulative, linear progression from ignorance to knowledge and modern life, the steady inexorable movement away from poverty to better social wellbeing” or to posthumanity, fully lodging sustainable development in the ambit of science and technology education.

In brief, in line with the ILSD, sustainable development is that long-term approach which takes into account the inextricable nature of relationships between science and technology, between technology and capital, and between developed and developing powers and ensuring appropriate combinations amid the correct standard for learning and doing things right and rightly all of the time. In other words, the macro and micro fundamentals or progressive change in the quality of life correspond with the means of economic growth with minimum waste or misallocation of resources. The social mobility, production methods and consumption patterns transform accordingly sustained by the ambient ecological balance and life support systems. To the CISDL (2005, p.3) this entails “...respect for regional, national and local ethnic and cultural diversity, and full public participation, peaceful coexistence in harmony with nature, without prejudice to and ensuring the quality of life of future generations.” It is the highest expectation of development excellence.

By description the development must be sustainable to usher the new Heaven which has rendered the concept the most popular and celebrated theory to hit the phenomenal-behavioural marketplace in recent times, however controversial. According to the Bradshaw Theory of Needs, materially, the people have migrated from the 'normative, felt, expressed and comparative' needs and, therefore, inequality and inequity (*Homo simplex*) and now live above the normative need of fulfilled necessities, rising to satisfied comforts, and finally, to luxurious lifestyles. This is full equalization through total access to technology and its complete array of attributes for survival in the high-tech environments.

Therefore, the learned scientific and technological arts must literally convert into a spontaneous psyche, into internalized custom and practice, and into a generic standard that resonates within the people themselves as they experience the turbulent challenges around them and how sustainability is characteristically unsustainable. One such uncharacteristic, according to Rabinbach (1992, p.297), is the meaning of work following decline of the 'human motor' to the extent that "meaning has disappeared from work; consequently, work has disappeared as a source of meaning" in life posing profound existential challenges and risks.

In many respects, sustainable development has been central to human development philosophy and ideology since classical times. Malthusianism, Marxism and Darwinism moving on to modern day Science and Technology, the Economic Theory of Value and New Environmentalism represent the multiple interpretive responses. Today focus is on human security which Tevera and Moyo (2000, p.5) define as a condition that "ensures options for the mitigation of threats to human rights and the environment as well as guaranteeing the freedom of those affected to exercise those options." As the pivotal philosophy, sustainable development must be tied to everything that humanity does, more so the curriculum.

Accordingly, the sustainable development must be taught, learned, researched, tested and practiced from all angles; it must be facilitated, exchanged, cultured, applied and collaborated in all ways practicable to guarantee higher investment returns, to the extent that the grass is being pulled in order for it to grow – a new phenomenon in human history. As the voice of the vision-mission statements, human security is the positive multiplier to assure the people full access to hard and soft infrastructures, as well as protection and empowerment to respond to risks and threats in a more sustainable manner than has been the case before.

Thus far, sustainable development has been a steep mountain to climb. The unfulfilled MDGs are testimony to this. As a result of the historical ill-planting of capitalism the nation states inherited massive challenges some of which they could not have foreseen (Cohen, 2015). The dilemma of the chicken-egg scenario, whereby massive “economic growth is needed to eliminate poverty and the elimination of poverty is needed for purposes of protecting the environment” has left the sustainable development mired in both the false positive and true negative glitches (Broch-Due and Schroeder, 2002, p.24). Obtaining, then, are turf wars between Human Capital Theorists, State Culturalists/Nationalists and Developmentalists versus Environmentalists. To sustain the torque and insatiable appetite for resources, the former perpetrate rampant socio-environmental problems in the name of development regardless of the data and grammar mistakes that get worse with time.

With corporatism and technological imperialism exercising the oversight, the misdirected inculcation of the capitalist psych and related propaganda have pushed the development fiasco to astronomical levels (Gundani, 2015), paradoxically, increasing the marginalization. Insiders like President Paul Kagame (2015) speak of degrading ‘begging, crying and whining’ for development assistance at international forums like the Sino/India-Africa Summits. Meanwhile, environmental lobbyists are denounced dismal theorists, if not, virulent pests and intellectual toxins peddling a monstrous ideology that persistently comes between man and the work he must do to sustain and improve his livelihood (Berliner, 2002).

Additionally, problematic power dynamics pushing their own brand of progress pose further strain on sustainable development. Naim (2013) defines them as the More, Mobility, and Mental revolutions in reference to: the rapidly growing population of Millennials together with the socio-political, religious and ethnic break-ups; the fast-changing individual, social, political, community and environmental diversities; and the soaring changes in attitudes, passions, beliefs and aspirations, respectively. Highly vocal, relying on social media and modern warfare, and driven by the desire for independence or to resist oppression, the revolutions fan multiple behaviour orgies linked to unbridled narcissism, radicalisation, separatism, and commodity fetishism. Their impetuses render collaborative efforts to curtail global problems critical to sustainable development much harder to achieve.

Hence, for the majority of the people in Africa, Verhelst's (1990, p.157) classical observation that "far from feeling themselves truly participating citizens of independent states, enjoying the fruits of development, the people find themselves threatened (*if not jailed*) by it, frustrated by dysfunctional capacity, official harassment and rampant corruption, hemmed in by state frontiers, and crushed by the alien, centralizing and unifying laws" (*Emphasis added*) still rings true and remains a dangerous social minefield. In response, sustainable development is witnessing the mushrooming of development and disaster management schools, institutes, humanitarian services and other bodies majoring in civic and development work and concerned with disease, hunger, poverty and other social safety nets to prepare the people and the status quo for the inevitable crush, hence, lessen the damage and cushion the lucky few against the Hell scenario.

Hence, not only is the sustainable development technological lighthouse receding in the distance making it so difficult to reach destination, debatable is whether the vision-mission philosophy justifies the restoration of the structural trap that has engulfed developing country populations and their systems for decades. Sachs (1992) and Suarez-Villa (2009) observe how, whether there is cooperation with, or resistance to, capitalism the enculturation metastases into explosive behaviours whose onslaught affect the psychosocial order reflecting a new fetish showcasing intense fascination with myopia. The gullible market is misled into believing that it is on its way to paradise and all that it needs to do is to teach and learn hard through investing more in science and technology, notwithstanding the disproportionately disappointing results and how the technocapitalist dispensation is failing to play an emancipatory role nor to create a more just society (Gatawa, 1998; Mavhunga, Madondo, and Phiri, 2009; Nyathi, 2014; Olivier, 2010).

Without doubt, the struggle for sustainable development and, therefore, more science and technology, will continue to hold centre stage, albeit, with the institutions pronouncing more eloquent statements which will either improve human prospects or turn out to be excess capacity. Equally, the people will continue to keep their feet on both sides of the Atlantic: for capitalism's coveted benefits but ready to recoil to their cultural milieu (*to homo indigenus*) once the chips are down. Indeed, Burgis' (2015) observation of prospects of educated societies wallowing in poverty across Africa is a grim reality.

2.6 Synopsis of the nature and scope of the construct

The vision-mission philosophy is the panoramic view of an institution's mandate and, seemingly, the ideal tool for public indulgence to attain the potential learning product. It delimits issues of identity, purpose, assurance and pledge for the journey to the Promised Land, however slippery the terrain. According to Clark (1986, p.20), such philosophies constantly emerge as a result of the rapid "expansions and fragmentations of knowledge causing academics to seek reassurance in formulations that promise to pull things together again and provide some overarching meaning", resulting in the proliferation of "purportedly new statements" packed with alteration phrases of dubious distinction. In the circumstances, the galvanising role of institutional philosophy cannot be overemphasised. While some go by this, the temptation to emulate other constructs is evident, creating the quasi-Bible versions.

The construct's rainbow spectrum is as philosophical and technical to define and comprehend as it is difficult and stressful to securely put on the ground. The nebulous stimuli generate nebulous responses whether for or against the construct. But, most coveted is the 'superior' status signifying the desire for high profile mandates, reflecting the right and might of 'power' as a social investment. Both *de facto* and *de jure* power to handle uncertainty, inform the wisdom and import of the construct as a policy yardstick, with propaganda spins to convince all and sundry the order of the day. Campbell and Tawadey (2016, p.194) sum up the Messianic appeal as follows:

When the organization has a clear sense of purpose, direction and desired future state and when this image is widely shared, individuals are able to find their own roles both in the organization and in the larger society... This empowers individuals and confers status upon them because they see themselves as part of a worthwhile enterprise. They gain a sense of importance, as they are transformed from robots blindly following instructions to human beings engaged in a creative and purposeful venture.

Ideally, the construct is the perfect ladder for change and growth to foster sustainable development. Theoretically, its benefits outweigh any demerits when potential for increases in profitability is factored in: multiplying perfectly sustainable products and services, styles and relationships (Opiyo-Newa); putting the institutions into full "gear towards sustained capacity building for the increasingly technologically-driven and enterprise-based developments" (Yizengaw, 2003); stemming the most common degenerative disease of organizations – excess zeal or reckless enthusiasm "splintering their always limited

resources on things that are 'interesting' or look 'good' or 'profitable' rather than concentrating them on a very small number of productive efforts" (Smit, 2006, p.163); and, above all, delivering a developed Zimbabwe: industrialised, democratic, and socio-economically sustainable. They may not use the complex scientific language but they are consistent with the cause to build a techno-economically productive nation.

This is conscious of Muzondo's (2012) caveat that such business models do not always land easily in all contexts, putting the construct-institution relationship operationally at odds. From a public choice perspective, according to Buchanan (n.d., p.132) the corporatism posits contradictory behaviour norms with regard "what men 'should' do in their public choice roles rather than what they 'may', in fact, do in such roles", hence, emasculating the catalytic behaviour required to confront the power-profit-efficiency motive. In the context, the 'should' is institutionally legalistic whereas the 'may' is a conditional expression of possibilities and customised prompts. One is a tinder-box for rules, dictates, directives and codes capped by the stickler-for-duty and obligation standard. The other reflects flexible, innovative egging endorsing market politics.

As Buchanan (n.d., p.134) argues, the 'should' then ushers the challenge on "the optimal or efficient structure of rules and codes" to galvanise the immense feat for complete certainty and predictability the internal and external decisions, events and outcomes taking place. Typically, moral hazard and rent seeking behaviour become the fetish, with no volume of 'police patrols' (auditing schemes, etc.) and 'fire alarms' (procedures for detecting and reporting malpractices), however stringent, able to unmask the concealed, conceited appetite for social control as self-interests or individual utility maximization assume the upper hand. As Jaffee (2008, p.119) argues, for the citizenry, the cocktail of coercive rules defining the efficiency drive signals inevitable personal and collective losses the values of "freedom, creativity, contemplation, quality and individuality."

Tragically, the losses usher the double bureaucracy–market 'failure' or crude capitalism, fanning unstable welfare economics. From this standpoint, the construct is guilty of importing and perpetuating the bureau's inefficiencies under the guise of the market workers, stakeholders and tax payers can do very little about.

2.6 Summary

The chapter highlighted the nature and scope of the vision-mission philosophy and its institutionalization as a public choice initiative, and the extent it blended with the dynamics of technocapitalism. The construct synthesises the multiple purposes of the mandate which justifies its adoption as the critical driver and locus of the intellectual process, shared values and standards, inspiring continuous improvement and related franchises. However, its normative role faces utilitarian challenges courting problems in the attempt to scale up the scientific-technological franchising with a greater downward spin towards disenfranchisement. This, then, was the contextual purpose of the literature review to build a philosophical understanding of the role the vision-mission statements interconnect and intermediate in institutional management–curriculum endeavours. The next chapter expands the diversity of the construct, recounting the imminent benefits, costs and consequences from the perspectives of the model footprints.

CHAPTER III

3.0 The Vision-Mission Statements Rationale from the Perspective of the Model Footprints

3.1 Introduction

As mentioned in the last chapter, the choice of the footprints model was influenced by the ecosystem nature of the institutions with characteristic dimensions, inputs, processes and outputs which generate outcomes and impacts, hence, key in supply and demand matters critical to both the institutions and the constituency market. Epistemologically and operationally, the institutions are, therefore, preoccupied with the complex realities of each footprint to distil uncertainty and other VUCA challenges. That being the case, the operations must address the bread and butter issues related to each footprint, figuratively, to create a high-resolution image and reputation of successful capacities, networks and competitiveness that is the climax of the envisioned technocapitalism.

As Figure 2.1 shows, driven by constituency servicing, the interactions simultaneously generate and drive the other footprints and reciprocal characteristics to achieve the critical outcome of sustainable development as the novel and noble culture. For the visions and missions to succeed, and posing the major challenge to ponder, is the extent the footprints are well networked for everything to gel or jelly together with the political economy of the institutions and nation. Crucially, therefore, should one of the footprints stall, divert, or fail, chances of the construct realising sufficient progress become limited and uncertain. How, then, do the footprints play out to guarantee the befitting 'prime' standard or potential learning product that is a cut above the rest, the ultimate in functionality and standards?

3.2 Constituency Servicing

Higher education is a client-driven system and, functionally, constituency servicing is the very reason for its existence. The constituency is the whole nation, or the separate communities, societies and markets, extending to the global community. Its politics embraces the diverse government bodies, business, private organizations, the mass student populations, and the institution and its workforce. The needs and demands of these units differ and must be addressed sufficiently and efficiently. Over and above enlarging the needs and aspirations of each niche, poverty eradication is the ultimate goal in line with one of Nelson Mandela's

famous quote that ‘Overcoming poverty is not a gesture of charity. It is an act of justice. It is the protection of a fundamental human right, the right to dignity and a decent life.’

The public indulgence is enacted through full- and part-time public, private, formal and informal product and service deliveries dealing in diverse subjects reflecting curricula density and the corresponding expertise. Through multiple forms of intercourse, contacts and interactions which include conventional, parallel and block release programmes, consultancy, independent study, online, conferences, seminars, workshops, videotapes, distance learning, community services, remedial basic literacy and high-school boosts, as well as joint ventures, partnerships and other social services, the constituency is guaranteed a supply-demand match of favourable products, goods and services that free the nation of the challenges posed by *Homo simplex*.

To that end, Morphew and Hartley (2006, p.456) observe that the institutions use the construct to legitimise themselves both nationally and beyond as “it would seem that not having a mission statement begs the very legitimacy of a college or university.” In other words, the statements legitimately communicate specific expectations for and by the constituencies. Arguing further, they suggest that the institutions “may be using mission statements not for planning or cultural purposes, but as means of telling important stakeholders outside the institution that ‘we understand what you want and we’re going to deliver it to you’” (p.468). In that sense, the statements are declarations of relevance, or motivation and accessibility to the constituency which “represents maturation on the part of colleges and universities who are getting better at recognizing their patrons and prospective consumers and focusing their attention on what these folks want.” Indeed, for accreditation, the ZIMCHE (2011, p.1) demands that

the institution has a stated vision and mission that is supported by specific and clearly defined goals and objectives within the context of national development priorities and the latest international trends in education; that it has policy statements and action plans which are formulated to fulfil the stated vision and mission; and that it has a strategic plan to ensure the implementation of the mission.

In totality, the goals of the constituency servicing devolve around the overarching pillars of the development superstructure, entrepreneurialism, and community service. From the spectrum of its programmes and activities, higher education must bring about the requisite macro- and micro-socioeconomic changes starting at the individual to the broader community

and national level. Avalos (1996, p.10) sums it most eloquently indicating that the education transmits the tools “required by human beings to be able to survive, to develop their full capacities, to live and work in dignity, to participate fully in development, to improve the quality of their lives, to make informed decisions and to continue learning” which augurs well for constituency stability and progress. Therefore, through the visions and missions, the institutions are obligated to apply themselves to functionalise each pillar extensively to the full satisfaction of the different constituents. The subsequent exposé details the preoccupations entailed.

3.2.1 The development superstructure

Ever since President Harry Truman’s famous speech of January 20 1948, that “...greater production is the key to prosperity and peace. And the key to greater production is a wider and more vigorous application of modern science and technology” (Sachs, 1992), the new world was ushered to a new beginning in which development became the dominant metaphor in their affairs. And American technology was available to pull them from the shackles of underdevelopment. This was and still is the ‘prosperity’ gospel, now commonly referred to as ‘empowerment’ or emancipation to increase the capacity of the people to be productive and, therefore, voiceful against being voiceless, or to be able to play the profit-power-uncertainty game. According to Tiercan and Bratucu (2009, p.248) a successful profit-power confluence equips stakeholders with the “daring and information to allow them to make correct decisions under uncertainty as both profit and power exist because of uncertainty and both accrue to possessors of information.”

In response, individual, family and organisational visions reveal deep conditioning and a category of mind with great passion for education. In line, Yizengaw (2003, p.1) declares higher education as playing a paramount role for economic and social development through “inculcating relevant knowledge and advanced skills...required for leadership, management, business, and professional positions.” Through research it generates, adopts, adapts and disseminates knowledge for the ultimate benefit of productivity, economic progress, political stability and peace ideal for the building of national competitiveness.

Echoing this viewpoint, the International Monetary Fund (1995, p.42) argues that “for individuals and families, education increases income, improves health, and reduces fertility

rates. For society, investing in education raises per capita GNP, reduces poverty and supports expansion of knowledge.” Likewise, critical theorists push the education lifeboat for purposes of praxis, emancipation, or simply social capital – that is, investment gains in social institutions like civic groups, unions, government, including the values of equality, equity, loyalty, productivity, and environmental stewardship. Young (UNESCO, 1992, p.116) cements the argument, reasoning that education “speeds up cultural change and encourages the development of value systems that promote sustainable investment”, while Kapfunde (1997) maintains that for the state, investing in education reduces dependence on expatriates and ensures advancement into the technological age. In short education means adequate product and service returns to meet the quality standards of the different markets at competitive outlays.

While yesterday it was said that education cannot transform the world but the world cannot transform without it, the current standard is that higher education *must* and *will* transform the people and the nation (Cross, et al. 2000; Petty, 2006). As Gurira (2010, slide2) sums it, this renders the social and public responsibility of higher education in national development both uncontested and immense in terms of “contributing the critical mass of the citizenry who possess the capability to engage the most intractable problems of society and to drive all manner of development.” Hence, many an institutional vision rallies with the ideals of the Legatum Institute to uplift the prosperity of citizens to galvanise: grassroots response to natural disasters; women and child rescue from slavery and trafficking; family income generating and empowerment opportunities; and maintenance of the ecological balance and the sustainability of human life – a decidedly complex socio-technical milieu.

Consequently, the institutions have become playing fields and battlegrounds of competing ideologies and philosophies pitting capitalism (democratic and autocratic), socialism, Pan-Africanism, and *Ubuntuism* driving both orthodox and unorthodox events and practices. As Table 2.1 shows, in calling for particular elements/themes/outcomes, the constituency reflects developmental interests compatible with its dynamics at that moment in time. In response, regardless of known and hidden challenges the combinations push along (Cohen, 2015) the curriculum has yielded ground either to the most powerful, or to the cheapest, or to the most voter-catching ideo-philosophies, often leading to the de-intellectualization of its matters away from the experts in education (Torres, Preskill, and Pointek, 1996; Petty, 2006)

from the political overrun. Hence, as the technocapitalist envelop deepens and the mixture turns more fudgy, it induces characteristically fungivorous policy reflexes the mandates address. It is this way today and a different ball game the next as the events become more controversial and less compatible with the local situations, complicating the platforms as the trappings of power usher more confusions.

The productive power of science and technology needs no visit to the deep sea. Western experience is sufficient evidence on the potential of the vested opportunities, driving both the 'catch up' and the 'dependence' development theories, with the Western model now the obligatory way of life, the universal goal of all peoples (Petty, 2006). Beginning with the multiple scientific exploits of the Industrial Revolution, in particular the technological applications of machine production, scientific planning and management, the West has surged forward enabling it to dominate the world ideologically, economically and culturally as Appleism, Walmartism, speed schools and other such philosophies expanded. The high gross domestic products (GDPs) mean that the people enjoy opulent lifestyles backed by high-tech industry, modern medicine, transport and IT, enhanced by more and better management of enterprises, societies and institutions, with similar trends now fashioning out among the BRICS countries.

To the developing world, the Western experience has translated into strong conviction on the super power of techno-science education (Gatawa, 1998; Mavhunga, et al. 2009; Education Review Commission, 1999; Yizengaw, 2003). The subsequent impact of the Lagos Plan of Action (LPA) 1980–2000 is the phenomenal growth of Curriculum Protocols and Models to leverage: development of priority sectors; skills and training for participation; and institutional development at the national, sub-regional and continental levels. Both locally engineered and imported curricula and non-curricula models prevail supported by macro- and micro-paradigms to galvanise institutional focus, with research playing a significant role. Examples include the UNDP's MDGs 2001-15, the Ibrahim Index of African Governance (IIAG), the Right to Education Index (REI; Mnkandla, 2006), the Africa Must Think paradigm (Pipim, 2013), the Legatum Prosperity Index (LPI; 2011-5) and the Zim-Asset (2013-8), extending to the new UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 2016-30, to end poverty, protect planet earth, and promote the human development index (HDI). This is a tip of the iceberg in a world of ideas and ideals about the development superstructure.

As common foci, the Indexes and Goals cut across the vast spectrum of constituency endeavours mainly to enlarge human security/HDI. The REI pushes the ideals of Democratization of knowledge, Human Development, a Strong Science and Technology Culture, and a Sustainable Environment-Development dividend. The IAG talks of Safety and Rule of Law, Participation and Human Rights, Sustainable Economic Opportunity, and Human Development; and the LPI's principles of prosperity include the Economy, Entrepreneurship and Opportunity, Governance, Education, Health, Safety and Security, Personal Freedom, and Social Capital. To realise the much-avowed autarky, the Zim-Asset seeks to boost the economy through bolstering the cluster pillars of Food Security and Nutrition, Social Services and Poverty Eradication, Infrastructure and Utilities, and Value Addition and Beneficiation. Equally, external models such as the Heritage Foundation's *Index of Economic Freedom* of 'rule of law, government size, regulatory efficiency and open markets' exert further influence on the development superstructure in the drive to usher more and better infrastructures and people rights befitting the technological society.

Summed up, the visions-missions enhance the policy dictate that science and technology is the springboard for development and related productivity breakthroughs. What the nations lack and, therefore, require is a full technogarchy – that is, 'government by technicians' and/or 'management of the economy and society by technical experts' (Geisler, 2001). Higher education must supply the human capital skills anchor to meet the wide spectrum of products, goods, services and related workflows the citizens have the right to expect and to access. In the interest of specialisation, curricula have shifted to the Honours Degrees model away from general degrees to ensure deep mining the cartography of VAE skills and related technological prerequisites, including the broader psychosocial skills for daily intercourse.

3.2.2 Entrepreneurialism

Joseph Schumpeter, the famous 20th Century economist, defined entrepreneurship as a function to reform or revolutionize the pattern of production...by exploiting an invention or, more generally, an untried technological possibility for producing a new commodity or producing an old one in a new way, by opening up a new source of supply of materials or a new outlet for products, by reorganizing an industry and so on. The word 'new' to mean change is the special trait and core of entrepreneurship and, therefore, the capacity to change

an important metric across the whole or part of society. Put another way, entrepreneurship is the capacity to innovate the business mind-set generating passion for enterprise and social missions or to venture into new business and social programmes that have both small and large-scale transformational benefits (Schramm, 2013), of which few people have the verve beyond being content once the job has been done or the client is satisfied. Once again McDonaldization and other such corporates are archetypal examples of the entrepreneurship market principles writ large – the difference between being poor and backward versus being rich and successful or competitive and self-sufficient.

Citing the Rwandan President, Paul Kagame, The Legatum Institute (2014, para.3) acknowledges that “It is becoming increasingly clear that entrepreneurship is the surest way of development.” Observing further, it contends that “Grassroots entrepreneurship not only empowers individuals but also leads to highly scalable and sustainable solutions. Targeted investments in certain sectors can create a ‘multiplier effect’ that accelerates prosperity through improved health, knowledge, and productivity and capital efficiency.” Epistemologically, entrepreneurship is the institutional test mark reflecting the capacity to craft nuclei and corps that successfully spearhead the development superstructure, and the political future of the institutions lie in and depend on it.

Technically, the entrepreneurship is the innovative exploitation of the factors of production – land, technocapital and labour. The innovation means creative decision making and problem solving that puts new ideas into action, or materials conversion, extending to inventions and new applications that break in to or obtain footholds in the market or society to serve old and new requirements, latent and existing needs – the heart of technocapitalism. As the cornerstone of the development agenda, it is all about new and better ways of seeing, doing and having to stimulate economic progress. This makes entrepreneurship a critical precondition in enterprise resource planning (ERP) optimized through the principles and skills of a goal-oriented mind-set (uniteforsight.org).

In response, some of the institutions use the term ‘technopreneurship’ (borrowed from the Singaporean model) defined, according to the HIT (2011, p.9), as the capacity to “deliver innovative hi-tech products and services to consumers...pushing the country into the hi-tech league of rapidly industrializing nations.” This is about achieving the requisite psycho-synergy

between technology and entrepreneurship to empower stakeholders, particularly the youth, and the poor, disadvantaged and vulnerable whose lack of educational skills or political and financial muscle to achieve such benefits by their own means leaves them marginalised. Thus, to stay buoyant, entrepreneurialism is the target strategy for full corporate innovativeness (Petty, 2006).

Currently, the challenge is that the body politic is still consumed by the reality of the Malthusian fear of a consumer rather than a producer, of a big, empty belly rather than two hands and an innovative mind, of a machine for eating rather than production, which if left unchecked, is the powder keg for serious social unrest (Mnkandla, 2011b). Therefore, massive wealth creation, in quantitative and qualitative terms, is the best strategy to marry educational philosophy, ideology and reality. It means and entails sufficient business and social entrepreneurs in the market to start up, run and rebrand businesses and social projects to transform the socio-economic landscape to approximate giant global corporations for the benefit of the nation.

The road to successful entrepreneurialism is crowded with target means and ends. In vogue is the urgency to decipher, to unpack the 4Es – entrepreneurship, employability, equal opportunity and employment creation often coupled together with and/or now superseded by the much more radical lot of empowerment, indigenisation and affirmative action (EIAA) indicative of the primacy of the goal. It is driven by the increasing realization that without human skills resources alone are not a sufficient impetus to prosperity (Mbeki, 2009; Hlabathi, 2012; Makunike, 2012). Defined, employability is the protracted versatility of the career skills; equal opportunity is impartiality and fairness in recruitment, especially against frictional unemployment and other corrupt practices; and employment creation is the economic independence and related capacity to expand existing enterprises as well as grow new income earning opportunities offering more jobs, products and services.

According to the EIAA entrepreneurship package, empowerment means capacity building of the people so that they are intellectually stronger and more confident to control the different means of production; indigenisation means bringing the national wealth under the control, dominance, and influence of the local people; and affirmative action or positive discrimination means taking action favouring those previously disadvantaged or discriminated against,

including empowering women for productive work and away from intensive, unproductive labour. Largely entailed is the setting up of vertically and horizontally integrated entrepreneurial clusters, reflecting a clear tendency to cooperate and share competencies, backed in a localised infrastructure of support. Hence, entrepreneurialism is the answer to the technological society expedition, enabling the state and business to expand and meet stakeholder needs for products and services (Robertson, 2015).

According to Makunike (2012), Singapore is the global example of successful entrepreneurialism outside the traditional markets which growing markets can emulate or learn from. Its success entailed numerous measures which began with the dismantling of all barriers associated with the political bureaucracy; followed by several measures like Technopreneurship21– to develop entrepreneurs in technology and innovation; SME21– to stimulate high-tech among small and medium enterprises (SMEs); Action Community for Entrepreneurship (ACE) to culture a pro-enterprise environment through facilitating discussion and debate on regulatory frameworks, changing culture and mind-set, improving access to finance, and facilitating networks and learning; and lastly, fusing entrepreneurship in university and college programmes supported by institutional incubators and tech-hubs. Today Singapore boasts of a broad-based middleclass with a per capita GDP of \$50 000. If, then, Singapore, whose GDP in the 1980s was equal to Ghana, has achieved such a high-tech cultural leap, surely Zimbabwe can achieve the same transformation too and the secret lies in the envisioned technopreneurship.

Institutionally, the entrepreneurship is indexed through the formation and nurturing of partnerships with knowledge-based business, which has seen the mushrooming of private-public partnerships, sponsorships, joint-ventures and other forms of local and international collaboration. The latter are applauded for physical infrastructure investments, research grants, scholarships, sponsorships, awards, internships, and personnel for advisory councils and promotions all of which enhance institutional reputation, financial standing and constituency relevance, ultimately uplifting the development superstructure and, with it, the macroeconomics and institutional rankings.

To sum up, while the 75 percent infrastructure investment threshold required to guarantee sufficient entrepreneurial competitiveness is still a long way from the low levels of about 20

percent, forecasts by entrepreneurship lobbyists like the International Monetary Fund, the World Bank, the African Development Bank, the Cable News Network and OECD to name a few, indicate that, driven by the vision-entrepreneurship model, and led by its growing number of millionaires, Africa's time has finally come (Sharara, 2015). Thus, as supporters and promoters of competitiveness, rather than strict competitors themselves, the institutions are part of the vanguard spearheading a broader entrepreneurial throughput and the visions-missions indicate that there is no letting off on that front.

3.2.3 Community service

According to Bringle and Hatcher (2000, p.273), community service is "supposed to mean greater scholarship work in the market or community by becoming a more vigorous partner in the search for answers to our most pressing social, civic, economic and moral problems through reaffirmed engagement." This means that community service further drives the corporate image-building agenda defined above. As the examples of VU and University of Illinois show, while not solely stealing all the credit, the vision-mission statements are profiled in such a manner as to appeal and engage the public and business for direct and indirect investments in order to assist the institution undertake community services or to fulfil its corporate social responsibility mandate. Elaborating further, Bringle and Hatcher (p.273) indicate that this calls for concerted efforts to muster critical conditions and factors of "building important collaborative partnerships, improving all forms of scholarship, nurturing the support of stakeholders, and contributing to the common good" to deliver high class services admired by the entire market and beyond.

Service learning is the most significant aspect of community service. Service learning programmes deliberately incorporate community interests, concerns, challenges, problems and issues, with the teaching and learning simultaneously taking place in both the field and classroom for high impact. According to Bringle and Hatcher this is not only to prepare and enhance students' sense of civic responsibility, but largely to expand the 'dual' education experience. In line with Wilson, et al. (2014), the starting point is to simultaneously find the course details including practical solutions in the field thereupon proceed to reconstruct and reconcile the practice with the classroom theory. By participating in organized, learner-structured service activities that meet identified community needs, the curriculum broadens learner understanding and comprehension of the course content while enhancing

appreciation and applicability of the discipline. While least dislocating and safe from the propensity to merely generate excess capacity, service learning is socially, morally and environmentally relevant education with the graduates readily absorbable in the job and investment markets (Bringle and Hatcher, 2000).

Summed up, through the vision-mission statements, the constituency is directly and indirectly assisted to identify, adopt and adapt development goals linked to a functional literacy, numeracy and technocracy across the wide spectrum of its endeavours. Echoing this viewpoint, MacMillan (2011) observes that, while an artefact of a broader institutional discussion about its purpose and setting resource allocation boundaries and the operational goals to be met, the constituents are able to generate changes that are creatively adaptive to the myriad local contexts and thereby diversify their own missions. To UNESCO (2000, p.3) this translates into capacity to “harness education more systematically to the process of sustainable development, so that individuals and society at large take full advantage of opportunities in the new world.” Higher Education is the all-time catharsis uplifting the spirits of all and sundry.

In tandem with Morley’s (2003, p.7) caveat about the “super-complex” curriculum and its “increasing emphasis on disposable, transferable and just-in-time knowledge”, the institutions continue to sell and the constituents to absorb the vision-mission promises in the drive to usher the Heaven scenario which, for all intents and purposes, is at their fingertips. A sub-standard throughput is unacceptable.

3.2.4 Constituency servicing hot-spots

In the midst of it all, the constituency servicing faces both seismic and tsunamic challenges, toll-heavy on the vulnerable. From the perspective of the Indexes outlined above, the crumbling aspirations indicate weak social optimality regardless of the Pareto efficiency/inefficiency discords, reflecting a development superstructure facing stormy seas. With a Gini coefficient of 0.80, coupled with the average intensity of MPI poverty of 50%, the paradox of progress is expanding rather than improving as illness, inequality and poverty gut too many victims, ironically, with even the rich severely threatened, unravelling the nation-building ethos (Burgis, 2015; Mnkandla, 2011b; Olivier, 2010).

On its part, the REI laments the dominance of theoretical versus weak *praxis* education. The

2014 reports by the IIAG and the LPI argue that, trends since 2000 show mixed progress on Sustainable Economic Opportunity, Human Development, Education, and Health, becoming much more erratic and problematic on Governance, Safety and Rule of Law, Participation and Human Rights / Personal Freedom and Social Capital. In addition is the dearth of a vibrant statistical culture in terms of advanced mathematics, statistics and predictive analytics to enhance accurate measurement, precision control and competitive accountability. The challenges leave the systems vulnerable to the spasms of short-lived growth accelerations, contaminated by the resource curse and other downgrade socio-environmental forces.

Entrepreneurship, more so unemployment, remains the biggest challenge. It is a very sensitive subject which the institutions and the market always promise to deliver on to little avail. Specifically, while the science and technology education speaks of an impeccable success story of functional graduates groomed to their highest potential, the promised 'technopreneurship' breakthroughs have scarcely been achieved. The reality is one of rising exposure to demand deficient, structural and frictional unemployment, vulnerable employment (with the state even engaged in labour exports – Chronicle, 31 August, 2015, p.8), and socio-economic uncertainty which continue to threaten livelihoods (Parliament of Zimbabwe, 2011; Robertson, 2015).

As the eco-social environments progressively become more disabling than enabling, with even agriculture, potentially the biggest employer, on the decline, estates have become more protective and corrupt. The falling investments across the economy – government, business, education, health, donors etc. – usher shrinking, high risk, brazenly exploitive labour deals. Only 'connections', or 'paybacks', or prostitution, or slavery, or clientelism make the difference between getting a job and staying without one which, coupled with invisible entrepreneuring create a vicious cycle of human deprivation, lost dignity and collapse of businesses at all stages of the Adizes' Corporate Lifecycle.

Therefore, judged from the Africa Must Think paradigm, events are not as 'Prime' as the visions portray. The 'Elephant-in-the-zoo' paradigm nurturing the 'African Chicken' bred and driven by the 'African Black Bean' drawbacks prevails (Pipim, 2013). Like an elephant in the zoo which remains tied down by a simple string, lacking the wit to venture to free itself even if such capacity exists, so too the populations whose gridlocked mind-sets make them

incapable to see challenges as “opportunities and setbacks as stepping stones enabling us to break the mental chains” (Pipim). While the education faces numerous impediments, they are secondary to the internal inertia stemming from the human capital gridlock and the institutional imperialism defined by Torres, et al. (1996, p.21) as characteristically “homogeneous, bureaucratic, hierarchical, compliant and centralised; operating with fixed boundaries and routines; with tasks accomplished through well-defined functional structures.” The overall implication is a technocapitalism at crossroads.

Additionally, the combination of the 1st generation leadership trap and the image of the black bean have been quite lethal. The former is reference to much of the leadership whose parents never reached the management positions that it occupies to be vital reference points. The latter, as described by Pipim, is the leadership that is black on the outside and white on the inside in reference to its being engrossed in the material fortunes of its past and present colonial masters with whom it blatantly connives, together with the transnational companies, to exploit Africa’s resources at the expense of the people. As a result, the institutions are left with little choice but to resign fate and freedom to the wishes and dictates of capital, with more emphasis on techno-property rights and much less the inherent sores of *Homo simplex* – the poor and marginalised.

In conclusion, resembling the Marshal Plan, the vision-mission statements elevate the constituency servicing footprint to a Messianic gift to the sunshine uplands of tomorrow: facilitating full academic, technical, professional, administrative, business and ecumenical achievements valuable for the activities of modern life and living, more so the technologically-based and entrepreneurially-driven enterprises (Yizengaw, 2003). The ‘master plan’ galvanises access to information, to science and technology and to decision making, hence, the capacity to exercise power over the colossal psychosocial drawbacks and weaknesses. Unproblematically, the statements’ authoritative voice influences policy experts to think alike even when the evidence contradicts them. As Olivier (2010) notes, the challenge to stimulate the science-technology drive maintains however open the VUCA viruses. But, with so much faulting, what obtains is the axiom: ‘when elephants marry or fight, the grass suffers’, signifying the grave consequences the ‘technological society–sustainable development’ elephants have inflicted on the people, compromising justification for the philosophy.

3.3 Governance

In its broadest sense, governance is the internal structure, organization and management of the institutions, in particular the spectrum of oversight roles reflecting the traditions and practices by which authority is exercised. According to the World Bank Institute (2009), it embraces the process by which leadership is appointed, monitored and replaced; the capacity to formulate and implement sound programmes and policies; and the respect the citizenry and external world give the institutions with regard their core business. Petkoski and Twose (2003, p.5) refine it to mean academic-administrative competence in the execution of the roles of “mandating, facilitating, partnering and endorsing” summed up in Figure 3.1. While largely the prerogative of the super-ordinates, in varying magnitude, the roles are inclusive of most duties and responsibilities which makes them relevant across the multiple levels of the hierarchy.

3.3.1 The nature of the governance

Governance is the foundation behind the institution’s life cycle with respect to time and other landmarks that it goes through. At every point, multiple challenges emerge some predictable and repetitive and others unique and once-off. To that effect, a specifiable constitutionalism exists pronounced through Acts, Charters, Ordinances and other relevant statutes and legal instruments establishing and positioning the institution in the marketplace. Operationally, whether strongly articulated, or clearly implied, silent and unknown, Figure 3.1 shows the wide spectrum of endeavours the due diligence mandating, facilitating, partnering and endorsing serve.

Briefly, the mandating entails originating, assigning and implementing command and control measures, programmes, directives, decrees, legal and fiscal penalties/standard operating procedures (SOPs), formal duties and responsibilities, admissions and certifications, operations, engagements, evaluations/audits, licensing and whatever warrants may be required. The facilitating covers the expediting of enabling legislation and instruments, funding and resourcing, promoting communications and accelerating growth, raising awareness and creating incentives, staffing and capacity building, stimulating markets and much more.

The partnering refers to entering into alliances, joint ventures and understandings/ agreements (MoU/As) to boost resources, stakeholder engagements, collaborations, internships and dialogues. Last, the endorsing entails advocating, approving, ratifying and sanctioning contracts, projects, reports and other multiple elements of the institutional operations, extending to publicity and promotions. Overall, the package is the basis of the formalization, openly and insidiously, with McDonalidization assuming the upper hand to firmly root in each and every role the principles of efficiency, calculability, predictability and control, now the ultimate accomplishments of the governance.

Institutional governance			
	Command	Programmes	Legal and fiscal
<i>Mandating:</i>	&	&	
	Control measures	Evaluations	penalties and rewards
	Enabling legislation	Communications	Capacity building
<i>Facilitating:</i>		Awareness	
	Funding support	Incentives	Stimulating markets
<i>Partnering:</i>	Combining	Stakeholder	Dialogues/
	resources	engagement	Communications
	Academic support		Publicity
<i>Endorsing:</i>			&
	Contracts, Projects, Reports		Promotion

Figure 3.1 Institutional roles (Source: Petkoski and Twose, 2003, p.5)

Accordingly, implied and applied, the governance must exceptionally execute, *inter alia*: official decisions and sanctions; get jobs done, issues resolved and problems solved; enact quality regulations and respect freedoms and the law or corporate social responsibility, stability and peace; guarantee broad-based security and flourishing rights, freedoms, liberties, voice and accountability; and last, ensure effective efficiency, including media freedom and transparency in resource procurement and allocation. Unqualified intelligence, more so, statistically aided decision making and problem solving, based on proofs and support data, or evidentialism, now plays a colossal role in governance work and is the distinction between excellent and mediocre governance. Ultimately, the quality of the governance lies in its dual decision making–problem solving capability to unravel both ‘tame’ and ‘wicked’ problems, involving technical solutions, on one hand, and the means to achieve psychosocial success, on the other. Unlike the former, wicked problems are not only

contested and difficult to define, they are subject to multiple interpretations which reduces consensus or agreement that success has been achieved (Jaffee, 2008).

The governance roles must be captured and deployed up-down-across in sync with the adopted leadership-management models complemented by available technological tools like boards and committees of experts and transnational networks. Among the models are the Katz model of technical skills, human resources skills, and conceptualization skills; the Birkinshaw 'Four Dimensions of Management Model'; and the Rooke and Torbert's (2005) 'Action Logic' model, to cite a few examples. According to the Birkinshaw theory the models advance, in separate but common ways, multi-dimensional parameters involving managing across which entails managing activities; managing down which entails managing decisions; managing objectives; and managing personnel motivation, in each case, either applying the traditional principles or the more innovative alternatives, or a combination of both. The managing across separates between bureaucracy and emergence (or spontaneity); the managing down: between hierarchy and collective wisdom; the managing objectives: between alignment and obliquity (indirectness); and, last, the managing motivation: between extrinsic and intrinsic motivation.

Bureaucracy, hierarchy, alignment and extrinsic motivation constitute the traditional principles, distinctively restrictive and authoritarian, while emergence, collective wisdom, obliquity and intrinsic motivation constitute the more flexible alternative principles ideal for autonomous and enabling governance. In the midst is the diverse range of opportunist, instructional, democratic, diplomat, expert, transactional, participative, transformational, achiever, strategist, individualist, moral and alchemist leaderships – the adjective list is endless. The ideal is a functioning skills transfer package for maximum constituency engagement with the governance duly reflexing the pulse of the system. In the final analysis, whichever principles are applied, in the words of Petkoski and Twose (2003, p.1), the institutions must display relentless commitment to “contributing to sustainable development, working with staff, the local community and society at large to improve quality of life, in ways that are good for the institution and for development.”

The governance involves multiple horizontal and vertical structures or hierarchies to establish a means of organizing an equally complicated cartography of stakeholders and relationships.

Writing in Forbes Magazine, Asqhar (2013) cites Warren Bennis who describes the university president or vice chancellor as an entertainer, a visionary, a priest, a psychologist, and a CEO of 10 or 20 vastly different enterprises gathered under the seal of one university. In other words, not only is the governance complex, it entails dealing with an intricately vast and unique system of units and stakeholders. Given the multiplication of programmes and services, without doubt, as Asqhar argues, the governance has few parallels making the university leadership job the toughest of them all, only second to the mayor of a big city.

The hierarchy comprises the chancellor at the top followed by the university council, the main governing board led by its chairperson, advised by numerous boards and committees lower down. Examples of these include the Senate, the Academic Board, the Finance Committee, the Salaries and Conditions of Service Committee, the Audit, Compliance and Risk Committee, Appointment Boards, the Non-Academic Staff Promotions Committee, and the Promotions and Grading (Tenure) Committee, to name a few. In addition are management committees like the Teaching and Learning Board, the Ethics Committee, the Library Committee, the Security, Safety and Health Committee, the Faculty Planning Committee and the Faculty Board answerable to the senate, the vice-chancellor or rector, or the administration, or to the faculty. Staff and student associations/unions complete the democratization process for purposes of collective bargaining, conflict management and other representations.

Beneath the council, the governance divides into the two domains of administration and faculty. The former comprises the chancellery or rector and related officers – the registrar, bursar, librarian, provost, proctor, directors, the student representative council (SRC) and non-academic staff complements. The density of the departmentation mirrors the diversity of the curriculum to ensure top class performance measuring to the institutional vision. Therefore, varying with the demand for support services, there is a broad assortment of departments and divisions comprising the bursary, internal audit, library, communication and marketing/public relations, student affairs, admissions and student records, examinations, information and communication technology unit, infrastructure/works and estates, security, quality assurance directorate, research and innovation/resource mobilization, continuing education service, and external offices whose leadership goes by different titles answerable to the respective board(s) or committee(s).

Secondly, faculty governance consists of academic deans, department chairs, lecturing staff and student representatives. Deans, chairs, senior academics, and the SRC are established through Ordinances. As Clark (1986, p.202) notes, the rationale is that with carefully guarded selection, the most highly competent academics will be given influence with which to mould the activities of their fields. The aim is to foster enough flexibility to allow the incumbents, individually and in groups, to engage in prolific exchanges unhindered by “petty bureaucratic restraints and the slow processes of democratic deliberation, to effect change in the more general domains of faculty, university and system through collegial planning.” Echoing this observation, the OECD (2011, p.3) also urges for the governance post of faculty deans, since, by virtue of “being at the interface between the institution’s decision making bodies and teachers on the job, it encourages the cross-fertilization of strategic approaches, build and support communities of practice and nurture innovation in everyday practice in the classroom.” Optimal faculty governance is the blue chip of the system, allowing and enabling the institutions to profitably weather adversity.

According to Ramo (2001) of the American Association of University Professors (AAUP), faculty governance issues comprise the curriculum, subject matter, methods of instruction and research; matters of faculty status (such as hiring, promotion, dismissal, retention and tenure); and the student-educational process. The governance is supervised and coordinated by the senate, the academic board and other faculty level committees like the faculty planning committee, the faculty board, the faculty of higher degrees committee, and advisory councils.

The overall cartography requires a functionally vibrant line-staff relationship exercising matching oversight across the vast spectrum of activities (see Figure 3.1). Faculty must studiously motivate and propel lecturing staff and students to teach and learn deeply and in ways that nurture sustained conscious competence reflected in the ability to exercise unqualified intelligence, hence, elevating everyone’s ability to validate, with robotic efficiency, firm academic, scholarly, technical and professional attainments. Similarly, the administration must exercise and acquit its oversight decidedly and professionally across the vast spectrum of duties and responsibilities – student enrolments and affairs, staff engagements, budget allocations and procurements, system-wide services, security, consultations, information and

publicity, evaluations, and external contacts with headquarters, the quality agencies, the community, and other institutions.

By its structure and nature, therefore, the governance guarantees systemic 'excellence' which, interpreted, means the workplace values embrace differentiated integrity marked by adequate participation and shared governance, diversity in institutional climate, academic freedom, authenticity and legitimacy of academic work, clean appraisals free of reprisals, proper due process, trust and good faith, open communications, responsiveness, accountability and mutual support across all departments and levels, with constituents well networked. More specifically, student affairs must be well coordinated and thoroughly knit in terms of its diverse functions concerning student welfare and health covering sport and recreation, membership of associations, clubs and societies, career guidance, and employment prospects and other support services to leverage dynamic campus life high in moral efficiency.

Naturally, membership of the governance requires fairly intensive experience in faculty leadership, senate and committee experience and other governing boards, as well as regular formal external exposure through professional contacts. According to the AAUP (2001) 'acknowledgement, representativeness, safety, mutuality, appropriate boundaries, open communication channels, influence, and responsible practice' are the key parameters in the formulation, design and delimitation of the faculty governance system. Crucially, the structures must guarantee adequate representation and safe working conditions and relations to ensure that each and every entity has a voice in the governance process, while also maintaining proper communication channels and remaining responsible and accountable with regard their own practice.

Without fail, liberalization of faculty must be the prime target assuring equality and equity with no members feeling intimidated, bullied or marginalized, hence, ensuring that possible obstacles and sources of conflicts are controlled, minimized and eliminated. The target is both to boost decision making through effective dialogue and to enhance the host of governance skills, with constituents kept informed and their views solicited on the numerous agendas by their representatives in the multiple organs or committees (AAUP, 2001).

Therefore, to stay Prime, the faculty-administration relationship must be correspondent and complementary, leveraging the requisite synergies of 'interdependence, communication and full opportunity for joint action and effort' among governing board, administration, faculty and students in sync with the legitimate disorder that culminates in commendable performance yields (AAUP, 2001). Effectively, the committee system is central to the operations, activating networks, the decision making, and the provision of conducive platforms attractive to all.

3.3.2 Other governance matters

The vision-mission statements are further blueprints for accreditation, strategic planning and the institutional epistemology all of which provide more evidence on both the normative and utilitarian roles of the construct. Of late the accreditation is tied to the existence of the vision-mission statements supported by policy statements and action plans to fulfill the stated vision and mission, as well as strategic plans and other documentation to ensure the implementation of the mission (ZIMCHE). As Materu (2007) aptly puts it, as a self-study and external quality review process, the accreditation is used to scrutinize programmes for quality standards and whether or not the institution has met or exceeded the published standards as spelt out in the vision construct or there is need for improvement.

Equally important, with an increasing role, is strategic planning to map out and promote, monitor and evaluate the vision-mission priorities; or how to establish the requisite benchmarks and indicators for closer scrutiny and reporting. The University of Johannesburg and the NUST offer examples of the strategic management approach. The strategic plan for the former seeks to: "give expression to its vision of being a pre-eminent South African and African university." Among others, the Plan seeks to: 'build a reputable brand; promote excellence in teaching and learning; cultivate a culture of transformation; conduct internationally competitive research; maximise intellectual capital; ensure institutional efficiency and effectiveness; offer the preferred student experience; and secure and grow competitive resourcing' (uj.ac.za).

Similarly, in advancing its vision and mission, the NUST Strategic Plan 2011-15 identifies 'five strategic directions' or priority areas: 'widen and deepen access to higher education; generate knowledge and develop skills and solutions through research to meet national imperatives and societal needs; develop and implement innovative strategies for knowledge transfer to enhance commercialization, consultancy and advisory services; and create and

sustain an environment conducive to effective learning, teaching and productivity'. With these priorities in place, however conducive and/or incompatible the ambient environment or however tough the challenges, governmentally, the institutions are well poised to deliver a pre-eminent South African-African university (UJ) and a world class mandate (NUST) comparable to any other – albeit, a tall order given the spectre and incompatibility of the Western university in Africa (Mabhena, 2016b).

Last, through justification and evidentialism, the construct is the appropriate platform for the institutional epistemology, propagating the necessary and sufficient conditions of knowledge, its sources, its structure and its limits (Steup, 2013). This means adequate room to leverage the multiple dimensional values and beliefs and how they come to dominate the psychosocial discourse. In other words, it rationalises epistemic parameters into curriculum milestones (packages, portfolios and concrete practices and processes) instrumental to prime classroom and extra-classroom behaviours, conditions and outcomes. This way, the construct harnesses curricula philosophies and sees to their attainment. MacMillan (2011, p.94) dittos the benefits as going beyond being a key component of an effective strategic planning process, but aiding “organizational members distinguish between activities that conform to institutional imperatives and those that do not; inspiring and motivating more progressive communications; and continuing to guide decision making around key issues of programme creation or termination.” Embodied is conscious ergonomics and competent management to initiate day-to-day activities; to stimulate and compensate the enthusiasm, efforts and trust of others; to harness resources productively; and to transform behaviours as well as control assets and resources, most resolutely.

Seen from the perspective of the Adizes' Corporate Lifecycle model, the target is the 'prime' stage of optimum income, market share, higher flexibility and 'legitimate disorder' with the governance exercising “variety and autonomy expressed through formal, informal and quasi-informal communications with room for fair amounts of discontent with regard the direction of the institution” (Clark, 1986, p.270). Observing further, Clark notes how the flexibility then allows parties to overexert themselves: to break the rules and operate defectively and disjointedly without inducing much harm to the system, hence, achieving a lot more than 'formal controls' are able to do. Ultimately, “given tasks, beliefs and authority patterns, this is the only way to encourage initiative, excellence, hard work and progressive choices.” The

standpoint assures the full meaning and impact of continuous improvement in the endless search for productively satisfying lifestyles in line with global trends to induce permanent certainty over both tame and wicked problems befitting liberation and struggle.

3.3.3 Governance drawbacks

Smit's (2006, p.164) observation that "like wine, words can describe a company's vision-mission statements and all, but the real test comes when you taste it", coupled with Morpew and Hartley's (2006) proverbial half-full/half-empty glass, and the P-AIUG's (2010) admonishing for Africa's institutions to "invent endogenous policies and procedures", sum up the challenges confronting the governance footprint. Arguably, in adopting the vision-mission construct, the bureaucracy assumed so much and overlooked many things which renders it a controversial proposition – the Trojan horse so to speak – both guilty of either fostering the exhausting realities of the predatory status quo or of being a victim of the same. However, to note is that the challenges are never the same nor uniform across the institutional scapes, but intermittently shift from one locale to the other. What is important is to take stock both before and after the event.

Numerous factors bring about the loss of taste which, like dead wine, leaves the visions and missions worthless propaganda of little or no substance and import at all. Indeed, the 'import' risks repetition of the same colonial experiments now under the guise of some obscure rhetoric, only for the institutions to suffer the indignity of exposure when they fall on hard ground and fail to live the hype. Among the immediately disputable inviting the taunt of 'high-sounding nothing' (Kwaramba, 2016) are the challenges of exaggerated Utopianism, one-size-fits-all/*bambazonke*, and manipulative sophistry.

First, evidently, exaggeration is the philosophy's lifeline, to create a Mecca of student mobility and, therefore, pull the institution out of whatever downgrade perceptions it is in. As Morpew and Hartley (2006, p.458) observe, the language is flowery and fiery "to evoke an all-purpose purpose" or to demonstrate "The importance of being broad and general." Indeed, with no one likely to go against "the pursuit of excellence", it appears the statements "exist because they are expected to exist", simply to promote flexibility and control. They further cite sources which argue that the ambiguity renders the statements "amazingly vague, vapid, evasive, or rhetorical, lacking specificity or clear purpose...full of honourable verbiage signifying nothing" (p.460). Smith, et al. (2002, p.4) also argue that the problem with "most mission statements

is that they are ‘paper tigers’ suffering from being too vague, having involved too few stakeholders, being too replete with hollow platitudes, and numerous suppositions.” Equally, to Kwaramba (2016, p.2) “the sort of language that is used is euphemistic, full of vagaries and contradictions, and yet often presented with force and charisma but still remains meaningless because the values have little true meaning to what happens on the ground.” Viewed this way, certainly the exaggeration impairs the philosophy as the springboard for more strategic outcomes. Morley (2003) would argue that what obtains is a captive market that keeps ‘travelling hopefully, but never to arrive’ – the sky is never the limit.

Second, Education World (2011) argues that the ‘one-size-fits-all’ stigma/*bambazonke* catharsis creates more harm than good as it “implies a sense of direction, clarity of thinking, and unity that rarely exists” in the face of the legitimate disorder typical of academia. Rather, they demonstrate the importance of being general, if not the desire for ‘sameness’, as the impetus towards higher ideals. On this point, Morphew and Hartley (p.458) observe that

rather than surfacing values that might guide everyday decision making, colleges and universities fashion mission statements that maximize institutional flexibility. They communicate that nothing is beyond the reach of the organization in question. In doing so, they ignore institutional limitations and side-step any effort at prioritizing current activities or future initiatives.

In a way, the institutions deceive themselves that they are the paragons of delivery, certainly of any product, service or solution to meet whatever expectations and aspirations. Oblivious of internal and external weaknesses and pressures, they proclaim themselves the all-weather and all-gradient road that never fails. Clark (1986, p.23) equates the standpoint to the notion of a garbage-bin – general enough to throw in/hide all manner of wastes (issues, problems, challenges, solutions), hence, justifiably important to attract enough different kinds of wastes to reinforce that importance. And true to fact, “activists will push for discussions of grand plans in order to draw the garbage away from the day-to-day arenas of their concrete objectives.” The usual hype is ‘our vision statements say so’ when in fact conditions are devoid of more pragmatic endeavours. Not to be outdone, the leadership translates its autocracy as effective action and efficient action.

Thirdly, in place of *in-situ* ‘disruptive innovations’, the statements merely chalk up manipulative sophistry to bolster prestige and visibility at the expense of real Third World matters: issues and problems of high conversion inefficiency rates, unmet utility and demand,

and the bottom-up collapse of food chains and the people with them. Instead, concern is more with world rankings, to be among the best in the world, with even budding institutions like the Lupane State University 'striving to be ranked among premier universities in the world in research-based knowledge, teaching and learning' – a newly born, still wobbling nationally, but already competing globally, what a feat! The system is so fastidious about the global pedigree at the expense of the local cultures – a continuation of the traditional centre-periphery model, if not reminiscing the adage 'follow-the-crowd'. The Western systems (the centre) produce for the backward zones (the periphery) to consume, and whether or not conditions allow, 'be like others', which leaves the statements remotely relevant to the local skyline, but merely pushing the conventions of the gold standard, however impure the concentrate. Indeed, against the background of both tame and wicked problems, the equivocation surrounding 'best' is not easy to reconcile.

Furthermore, in embracing the 'world class' status the institutions overlook several realities. On one hand is the reality of developing country status and how they are yet to escape the 'low income' trap, migrate to, and overcome, the 'middle income trap' and, finally, reach the 'high income' status of Western institutions – a mammoth challenge by the stretch of any imagination. This is within the ambit of bureaucracy as the very system of government and, as usual, with no direct profit-efficiency targets to pursue. Consequently, as Tieréan and Bratucu (2009, p.249) observe, given the uncompetitiveness of the bureau and, therefore, "weak external control on efficiency and weak internal incentives", power qua profit is the commodity at the hands of the bureaucrats who, through their 'conditions of service', translate it into rent-seeking behaviour, pushing as their stoke-in-trade, the arbitrary goals of "salary, office perquisites, public reputation, power, patronage, output of the bureau, ease of making changes and ease of managing the bureau." Hence, the tendency to use as evidence of efficiency and excellence routines and cues like meetings, conferences, invitations, foreign travel, prestigious visitations, ceremonies, consumption, entertainments and mass enrolments anchored on a high finance 'burn rate'. Hanging in the balance, and virtually lying beyond the scope of the bureau, is dedication to farsighted prime social targets whereby progress is better.

Thus, riding as they do on highly porous aspirations, the institutions mislead themselves into believing that they are delivering outstanding services to the local environments when

benefits are infinitesimal or are still more colonial in character. As Tung (1999), Morley (2003) and Nwagbara (2011) observe, history reveals how, scholarly achievements rarely translate into pragmatic wisdom and total horizontal social transformation and emancipation. If anything, the difficulty with concretizing the knowledge goal hatches new forms of consumptive rather than productive education, perilously driving disruptive social cleavages that culminate in the mischaracterization of the academy.

In its assessment of the dilemma, the P-AIUG (2010) observes that the governance challenges come about as a result of direct importation and/or corruption of Western models which are often incompatible with African experiences and circumstances. Arguably, trends continue to point towards the 'classical models of cooperation in which the "expertise" of the North are transmitted to "addressee" and "consignee" of the South, leading to the principles and attitudes of copy-write'. Similarly, Nwagbara (2011, p.85) views such philosophies as typical Western extensions of the 'colonial management practice hangover' that does Africa's institutions very little good, except repeated exposure to the theory of Learned Helplessness or the "failure or lack of capability to tackle harm-violent responses or to reverse harm-inflicting conditions, even when such could lead to reduced exposure to (anticipated) harm or risk of harm." With the bulk of board, committee and council membership least trained in corporate governance, decision making is often rudimentary, skewed and *ad-hoc*, exposing the forlorn expectation that events are 'uncontrollable' and 'inexorable', with reduced diversity in contingency rendering reaction virtually placid. As if a permanent arrangement, the institutions are ready to receive once the North has decided or produced for all to consume.

Last, within the institutions themselves, bureaucratic ambiguities and pressures, fuelled by the collapsing fiscuses, coupled with the complexities of the non-linear, zigzag, forward-backward governance usher crippling administrative shortcomings. In his analysis, Clark (1986, p.203) describes the overall picture and norm as one of a well-entrenched bureau riddled with uniformities: "External groups, internal constituencies and segments of political officialdom closely guard those activities of direct interest, enlarging and making more complicated the web of veto groups." Echoing the argument, Morley (2003) and Lewis (2007) indicate how the perverse bureaucracy dictionary (BD) propels simplicity, monopoly, protective controls, brinkmanship and narrowness, subjecting the institutions to malfunction, dysfunction and losses. Indeed, as the discussion will show, not only are many challenges

traceable to the BD, it is insuperably averse to complexity, complication and sophistication and, ultimately, sustainable development.

At stake are the tight communications, attack on academic freedom and the professoriate; compromised outcomes; parochialism and abuse of power; hapless dependence on non-performing budgets and hand-outs; and undermining of the conditions of service, initiative and adaptation. To sustain the bureaucracy, institutions resort to unethical massification in the form of huge enrolments, notwithstanding the strain on facilities and the corresponding drop in the quality dividend, while the huge fees hikes impact the values of equity and liberty with higher education out of reach for the bulk of the constituency.

Arguing further, Lewis (2007) notes that, the disfigured communication is the worst killer of them all. He observes how slowly, contrary to more openness and transparency, as the tight controls worm in, the communications become highly curtailed, only through the public relations office or spokesperson, in fear of imagined unsavoury deviations from the official position. In response to pressure from the press and in fear of public embarrassment, the institutions resort to strongly guarded press releases or memoranda highlighting platitudes and peripheral matters rather than real issues. As he puts it, “when the press of bad news drives policies institutions patch things that look bad rather than understand and repair things that truly are broken” (Lewis, p.14). Hence, becoming the norm is the practice to suppress genuine debate as well as hide issues on complex topics, leaving only the privileged few enjoying access to ‘real’ information while the rest survive on the rumour mill. Rightly, principled deliberation suffers as reasoning degrades from the empty rhetoric of the stale news communiqués (Lewis). They deliberately gag themselves under the erroneous belief and guise of exalted information management.

As the muzzling of the communications expands, infections also rise. Authority resorts to controversial decisions and scenarios difficult to justify, or denies issues, or leaves them to chance in the hope that they will correct or resolve themselves. For instance, Lewis (2007, p.15) argues that it is not uncommon for the institutions “to fail to explain illuminating tensions such as the costs of initiatives, the balance between announced goals and opposing imperatives, and what is not being done so other things can be done.” The incendiary decisions create friction and tension which stir up dissatisfactions, divisions, and rebellious

behaviours, rendering fraught capacity to foster the institutional lifelines and the expected working consensus nurtured on academic freedom, corporate responsibility, cooperation, equity, adaptability, open-mindedness, flexibility and versatility.

Given the magnitude of policy, programme, project, and curriculum stress, livened by a plethora of rigid, opaque and authoritarian rules and practices, governance ills will remain many an institution's Trojan horse. This casts doubts whether the institutions ever attain the Prime stage in the first place, or, they merely migrate straight from Infancy to an early bureaucracy, stabilising at the Bureaucracy stage (Adizes'). The rigid centralization and formalization have proved lethal, upsetting balances and driving idle speculation and a penchant for resistance. Operations narrow down to the benign interests of power groups who continuously rigidify the control instruments. The result is one of "fewer people making decisions in fewer decision making arenas; of more rules and sanctions to enforce the rules" (Clark, 1986, p.226).

In conclusion, the governance footprint reflects successful mandating, facilitating, partnering and endorsing and other related interventions for premium product and service delivery. It is the hub of the 'Prime' stage giving confidence to the MHTE,STD 'to guarantee Zimbabwe leadership in the delivery of high calibre manpower proficient in the creation and use of new and existing knowledge, skills, attitudes and resources'. The institutions echo the ideal for a strong intelligence superstructure that is the crucible of ideas crucial to the host of human endeavours, chiefly the development superstructure. However, prevailing internal and external faults and breaks, more so, the construct's equivocal rather than absolute reflection of the institutional reality, compromise the dynamism of the governance whose lack of a positivist theory, coupled with the inherent neo-patrimonial tendencies induce endless illnesses. While clearly the desire of Africa's institutions to decolonise reliance on the 'Western model' in preference for a home-grown 'currency' (Mabhena, 2016a), such attempts have suffered still births given the power dynamics of globalization which outweigh the merits of such a shift. Ultimately, however the realities play out is the talking point, the crucible behind the vision-mission discourse.

3.4 Quality Assurance

Quality assurance (QA) is the most pivotal footprint with everything radiating from and converging onto it. Its main role is to protect as well as offer guidelines to old and new market players on the official standard of service delivery. It is a synthesis of quality issues and standards criteria into an achievable market grade everyone cherishes, lives, and works by. The oft given example on the role of QA is the operating theatre whereby there should be no lingering doubt regarding the person holding the knife approaching the table. In the final analysis, the quality approximates the set standard and the set standard resonates with the achieved quality, identically.

Purcell (2003, para.1) defines standards as the “mostly quiet, unseen forces, such as specifications, regulations and protocols which ensure that things work properly, interactively, and responsibly.” It is a complex process involving the crafting and acceptance or adoption of a highly valued universal measure or yardstick, specification and process with the gold standard a typical example. Like the body’s DNA, the standard provides the essential building blocks for economic, political and social networks, for example business standards, health and safety standards, the Hazardous Analysis and Critical Control Points (HACCP) standard, and market competition standards to ensure or guarantee more and better productivity, or proper and fair practices, or to avert likely risks, threats, hazards and other impairments.

Materu (2007, p.3) defines quality as “fitness for purpose – that is, meeting or conforming to generally accepted standards as defined by the institution, QA bodies and appropriate academic and professional communities.” The International Organization for Standardization (ISO) 8402 defines quality as “All the planned and systematic activities implemented within the quality system, and demonstrated as needed, to provide adequate confidence that an entity will fulfil requirements for quality.” Simply put, quality is the intelligent, conscious action by which a theory, or philosophy, or practice, or standard becomes reality on a universal scale for purposes of social action and benefit.

In comparison, while varying with the diversity of products, quality is more absolute than standard which is more processual. Hence, as Figure 3.2 shows, simply put QA is the extent the inherent product or service characteristics fulfil the ‘delivery standard’ in terms of each,

some or all of costs, safety, health, relevance, customer satisfaction and other properties subtended to curriculum literacy with minimum misallocation or waste of resources. Gwati (2010, slide10), citing Professor Donald Ekong's report on UNESCO Regional Consultants on Higher Education, buttresses the role of the QA as involving

All the policies, systems and processes directed to ensuring the maintenance and enhancement of the quality of educational provisions within an institution. A quality assurance system is the means by which an institution confirms to itself and to others that conditions are in place for students to achieve the standards that the institution has set.

As Materu (2007) further notes, rather than a standard definition of the QA, what matters most is confidence with the qualitative and quantitative nature of the vision-mission statements to assess and measure the effective and efficient metabolization of inputs, processes, outputs and outcomes, thereby giving assurance to all interested parties that the institution is keeping its promise to achieve the best products practicable. From the perspective of the Lifecycle model, the institution achieves all-round aggregation of the footprints reflecting complete "balance between control and flexibility, and between growing and aging processes." While it is a fact that products and services can differ in quality but still meet the same standard, higher education requires uniform and matching QA across the board, hence, the contradiction in the 'fitness for/of purpose' definition. The concern with 'defective content' aside, the 2012 temporary cancellation of certificates for ZOU primary school graduates showed how the purpose was very fit for some and unfit for the QA Agency, raising the red flag on the levels of the formal training undertaken. In short, dependence on experience and borrowings is always inadequate and ushers the likelihood of poor practices/sloganeering which compromises the needed professionalism.

3.4.1 Quality assurance infrastructures

The tricky challenge with QA is that it is like an amoebae and, hence, difficult to index in social systems like education. Compared to industrial products, its specific substance and import is difficult to define in a classroom situation. Hence, while crystal clear to the experts, QA can be as clear as mud to the uninitiated. Van den Berghe (1998, p.23) sums it as follows:

The standards process is perhaps the most crucial to set and develop the overall requirements of the quality system – responsibility of management, quality manual and procedures, specifications on delivery, appointment of a quality office, availability of sufficient resources and qualified staff; the need to maintain documented procedures on the key processes of the organization (design, development, purchase, delivery, etc.) and implementation of activities according to the procedures; and the need for specific quality assurance mechanisms, including test and inspection, keeping quality records,

dealing with non-conformance, keeping documents up-to-date, conducting internal audits and holding regular management reviews.

As the citation shows, the QA footprint is an admixture of multiple parameters whose material essence is crucial for the up-keep of quality. It is in many respects highly cultural and delicately dependent on, and subject to, the strengths of surrounding conditions and factors. Academically, it embraces characteristics of good teaching, meritocracy, academic (intellectual) freedom, research capacity, entrepreneurship and other such outputs and outcomes to achieve absolutely unique and remarkably outstanding product and service excellence unmatched by any other.

The UK Quality Code for Higher Education (QCHE) defines the scope of QA in terms of the four academic infrastructure parameters of 'qualifications framework' which are the qualifications earned or achieved; the 'subject benchmark statements' or the expected abilities and skills needed to enhance the intellectual process or subject competence; 'programme specifications' which are the intended learning outcomes and how they can be achieved and demonstrated; and the 'code of practice' which provides guidance on how to maintain the quality and standards. El-Khawas (2001, p.111), on the other hand, advances 'institutional context and commitment, curriculum and instruction, faculty support, student support, and evaluation and assessment' *the* core principles defining and directing the QA protocol and related initiatives. Hence, systems converge in their conceptualization of the footprint with differences and variations more processual than in product, which for all intents and purposes must meet the same definition.

Figure 3.2 sums up some of the dimensions reflecting the overall curriculum literacy entailed in the QA footprint. As shown, the QA starts with the governance which enacts the relevant principles to provide the structural frame to support the footprint, much of which has been said under governance above. The rest of the discussion focuses on the other dimensions of Figure 3.2 and the complex interplay of both generic and exotic factors constantly undergoing standardization and change. Hence, in order to enhance the quality system to meticulously and meritoriously deliver the expected and cherished plateau levels, the institutions must vigorously deal with the challenges subtended to the inner dynamics of the principles and related protocols.

According to Purcell (2003), the basic determinants of the QA protocol include: the standards process itself; policy, legal, regulatory, merit and trade issues; technology and engineering issues; and access to standards and one can add ‘intellectual property’ (IP) issues. These then translate into the responsibilities which are the formal and informal activities that refine and put the QA into proper context. They cover the documentation and delivery specifications, QA offices and mechanisms, and resource supply chains, etc. Both the determinants and responsibilities make up the breadth and depth of the quality assurance varying with sector practices. Therefore, whatever the QA model, all activities must be attuned to the set principles and related indicators in order to fully maximize the output indicators, whether routine, strategic or special.

Figure 3.2 The Quality Assurance dimensions (Source: Author)

Last but not least, the output indicators collectively describe the core elements of curriculum literacy defined in terms of the ‘delivery *finesse* or standard’ – being the extent the inherent

product or service characteristics fulfil each and all of teaching and learning, research and innovation at premium costs, safety, motivation, relevance, durability, precision, usefulness, competitiveness, environmental justice, maintainability, and conformance to national specifications. As the QA trademark, this means precision and flawless finishing consistent with technocapitalism and product consumability. Therefore, to work, the QA must take stock of, and skilfully weave together, the multiple parameters to yield the requisite delivery standard whose subtle strength is the very justification for the adoption of the vision-mission philosophy.

Last, the outcomes are the recharged 'prime' institutions famous for *robotic efficiency* or top class, flawless product and service achievements. Hence the demand for high-tech skills, according to Lou's (2013) category of skills, comprising pools of *Thinkers* who are "the visionaries, strategists, intellects, and creators of the world" from whom spring or originate all big ideas such as new products, new services, and different ways of fulfilling the mandates; *Builders*, the experts and professionals who convert the intangibles into tangibles; *Improvers* who "upgrade, change or make a repeatable process better" (perpetual betterising) and *Providers* who "...execute or maintain a repeatable process" with remarkable quality excellence. While the relationship is usually pyramidal, marked by a few *Thinkers* at the top end of the scale and a bulky range of *Providers* at the bottom, important is a balanced job-mix with all categories operating beyond simple, routine maintenance functions.

The above qualities cement Bradt's (2012) critical attributes of 'Strength, Motivation, and Fit' – the three pillars that make or break jobs. Defined, Strength is guaranteeing that the thinker, builder or provider can and has the psycho-physical stamina to do the job; Motivation means they all love what they do with the zeal to do it even better now and forever; Fit means the recruit is a perfect match for the job and can tolerate working with other people and vice-versa. Therefore, reciprocated, the trio mean that the recruit will be enabled to do the job; will be loved and fully supported to do the job; and will equally tolerate the working station or environment, as the footprint is never one-way traffic. Consequently, to enhance productivity, it has become paramount for the education to ingrain issues of support and intrinsic motivation to all who work and go through the system.

So, organizationally, the practical centrality of the different categories in the teaching and learning and, therefore, their collective role as the perfect condition for *robotic efficiency* with respect to corresponding expertise, responsibility and flexibility patterns to handle myriad situations, cannot be overemphasised.

As in all systems, the feedback serves to redesign and improve each of the footprints. It is at this point that critical stakeholders come in to satisfy the 'principal' that policy, rules and procedures are being adhered to and meet the dictates of the bureaucracy. Summing up the role of the academic infrastructure, the QCHE observes that "by setting out the attributes and abilities that can be expected of the holder of a qualification, the academic infrastructure helps students and the market understand the meaning and level of qualifications, while also providing public assurance that qualifications bearing similar titles represent similar levels of achievement." Therefore, once the standards process is in motion the rest of the other issues also fall into place ensuring continuous access to the standard and to other standards by all units for reference purposes.

3.4.2 Quality assurance modalities

Through 'excellence', 'world class', 'innovative', 'high quality education', 'superior service', 'stimulant', 'best', 'premier', 'integrity/*ubuntu/hunhu*', 'Holistic Education for the Whole Person', 'patriotic and competent' and a host of other powerful forms of rhetoric, the vision-mission statements set the pace for QA modalities and infrastructures. Without exception, the terminology is identical in meaning for which by 'excellence' or 'world class' or 'best/premier' the institutions embrace the international experience of an 'ivory tower' that delivers top-notch products and services – that is, products and services that remarkably exhibit the ability to act suitably and sustainably in any situation and/or display expert knowledge of the world and the ways of society, including the ability to conduct business immaculately and sophisticatedly. By ensuring that such inherently unique properties are in place, each institution guarantees the market, in its own way, unique products and services second to none. In short, the target is to be education movers and shakers: the Harvard Business School, London School of Economics, Manchester Institute of Technology, UCT; or Africa's Eton, Oxford and Cambridge Colleges of today, if not even better than these.

Undoubtedly, with social and production systems now under intense scrutiny, pressure for more and better quality education continues to mount to guarantee unqualified service

delivery in the first instance. There is a raft of commercial and open source quality standards and systems that serve as models for design, development, production, installation, servicing and enforcement of the QA footprint. Examples include Systems Thinking, Six Sigma, Lean Management or Kaizan (or continuous improvement for quality), Decision Gates (DGs), World Class Manufacturing (WCM), Results Based Budgeting (RBB), the International Institute of Education Standards (IIES), and the ISO 9001 and 9002 family of standards to name a few. The models suit all manner of institutions, while the IIES is specifically designed for continuing education and the liberal arts/humanities education. Applicability is both the driver and snag for many a standard: dependent on whether the model focuses on the 'process' approach or on the 'absolute' product approach to quality which, as Van den Berghe (1998) observes, has a bearing on the challenges or capacity of the standard to gel with local conditions. As mentioned in Chapter 1, the philosophy of continuous improvement has assumed greater ascendancy to become the surrogate mother of the visions-missions and other standards, including techno-progressivism.

The quality systems are mostly the centralised units like the UK Quality Code for Higher Education, South Africa's Council for Higher Education, Mauritius' Tertiary Education Commission, and Zimbabwe's Council for Higher Education, working in collaboration with professional boards, institutes, associations, audit committees and departments. Institutionally, in-house quality structures, managed by quality assurance offices, supported by internal quality auditors who are local academics or professionals have been set up. Clark (1986, p.243) justifies these agencies on the grounds of "standardization to avoid ludicrous dissimilarities across programmes of study and related awards, thereby certifying that the many graduates of the many institutions have met uniform standards and awards." El-Khawas (2001) further adds that, from an external perspective, the agencies and bodies provide that extra voice of caution critical when planning change. From the rules the institutions gain other views on the proposed changes which afford them 'access to other approaches or refinements that result in better changes'.

Socio-politically, though, as Clark (1986) argues, the quality organizations suffer the bureaucratic stigma, always out to kill the vital 'differentiation' through seeing differences as risky loopholes prone to liberty and privilege, with uniformity the correct cure. Through 'dedifferentiation' and for ease of management, the institutions are reduced to common

practice. The effect of the official order narrows options inducing excessive and strong formal integration which interferes with the structural flexibility required for future progress.

As noted earlier, QA resonates with the curriculum literacy elements of the academic review, academic audit, accreditation, licensing and other evaluation procedures. Among the advantages, the objective assessments enable the institution or programme to identify its strengths and weaknesses as well as generate awareness of key performance indicators, while empowering the personnel to take charge of the quality of performance, free of pressures from external review (Materu, 2007).

The conferment of the quality standard may or may not involve certification with “relevance and cost-effectiveness” dependant on the context and, therefore, “the external demands and opportunities, as well as the internal needs and possibilities” (Van den Berghe, 1998, p.25). As Morphew and Hartley observe, it is only with such display of total quality indicating that “acceptable standards of education, scholarship, and infrastructure are being met, maintained and enhanced” that consumers would experience complete satisfaction with the products or services ensuring coveted institutional brands. However, as Van den Berghe (p.23) notes, the process approach to quality merely

provides ‘assurance’ that the institution is well organised and that the outcomes of programmes and courses meet the intended goals and needs of the users; however, it does not necessarily guarantee that the content of these courses and programmes meet a particular educational standard.

The ZIMCHE is mandated to coordinate and promote QA in collaboration with the Division of Standards Development and Quality Assurance in the MHTE,STD and numerous other professional bodies and institutes. It, therefore, regulates and monitors the design, maintenance, evaluation and recommendation of quality standards through the registration, inspection and accreditation of higher education institutions, their programmes and courses; through academic and institutional audits for quality upkeep; and, through the development of curricula to facilitate student mobility. Among its key quality framework blueprints are the Compliance Assessment Criteria for Programme Accreditation (Conventional Institutions), the Criteria for Institutional Accreditation (or Final Registration) and the Criteria for Assessing Institutional Compliance for Accreditation (Facilities Audit; zimche.ac.zw). It is the hallmark of QA when the market openly invests more rather than desperately from lack of alternatives.

The following brief sums up the quality criteria for all activities to which QA applies and the related procedures monitored for conformance (using ZIMCHE criteria) based on El-Khawas' core principles to ensure that quality standards are met.

The institutional context and commitment principle is catered for through: the existence of a clear vision, mission and objectives that guide the institution's policies and activities as well as meet the felt needs in Higher Education; programme accessibility, affordability and sustainability; existence of appropriate governance ordinances and statutes with clear roles and responsibilities; effective communication; student representation; suitable and sufficient venues, IT infrastructure and library resources; regular staff development; effective work-based learning; general institutional welfare in terms of the requisite hardware and software resources; regular-user surveys, reviews and impact studies on the effectiveness of the programme to improve programme design, delivery and resourcing and also for staff development and student support; regulating structures of the diploma, undergraduate and postgraduate study programmes, the standards of teaching and examinations, the academic qualifications of students and teaching personnel; proper supply of the physical infrastructures; internal quality audit support by local academics or professionals.

The curriculum and instruction principle is fulfilled through ensuring: programme consistency and coherence with the mission and other programmes; effective teaching and learning methods, coupled with suitable learning materials and opportunities that facilitate achievement of the purposes and outcomes of the programme; institutional planning and resource allocation; ideal bearing on national requirements, the needs of students and other stakeholders; intellectual credibility; appropriate teaching and learning strategy/general pedagogy and other teaching and learning methods, mechanisms and forms of upgrading; effective administrative, information, and other programme management services to cater for the diverse student populations; strategic plans for programme implementation, monitoring, evaluation, and effective improvement; the integrity of processes leading to certification of the qualification obtained through the programme.

The faculty support principle is mirrored by: the establishment of the QA offices; appointments of fully qualified personnel to meet and maintain minimum academic, business

and financial management standards; ensuring proper teaching qualifications, relevant experience and competence; appropriate ratios of full-time staff; recruitment and employment of staff following relevant legislation and appropriate administrative procedures, including redress and equity considerations; research and publication and other academic development initiatives; appropriate procedures and criteria for appointment, promotion and tenure; professional growth and development; adequately qualified support staff.

The student support principle is enhanced through: proof of full registration; adequate class numbers that tally with capacity and/or lecturer/student ratios; accurate and adequate information on the nature, content and outcomes of each programme; academic support when necessary; funding and internships; diversity of skills; graduate employability; access to special physical infrastructures/ facilities (specialist rooms and equipment, computers, the Internet); wider extra-curriculum facilities for full life experiences.

Last, the evaluation and assessment principle is reflected through: full internal assessment policies, regulations and procedures; internal and external moderation; monitoring of student progress, clarity, validity, and reliability of assessment practices; management of results and security of the assessment system; disputes settlement; staff competency development in the coursework, the final examination, and the project, including the calculation and weighting of the pass mark and determination of the final award; procedures for test and inspection, conducting internal audits and holding regular management reviews; setting up conformance procedures like accreditations, dealing with non-conformance; and, regular and objective systemic monitoring and evaluations.

Put together, it is a comprehensive spectrum of policy issues, legal issues, regulatory issues, merit issues, technology issues or target safeguards, benchmarks, specifications, practice codes, protocols, outcomes and competencies – total assurance of the requisite potential learning product. Depending on the purpose of the review, audit, check list, etc. the programme or institution must meet the respective criteria in order to be accredited, registered or licensed. As indicated before, the business of the ZIMCHE is to protect the market from undue exploitation and exposure to sub-standard education and worthless certificates, hence, maintain and enhance the reputation of Zimbabwe as a provider of high quality education (ZIMCHE, 2011). While not recommending a particular standard, the

availability of a vision-mission philosophy has been made compulsory to strengthen the culture of quality with remarkably high academic standards coupled to measures that ensure commitment to technocapitalism. Hence, functionally, the totality of the procedures and protocols provides the “assurance” that the standard is well set and that the outcomes of programmes and courses on offer meet the intended goals and needs of the users. However, as said before, it least guarantees that the course and programme content absolutely meet the national demand for robotic efficiency.

3.4.3 The delivery *finesse*

As Figure 3.2 shows, delivery *finesse* is the heart of the QA footprint which, according to the production-function approach, denotes the internal and external efficiency of the curriculum reflecting deep-seated individual classroom and extra-curricular events. Of interest are the inherent product or service characteristics and the extent they satisfy the host of factors, nuances, needs and wants. In line with the Corporate Lifecycle model, the delivery *finesse* is anchored on continuous alignment between vision, strategy, structure, decision making, resource allocation and rewards, forms of accreditation, and intra- and inter-organizational and community integration, culminating in profitable innovation. It is the evidence of the ‘Prime’ stage showcasing flourish, boom and optima typical of world class mandates.

Among the most outstanding attributes of QA are quality teaching and learning, quality research and innovation and, with these, quality rankings all of which assure stakeholders that the policy decisions and education offered meet the highest local and international standards (Materu, 2007). Buttressing the attributes are quality resource inputs defined in number, scale and timing, including aesthetics. Rightly or wrongly institutions succeed or fail here making quality throughput the soul and breath of the socio-HR beneficitation process. The capacity of the curriculum-management to deliver is as critical as bullion by whatever description. Hence, QA is as much the obsession gripping the minds and efforts of all in the judgment of the institutions, overshadowing everything else. The following discussion examines these aspects and other attributes shown in Figure 3.2.

3.4.3.1 Teaching and learning

The academic infrastructure of teaching and learning is the pinnacle of the curriculum literacy, whether or not, epistemologically and ontologically, the ‘curriculum’ is branded and fixed in the realism of the socio-economic *pracademics* to meet Selingo’s (2014) top-class

aspiration for the “dual experience of high-impact, in-classroom learning and out-of-the-classroom, experiential, and hands-on learning” to culture sufficient pools of *Thinkers, Builders, Improvers* and *Providers*. Operational models and facilities are as ubiquitous as the teachers and learners so much that practitioners are spoiled for choice, although the results have not always been fully satisfactory, leading to incessant complaints (Petty, 2006). Most important is how each and every vision-mission statement vouchsafes that the products and services will match the exacting product standards reflected in its teaching and learning. This is in-keeping with the observation by Morphew and Hartley (2006, p.458) that “a tertiary institution is only as good as the quality of its teaching staff who are the heart of the institution who produce its graduates, its research products, and its service to the institution, community, and nation.”

Experimentalism, propelling commercial research and innovation, is the heart of the epistemology and pedagogy to rattle mindsets, sharpen intelligence and stimulate rational and radical behaviours befitting technocapital’s conscious competences – in particular individuals with creative aptitudes. According to Science Education Initiative (SEI), the pedagogy entails optimizing the three key fundamentals of ‘content, process and methodology’ summed up in the simple questions ‘what should students learn?’, ‘What are students learning?’ and ‘Which approaches improve student learning’, respectively? As shown in Figure 3.3, the critical relationship is the way the triangles fold into the inner triangle to form one unit in answer to the question: which triangle should come first or last and why – and by no means a simple equation?

In the first two questions, the relationship is between ‘should’ and ‘are’: whether there is agreement or disagreement between imperatives, on one hand, versus the reality on the ground, on the other, with the two often working at cross-purposes or failing to match – which is often the genesis of future problems. The ‘what...’ highlights the symbolic interactionism or fixed facts approach and the tendency, if mishandled, towards content overload, hence, banking education. The ‘which...’ focuses on the methodology or actual delivery which incubates the ‘how to...’ in order to promote praxis, or pragmatism, or practical application as the pillar strength of the delivery standard. Its low key at the expense of the ‘what’ is the dilemma of the education.

Figure 3.3 Content-process-methodology relationship

(Source: cwsei.ubc.ca)

Continuously rebranding the theoretical and practical foundations are the teaching and learning theories, principles, methods, blueprints and dossiers, as well as research and innovation models deployed to interface a subject matter-learner interaction that merits the quality standard. The Schreyer Institute for Teaching Excellence (2011) best illustrates the prevailing aspirations to motivate students “to learn in ways that make a sustained, substantial, and positive influence on how they think, act, and feel, while also elevating them to a level where they learn deeply and remarkably because of teacher attributes” – epistemologically, the Maslow Hierarchy of Needs theory.

In line with its philosophy, the institution’s vision-mission describes the attributes of an excellent teacher as ‘one who contributes positively to the learning environment by providing exceptional energy, keen interest in students, and extraordinary strengths within the framework roles of *Subject matter expert*, *Pedagogical expert*, *Student-centred mentor*, *Excellent communicator*, and *Systematic and continual assessor*, hence, inducing the best teaching-learning environment practicable (schreyerinstitu.psu.edu). The comprehensive teacher attributes are the ideal behind continuous regeneration of both new and tried and tested theoretical and practical methodologies as the following highlights illustrate.

The *Subject matter expert* is described as ‘possessing thorough knowledge of subject matter and demonstrates a contagious enthusiasm for it; goes further than the standard textbook materials; researches and develops important and original thoughts on the subject specialty; thinks about the discipline, analysing its nature and evaluating its quality; follows regularly intellectual developments in the discipline and related fields; and, takes strong interest in broader issues, and is intellectually admirable.’

Similarly, the *Pedagogical expert* ‘sets appropriate learning goals and objectives and communicates them clearly; demonstrates a positive attitude toward and trust in students and continually works to overcome obstacles that might subvert learning; evaluates and grades student work fairly and promptly; encourages students to think and empowers them to find their own creativity; promotes a wide range of ideas and the open expression of diverse opinions while maintaining an atmosphere of integrity, civility and respect; guides students successfully through exploration of the creative, critical thinking, and problem solving processes and helps students grapple with ideas and information they need to develop their own intellection; promotes student self-discovery; pursues teaching and learning as scholarly activities; exhibits a strong sense of commitment to the academic community in addition to personal success in the classroom; provides, on a regular basis, constructive and objective feedback to students; and finds unique and creative ways to connect students to each other (Source: Schreyer Institute, 2011).

Complementing classroom vitality are learning styles to cater for individual differences that obtain in learning situations. One classical example is the Richard Felder and Linda Silverman’s Index of Learning Styles comprising the four continuums of ‘Sensory–Intuitive; Visual–Verbal; Active–Reflective; and Sequential–Global’ learning styles. According to Manktelow and Carlson (MindTools, #263, 2012), to balance the pedagogy succinctly

with Sensory–Intuitive learners there is need to provide both hard facts and general concepts, with Visual–Verbal learners, to incorporate both visual and verbal cues, with Active–Reflective learners, to allow both experiential learning and time for evaluation and analysis, and with Sequential–Global learners, to provide detail in a structured way, as well as the big picture.

Overall, notwithstanding inherent weaknesses, what such comprehensive blueprints and dossiers emphasise is the fact that: expertise-cum-excellence should be the pivotal teaching principle; curricula design and expatiation should be an admixture of faculty-student interests;

innovation and change must permeate the whole environment; and life-long learning should be a strong component of the education vision. Therefore, delivery *finesse* is revealed as neither a one-size-fits-all nor one basic capability. Rather, it is a string of skills developed and/or learned in many different ways. As a result, the subject matter-learner interface has increasingly become a complex process requiring constant movements and adjustments in response to the psycho horizontal and vertical developments of the learner. Among others, a hypercritical and punctilious workmanship girded by a strong research and innovation culture is critical to strengthen student disciplinary bones.

Boosting the delivery standard are the library and IT media services offering unrestricted access to literary disciplines and other resources to foster the knowledge-cum-professional society. The advent of the 'Open Access' facility has expanded library resources for research, teaching, learning, and other user needs. As IFLA's (rather politically inclined) pledge commiserates: "Free, democratic, peaceful, successful societies based upon the rule of law, representative political institutions, equality of economic opportunity, institutional transparency and freedom of expression" are additional returns to librarised delivery.

Allied is the tug-of-war between online learning, blended learning, traditional face-to-face practice, and distance learning. Notwithstanding fears to the contrary, technology enthusiasts are beating the drum in credit of the IT devices while fiercely discrediting traditional teaching as the bureaucratic cemetery of indigenous cultures, only good for banking education. It is as if learning as mechanism has just arrived when it has been in existence for millennia with learning methods barely changing with technologies except new insights in the way the new technologies illuminate how our brains work in ways not experienced before. The dilemma then is whether learning occurs better with the new technologies or it still occurs despite them. But, continuing to vex the institutional metric is the stubborn mismatch between curricula and the much sought after technopreneurial breakthrough.

Worth extra attention is Student Affairs whose contribution is often underrated. The demand is for relevant, quality student welfare programmes – a big challenge given its hybrid nature with so many, non-core activities under its roof all going on at the same time. A vibrant Student Affairs is vital to mould the correct conduct, character and personality profiles that meet the requisite social 'strength, motivation and fit' across the board. As a result of the

non-central role of its functions, coupled with the complexity of the student body, Student Affairs often finds itself playing a peripheral role in the grooming which ultimately impacts the delivery standard. The related challenges that cripple the QA formbook include the domination of first generation students, relationship problems, alcohol and substance abuse, anxiety, depression and career mismatches.

3.4.3.2 Research and innovation

Research and innovation complement the teaching and learning. As mentioned before, the two represent the 3rd generation creative force whose miracle is not a result of random forces, but an outcome of one of the greatest developments in modern history. As endowments, they are the mainstay of material production and social change and, therefore, the key to the sustainable development paradigm.

Both basic and applied research constitute the bulk of the process to generate classroom knowledge; as a value standard for all who pass through the system; to access new discoveries and inventions to boost the economy or for solutions to *in situ* challenges; to evaluate the behaviour of the market; to reach a new understanding; for purposes of initiating, modifying or terminating a particular technology or investment; or to propagate an ideology, policy and philosophy. As hubs of research and innovation, the institutions sustain the delivery standard through both incremental and radical innovations. The former, also called sustaining innovation, is the small-steps-improvements on an existing product or product line while the latter, also called disruptive innovation, is the more dramatic, sweeping changes behind the 'perpetual betterising' – that is, continuously making market products or conditions better forever and ever (Chulu, 2016a). This translates into more and better error reduction and prevention, signifying the criterion of zero defects and high level competitiveness. It is the intelligence with which the systems successfully play around with the innovations or betterising that they either access greater opportunity or experience failure.

Both classical and modern models inundate the market to describe the perceptible and imperceptible behaviour of innovations. They include the Diffusion Wave model, the Innovative Efforts Continuum model, the Disruptive Innovation model, and the Gartner Hype Cycle model with a great deal of overlap between them. In almost all models, the innovation undergoes the fairly definable stages of diffusion, condensing and saturation (the Diffusion

Wave), or diffusion, enclaving, resocialization and termination (the Innovative efforts continuum) or the wave-trough Gartner Hype Cycle model.

Briefly, diffusion is the wildfire flare as the innovation wave catches on, initially contrasting sharply with the remote hinterland but spreading out successfully and only ceasing influence when saturation is reached. In the process is condensing or the relative expansion in the number of acceptances equal in all locations or directions irrespective of distance from the innovation source. Enclaving occurs in the event of internal challenges whereby the innovation maintains its existence but in isolation within the larger institution (usually where it started). In the event of extreme adversity, resocialization takes over whereby the innovators are forced to fall back in line with prevailing traditional values and practices. Finally, with lack of sustained interest or outright opposition, termination ensues, whereby the innovation is eliminated altogether.

The Gartner Hype Cycle wave begins with the 'technology trigger', rising sharply to the 'peak of inflated expectations', then falling sharply in the 'trough of disillusionment', and then slowly rising along the 'slope of enlightenment' to finally reach and maintain the 'plateau of productivity' once mainstream adoption has taken off. Last, the 'Disruptive Innovation' model is where, by means of technology, the initially unattractive and inconsequential budding service provider cuts into traditional markets by reducing complexity and introducing simplicity, convenience, accessibility and affordability, hence, enabling the innovation to take root. As a result of the technology, consumability rises compared to previously where complication and high cost are the norm, carving out a niche market that redefines the industry. Ultimately, whatever the model, recognisable spread effects or transformations positive to society take place.

Proponents of the different models argue that, not only do they ensure insightful decisions on innovations, according to the Gartner Hype Cycle, they also assist the market 'discern the hype from what is commercially viable.' Chulu (2016a, p.6) then argues that getting the categories of innovation right is a must signal of intellectual acumen, if the innovations are to solve real market challenges as well as open up avenues to explore further opportunities. Successful research and innovation puts research policy and practice in a better position to

manage risks through better verification of the potential relevance of innovations hence enabling ascendancy towards the much sought after world class status or gold standard.

3.4.3.3 Rankings

Rankings influence the delivery standard indirectly in the sense that they are used to compare institutional capacities against the primate standards. Therefore, whether popular or not, or still experimental like the cyber-systems, the rankings have become synonymous with quality checks and balances. There is a host of ranking systems which include the Shanghai Jiao Tong Academic Rankings of World Universities (ARWU), the Times Higher Education Supplement (THES), the Webometrics Ranking of World Universities, University Rankings by Academic Performance (URAP), the G-factor, and the LinkedIn University Rankings to name a few. The bundle keeps growing in an effort to accommodate diversity in criteria and resolve the controversy arising therefrom.

Among the measuring criteria, education and research excellence are the most commonly ranked relying on both objective and subjective criteria. According to Taylor and Braddock (2008, p.249), the objective criteria include “publication rates in academic journals, citations in academic journals, researchers’ ability to attract competitive funding, staff-student ratios, class sizes and annual university spending per student”, with the ARWU considered the most objective system in this respect. Among the subjective criteria are expert rankings, peer review surveys, employers’ or recruiters’ ratings of a university’s graduates, number of foreign students, and course satisfaction surveys among students and graduates.

The objective of the Africa Association of Universities’ (AAU) African Higher Education Excellence Award (AHEEA) is “to stimulate the revitalization of the African academy through supporting outstanding research, social responsiveness, teaching, and innovative leadership by Africa’s academics.” Last, the LinkedIn method bases on career outcomes according to the disciplines of Accounting, Designers, Professionals, Finance Professionals, Marketers and Software Developers, etc. Drawbacks notwithstanding, as Loannidis, Patsopoulos, Kavvoura, Tatsioni,...and Liberopoulos (2007) argue, the rankings have the potential to enhance career choices, rationalise funding, prioritise investment and public information, and to boost internal self-evaluation and improvement. They are the appropriate measurement whether or not full technocapitalism has been realised.

3.4.3.4 Additional resources

As Figure 3.2 shows, constituting further prerequisites to the delivery *finesse* is the host of inherent non-academic indicator variables related to premium physical infrastructures, costs, health and safety, customer satisfaction, institutional values, maintainability and compliance to policy specifications. A great deal has been said about these and more illustrations follow in the next chapters. Collectively, these properties imply full access, affordability, precision, durability, and relevance, with policy blueprints, infrastructures and working conditions kept buoyant and attractive to clients and the workforce.

As the cornerstone of the delivery standard, the physical infrastructure entails state-of-the-art buildings – that is, lecture rooms and theatres, libraries, laboratories, workshops, offices, technology incubators, and halls of residence, that are fully stocked with smart contents (furnishings, equipment, apparatuses, books, journals, ICT and the Internet, and other network resources); nestled in splendid landscapes of attractive gardens and avenues; and propped up by sports and leisure facilities, catering and transport services, lifts and shuttle trams, and sufficient water, electricity and other supplies. Such an environment is not only refreshing and admirable, exciting and pleasurable, but ensures genuine enculturation through assuring the teachers, learners, administrators and the whole workforce minimum disruptions, and in return, unparalleled performance with high investment yields.

Furthermore, as Clark (1986) urges, among the numerous benefits, the workforce must be afforded the opportunity to educate and train in the various teaching, leadership, management and production perspectives; in web delivery, research, dialogue and peace; and in corporate social responsibility. In boosting credits, there must be total elimination of disincentives, especially fees controls and procedural impediments and offer in their place attractive fees packages, bursary and scholarship funds, tax exemptions, land and housing, contact leave, moonlighting, efficient oversight, and accreditation mechanisms.

Beyond taking care of the normal challenge of insufficient managerial depth and the need to embrace change to expand the legitimate disorder, the constant 'skills' upgrades must extend to sporting competitions, internal and external disputations for alternative ideas and perspectives, as well as access to information and communications and other habits that foster the requisite positive attitudes. And, as the very driver of the competitive market, the

professoriate must be afforded the status of free agents in terms of flexible, sustainable demands. Last, endogenous schemes like tabloids, client charters, prospectuses or yearbooks, and staff and student portals, complemented by audits, research and seminar publications, magazines, and *newsletter* bulletins buttress the delivery standard.

Among notable examples offering the requisite exchanges are the Southern African Regional Universities Association (SARUA) and the AAU, coupled with numerous institutional summits and conferences which bring together the different categories of faculty and administrative personnel in an effort to revitalise and strengthen the academy so that the social actors are more meaningfully responsive to the developmental challenges facing them and their respective regions. As pointed out in Chapter 1, lack of such exposure means that there is so much that the institutions are missing out or are not doing generating the usual sore weakness and misconception that once the vision-mission statements are in place everyone understands and knows what to do.

It is, therefore, when these resources are in place that the generated economies of scale reflect quality institutional climate, quality improvement plans, quality supply chains, quality home background, quality support services, and quality stakeholder rights – staff tenure, staff-student ratios, extra-curricular activities and human relations (Materu, 2007). Deserving special attention is the extent the body politic must remain anti-bureaucratic and anti-chock: realising that “the greatest problem of Prime is staying in Prime” (Adizes’ 2015). Such actions serve to counter the abnormal governance challenges associated with a fastidious status quo, insufficient decentralization/devolution, reliance on the past, a *laissez fair* sense of security or achievement, weak entrepreneurial activity, order for the sake of order, and more time spent in the office behind the desk (Adizes’). The opportunity costs tend to induce revolutionary rather than evolutionary events destabilising the systems.

Altogether, a well-orchestrated delivery standard means that all sides of the governance are pragmatically astute. The academic governance studiously motivates the students to learn deeply and in ways that nurture sustained competence, reflected in the ability to think, act, feel and behave judiciously, hence, elevating their ability to validate firm academic, technical, professional and socio-environmental emancipation. Equally, in line with the Katz Skills model (1986), the administration practices well defined technical, human relations, and

conceptualization skills involving the nuts and bolts of the different jobs or employee know-how; effective, interactive management skills; crowned by deeper and broader oversight, respectively. Entailed is the veritable capacity to execute the baseline skills of leading, team-building and managing (planning, control, communicating, organising, etc.) duly acquitted in consultation with the relevant parties and stakeholders. Ultimately, the much sought after 'Prime' stage is all about executing the letter and spirit of these baseline skills to muster and master uncertainty and other VUCA challenges.

Summed up, numerous academic, non-academic and physical infrastructures play a pivotal role in the QA footprint to inspire studious delivery and wise mentoring to enable the power and scope of ideas to deepen the potential learning product portfolio. At the same time, this frees the students from childhood presumptions, stigmas and prejudices "to pursue their own path of life so that they more than understand the complexities of the human condition or at least what others, men and women of acknowledged wisdom, have thought about life's challenges" (Lewis, 2007, p.16). This leaves the footprint the most heavily loaded, raising the vision-mission stakes to a credible zenith in the successful deliverance of perfect knowledge, skills and values for sustainable development. The ultimate outcome is the qualified and/or unqualified intelligence the products exhibit as they interact with novel technologies as well as adapt to unfamiliar situations consistent with the principles of legitimate disorder and related technological changes. The current challenge is how, through errors of omission and commission, the options deployed invariably stymie the subject matter–learner interface leaving it functionally raw than fully cooked.

3.4.4 Quality assurance glitches

Problems and challenges everywhere in higher education generate immediate and long-term QA shocks. In an extensive critique on QA in higher education, Morley (2003, p.5) observes how it is reeling under a "powerful discourse of crisis, loss, damage, contamination, and decay." Set up as a critical check to the feared 'chaos' emerging from the global expansion of higher education to ensure that systems and structures can process the ever-increasing student numbers, its neoliberal discourse belies "deeply conservative underpinnings", now extensively dogged by "institutions in ruins or crises, degradation of academia, death of autonomy and proletarianization" which constitutes its undoing. The quality audits continue to "manipulate and unleash emotions of fear, powerlessness, greed, desire, anger, pride and shame", while its democratization engenders more risk aversion leading to institutions

adopting “authoritarian and exploitative forms of capitalism.” Hence, higher education has become both the necessary and willing ally and victim of ruthless state and economic oligarchies peddling controversial QA ideals and interests.

The first evidence of Morley’s critique is the sub-standard physical infrastructure. The challenge with classroom space, library, laboratory and IT resources (especially critical software in engineering disciplines) has tended to cripple pedagogy and service delivery to the barest medium and minimum. Often, not only is the technology outdated or in short supply, it is handicapped by the numerous bottlenecks of affordability, equitability, erratic power supply, shortage of consumables and Internet facilities, extending to the shortage of quality instructors. Meanwhile, the decline in funding per capita amid congested enrolments continues the alarm and concern with falling delivery and output standards. Last, are the high costs of installation, implementation and certification, coupled with excessive volumes of paperwork and time lost to maintain and audit the QA mechanisms, which contribute to dysfunctional efficiency.

The second evidence are the opportunity costs surrounding the academic infrastructure repeatedly fanning out disvalue education, with the alumni still to unleash the illimitable innovations and inventions. As Suarez-Villa (2009) argues, the commodification of creativity, experimentalism and the knowledge explosion drives the culpable burdens of ‘compulsions, exploitive schemes, and diverse pathologies’, blinding and curtailing capacity for appropriate expressions. The delivery is distortedly reduced to secondary and consumptive rather than primary and creative education. Rising opportunity costs driven by the constant expertise and resource shortages arising from the high staff turnover, the brain-drain and weak funding complement the carnage.

At the classroom level, as Stein (2014) argues, despite the high-profile preparations, the institutional approaches are far from ready to meet the learning needs of the 21st century student. Their ‘traditional student’ approach only exacerbates the rapid shifts in student mosaics against the backdrop of learning needs that become highly complex by the passing of each day. As he puts it, there are clear-cut difficulties to ‘more effectively serve and interface with the student populations’ whose enthusiasm and reticence about their education is only paralleled by disillusionment about their futures. Not only do they define everything

radically differently, they are fastidious about employment paths which must offer high investment returns to match world class standards regardless of productivity. Accordingly, the technocapitalism drives global worldviews and less ambient, indigenous perspectives, with the education a passport for duty and responsibility elsewhere in the international market and secondarily to the local scapes.

In turn, the market is often dissatisfied with the commodified labour, invoking concern with product 'strength, motivation, and fit' or entrepreneurial employability (Schramm, 2013). Commenting in Tony Karrer's eLearning Blog, Jack Slash (2007) describes degrees (particularly the Masters degree) as uninspiring so long they are unaccompanied by 'something real-world-tangible to show for it'. In his view, a degree tells very little, except that one 'may not be a real, self-motivated learner' when employers require solid experience as evidence that the degree holder 'is a dedicated, resourceful, hardworking person.' Above all is the question of attitude and whether 'a can-do, confident, positive, buck-stops-here attitude' prevails, something which requires hands-on practice to instil. A 2011 deVry University study echoed similar sentiments, highlighting how the Masters education was unable to prepare candidates for top management jobs across the most valued skills of strategic perspective, high integrity, global outlook, strong base work ethic (dependable), and accountability management looks for among recruits. Sadly, it is an Improvers and Providers education rather than one for critical Thinkers and Builders.

As a consequence of the consumptive education, the teaching and learning exhibits the trappings of the elephant-in-the-zoo or chicken mind-set (Pipim, 2013) leading to market dissatisfaction (Gatawa, 1998; Mavhunga, et al. 2009; the Education Review Commission, 1999). What are peddled most of the time are the symptoms of QA, mainly, relevance, satisfaction and symbolization (grades) rather than the essence and nuances of technocapitalism. The unfortunate part is how consumers are subjected to mediocre services; or have to endure exposure to unethical practices and external pressures; or have to resort to expensive imports whenever they can against the backdrop of a rising misery/*Homo simplex* index.

Issues of ideology compound the quality of the products further in that, as a result of their non-neutral nature, curriculum matters remain ideologically conflictive and hard to resolve

and justify. With endogenous ideologies rendered redundant upon the advent of the unipolar world dominated by the science-globalization combination as the engine of human progress, the status quo has become more egregious (Mavhunga, et al. 2009; Morley, 2003). Banking education transmitted through the Socratic–technocratic approach is the new rationality which, according to Dale and Hyslop-Margison (2010, p.83) entails massive “transfer of ideology and the supporting perspectives and information from the hegemonic minority to the powerless majority”; from knower to empty knowee (*tabula rasa*).

Arguing further, they observe that both the instructional and review exercises are rarely to confront students with their misconceptions, or to question the ideological messages of the curriculum, or of its individual disciplines, nor to bring in local alternatives, but largely to replicate the status quo’s quasi-colonial objective to “create a like-minded citizenry” (p.73). The result is the same old story of the African elite who are always attracted by theoretical education (the supremacy of theory paradigm) rather than to foster psycho-technics education (the supremacy of practicality paradigm). The net impact is perpetual dependency on technogarchic nations.

This, then, dovetails with the blind importation of philosophies without thorough vetting: and continuous improvement is *the* very example. Morley (2003, p.14) defines it as “travel hopefully but never to arrive” – a derisive remark rather than a compliment on the philosophy. In essence it implies and means exactly this, which raises the question on the social benefits of the unattainable ideals. As he notes, continuous improvement underlines the “sense of permanence of struggle, the elusiveness of satisfactory goals, and the ambiguity of measurement measures” but inundating the market with assurances of solutions *absolutus*. Hence, replicating the McNamara Fallacy, systems resort to measuring what can easily be measured; ignore as unimportant or non-existent the non-quantifiable metrics, although the silent shift to technocapitalism appears to address this loophole to keep more busyness on track to ingeminate and enhance greater competitiveness.

Therefore, claims that the delivery standard is being offered through continuous improvement of the selected methodologies and models, ensuring that learners acquire the know-how in ways that enhance the QA, are scarcely borne out by facts. If anything, rather than the technology exponential syndrome, the delivery trajectory ushers the technology regression

syndrome that ebbs from freedom from ignorance, and perversely scales to conscious incompetence, to technological dependence and, finally, to lifetime bondage to technological imperialism. The utilitarian value of the teaching and learning grooves at best *providers* of maintenance services, enjoying the capacity to copy and import, while, the assurance to students of a bright future equivalent to the West only spawns massive corruption as *the* access route when breakthroughs fail to materialise. Rather than a spontaneous psych, the vision-mission philosophy is reduced to a grafted emblem plainly repositioning the ills and challenges of technocapitalist hegemony.

In conclusion, despite its intangible nature, the QA footprint is the *nerve centre* of the vision-mission construct. The inherent product and service characteristics must not only be uniquely proficient, but must clinically and holistically be the right grade reflecting effective fact and efficient action, exceeding both customer expectations and/or competitors. Ultimately, the academic-physical infrastructures union must be expertly integrated with processes progressing rationally, professionally, democratically and energetically in a very conducive learning environment free of downgrade malpractices. However, it is one thing to fancy the Adizes' 'Prime' stage and it is quite another to achieve it. Multiple burdens curtail real relevant 'dual-experiences' for cutting edge curriculum literacy and programme models and better student lifecycle management platforms and services. In the end, rather than quality, obscure substitutes prevail.

3.5 Comportment

The comportment footprint is the instilling of market behaviours to produce the desired cultured behaviour, change in esteem and bearing conduct; or complete personal and professional deportment and other psychosocial principles, norms and ethics critical to society. Put another way, it is the inculcation of the host of acceptable affects or refined moral values and ethics, exclusive and exemplary attributes and other logistics to enable the products to live and work totally fulfilling lives for themselves, their communities, nations and the world. Hence, the enculturation or acculturation has become a complex affair embodying nurturing the whole gamut of 'hard' and 'soft' skills in leadership, innovation, integrity, honesty, hard work, *ubuntu*, etc.

As a result, the comportment footprint is not only the most overloaded envelop, it has become even more complex with diversity in cultural exchanges in the drive to conquer wicked problems and balance the ‘academic-productivity-humanitarian’ interface. Significantly, at the end of their education and training, and throughout their working lives, the products must exhibit scholarly conduct and behaviour, imbued with altruistic attitude-value complexes rooted in self-discipline and presence, guided by the philosophy of the ‘greater many’ working for the ‘common good’, devoid of the tragedy of the commons or opportunism and other forms of moral hazard.

3.5.1 The core dimensions of comportment

As constantly indicated, the comportment reduces to the three dimensions of ‘technocracy, the normative-moral virtues/ethics canon and environmental justice’ varying in elasticity with institutional philosophy bringing about integrated differentiation and the critical niches institutions carve out within the higher education landscape. Structurally, it means full technocapitalism for more and better social equity, welfare and related benefits, coupled with psychosocially high-net-worth individuals that are well versed in community science and are able to deliver both basic and extra services to the needy, vulnerable and disadvantaged. Epistemologically, therefore, the three dimensions form the precondition to a vibrant human–nature interface compatible with the technological society. This is to say, they are the broader objectives of the curriculum to culture the HR infinite that is the flagship of a rational technocapitalist spirit befitting modernity.

3.5.1 Technocracy

From the discussion, technocracy is the psycho-technical know-how to experiment and manipulate physical forces, materials and systems in practical work to meet entrepreneurial demands for the increasingly technologically-driven and enterprise-based developments (Yizengaw, 2003). Put another way, it is ‘conscious competence’ or the intelligence individuals bring to life-work situations consistent with the evolution of these situations and the problems they create (Mnkandla, 2011b). It is underpinned by the distinct technical rationality value of proficiency – the timely, accurate, precision movements that deliver quickly and easily quality products, goods and services. The proficiency reflects the collective efficiency of the psycho-technics and other acts of industry and judicious behaviour like intellectual property rights (IPs) and emotional intelligence (EI) that are the basis of productivity and utility maximization.

From a psychological perspective, the psycho-technics is the practical or technological application of perceptual and conceptual cues, nuances and creations in the unravelling of socio-economic challenges and problems. Epistemologically, it is a series of learned physical and/or mental acts requiring simultaneous or sequential coordination. The application reflects the intelligent blending of cognitive and psychomotor skills critical in the efficient conversion of materials, energy, data and information to work resources and the environment to enhance productivity. In scientific terms, its successful acquisition is reflected through the process of negentropy or the economic and efficient use of 'energy'; or, according to Mnkandla (2011a), through exhibiting prominent features of creative results like IPs, accuracy in timing and anticipation of movement, economy in appropriate movement and flow of movement with minimum misallocation of resources. KAIZAN philosophers will say doing it in order to know it with zero defects or losses.

Second, IP has become the technocracy standard indicator. It covers both tangible and intangible formulations of the mind like literary and artistic works, creations, inventions, as well as symbols, names, logos, images and designs. It is either industrial property (patents, trademarks, industrial designs) or copyright (films, musical works, novels, plays, and artistic works like drawings and paintings) over which there are exclusive rights recognised in law, extending to community property accessible to all stakeholders, reflecting technology as social capital. As the backbone to modernization, IP has become a priceless subject with both the World Trade Organization (WTO) and the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO), in association with local chapters, actively involved in its growth and development.

Last, crucial to a safe, healthy, durable technocracy is EI, defined by Manktelow and Carlson (2012) as "the awareness of one's thoughts and emotions, as well as of the emotional wants and needs of the people around you and synergizing the two to greater effect." It entails demonstrating qualities of compassion, empathy and dialoguing for more and better people acumen to keep the life-work psycho-technics friendly and humane, filled with generative communications and relationships that stimulate higher productivity and the greater good (Hlabathi, 2014). In exploring the 'why' difference, and any other difference for that matter, EI serves as the latent incentive motivating the most and best out of the workforce.

In line with Rabinbach (1992, p.289) and Roldan (2010), the philosophy of psycho-technics is rooted in the classical metaphor of the 'human motor' which posits that "the working body is a productive force capable of transforming universal natural energy into mechanical work and integrating the human organism into highly specialised and technical work processes." Its modern meaning encapsulates superintelligent acquisition of advanced mental and physical dexterity competences (the psycho-technics) capable to sustain the complicated and sophisticated transformations associated with modern infrastructures and livelihoods. The human motor has since been enhanced by socio-industrial intelligence involving greater contact with machine technology which is now the cornerstone of the epistemology.

Invariably, the psycho-technics emerge as the high-impact capabilities ingrained through the dual learning experience enhancing product capacity to rationally, productively and interactively validate firm academic, technical, professional and environmental involvement. Robotic efficiency represented by superintelligent human beings and machines (for example, 3D manufacturing and cloud computing) is the new standard. As the core and top strategy, the psycho-technics are proving the biggest test and let down leaving the constituents with many questions and doubts than answers. This is to say the delivered education is infinitesimal to inconsequential in terms of mind-on-hands-on applications, with hope now turned to the market approach to deliver the exceptional results.

Summed up, technocracy is the heart of the modern-day technocapitalist system, significantly crucial to resource beneficiation and value-addition (Zim-Asset, 2013). As the foundation of the technological infinite, it inspires a whole range of perceptions and conceptions that activate the socio-environmental responses of technopreneurship, innovation, invention, self-reliance, etc. This demands an educated class (or *literati*) that is able to galvanise a vibrant technogarchy to excel in the different fields of production and service as the right foot forward. It is the lack of a vibrant value-addition sting to the entrepreneurships that is the undoing of developing economies.

3.5.2 The normative-moral virtues canon

The normative-moral virtues canon embodies the host of liberal and conservative demands and expectations such as liberty, loyalty, equity, rights, freedoms, commitment, security and incorruption and service, on one hand, and the related norms decidedly to foster

humanitarian principles of healthy social wellbeing, self-discipline, communality, social giving and service and concern for others, on the other. The two work together to inculcate the soft skills the people and systems savour most and are accustomed to.

In liberty are expectations of choice, initiative, innovation, fairness, criticism, and variety. In loyalty are the demands and expectations of patriotism, integrity, *ubuntu/hunhu*, communality and professionalism critical to nation building and statehood. In equity are issues of kindness mixed with justice, equality, fairness, communality, access and affordability, and *esprit de corps* crucial to achieve an even playing field across the constituency-institutional spectrum. In rights and freedoms is the exercise of both inalienable (natural) and vested (legal) rights or aspirational and positive rights as enshrined in the UN and African Charter on Human/People's Rights and in constitutional statutes. In particular, is the right of assembly, association, worship and to employment, information, health, education, peace and justice, and property entitlements, as well as freedom from child labour, abuse, violence, etc. and to abort and to choose careers and marriage, often referred to as social capital.

The core of *ubuntu/hunhu* is the cosmovisional perception of the relationship between 'people, nature and religion' and the influence the hybrid natural, spiritual and psychosocial mix exerts on shaping, remaking and creating a stable eco-culture for the sustenance of all. Given the interplay of culture and religion, the *ubuntu* worldview is, therefore, both rational and metaphysical, or ethno-logical and mystical. Things happen through work, belief and faith, with views on reality based on people, imbedded in religion, and shrouded in secrecy. 'I am because we are; an injury to one is an injury to all; none of us is greater than all of us' are some of the common value-frames depicting the unity, solidarity, communality, stability and beliefs typical of *ubuntu/hunhu*. From the fixed 'attitude-value' complexes, the worldview runs parallel with modern value-models with mixed results and achievements.

As defined by Nwagbara (2011, p.82), "commitment translates into whatever makes a person to be *fully devoted and dedicated* to a task or course of action when difficulties or positive alternatives influence them to abandon the endeavour" (*emphasis new*), or *esprit de corps* for short. It is successful promotion of the host of unflinching vows, oaths, obligations, pledges and promises to galvanise most focused undertakings to cement the requisite social engagements predicated on dedication, devotion, discipline, sincerity, determination and

sense of indebted pride to the cause, society and country, with the Engineer's Pledge and the Hypocritical Oath appropriate examples. Socially, it translates into remarkably cohesive compatibility among the numerous stakeholder variables in the face of negative, positive, cutting-edge, empowering and disempowering life-work forces and situations with potential for much higher yields, with Zimbabwe's liberation war a case example. As the adage goes, with commitment half the job is already done.

Incorruption and service is open resistance to corruption by participating in, and offering one's services across the wide spectrum of public and private social responsibilities. It embraces the sense of guilt and regret in the event of misdemeanours with capacity for non-repeat. Whatever the challenge or problem, it is immoral to shift the blame to others or to deny them their right, but to remain totally responsible and accountable. Expanded, it is an assurance that public resources are distributed fairly and equitably; that power is exercised responsibly; that peace, justice and non-violence prevail; that public authorities are transparent, effective and efficient in their duties; and that resources and the environment are used sustainably (Mnkandla, 2011b). Incorruption and service, therefore, calls for a willingness to tolerate uncertainty accompanied by the relentless pursuit of honesty and integrity, reflecting solid levels of ethical intelligence, transparency, efficient work practices, and responsible and accountable service delivery – 'the buck stops here' maxim.

The moral ethics are expressed through values like love, patience, respect, servant-hood (or Christlikeness), trust, integrity/*Ubuntu/hunhu*, modesty, generosity/altruism/philanthropy, responsibility, accountability, and other aspects of wellbeing. According to Gert (2011) they basically mean successful management of longings or issues of belief, disbelief and suspension of judgement so as withstand the wicked problems of moral judgment, fallibility and vulnerability for the greater good. As evidence of God's creation, humanity must reciprocate His love and good will by embracing religion's moral high ground, exalting human dignity and exercising responsible stewardship to eliminate inequality and inequity gaps through acting and remaining liable, answerable, as well as morally and legally bound to one's words and actions. This is counter the controversial, mostly consumptive appetites, which generate the destructive forces of evil, hate, cruelty, despair, violence, ferocity, occult practices and other vile natures and maladies inundating the different scapes.

Similarly, Koestenbaum (2001) observes that as the cornerstone of the comportment footprint, the moral virtues principle requires baking together life's negative and positive challenges into a 'social contract' premised on ownership, freedom, dialogue, ethics, sacrifice, negotiation, rationality, self-discipline and presence. In that regard, he advances "anxiety and guilt, courage, duty and integrity, self-sufficiency, co-creation, community, and evil (offence)" as the main ingredients of the social contract. This is because human beings experience these virtues-cum-VICES repeatedly and it is what to do with them which makes or breaks the comportment's moral high ground. This calls for deep soul-searching – that is, the capacity to consult the subconscious, going deep into issues, sustaining ethical standards and exhibiting evidentialism in judgments.

The theological background of the normative-moral virtues canon raises prospects for a 'Theo-technology' to define the extent the virtues blend with technology in the nurturing of the technological society. Reminiscent of the World Peace Technology model (2010), the Theo-technology is about the relationship between 'spiriton' (the peace consciousness energy particles) and the atom and the cell as the energy particles driving 'thought' and 'emotions' of 'collective mind' which is the essence of technology. Although it has never been exploited fully, the spiriton-atom-cell relationship is the possible answer to the unprecedented creative destructions (warfare technology, rampant conflicts, environmental hazards) ingeminated by the sciences of the atom and cell. The Theo-technology, therefore, means successfully converging the sciences of 'spirituality' and 'matter' as the springboard to stabilise a technological society which will not self-destruct into oblivion, but rather, will exist in peace and safeguard itself and all of God's creation (worldpeacetech.com).

Together, the normative-virtues jungle must be exercised and enjoyed with utmost impartiality, that is, without fear, loss, discrimination or injustice of any kind whether on the grounds of race, sex, colour, language, religion, political or other opinion, material or social origin, property, birth or other status – by no means an easy endeavour. As Humphrey (1989) would contend, it is only when the institutions are able to exercise the normative-virtues canon enshrined in the curriculum's democracy that they can either adapt to a better world than has ever been before, or to the deep social malaise symptomatic of the modern world.

3.5.3 Environmental justice

Last, environmental justice distinctly defines issues of environmental stewardship, sustainability, equity and environmental rights. Or, as defined by the 2003 Budapest Central and Eastern European Workshop, “environmental risks and hazards and investments and benefits whether they are equally distributed without discrimination, whether directly or indirectly, at any jurisdictional level; whether access to environmental investments, benefits, and natural resources are equally distributed; and whether access to information, participation in decision making, and access to justice in environment-related matters are enjoyed by all.”

In reverse, the Budapest Workshop defines environmental justice as meaning divesting environmental injustice, which “exists when members of disadvantaged, ethnic, minority or other groups suffer disproportionately at the local, regional (sub-national), or national levels from environmental risks or hazards, and/or suffer disproportionately from violations of fundamental human rights as a result of environmental factors, and/or are denied access to environmental investments, benefits, and/or natural resources, and/or are denied access to information; and/or participation in decision making; and/or access to justice in environment-related matters.”

Both definitions seek to galvanise detectable quality gains typical with portable, creative curricula to culture an ecological community of discourse, thinking and action. The products are able to translate environmental models into higher principles of informed judgment, respect for human dignity and labour, lateral thinking, productive work and design, and social commitment. Through informed decision-making and problem solving, the stakeholders build capacity to manipulate the intricacies of environmental diversity, scope and uncertainty and adopt and adapt more sustainable values within the given action spaces, conscious of the dire consequences of perverse incentives emanating from uninformed individual and collective choice (Mnkandla, 2006).

Hence, the subject of environmental justice/injustice has become so vast in scope to be treated fully here. According to O’Brien and Leichenko (2007) it includes issues of climate change, rural-urban decay, landlessness, faminogenic practices, and extractive politics and educational intrigues and their impact employment, livelihood resources, psychosocial

relations, and pollution and waste management. By category, the threats and hazards are either unsuspected, or improperly managed, or instrumental, variously many of a kind, one of a kind, first of a kind, or worst of a kind.

On the main this is the entire field of human security or the combination of human development and health, not only in terms of absence of injury and disease, but also protection from threats, empowerment to positively respond to threats, freedom from fear, bitterness and intense emotions, as well as the right to physiological health, reproductive health, social health, domestic health, child health, economic health, environmental health and so on. As the *nerve centre* of the M/SDGs, what is implied is full social wellbeing marked by sufficient income to meet basic needs, sufficient clean water and clean air in pollution-free environments, access to goods and services, as well as social mobility, peace and justice under democratic governance – the core of technocapital.

Evidently, the call is for stronger humanization or the capacity to create positive quality life processes and practices that breakdown the degrading forces associated with injustices. The environmental benefits must enjoy more and better currency with dehumanizing forces strictly controlled or completely eliminated, which is good for environmental quality. Indeed, alarm bells now ring wide and loud on the onward march of environmental injustice at the expense of environmental justice, with desperate Diaspora journeys good examples.

Naturally and arguably, through the Global Sustainability Initiative Framework (discussed below), all institutions closely identify with the environmental justice agenda as they seek to successfully couple a sustainable environment-development dividend to contain whatever hazards and calamities affecting them, such as those facing the city of Harare: air, water, sewage, garbage and vendor pollution exceeding both recommended and allowable limits, hence, posing constant health and social threats to the city and its inhabitants (Moyo, 1997). Coming into question is how, ultimately, products must formulate a responsible comportment towards sustainable development, appreciated and fulfilled through a positive psychosocial ethic befitting techno-progressivism.

Aggregated, with the comportment in place immense benefits are envisaged. The teachers, students, administrators and other stakeholders are assured of toleration, diversity,

productivity, innovation, self-development, social cohesion, renewed cultural and multicultural emancipation and much more. For the constituency, there is positive egalitarianism and internationalism from the relevant socio-economic patriotism or practical professionalism to uplift national imperatives and societal needs by a like-minded citizenry. The elimination of *Homo simplex* means full social wellbeing and total environmental justice. In short, in the perspective of the American experience, there is sufficient room for the systems to continuously renew, redefine, recreate, re-establish and readapt themselves as they strive to exalt the global pedigree and realise a fully-fledged cosmocentric democracy in the footsteps of Western multiculturalism.

From the exposition, it is safe to say comportment is what is meant by human development. It is the heart of that philosophy to inculcate quality educational, informational, pleasurable and propaganda cues and other standards that foster holistically sophisticated products. The ultimate value rests on the available choices, the freedom of those choices, and the nature of the grooming accompanying the choices. Comportment's complexity generates and projects an array of contradictions and inconsistencies pervading the systems, symbolising the practical challenges confronting the construct. The next challenge is locating the best comportment-building philosophy or ideology from the highly chaotic mosaic.

3.6 The comportment controversy

The comportment controversy is the stark reality on the challenges confronting the potential learning cultural drive. With such a central role, controversies and contradictions are inevitable on the best way to beneficially exploit the conceivable comportment without turning any of its variables, fully or in part, into propaganda tools or tools for expropriation, slavery and other psychological atrocities (Mavhunga, et al. 2009; Mnkandla, 2006). From a public choice perspective, the absence of a positivist governance theory analogous to the economic theory of the market is the biggest challenge. Hence, management systems falter the most generating both primary and secondary tensions. The former are employee related and the latter emerge from the management process. In his assessment of the problem, Clark (1986, p.241) observes how, often, the decisions and actions carried out fail to reconcile the emergent discords necessitating coercion, or compromises, or accommodations, or propaganda spins, some of which rigidify and others soften the status quo. In sum, 'impropriety and dereliction of duty' or, in the eyes of the market, failure to handle non-market

decision making to solve both tame and wicked problems best capture the myriad labels, criticisms and controversies the institutions have to endure.

The numerous challenges facing the technocracy have shown how power and profit still fail to dismantle uncertainty. The rest of the discussion, therefore, looks at the other aspects of the compartment. The multiple tasks, relationships, differences and related beliefs, faiths and other orientations do trigger controversial disconnect within the normative-virtues canon. Most outstanding is the value-disvalue discord (the half-right / half-wrong dualism) which makes it difficult to pursue the norms and virtues fully to their logical conclusion, bringing about the discord that breaks the vision-values momentum. The division of power requires that each be stopped or toned down here, attenuated there and redefined elsewhere in order to ensure sufficient zest, equity and fairness, creating circumstances that are recipes for VUCA, resulting in agency misunderstandings, confusions, angst and conflicts, etc. in an effort to stem whatever unfavourable tides.

Clark (1986) provides useful insights in his analysis of this subject. Despite the passage of time, the observations remain fundamentally true to this day. They are cited fairly extensively here to illustrate the challenges. As he notes, liberty is not necessarily reconcilable with equity and competence as full liberty works against both to enhance freedom, choice and variety, hence, its antithesis to fairness and standardization, while its rhetorical 'open-door' policy subordinates justice, merit and servant-hood (Clark, p.253).

On the other hand, loyalty subordinates everything: freedoms, rights, justice, competence, liberty and merit in the spirit of a single higher good. In fact, as he points out, preoccupation with loyalty of faculty and students courts little heed to equal treatment or competent training or freedom of choice (p.254).

Equity or fairness means equal treatment and equal rewards to everybody in the bureau and at the end of their studies, often with little regard to heritage, distinctive character, accumulated pride and personal opinions (p.244). Also, the bureaucratic order drives the principle of fair share relying on coercive comparisons to reveal unequal treatments, make them invidious and leverage them by ideology and power (p.244).

While necessary, 'elite functions' like research, sport and conservation are always in tension with mass participation and certain cultural and democratic ideals. In addition, they expose the democracy inherent in knowledge to attack as some pursue self-interests at the expense of general welfare (p.247-8).

Likewise, servant-hood and its synonyms of patience, respect and philanthropy belies excessive loyalty or docility, laziness, conservatism and subservience to the status quo which stifles liberty and even entrepreneurship. Equally, in the face of mounting pressures and risks, security translates into repression from the top and resistance from below triggering confrontations and fragile relationships, while creativity is the flipside of inconsistency, eccentricity and corruption shrewdly indicating how richly rewarding it is to cheat for knowledge and ill-gotten wealth, riches and fame as the world has shockingly and rudely come to know (p.249).

Meanwhile, criticism of institutional and national affairs is easily and quickly labelled troublesome, unpatriotic behaviour especially where stigmatization and stereotyping are the norm with some groups and sections branded illegitimate, or illegal, or sell-outs, or fake, or agents of external interests. Constructive criticism is preferred to transparency to foster subservience to the tenets of the status quo (p.251). The inevitable outcome is greater resistance and revolutionary uprisings rather than evolutionary change – paradoxically, uprisings that always rigidify the status quo.

Alongside and usually ignored are the contradictions surrounding integrity, honesty, efficiency and culture. Integrity is associated with royalty and sovereignty, plainly, a hard currency aspiration and/or ideal for all and sundry, while relentless honesty is not only hard to pursue, it is also anti-risk, anti-competition and anti-creativity. Efficiency connotes greed while culture begs the question whose culture with multiculturalism wreaking havoc on traditional systems. Thus, together with equality and equity, all these values are meaningless as they can never be achieved, unless to downgrade opportunity, excellence or achievement.

Commitment and *ubuntu/hunhu* are powerful socio-environmental impediments from lack of transparency, the traditional gridlock, and rampant invocation and feminization of downgrade processes, including the cancers of ethnocentric bigotry/imperialism, and radical

retribalization constantly tearing African societies apart. In fact, *ubuntu's* cosmovision is *ultra vires* the institution and vision of a technological society.

Last, student emoluments like affirmative action entrench the colonial legacy of discrimination, patronage, favour, stringency and moral exclusion.

Thaler (2009, p.139) further observes that, except love, there is total exclusion of the exceptionable traits like anger, hatred, guilt, pride, fallibility, vulnerability, radicalism, regret, joy, grief, jealousy, envy, offence, fear and belief-disbelief considered too personal, or extra-academic, or negative and miniscule and, therefore, irrelevant or difficult to handle. Yet, as Koestenbaum (2001) observes, these traits have colossal influences on human interactions and operations – and the dark shadow of hatred is clear evidence.

Lynch (2010, p.54) argues that the incompatibility could be a result of 'carelessness' on the part of higher education as a result of the pervasive positivist influence which argues that fact and value/virtue are separate entities and must be managed separately. She argues that the classical *Cartesian* view that "scholarly work is separate from emotional thought and feeling, and that the focus of education is on educating an autonomous, rational person, *Homo sapiens*, whose emotionality is not regarded as central to her or his being" is the source of the challenge. Yet, the two are an expressive mode of the same continuum. The end result is contradictory personality and leadership profiles that live by certain norms and virtues today and proceed to justify the most exceptionable next.

Just as volatile are the internal institutional cultures and politics marked by bureaucratic red tape, pilfering, incessant staff-students industrial action, troublesome subculture groups, abuse of authority and other such burdens. Reflecting the perverse breeding ground, according to Lewis (2007), are the dysfunctional communications – always quarrelsome and riddled with misunderstandings, confusions, fear power and complaints and accusations of favouritism, intimidation, harassment and other division-fuelling picks. From the perspective of the 80:20 rule, management must spend 80% of the time dealing with 20% of the people responsible for the bulk of the misdemeanors and conflicts.

But, the highest stake is the element of crime which the institutions have to contend with. While many moral values like gay marriage, homosexuality, usury, bribery, alcoholism, gambling, abortion, extortion, misogyny, and the desecration of the environment were cardinal sins and, therefore, strictly forbidden in the past (*kuyazila* – meaning it offends God), today they are open practices, with the institutions expected to promote some, however controversial. According to Woods and Grant (2003), the wicked reality is one of fabulous fortunes made through speculation, greed, and corruption employing shrewd ways, brain-washing tactics, blackmail, liquidation and other market driven strategies, which calls into question the relationship between integrity or probity and ‘prudence’ versus the endemic fallacy of false dawns.

The corporate colonization propels perverse scandals concealed behind a screen of hypocritical moralising about sin, right and wrong and the whole gamut of moral values. In line with Magaisa (2016), where is the normative-virtues canon with the institutions and constituencies consumed by an unprecedented epidemic of corruption, swindling, lying, cheating and looting on a massive scale perpetrated by their very alumni of politicians, administrators, judges, executives, business, professors, teachers, engineers, securocrats, pastors and students to amass wealth and get rich quickly? Debating on the impact of technocapitalism, Suarez-Villa (2009, p.2) argues that “our creativity, our knowledge, and our learning thus become not qualities that emancipate but commodities that bind us to our alienation from the human condition, from society, and from nature.” In short, the ethics canon is at crossroads despite the fact that the institutions are paragons of building and promoting values and virtues even at the expense of keeping Africa a spectator in some critical aspects of human endeavour like economic espionage.

Last, as noted earlier, *environmental justice* is under immense pressure from its expanding opposite, environmental injustice, for which there are numerous episodes. The multiple threats and hazards, more so climate change, disease epidemics and pandemics, toxic wastes and warfare endanger peace and livelihoods, leaving many wondering whether Africa’s time will really come (Sharara, 2015), while the *consumer/provider* tag has perpetuated technological imperialism and with it mental slavery and the dependency syndrome (Gundani, 2015). Not only are the poor countries of the South paying the price for the unstable weather patterns, they face severe social upheavals from the weakened

productivity levels (Tandon, 2008). With droughts now a seasonal reality across much of the sub-continent, adversely affecting the productivity of small farmers, amid collapsing national fiscuses, many people are having to survive on donor aid and food assistance (Marcus, 2003). Even more disturbing is conjecture that the rising temperatures have something to do with the rising levels of human aggression and violent behaviour.

Alongside is the peril of 'resource-dependent economies' whose extractive politics (characterised by looting and greedy exploitation) is responsible for environmental atrocities and crimes against humanity. In the prelude to his book 'The Looting Machine', Burgis (2015) argues that the prosperity of Africa's growing middleclass "could pitch back into destitution just as quickly as they climbed out of it. Indeed, the ground beneath their feet is as precarious as a Congolese mine shaft, and their prosperity could spill away like crude from a busted pipeline." Clearly, environmental paradoxes and injustices have become a big poser to human security calling for new forms of adaptation to safeguard livelihoods (Magaisa, 2016; O'Brien and Leichenko, 2007; Tevera and Moyo, 2000).

In conclusion, as human development, the comportment footprint mirrors the superior conduct, character and personality profiles befitting modernization. The homogenization galvanises both conservative and liberal norms grounded in the most affirmative values-standards to build socialites with a vibrant humanitarian culture (the Education Review Commission, 1999). However, numerous obstacles lie in the way chief of which is lack of a positivist government theory to base projections, hence, the values discord and the difficulty to effect a properly envisaged comportment. The division of power renders it quite tricky to execute a normative or virtue to its logical conclusion, resulting in multiple interpretations. Apparently, the methodology relied on to survive the tensions and conflicts tends to rigidify the bureaucracy, while staff-student turnover rates paralyse delivery of a long-lasting comportment base anchored on stable teams.

It is apparent that alternative value-chains advocating self-mobilization, moderation and dialogue are being called for with the teaching and learning digging deep to groom the learners on how to balance both new and routine conditions and contradictions. However intractable, the goal of a flexible comportment must be sustained which means concerted

attrition of unwanted wastes to create a high quality psychosocial dynamic compatible with the potential learning product and the ideals of a technological society.

3.7 Evaluation

As mentioned in Chapter 1, while implicit, evaluation was deducible from the statements. Trochim (2006) defines it as the systematic acquisition and assessment of information to provide useful feedback about some object such as a programme, policy, technology, person, need, or activity. As Figure 2.1 shows, whether ex-ante or ex-post, it is the basis of all feedback be it formative evaluation as the plans and schedules are formulated; process or progress or confirmative evaluation or evaluation monitoring as programmes and projects are being implemented over the period; and summative evaluation, at the completion or termination of a cycle.

According to Torres, et al. (1996, p.31), “the objective of all evaluation work is to promote insight, and the ownership of that insight in such a way that it precipitates just and appropriate action.” Formal and informal, internal and external evaluations whose generic goal is useful feedback that aids in stakeholder decision making and problem solving are the norm to validate operations according to ways and patterns of implementation. The evaluations assess and measure the latitude and altitude of the institution: whether outputs and outcomes justify the expended inputs, and whether processes and products comply with and conform to the aspiration to foster the potential learning product for sustainable development.

The evaluation is guided by an evaluation policy which Trochim (2009, p.5) defines as “any rule or principle that a group or organization uses to guide its decisions and actions when doing evaluation.” According to Chelimsky and Shandish, (1997), and in line with the ‘agency problem’, the purpose of the evaluation policy is to fulfil either the accountability perspective, or the developmental perspective, or the knowledge perspective. The accountability perspective seeks to measure results or return on investment, hence, its central role in policy determination and reform; the developmental perspective, to strengthen capacity building; and, the knowledge perspective, knowledge building or to generate insights about public problems, policies and programmes.

The perspectives are mutually correspondent and complementary, each meeting and solving different problems and answering different questions in social life. But, importantly, from a cost-benefit perspective, the evaluations check the extent policy and curricula are answerable to the stakeholders; the levels of introspection and related growth in knowledge; and the potential for innovation and reform (Torres, et al. 1996; Development & Cooperation). Quite crucial is the capacity to use the correct perspective to satisfy the relevant dimensions. According to Bronte-Tinkew, Joyner, and Allen (2007), at play are the factors of affordability, ready knowledge of processes and practices, systemic flexibility, existence of specialized skills, level of objectivity, observance of ethical issues, and whether the evaluation is short- or long-term, internal or external. In addition is the relationship between the researcher and the participants; between the participants and the settings in which they work; and between the researcher and the external world.

According to Bronte-Tinkew, et al. (2007) and Trochim (2009), factors favour internal rather than external evaluation, notwithstanding the disadvantages of the likelihood of insufficient experience or expertise, weak levels of objectivity with outsiders and potential partners doubting the validity of the evaluation, and extraneous participant weaknesses, after all, to them, the researcher or evaluator is part of and owns the system. External evaluation, on the other hand, enjoys the capacity to inject fresh insights into the system to counter such weaknesses. Its drawback are the heavy cost outlays, the strong likelihood of inadequate and distorted understanding of programme context or the target population, and the tendency to strip staff of accountability and responsibility on what is, for all intents and purposes, their business, deflating them to view the evaluation as the responsibility of someone else.

These considerations influence the model of evaluation to be adopted between scientific-experimental models, management-oriented systems, qualitative/hermeneutic models, and participant-oriented models (Trochim, 2006). Ultimately, the merit of the evaluation hinges on the emphasis put behind the collection and sifting of data as the real process is critical to ensure valid information and, therefore, informed inferences, conclusions and judgments. Seldom are the models used simultaneously nor does one solve all evaluation questions. As noted, they complement each other as what is relevant to one model may be inappropriate for another. For effective evaluation, Torres, et al. (1996) emphasise regular and special attention to communication and context, close stakeholder collaboration, and timely reports

tailored to meet audience needs and expectations, cognizant of institutional politics, complexities and constraints. This is hoping institutions embrace the principle of learning organizations and, therefore, change, without perceiving it as a mark of failure.

3.7.1 Evaluation approaches

According to Trochim (2009), the scope of the evaluation embraces individual programmes, all programmes, certain programmes, programme clusters/bundles; funding; contracts and oversight; situationality and the methodology to be used; criteria for selection of evaluators; stakeholder participation and involvement; and systems of reporting, dissemination, and facilitation of findings and results for further use. Accordingly, the techniques of grading, the academic review, the audit and programme exchanges, coupled with global rankings and the Global Sustainability Initiative Framework (GSIF) or the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) come into play to check if institutional events and phenomena are wholly or partially in sync with the vision-mission statements. However, as Rafael, et al. (2016, p.404-5) caution, “...these tools are not enough for universities, because they lack curriculum, research and services evaluations”, although this should not be taken as the reason to neglect them.

Grading is used to validate learner performance using a particular system such as the criterion-referenced system, the norm-referenced system, contract grading, peer grading, learner self-evaluation, or the notional credit method. It is standard practice across all institutions, combining formative and summative assessments cross-checked through external examining and review. While controversial, the Douglas College, USA, (2012) defines the purpose of grading as to “enable student achievement to be recognised formally and communicated meaningfully beyond the institution while maintaining an atmosphere in which a spirit of inquiry, personal challenge, and commitment to excellence can flourish.” Overall, grading supposedly accomplishes the objectives of motivation, accreditation, further education, prospective employment and higher rankings. The dilemma is how the tail has come to wag the dog rather than the other way round inducing contradictory behaviours.

Materu (2007, p.3) defines the academic review as the “diagnostic self-assessment and evaluation of the institution’s own academic activities (teaching, learning, research, service, outcomes) based on a detailed examination of the curricula, structure and effectiveness of a programme as well as the quality and activities of its faculty.” It is undertaken by a unit or a peer review by colleagues outside the programme and is usually accompanied by a report

on the findings. Unlike an audit an academic review can be limited to a single programme and does not involve a site visit by external reviewers. Meanwhile, the audit is an intensive review of an institution or programme to determine if it is in tandem with its vision or set standard. It entails a site visit by external evaluators following self-assessment and peer review to recommend improvements or for accreditation. Complementary evaluations embrace student-staff appraisals, external examining, and exchange programmes among and between local and external institutions.

The world rankings system is another useful method of evaluation. Reference has been made to some of the methodologies which differ markedly over criteria for validation. The ARWU highlights Nobel Prizes and Fields Medals won by alumni and by faculty members, highly cited researchers, articles published by staff in the journal *Science* and *Nature*, plus in academic journals and other areas of academic performance. The THES uses peer review, ranking by major (mainly international) graduate recruiters, citations (per capita) of published academic papers, teaching staff-student ratios, and international orientation. For eligibility criteria, the AHEEA advances breadth, originality, diversity of scholarly publications, innovative leadership, distinctive contributions in institution building, outstanding public service and ethical conduct and professional integrity (AAU, 2013). The bulk of the other less popular methods use the same criteria with additional modifications like faculty expertise, resource availability, socially significant activities of graduates, web publications or visibility and impact, international opinion, the scientific impact of the university activities as well as the economic relevance of the technology transfers to industry, community engagement, extending to political influence.

According to Taylor and Braddock (2008, p.260), notwithstanding the challenge of validity, the ranking systems yield information that is of value to a wide spectrum of interest groups – individuals, institutions and nationally. Prospective students use it to compare performances for career choices; faculty, for inter-departmental comparisons across similar institutions; and administrators, to adjudge institutional comparative advantages, weaknesses and limitations. Overall, the whole range of stakeholders draw upon the rankings to assess and keep abreast with higher education's influence and impact and the wisdom of policy options and mediation measures. Inter-institutional collaborations and partnerships are part of the equation.

Last, the expanding field of sustainable development has ushered the GSIF/GRI to inject more rigour and pace in the evaluations. The point of departure is the emphasis on environment-climate change indicators, in particular identifying, acting upon and disclosing opportunities and impacts relating to governance, economic, social and environmental performance indicators, or total corporate social responsibility for short. Rafael, et al. (2016, p.405) refer to the latter as the 'Campus Sustainability' model triangulated through the 'University Environmental Management System, Public Participation and Social Responsibility, and Sustainability Teaching and Research.' A complete construct must enshrine the three in sync with institutional philosophy and mandate.

Briefly, according to the GSIF, the governance indicators include rights and treatment of stakeholders, social policies and business principles, information disclosure and reporting, and customer/end-user care. The economic indicators cover economic performance, market presence, employment and human resource development, curriculum literacy, technological transfer and intellectual property rights, and other indirect economic impacts. The social indicators cover labour practices and decent work, products responsibility, human rights, gender and society, corruption and bribery, violence and conflict, charitable giving, social investment (education, health, etc.), social impact assessment and management, and community and stakeholder engagement (non-commercial). Last, the environmental indicators embrace materials usage, energy, water, green campus/ biodiversity, routine and surprise hazards like emissions, effluents and wastes, recycling or pollution prevention through environmentally safe workflows, products and services, and how the stakeholders are engaged and respond to the issues at stake.

The GSIF is based on the premise that all organizational events are significant investments and ought to be treated as such. It is vital therefore that they are measured and reported in terms of impacts that cross thresholds, hence, affecting the ability to meet the needs of the present without compromising the needs of future generations. For the institutions, they must run on low costs productions which embrace low carbon footprints, clean energy and water, and the recycling of wastes. Further, they must build an environmental legacy through supporting environmental initiatives both inside and outside the academy and through establishing integrated units responsible for sustainable development matters within their ranks. The materiality of such reports promotes transparency and accountability since

institutions disclose information in the public arena and stakeholders can track them over the pronounced broad band of indicators. Such measures are good for democracy and other governance and welfare ideals.

3.7.2 Evaluation pitfalls

As already alluded to, the success or otherwise of evaluation depends on the professionalism of the system and whether or not, for good reason, evaluations are undertaken. Unlike the other footprints, evaluation policy is not always apparent to vigorously impact institutional consciousness and consequence (Trochim, 2009). Hence, unless written down and constantly communicated, differences are often the norm with administration holding a more expectant position on evaluation which it might even go on to enforce, opposed to staff who may be unaware of, and indifferent to, such expectations and even opposed to them leading to parties working at cross-purposes. Indeed, by enabling and constraining certain practices and processes, evaluation is known to arrest decay while contributing to growth, but worse off are the negative consequences of bad evaluation policy whose impact is further stagnation and decay (Morley, 2003). Meanwhile, methods like grading have come under intense scrutiny on what it means and achieves with audits and rankings steeped in validity challenges from too much subjective criteria. Resource shortages further mar the full implementation of the GSIF/GRI with some aspects undertaken and others left out.

In conclusion, evaluation permeates all institutional activities, informing parties on the status of developments, whether the 'Prime' stage has been reached or reform has become necessary. To guarantee continuous improvement, Trochim (2009, p.14) urges as more important "developing well-informed evaluation policies that can guide evaluation practice to achieve better results" beyond concern with the correct methodology, or validity, or ethics, or making evaluation participatory, or using it for empowerment as evaluation encompasses all these. As the bulk of the discussion has shown and will show, far-reaching evaluations have been undertaken whose findings and recommendations, however, continue to disappoint.

3.8 Synthesis and implications for the study

There are multi-fold reasons justifying the adoption of the vision-mission statements. On one hand is the drive to introduce the market model to government systems to stimulate the application of rational choice in non-market decision making. On the other is the desire to

blend the disparate knowledge frames into manageable units. Technocapitalism reflected by corporate models like Appleism, Fordism, McDonaldisms or STEM education has assumed the upper hand to enhance the footprint frames of constituency servicing, governance, QA, compartment and evaluation in response to market factors. This puts the construct right at the forefront as the stimulus elevating institutional public indulgence and informing and confirming the potential learning product, in particular quality academic, technical, professional, and socio-environmental aspirations.

A diverse range of excellent, good and average statements inundate the higher education market. Whether informative or plain rhetorical superlatives, they all qualify in linguistic virtue, inviting criticisms of flowery clichés clothed in technical jargon in the drive to portray the cherished levels of public choice, excellence, idealism or pragmatism, etc. As such, they do as ideals, but it is a different ball game when they are put on the ground to work to the satisfaction of all involved and concerned. The internal and external faults rooted in the bureaucracy render them as diametrically liberal and conservative as they are controversial and economical about the reality they seek to portray.

The footprints model provided sufficient scope in the investigation of the problem, in particular, whether the claim that the statements animate the mandates and optimize the potential learning product is borne out by facts. Or, to the contrary, whether or not the statements exist, it is business as usual: the same post-colonial prophecy of the false infinite told by the African elite. Their utopian stance struggles to sustain stakeholder focus on more pragmatic endeavours, as what is a vision to one may be a no-brainer to another. Questionable are the 'choice' profiles (world class, premier, leader, knowledge hub, etc.) against the stubborn realities, as they appear either meaningless or too advanced to scale at this moment in time, amounting to delusions of grandeur (Thaler, 2009). Scarcely much change has accrued in the direction of a ubiquitous science-technology model, with the challenged narrative of yesteryears bearing down on the construct.

It is a historical fact that philosophies are born and die often having enjoyed mixed achievements (Russell, 1996). While the vision philosophy has raised little controversy, as the institutions adopted a narrow, parochial view of its efficacy – a good thing to have – practically, it is quite a conundrum to grapple with. The challenge is linked to the

understanding and secure implementation of the technocapitalism which, as we know, is not an innocent soul, but one torn by the inherent contradictions related to the paradox of 'unintended perverse and self-defeating consequences' common with bureaucracies (Jaffee, 2008). Against the projected 'emancipation', the corporate colonization entrenches new forms of socio-technical domination never witnessed before, with grave consequences for both the institutions and the wider constituency.

According to Suarez-Villa (2009, p.152-168), accountability and public democracy pose the most acute challenge and biggest victims. As he puts it

the most serious challenges posed by technocapitalism revolve around the need for accountability and public democracy. Given the power and reach of this phenomenon, greater accountability to society and the need for new forms of public democracy are important priorities. The new relations of power that accompany this new version of capitalism are likely to affect most every aspect of work and governance, our social relations, and life itself.

Paradoxically, in spite of the adjustment of power relations, the technocapitalism narrows both accountability and public democracy space. The formalization the new networks define exacerbates subjugation to corporate power and to technology itself, while generating diverse social pathologies never experienced before. Given the extent to which the principal-agency problem has prevailed, the systems remain exposed to the challenges of conscious incompetence, stunted impact, and disunity, consequently, as Jaffee (2008, p.120) observes, with "the parochialism generating sub-goals, conflicting interests, and restricted loyalties in place of universal attachment to the larger organisational mission." Primary and secondary tensions continue to prevail from the shifting technical roles and values, negatively impacting progress, with the institutions unable to reap the prospective benefits from the "mobilization of multiple intelligence" associated with, and derived from, "collective efforts, teamwork, multiple skills, increasing autonomy, and pragmatic evaluations" (Jaffee, p.121).

In contradiction, the statements emerge as both a realistic novelty and fantasy to redefine institutional power and politics within the domains of market and cultural capitalism, leaving little room to see things differently: heads I win, tails you lose. They play a more pseudo role than genuine advancement of the technocapitalist goals centred on growth and productivity. As Suarez-Villa admonishes further, required to sustain hope are definitive "checks provided by greater social accountability and democracy...to make technocapitalism responsive to

human needs.” Caught in the technocapitalist time-warp, the institutions risk questionable relevance for reincarnating imperialist traps.

However, drawbacks acknowledged, Petkoski and Twose (2003, p.1) remind us to concentrate less on “finding the correct constructs or faults with them, but rather to manage the dialogue between the various stakeholder groups by building coalitions for action as well as create additional learning opportunities through the implementation of sustainable action plans.” Nonetheless, an informed position remains critical to sustain the open and hidden narratives essential to navigate the unfolding consequences of technocapitalist education. The trend to copy and endorse has proved lethal to the national fabric.

3.9 Summary

In the context of the literature review, the chapter elaborated the political economy of the vision-mission philosophy as a public choice initiative and the extent it communicated and facilitated the dynamics of constituency servicing, governance, quality assurance, compartment and evaluation. Epistemological, methodological and normative ideals were examined to build a philosophical understanding of the role the statements play in institutional management–curriculum endeavours and related franchises. The immense potential is countered by immense challenges which mar and scuttle utilitarian practice courting problems in the attempt to give institutional direction as well as substance and import to that direction. In particular, the bureaucratic norm pitting the formal rationality–substantive rationality controversy stymies successful implementation with unintended consequences. The next chapter verifies the fieldwork to garner evidence to confirm or disconfirm the problem configuration and setting.

CHAPTER IV

4.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

4.1 Introduction

The chapter puts together the multi-facets of the methodology and how the study was mobilised and executed. Constituting the heart of the methodology are the multiple design variables of the research paradigm and the research design, the population and sampling scheme, and the fieldwork that provides the means to acquire the relevant data and information to answer the research questions, hence, guide the relative worth of the study and the pragmatism behind theory generation. In short, using generic constructions the investigator undertook the said action to search the socio-cultural spaces for practical evidence to fulfil the study rationale for a professional interrogation of the role of the vision-mission construct.

4.2 The post-positivist paradigm

A paradigm is a “commonality of perspective which binds the work of a group of theorists together” (Hirschheim, n.d., slide 15). The knowledge aim set the empirical agenda and the adoption of the post-positivist paradigm as the basis of the critical inquiry through which the problem underwent extensive, microscopic scrutiny or cross-examination to verify the substance and import or pros and cons of the vision-mission statements. As a ‘paradigm of choices’, the post-positivist constructions and interpretations highlighted the diverse, fluid, provisional and open nature of the knowledge aim distinct from the preconceived, singular methodology of the positivist paradigm (Hammersley, 2012).

Concern with social phenomena naturally emphasised the primacy of the social actors in their historical, cultural and social settings, while interest with 'everyday processes and practices' highlighted the importance of perception, creativity, thinking, beliefs and human experiences and values in formulating ideals by the higher education players. What was attractive with the ‘paradigm of choices’, then, was its capacity to gel with the dynamics of the footprints model to catalyse the requisite immersion and interpretations: to accommodate the diverse issues of context, natural setting, emergent design, variability in human behaviour and scientific rigour, while remaining neutral, ethical and logical, allowing for interactional

and situational analyses of the vision-mission issues and events the scrutinized actors and institutions were dealing with. Through engaging both the inductive (open) and deductive (pre-structured) approaches, coupled with abductive and dialogical reasoning, the study was able to muster as much dispassionate knowledge and evidence from the multiple sources to sufficiently demonstrate and validate the philosophical and material dimensions of the vision-mission construct.

Therefore, the study was more constructive, generative, inductive and inter-subjective, with emphasis on greater depth and detail, supported by numerative, verificative and objective quantitative data to strengthen the descriptions, cause-effect relationships and answers to the emerging 'why' questions related to the positive-negative aspects of the study proposition that: Vision-mission statements play a high profile role in institutional mandates; and/or that Vision-mission statements do not play an influential role in institutional mandates. In aggregating and disaggregating the reality of the statements, in many respects, the study mirrored the personal and social experiences of the researcher and the researched in the process of building knowledge or to confirm theory, extending to substantive and formal theory formulations critical for the way forward.

4.3 The multiple-case study design

The study adopted the multiple-case study design involving four science and technology universities which suited the diversity of the formal object using the few easily researchable examples. As the units of analysis, the four institutions were treated as a class which not only narrowed down the very broad field of an otherwise not well-known phenomenon into one or a few appropriate choice units but also, according to Crabtree and Miller (1999b, p.345), provided the basis to understand the "social processes in a group, community or collectivity that reflects accurately the standpoint of participants." In addition to strength on what is already known about the construct, the design extended experiences on its dynamics given the paucity of local studies to explain vision-mission issues. In short, there was scope to extend experience or to add strength to what is already known from previous research, coupled with immense potential to provide detailed descriptions and explanations of specific and rare cases and issues. Ultimately, the design reduced the usual tendency for case studies to be overly relevant and applicable to the sampled case or cases only, to being much more generalizable and, therefore, useful to more situations.

The case study design was treated with caution given its weaknesses, lest the research was rendered defective. According to the USC Libraries (2012) single, small number and unusual or unique cases limit representation and, hence, understanding and reliability. Meanwhile missing information, biased selection and biased interpretation of the findings as a result of intense exposure to the case(s) often create tunnel vision, with the study rendered oblivious to the more powerful forces operating on or in other situations from outside (Pratt, 2006). Furthermore, alone as a design, the case study sometimes fails to facilitate assessment of cause-effect relationships which, in this instance, was taken care of through the case-oriented understanding.

4.3.1 The population and sampling frame

Scott and Usher (1999, p.113) indicate that the study of the functional properties of social systems like higher education "cannot successfully be carried on, or its results interpreted, without reference to the knowledge frames of the relevant agents and actors" which can only be achieved through direct immersion in the system. Out of the five science and technology universities in the country, one declined participation and the remaining four constituted the eligible case study population of about 10 600 who constituted the target of the inquiry. By category, the population comprised 100 senior academics and senior administrators, 600 lecturers and administrators, 900 support staff and about 9 000 students.

The QUAL+quan design influenced the choice of what Onwuegbuzie and Collins (2007) call 'Type 4: Frequent Combination' sampling scheme involving non-random qualitative-quantitative sampling mix for concurrent/simultaneous data collection as well as ensuring adequately balanced participant representation. Predominantly purposeful, the design entailed a purposive, multilevel heterogeneity sampling frame based on the existing staff categories to define the population subset. Trochim (2009) defines heterogeneity sampling as a form of representative sampling which deliberately sets out to capture opinions, views and perceptions from the heterogeneous population without being concerned about strictly representing the participants proportionately. Therefore, judgements conveniently targeted specifically selected and most accessible individuals with good prospects to yield accurate and appropriate information to sufficiently and adequately address the credibility crises of "representation, legitimation, integration and politics" (Onwuegbuzie and Collins, 2007,

p.305). To enhance the quality of the descriptions and interpretations or analytic internal–external generalizations the study made, close attention was further paid to the sample size which must neither be “too small as to make it difficult to achieve data saturation, theoretical saturation or informational redundancy nor so large that it is difficult to undertake a deep, case-oriented analysis” (Onwuegbuzie and Collins, p.284), which made the heterogeneity sampling a fairly complex undertaking.

Table 4.1 sums the staff categories of the target sample (and the related questionnaire – Q_{A1}, etc. instruments). The Vice-Chancellors and Pro-Vice-Chancellors, Registrars, Bursars, Librarians, Deans, Directors and Professors comprised the senior category; the departmental Chairpersons, Senior and other lecturers, Senior Technicians and Senior and Assistant Registrars, the lecturing and administrative personnel; and the Secretaries, Administrative Assistants, Assistant Technicians, Messengers and Security details, the support staff. Last, were the students, mostly Part IIIs and IVs. Among the academics, there was deliberate bias towards the science and technology disciplines, with an effort made to balance the experience of older staff with that of recent entrants.

Table 4.1 Composition of population sample

Staff category	Targeted # of participants	Description
Senior academics/ Administration	30 Q _{A1} & Q _{A2}	Vice-Chancellors, Pro-Vice-Chancellors, Registrars, Bursars, Librarians, Deputy Registrars, Deans, Directors.
Lecturing and administrative staff	40 Q _{A3}	Departmental chairpersons, Senior lecturers, lecturers, Senior Assistant and Assistant Registrars/ Technicians
Support staff	20 Q _B	Secretaries, Technicians, Administrative Assistants, Security, Others
Students	20 Q _C	Part IIIs / IVs
Total	110	

Specifically, the sample comprised 30 senior academics and administrators in both identical and nested relationships. In the former, exactly the same sample members participated in both the qualitative and quantitative phases of the study, while in the latter some of the sample members were further selected for post-fieldwork interviews for member checking.

There were 40 lecturing and administrative personnel and 20 of each of support staff and students giving a total of 110 participants. The class was built around approximately 28 participants per institution comprising at least 8 senior academics and administrators, 10 lecturing and middle level management, and 5 of each of support staff and students. Logistics, though, made it difficult to stick to this allocation strictly. An additional 25 participants took part in the post-fieldwork interviews to consolidate the findings and results. The bio-data details on gender, qualifications, status and length of service were collected and are shown in Figures 4.1 and 4.2.

This was conscious of the inherent weaknesses of the sampling error, coverage error, and measurement error. Invariably, only some and not everyone took part in the study (sampling error); the lack of an equal or known non-zero chance of being sampled for participation (coverage error); and the dilemma of the measurement error which arises from inaccurate, imprecise answers or answers which cannot be compared in some useful way to other participants' answers as a result of whatever causes all of which then dent legitimation.

Figures 4.1 and 4.2 show the bio-data characteristics of the population to confirm the professional grounding of the investigation from and by a credible, trustworthy population. The gender ratios stood at 60% males and 40% females. While deliberately biased towards senior and long service individuals, the reality was such that 77%, which was the bulk of the population, was below 10 years' service, while 18% were 11-20 years, and 5% were over 21 years. In terms of positions, the lecturers and administrators comprised 36%, senior academics and administrators, 27%, and the support staff and students were 18.5% each. Educationally, 50% of the participants held the Masters degree qualification, while 16% were PhD holders, with 9% and 5% degree and diploma holders, respectively.

In terms of quality credentials, then, the individuals had the right attributes and, presumably, the information to fully unravel the problem, which satisfied the objective of the study. Hence, to strengthen its voice, the study deliberately targeted individuals within the science disciplines, which meant that it was not necessarily everyone within the institution who stood a chance to be sampled. However, participants in the non-sciences with the potential for full answers were targeted.

Figure 4.1 Participant composition

Figure 4.2 Participant positions and qualifications

4.4 Mixed Method

The diversity characteristics of the knowledge aim and the Dominant/simultaneous QUAL+quan design anchored the study in the mixed method approach. This is to say, while predominantly qualitative (QUAL), with measurement reduced to observations and explorations of the diversity in meanings and practices, the quantitative (+quan) was

employed with means and frequencies determined for some variables in the process of generating further support for the study (Kroeze, 2012). According to Creswell and Clark (2011) whether fixed or emergent, the mixed method approach is justified on the grounds of the insufficiency of one data source, to explain initial results, and to generalize exploratory findings. Molina and Cameron (2010, p.98) cite the advantages of 'development, treatment integrity, expansion, participant enrichment, reciprocal facilitation, and significance enhancement' the method offers. In compensating for the weaknesses of each other, the combined strength of the three sub-methods boosted the capacity to address practice and policy issues from the point of view of both narratives and numbers, which consummated the analyses, inferences, conclusions and interpretations. In that vein, the construction detail is as critical as the administration, both of which must show quality, relevance, ease of understanding, clarity, non-bias, and correct culture and ethics.

The fieldwork was triangulated through document analysis, the diversity survey and interviews, each accompanied by an inventory or instrument standardised through pre-exercises. A total of fifteen participants took part in the pre-exercises using both hard and soft copy returns supplemented by face-to-face interviews to standardise the instruments and reduce errors and weaknesses. Additional methods included informal conversations and post-fieldwork interviews carried out with the different groups. The ensuing cross-validity minimised the distortions associated with the reduction of social reality into numerical forms and misrepresentations common with the single method.

As in all research, the study assumed that, given the social pressures and the varying levels of specialisation, the handling of the instruments depended on the participants' perceptual management of the issues involved. The following account outlines the advantages and disadvantages of the sub-methods used which, as sides of the same coin, holistically contributed to the ecology of the mixed method.

4.4.1 Document analysis

Documents refer to independent materials, mostly textual and artistic infrastructures, both primary and secondary, interrogated for information about the vision-mission construct. Public records, specifically the vision-mission statements, annual reports, policy manuals, strategic plans, student handbooks, prospectuses, researches, journals, consultancy reports,

newspapers, files, newsletters and websites were the main source documents. The document analysis ensured that the multiple sources were translated into tools of the same trade providing reciprocal and evidence-based proofs. They were, therefore, checked for authenticity, credibility, representativeness and meaning, the standard quality control criteria for handling document sources.

Briefly, “authenticity refers to whether the evidence is genuine and impeccable; credibility, to whether the evidence is typical of its kind; representativeness, to whether the sources fully represent the totality of the relevant documents; and meaning, to whether the evidence is clear and comprehensible” (Mogalakwe, 2006, p.224). This is to say, in both content and context, and in both their literal (face value) and interpretative meanings, to enhance reliability and dependability, the source documents must provide genuine, original data free of error and distortion, which the source documents fulfilled.

The study was conscious of the inherent weaknesses of documents with respect to inaccuracies, incompleteness of data, misrepresentations, inconsistencies and propaganda spins which need to be taken care of. Clearly, not only are the documents not written for the same purpose as the study, the omission of critical statistics like graduate outputs, for example, in the annual reports was a significant departure from the norm and, therefore, cause for concern. As a result, the documents were sometimes incomplete or difficult to locate which made extractions and conclusion drawing challenging and the authenticity of the method questionable. Additional caution was exercised with respect to protectionism, as many documents are usually bracketed ‘private, classified, confidential, or official secret’ and are inaccessible for public use. Fortunately, protectionism did not turn out to be such a big limitation as previously feared.

The online method was relied on to access some of the source documents. It entailed the downloading of the main institutional documents: the vision-mission statements, strategic plans, reports, evaluation records, and publications like bulletins, journals and web sources. It was also used to track other iconic forms of stakeholder participation to capture accurately and fully those activities and experiences that represented successful delivery or otherwise of the vision-mission construct. The research Assistants acquired the documents which could not be accessed on line and, in the event of problems, the researcher did so during the visits.

The documents were analysed using an inventory similar to Table 1.1 (Chapter 1) to search for specifiable indicators explicit to each footprint. As the basis of the infrastructural and qualitative groundwork, the documents threw light on whether or not the statements were working as envisaged. Without them the study would have been incomplete. As always, after the research findings had been analysed and categorised, the study reviewed the literature again in order to theoretically relate the findings with the existing state of affairs.

4.4.2 The diversity survey

The diversity survey suited the quest to determine the diversity of the construct. Unlike the quantitative survey which places emphasis on the value-count of the variable, its focus was to establish the meaningful variation (relevant dimensions and values) of the construct within the sample population. In short, emphasis was the evaluation/assessment of the diversity (and not distribution) of the construct in the population. Echoing this viewpoint, Ngulube, et al. (2014b, p.4) indicate that “the focus of qualitative analysis is on meaning of events and actions rather than statistical significance and relationships between variables.”

The diversity survey was, therefore, more about frequency variations – that is, the relative occurrence and dynamic ramifications of the statements as opposed to absolute frequencies, probabilities and correlations. In tandem with Jansen (2010, p.7), to achieve the requisite empirical saturation, the design did not detail concepts exhaustively for a theoretical domain (i.e. covering all theoretical possibilities), but covered relevant (in terms of aims) diversity within the empirically-defined class.

The survey comprised three questionnaires, and in line with the methodology used by Darbi (2012): Appendix 2, Q_{A1/3} for administrative and academic staff; Q_B for support staff; and Q_C for students all consisting of low inference descriptors defined as the “easily observable and readily quantified or countable indicators or responses” (Zohrabi, 2013, p.260). Q_{A1/3} comprised 9 indicators for constituency servicing, 11 for governance, 12 for QA, 7 for comportment, and 6 for evaluation. The functionality of the footprint indicators was rated on an ordinal scale coded as follows:

- (i) inadequate/sub-standard (S/I) to mean that the descriptor or indicator variable was a poor/invalid measure of the footprint (1);

- (ii) normal/adequate (N/A) to mean that the descriptor was a weak and bland measure of the footprint (2);
- (iii) functional/commendable (F/C) to mean that the descriptor was a valid measure and positively equated with the footprint (3); and
- (iv) exceptional/world class (E/W) to mean that the descriptor was a strongly valid measure that actively boosted the footprint; precisely what the institution wanted, deserved and worked by (4), befitting the technology exponential syndrome.

In addition, was the un-coded 'unable to judge' (U/J) which meant that the descriptor was invalid and irrelevant, or was difficult to rate, or was remote and unknown to the participant. For final analysis, U/J was computed separately from the main ratings. As discussed below, ultimately, it was very insignificant and did not distress the results.

The questionnaires for support staff and students were made up of 11 identical Likert-scale descriptors nominally rated from 'strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree and strongly disagree' to solicit information on the three parameters of 'awareness, ownership and impact'. The only difference lay in that while the staff questionnaire talked about 'work', the students' questionnaire talked about 'studies and learning'. Neutral equated with 'unable to judge' in Q_{A1} to mean that the participant was indifferent to the descriptor or it was unusually weak/low, or was unknown/irrelevant to them. In the final analysis, it was computed together with disagree and strongly disagree.

Except for Neutral and U/J, the other responses were formal active/positive ratings and the final computations then determined the status of the issues under consideration. To adequately and sufficiently cover each footprint, questionnaire Q_{A1/3} consisted of 45 variables while Q_B and Q_C comprised 11 similar variables. Both formats combined the structured and unstructured response-type surveys approximating an analytical survey to enhance inclusiveness and exhaustiveness through having participants make additional information/comments should they be so disposed. To control excesses, participants simply marked the appropriate rating. Both the U/J and Neutral served as outlets to reduce undue contamination of the results arising from perceived pressures.

4.4.3 Interviews

The study adopted the guided interview approach whose purpose was to find out what was in or on the participants' minds, or to access their perspectives on vision-mission statements. It consisted of six core questions plus two follow-up questions modelled along the research questions (see Appendix 3). Specifically, Qs1&2 interrogated the justification for the adoption and, in many respects, the productivity of the construct; Qs1&4, its impact curricular strength; Q3, its instrumental efficacy/marketability to inject the vigour of the market model in the institutional operations; and Qs6&7, its transformative role. Q4 was largely a filter question, specifically to cross-check the credibility of the answers on the status of the statements whether or not they are a definite counterfeit as courts of public opinion allege. Last, was the open question for any additional detail the participants wished to bring to the attention of the study. In delivery terms, Onwuegbuzie and Collins (2007) count on the advantages of flexibility, being participatory, and allowing for hints and prompts, probing and prodding questions, hence, freedom of expression, while Williams (2007) adds that the design increases the comparability of data since the participants answer the same questions.

For maximum results, the set questions were kept few to speed up responses as well as reduce fatigue. But, most importantly, in the words of Agee (2009, p.446), the guide was made sharp enough to "function as lenses that are directed outward by the researcher to capture the nuances of the experiences and perspectives of the participants." To fathom the delicacy of the construct's distinctions, the study concurred further with Agee's (2009, p.433) framework for developing interview questions, chiefly, "What are you asking? How are you asking it? What data will you need to provide a good answer?" – the last question being the most important, since where this obtains the research process progresses smoothly and fruitfully. Since they were liable to "change during the process of research to reflect an increased understanding of the problem" (Agee), and to avoid tunnel vision, they were never finalised. Instead, they were made discursive in-keeping with a discovery-oriented paradigm to allow the participants to open up and express their minds while observing the interview protocol of good rapport to allow the interviewees sufficient scope to express their views and opinions without interruption, spiced by follow-up and probing questions.

The study relied on the face-to-face interview and the self-administered electronic email recorded both manually and electronically, to maximise on synchronous/asynchronous

communication in time and/or place and other advantages. Among the many advantages, the electronic forms gave the respondents, where possible, opportunity to access virtual sites to find the required information and, therefore, more time to respond. The free debate allowed the respondents to brainstorm, analyse and synthesise issues and views that were of concern to themselves and their institutions as they responded to the study. The personalised contacts allowed direct observation of the feelings and nuances of the participants and elicitation of information on topics of a sensitive and private nature otherwise inaccessible through the other instruments, while the researcher was in a position to rephrase questions or to go back on issues as and when need arose. Further, the material was easy to decipher and reminders and follow-ups on non-responses were relatively easier. However, from the delays, the electronic methods did increasingly experience asynchronous communication which required endless follow-ups.

Aggregated, several advantages accrued from the mixed method fieldwork in yielding the intended results. The pre-exercises enhanced instrument fidelity and coherence in multiple ways. The questions or indicator variables were kept short, simple and clearly worded, devoid of phrases and containing a minimum number of related ideas to eliminate the common weaknesses of vagueness, biased wording, biased responses and participant fatigue. They were made broadly selective and realistic to balance the enquiry as well as control the complications posed by the impersonal nature of the questionnaire versus the personal nature of the interview and thus give the study the required saturation. Last, the measures enhanced ease of understanding, answerability and completion with minimum assistance and within reasonable timeframes, which reduced both unit and item non-response rates, error processing and the need for intelligent ascriptions. As a result, the high instrument quality positively impacted credibility and trustworthiness.

Further, complemented by the online method, the fieldwork was sufficiently broad and deep to enhance academic and professional appropriateness and inter-subjectivity. The triangulations minimized the negative consequences of researcher, participant and measuring instrument effects and maximised flexibility, anonymity, and easy-to-use and inexpensive instrumentation to handle the sample for ease of comparison and analysis. This allowed the study to critique and turn itself inside out resulting in dynamic interactional and situational analyses of the construct and the events surrounding it. Ultimately, far from a

recipe for misinformation and misrepresentation, as a result of proper planning, the mixed method sustained its reputation of being a robust research method and tool.

In sum, the verification sources contributed to substantive theorization, finally building to the generation and consolidation of both new and existing knowledge frames and practices about the socio-technical diversity of the vision-mission statements. Epistemologically and ontologically, from the analyses and syntheses, the study was well poised to interrogate the complex role and impact of the statements and whether or not, as platforms, they stimulated a more rigorous interpretation and implementation of the vision-mission thesis to achieve the foresighted and farsighted expectations and judgments befitting the institutional and national transformation towards a full technocapitalist order.

4.5 Data collection procedures

From the onset, it was important that the right questions be asked of the right people and in the right way in order to deliver authentic insights. The researcher and the four research assistants undertook the data gathering. The latter were all postgraduates with research experience and occupying senior positions in their respective institutions. This was to maximize on locational advantage through having the practitioners themselves observe, reflect and comment on their own and their colleagues' practical actions. The data collection commenced following the pre-exercises and familiarisation with the instruments and their varied ideas and views were very constructive and useful. The approach, therefore, not only boosted the response rate, but the fact that they were in their situations and not detached from them, rendered the Assistants all the more qualified to research the system. This was in line with the observation by Best and Kahn (2007, p.13) that the contextualization "makes the data sensitive to the social, historical, and temporal contexts in which it was collected."

In-between preparations were made regarding the administration of the instruments: Q_{A1&2} in soft copy and Q_B and Q_C in hard copy, as well as stationery and audio equipment for conducting the interviews. The availability of online data speeded up instrument construction, the pre-exercises and fieldwork which combined concurrent and phases gathering. As indicated, the qualitative data from document sources were used to construct the questionnaires and the interview schedule which were administered simultaneously. All the sampled participants took part in the diversity survey exercise because of its capacity to

accommodate a large population, with the 30 senior academics and senior administrators doubling up in the interviews. Ultimately, the choice methods substantiated the emergent themes, inferences and conclusions

The interview guide (Appendix 3, Q_{A2}) was administered concurrently with Q_{A1} directed at the senior personnel who, invariably, were the main consumers of the vision-mission philosophy. For the interviews administered through the email, participants wrote their answers to the questions. In the face-to-face encounters, once an appointment had been secured, the interview process began with the welcome remark and informing the participant on the purpose of the meeting. Next, was question presentation according to the schedule, spiced up with probing and follow-up questions with the answers recorded manually and/or electronically for transcription later when events were still fresh in the mind. One advantage with electronic data was that it could be played over and over generating fresh insights.

Following after Kenneth and Michael's (2012) observation, through bracketing and intuiting the researcher listened to what the participants were saying about vision-mission statements, kept an open mind and suspended preconceptions, prejudices, personal opinions and rumour mongering in case they influenced or interfered with participants' experiences and the interpretation of the findings and results. When no further contributions were forthcoming, the researcher thanked the participant(s) for their time and efforts and closed the meeting. In the informal interviews, the conversations were entered into once it was conceived that conditions were favourable for such engagements and the politics of the situation tended to dominate discussions. Saturation was reached when no new ideas were emerging at all.

However, typical of emailed questionnaires was the high slow response rate, which posed challenges of bothersome follow-ups and constant reminders. The explanation for the delayed response rate was that the participants were 'too busy' while multiple other causes could not be ruled out.

Last, the researcher followed up to conduct more interviews as well as post-fieldwork interviews to verify and authenticate the findings. The latter involved both individuals and groups with the draft abstract the basis of the conversations to close any gaps as well as enhance member checking. The formal data collection was complemented by tacit

knowledge, defined by Crabtree and Miller (1999b, p.331) as “the largely unarticulated, contextual understanding that is often manifested in nods, silences, humour, and naughty nuances.” As they observe further, as an inevitable source of information, it reflected “the credible sense of understanding of social processes that reflects the researcher’s awareness of participants’ actions as well as their words, and of what they fail to state, feel deeply, and take for granted.” Its sociality is a powerful indication of the strongly influential, hidden behaviours and communications, difficult to fathom through other means.

Overall, critical to the study was whether the vision-mission statements positively injected the requisite sustained innovations and/or disruptive transformations – that is, the catalytic capacity to practically direct and uplift the institutions to fire the economy; or else, as Morphew and Hartley (2006) put it, they are plain ‘everywhere’ statements resembling the proverbial ‘half-full’ or ‘half-empty’ glass – to mean quasi-substantive/irrelevant, fashionable/unfashionable tools devoid of reasonable justification and, therefore, whether the fieldwork sufficiently reflected the true position.

From the evidence, the methodology was effectively usable and allowed for critical, balanced, integrative, controllable investigations and interpretations, while further dialogical in the sense that the investigation and the emergent knowledge were not the prerogative of the researcher alone, nor was the research a matter of subject and object becoming identical, but that all the parties entered into, and benefited from, the necessary dialogical relationship. By having the different types of data provide cross-validity, the multi-fieldwork minimized errors associated with the single method approach, which allowed sufficient tracking of the levels of participation as well as perceptions of satisfaction with regard vision-mission achievements and outcomes. On that score, the fieldwork facilitated the collection of detailed data and information pertaining to the situation on the ground, while ensuring closer cooperative interaction with the social actors as they live and construct their world.

In conclusion, the mixed method approach suited the formal aggregation-disaggregation and the need to understand and portray the reality of visions and missions as was, fathomed through scientific rigour for more valid interpretations and conclusions. In line with Molina and Cameron (2010), it ushered the simultaneous advantages of: complementarity through promoting elaboration, illustration, enhancement and clarification of the different overlapping

aspects of the visions and missions; triangulation or functional convergence of findings and results; and initiation or discernment of paradoxical, ironic and contradictory interpretations of the philosophy, while collectively extending the breadth and range of the inquiry. From the design, the findings and results conformed to or disconfirmed the evidence, with scope for genuine insights into what people actually thought about vision-mission statements against the reality on the ground. In place of suppositions and conjectures, the data offered the requisite objective evidence which enhanced the descriptive, exploratory and explanatory insights that directed the interpretation and conclusion drawing, pushing to the forefront 'what works' in social research (Creswell, 2015; USC Libraries, 2012).

4.6 Data presentation and analysis

Following the fieldwork, data were refined, aggregated and categorised more accurately. Also, patterns and frequencies were determined while events were still fresh in the mind. It strictly focused on the social actors in their settings and on their own terms rather than on the researcher's terms. Notwithstanding the intermittent internet facilities, the availability of online data speeded up the processing, presentation and analysis. Matrices, tables and graphic charts were used to present the collated data, tabulated by footprints and triangulated by method of verification. Enumerative content analysis constituted the bulk of the data reduction and refinement which progressed in stages, beginning with the 'primary analyses' of initial data bundles as they came in, moving on to 'progressive focusing' as more data rolled in and the iteration increased and, finally, 'category and concept formation' involving final coding and description for order and meaning, ready for interpretation or 'theory generation' at both micro and macro levels (Pratt, 2006).

In both document analysis and the interviews, the procedure was that all elements of the open response text were cited and itemized as described in the verification sources and according to 'best fitness'. Since both criteria and questions had been pre-coded, the data reduction proceeded smoothly. Few problems were experienced during the final coding as the data fitted with the laid-out criteria. While it is a weakness of enumerative content analysis in that it isolates the soft data into bits and pieces of discordant information outside its home (vision statements or source documents), often leading to the loss of the contextual meaning or such meaning being made problematic to reconstruct the original, it is also its strength in that it broadens the analysis and synthesis of the construct, especially following a review

(Ngulube, et al. 2014b). The study exercised tight selection, accepting the soft data only once per footprint in order to accommodate the massive output from the different sources. Any repeats across footprints are according to original classification or participant categorisation.

In the diversity survey, participants responded to two separate questionnaires: the ordinal 45item for academics and administrators and the nominal 11item for support staff and students, with the former rated on the 4-point rating scale mentioned earlier. Data were subjected to Qualitative Comparative Analysis (QCA) and Excel programs to determine the quantitative dimensions of the responses. The upward syntheses yielded information on means, standard deviations (SD), frequencies and cross-data comparisons, while also useful for data cleaning. Altogether, there was a highly valid item response rate of 96% with 4% of the indicators, for one reason or the other, omitted or not responded to. Equally, 99% of the indicators were appropriately rated, while the U/J averaged a negligible 1.6 per participant. At 50%, the GSIF was the highest U/J, followed by global rankings at 23%, and lastly, evaluations, impact assessments and reporting at 19%. At 34% entrepreneurship training followed by employment creation and the strategic plan and related instruments at 38% were the most divergently rated, while funding at I/S 74% and the quality of teaching/service delivery at F/C 62% were the most convergent, albeit in different directions. Statistically, 34% was the average, median and mode which confirmed the validity of the N/A as the final rating. Across the board conditions were weak or bland, let alone F/C, and still far from E/W.

Further, the computer programs enhanced credibility by curtailing manual problems and weaknesses of general impressions, the halo effect, the generosity error and the error of severity. However, in the interest of objectivity and rigour, they subjected the study to appropriate/inappropriate deterministic and rigid processes. While, on the one hand, the flexibility reduced excessive manual work, and speeded up the processing and management of huge amounts of data, thereby boosting credibility and auditability, on the other hand, the excessive data reification with its emphasis on coding and retrieval methods, deviated focus away from depth and meaning, to plain volume and breadth of data. Meanwhile, the amount of time and energy spent learning to use the computer packages distracted from the real work of analysis.

Overall, the trans-paradigmatic and trans-disciplinary advantages of the multiple-case study

and the mixed method enhanced the intellectual capacity of the study for studious interrogation and deeper penetration of the formal object to explore and discover its inner essence, substance and import, which would have been made intractable with a larger sample. There was quality interaction between the qualitative and quantitative, inducing the advantage of triangulation, complementarity and initiation. The yielded data substantiated the veracity of the footprints model and, therefore, went beyond being relevant only to the case-institutions (substantive theory). The generated spatial deliverables comprising high profile meta-themes induced higher abstraction (formal theory) that cut across institutional domains which enhanced the generalizability of the results, hence, the ultimate goal to portray the complexities of the vision-mission construct in sufficient depth and detail so that the readers and users can understand it clearly and fully.

This was cognisant of post-positivism's inherent weaknesses which, according to Scott and Usher (1999), no amount of scrutiny can eliminate completely. Among them is the assumption that all participants have equal knowledge of the construct which ignores problems associated with power relations as some people have fewer opportunities while others are more knowledgeable and impose their knowledge on the less privileged. Second, is the extent it perpetuates the positivist position of separate knowers and doers, of theory always superintending practice and therefore in command of all knowledge. Thirdly, because of its openness, coupled with emphasis on reflection and reflexivity, findings and results are often vague or indeterminate fostering sameness or an understanding that reduces the unique to the familiar which does not augur well for policy makers seeking to ground practice in a particular paradigm nor to critical theorists eager for change.

The weaknesses compromise research's critical theory role as, often, the "emphasis on understanding the world is secured at the expense of changing it" (Scott and Usher (1999, p.30). Consequently, the study could at most be retrospective more than it was prospective and predictive, which limits the power of the research to offer more forceful change and reform. It is hoped, by taking into account the fluidity of both epistemic arrangements and ontological relations, the models, arguments, conclusions and recommendations put forward compensate for the drawbacks.

4.7 Credibility and trustworthiness

According to Onwuegbuzie and Collins (2007) the internal and external generalizability fundamentals of representation, legitimation, integration, and politics are both the backbone and burden of mixed methods research. As a result, researchers are seized by the 'crises' (as they call them) whether the text (let alone numbers) authentically reflect the views and standpoints of all parties (representation); whether the findings and/or inferences espouse credibility, trustworthiness, dependability, transferability, confirmability (legitimation); whether the combined qualitative-quantitative approach adequately addresses the research goal, purpose, questions and all (integration); and lastly, whether the tensions and paradoxes arising from comparing and/or contrasting the combined qualitative-quantitative data are well managed (politics). This leaves the four crises the Achilles heel of research which calls for appropriate checks and balances for purposes of intrinsic and extrinsic generalizability.

Both ex-ante and ex-post credibility criteria were weaved into the study echoing Silverman's (2009) admonishing that doing qualitative research should offer no protection from the rigorous critical standards that should be applied to any enterprise concerned to sort out 'fact' from 'fancy'. The study deployed numerous processes to ensure that the findings remained "true and certain – 'true' in the sense that they accurately reflected the situation; and 'certain' in the sense that they were supported by the evidence" (Guion, David, and McDonald, 2013, para.1). Creswell and Miller (2010, p.124) echo this forceful believability of the findings in terms of "how accurately the account represents participants' realities of the social phenomena and is credible to them" and is, therefore, dependable and consistent in fostering confirmability, accuracy and reflexivity.

The study deployed Morse, Barrett, Mayan, Olson, and Spiers (2002, p.9) concurrent criteria of methodological coherence, investigator responsiveness, theoretical sampling and sampling adequacy, an active analytical stance, reliance on multiple sources of data, and saturation, buoyed by prolonged engagement in the system, and sufficient rigour to enhance the utility criterion (or degree of usefulness of the research to the different stakeholders). As repeatedly pointed out, the multiple measures assisted to correct the development of the study and direction of analysis as necessary to contain the crises.

Briefly, investigator responsiveness (openness, sensitivity, insight, introspection and retrospection, creativity, innovativeness), coupled with investigator triangulation (working with supervisors and assistants, doing member checks, peer debriefing, the long time spent in the social space, and periodic presentations) guaranteed full representativeness and legitimation. Through precepts reflecting stakeholder voices as well as inferences drawn from numerical data and information, the study took care of actual and potential variables to see to it that the research was kept truthful, dispassionate, consistent, coherent, and free of the pitfalls of self-assured paradigms or the trappings of local power politics. The methodological triangulation ensured corroboration between the proposition and the fieldwork methods, while the active analytical stance ensured access to relevant paradigms, theories and models which enhanced flexibility and rigour.

Further, the reliance on multiple sources of data enhanced data saturation and, therefore, inclusiveness and exhaustiveness on the degree of the diversity, hence, not only grounding the study in the data collected, but ensuring a holistic thesis (Onwuegbuzie and Collins, 2007). Last, was 'peer examination' involving applying and utilizing the research findings and conclusions of various scholars detailed in Chapter 2.

The credibility of the study was also confirmed in the field. Apart from progressing smoothly, with both the Assistants and the participants handling the exercise successfully, resulting in a high safe yield, no cases of dissatisfaction were reported. Participants acknowledged that they had never questioned some of the issues in that way. Altogether, the multiple triangulations not only generated the needed confidence in the research data, but also produced multiple findings and ways to challenge as well as integrate theories. In the final analysis, the findings and results were similar to yield the same conclusions, while disconfirming evidence was exposed revealing much more about the diversity of the construct. Last, with the assistance of the supervisors, the researcher went through the tables and matrices much more meticulously to note any errors of omission and commission and the overall credibility of the methodology and instruments.

In the final analysis, the study fulfilled its objectives to suit the endeavours of both educationists and the external world. Not only does it offer the reader the opportunity to make proper judgments, more specifically, it induces capacity for insightful explanation of policy

issues and problems and capacity to address them. This resonates with views on the credibility of such studies: being able to “assess the effectiveness of a given practice, intervention or social programme” (Mouton and Marais, 1990, p.45) or, the extent the research “provides solutions to real life-problems as well as contribute to better decision making in practical situations” (Scott and Usher, 1999, p.135). The quality of the discourse to sufficiently aggregate-disaggregate the statements to generate both substantive and formal theory to achieve one or more of these goals, both the short- and long-term, was the distinctive significance and relative worth of the study.

4.8 Ethical considerations

The fieldwork demanded and maintained strict adherence to the ethical protocol. As Hammersley (2012) admonishes, the professionalism demands due diligence and care to guard against corruption, disguise and self-delusion for the study to ensure deeper penetration to overcome multiple challenges as well as control and manage all eventualities. In line with MacCoun (1998), among the cornerstones of research, therefore, was the importance to uphold the post-positivist principles of universalism/impersonality, critical realism (or inter-subjectivity) and organised scepticism (or strict scrutiny) for purposes of communalism or knowledge sharing.

Ethically, participants’ rights were paramount and they were respected and protected. All the necessary permission, cooperation and consent were duly sought and utmost anonymity assured as the best way to ensuring the authenticity of the researched. The participants were assured absolute protection against divulging sensitive data to competitors or unauthorized persons, while further guaranteeing them the freedom of expression, fair treatment, confidentiality and privacy. Not only were they guaranteed freedom from exposure to risks and to withdraw should they so wish, identities and findings remained the prerogative of the researcher for the express purpose of the study and nothing beyond. Effort was taken to avoid undue inconveniences and personalising information.

Also, to steal a leaf from Archer (2007), to incentivise them, the study negotiated a token of appreciation with the Assistants, while response messages thanking the participants were sent out in order to encourage the collegiality motive behind the institutional exchange

programmes of this nature. Last, all cited sources were acknowledged lest the study be found guilty of plagiarism – the pro- versus anti-capitalist ploy.

4.9 Summary

The chapter described and explained the various dimensions of the research methodology, beginning with the post-positivist paradigm and its justification followed by the multiple-case study design which included the population sample and the sampling scheme, and the mixed method approach for the fieldwork. It outlined and critiqued issues of structure, relevance and procedures adopted, embracing the instruments and pre-exercises to test the practicability of the data collection procedures to prove or falsify the proposition. Last, it outlined the data analysis and presentation as well as issues of credibility and trustworthiness and ethical considerations. Given the immersion, the methodology was inclusive and exhaustive enabling the study to gain intimate familiarity with the complexity of the problem amid the practical workings of the vision-mission statements. The next chapter presents and describes the analysed data before full interpretation, discussing and unravelling the opportunities and challenges portrayed.

CHAPTER V

5.0 DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

5.1 Introduction

This chapter processes the fieldwork, aggregating and disaggregating the data-findings into concepts, principles, domains and frameworks defining the vision-mission theory–practice relationship. Using the tools of criticism, inductive, deductive and abductive reasoning, the data reduction and refinement unravels the evidence in order to shed light on the implications and applications of the visions of ‘world class, technopreneurial leadership, innovation and excellence, sustainable development’ among the host of terms dominating the institutional metric and how the tangible and intangible indicators sustain the statements’ productivity, curricular strength, marketability and transformative role. The epistemological target was to verify whether the institutions were resolutely harnessing the construct’s inherent opportunities while addressing the related challenges to render all the footprints firmly grounded and much less their Achilles heel.

From the data presentations, there was an ocean of indicators for which institutions were never short of words, terms and phrases to portray their hardware and software elements. Each presentation is accompanied by analytical descriptions of the data sets highlighting salient points before proceeding to the overall aggregation and interpretation. Critical was whether, as the default policy yardstick the statements lived up to the proclaimed role and standard, exhibiting the ‘truth to power’ maxim. In the process, what has it taken the institutions to realise the preferred states; what complexities, odds and ends have ensued for and against the full realisation of the goal of technocapitalism and/or sustainable development? In a nutshell, the vision-mission construct was revealed as grounded in particular ways and in recognisable discourses peculiar to the social actors within their environments. As a social utility, the statements largely promoted normative ideals more than concrete utilitarian endeavours.

5.2 Data presentation and analysis

The following matrices, tables and graphs present the data and findings triangulated by method of verification by footprint with the case institutions treated as a class. Each case

presents comparisons and contrasts between the data sets. In document sources, the indicators in *italics* were enumerated strictly from the vision-mission statements to show at face value what the statements themselves actually say on each footprint prior to further elaborations (see also Appendix 1). The non-italicised data were enumerated from the other multiple sources. To contain the flood of indicators, tight selection and editing were exercised to avoid unnecessary repetitions and overlaps.

In sync with the mixed methods approach, details from document sources and interviews indicate relative frequencies or the qualitative occurrence of the responses while those from the diversity survey indicate absolute frequencies or statistical occurrences (Zohrabi, 2013). Each presentation is accompanied by a summary description to highlight salient features while open response text or data excerpts reflecting stakeholder voices to support particular viewpoints are cited, before proceeding to interpretation and conclusion drawing. Suffice to say everything that can be said about the mandates and the advancement of the economy and all is said with full conviction and touch of class.

5.2.1 Constituency servicing data categorization

Constituency servicing is the reciprocal relationship between the institution and its hinterland involving mutual support and exchange of resources for sustainable development. First, as outlined in Matrix 5.1, the document sources indicate how everything starts with and terminates at the constituency as the key institutional driver supplying inputs and providing markets for the products, whose feedback operationalizes the recurrent variables of the development superstructure, entrepreneurialism, and community service. From the host of indicators, no stone is left unturned in the drive to access the constituency with and for knowledge and technology to re-engineer its constituent parts: to super charge the institutions “towards sustained capacity building for the increasingly technologically-driven and enterprise-based developments” (Yizengaw, 2003). No problems are envisaged at this state and, barring the public choice conundrum, the technological society for sustainable development is the exceptional standard.

Second, the interview data echoed the document sources and questionnaires in terms of points for and against the construct. In support, as the following excerpts or voices indicate, it was highly commended for its capacity to address the footprints to the satisfaction of all:

- a) gives direction and purpose to the core functions of teaching and learning, research and community engagement.
- b) provides clear management of the people and resources; assists institutions to keep track of mandates with excellence.
- c) stops mediocrity, aspires for sustainable development along the Lagos Plan of Action; more to redress the colonial system.
- d) normal for modern administration to have these; an embodiment of the entire strategic plan which drives the institution.
- e) to mainstream many issues in the strategic plan, and when well-articulated, they make workers have a sense of belonging.

Matrix 5.1 Constituency Servicing findings from document analysis and interviews

Document indicators	Interview indicators (#=30)
<p><u>Vision-mission statements:</u> <i>entrepreneurship; innovation; technology; teaching; training; learning; excellence; research; knowledge; scientific, economic and social challenges; cultured citizens; highly acclaimed graduates; technical skills; sustainable development; national and international community services; commercialization; leadership; humanity</i></p> <p><u>Other documents:</u> extension services; quality environment; stakeholder needs; wealth creation; manpower development; employment opportunities; knowledge and skills in science education; new research knowledge; generation, dissemination and application of knowledge; advancement of humanity; problem solving; industry linkages; knowledge-based society/solutions; enterprise development; multicultural society; societal issues and national</p>	<p>Bring value to the community; something to follow; direction and purpose to the core functions of teaching and learning, research and community engagement; stop mediocrity, aspire for sustainable development along the Lagos Plan of Action; more to redress the colonial system; reproduction throughout all units in the context of their operations and routines; tackle Zim-Asset; an embodiment of the entire strategic plan which drives the institution; informed by other instruments that outline national imperatives; to mainstream many issues in the strategic plan; gourd institutions to ensure good service delivery; great potential for success if adequately resourced; development-oriented research and innovation, science and technology education; accessibility to more people</p> <p><u>Challenges:</u> acidic political/socio-economic climate which induces more challenges and dampens morale; aspirations too high and not in harmony with the reality on the ground; poor national (political) policy and strategic initiatives; lack of</p>

concerns; goods, products and services; address Zim-Asset; community service	stakeholder involvement in the development of the statements
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Thirdly, as shown on Table 5.1, the diversity survey constituency servicing indicators covered socio-economic and environmental issues comprising the policy mandate, capacity and performance, market presence, and science and technology outcomes among others. The F/C ratings were registered for the constituency servicing mandate (3.1), graduate competency levels (3.1) and competitiveness (3.0), with the status of the leadership coming close at 2.9. In effect 29% of the participants rated these indicators E/W which was the highest of all the ratings.

Table 5.1 Constituency data from the diversity survey questionnaire (#=70)

Specifiable Indicators	Mean rating	SD	Frequency (f)			
			I/S	N/A	F/C	E/W
Institutional constituency service mandate	3.1	0.82	5.7	12.9	48.6	32.9
Graduate competency levels	3.1	0.65	-	15.9	56.5	27.5
Leadership status	2.9	0.84	5.9	22.1	47.1	25.0
Entrepreneurship training	2.4	0.95	21.5	33.8	32.3	12.3
Employment creation	2.1	0.87	31.3	37.5	26.6	4.7
Human resources development	2.7	0.87	9.2	27.7	44.6	18.5
Institutional capacity to meet market/ constituency needs	2.8	0.79	5.9	27.9	50.0	16.2
The institution's competitiveness	3.0	0.87	7.2	15.9	46.4	30.9
Science/technology outcomes	2.7	0.86	11.9	20.9	52.2	14.9
Average mean, standard deviation and f	2.8	0.84	10.9	23.8	44.9	20.3

The position is brought low by the rest of the other indicators resulting in an average mean of 2.4. From the E/W perspective, employment creation 5%, entrepreneurship training 12% and the science and technology outcomes 16%, received the lowest ratings or, conversely, the highest I/S ratings. Hence, overall, the results describe a strong N/A rating with a mean of 2.4 and a SD of 0.84.

With respect to challenges, according to the interviews, not only were the aspirations set too highly and did not involve all stakeholders, they were incompatible with the acidic political environment all of which prove a stumbling block in the fulfilment of the construct. To most

of the participants, the acidic status quo was the greatest drawback to the full realisation of the statements. Overall, the data findings heralded a challenged constituency servicing.

5.2.2 Governance data categorization

Governance is the whole spectrum of oversight roles reflecting the way authority is exercised, especially the co-process of faculty governance—administration and the related capacity to direct and manage effectively. Among the multiple indicators, it was propagated through variables like full semesterization, the committee system, creating and sustaining conducive learning, working and productive environments that meet the world class standard, public and international relations, guidance and counselling, student and staff welfare, diversified funding and staff retention, and efficient human resources and quality management systems. The language is reminiscent of the discussion in Chapter 2, apparently, to run first class institutions befitting a technological society.

Matrix 5.2 Governance findings from document analysis and interviews

Document indicators	Interview indicators (#=30)
<p><u>Other documents</u>: committee system; public and international relations; staff retention; student and staff welfare; diversified funding; develop and maintain efficient financial management systems; effective corporate governance/better management system; regulations and environment conducive to learning/ productivity; full semesterization; efficiency and effectiveness; appropriate physical infrastructure; PPPs for infrastructure development; efficient human resources policy: staff conditions of service (funeral cover, disability policy, etc.), indoor and outdoor sports facilities; HIV/AIDS</p>	<p>normal for modern administration to have these; provides clear guidelines and management of the people and resources; conducive conventional set up: offices of the Vice Chancellor and the Registrar, Consultants, Committees, multiple units, audits, research boards, business units, creation of departmental statements for full uptake of the philosophy; alignment of expectations with the statements; continuous staff development and awareness; rules, regulations and policies in place; full time management to liven the strategic plan; stakeholder usability for trickledown effect/impact; imbued sense of belonging; third-stream income generation for implementation funds; good parallel progression for academics</p> <p><u>Challenges</u>: lack of funding and buy-in turn statements into a pipe dream; lack of innovative leadership which is always apologetic about its inefficiencies; acidic environment, non-functioning economy and inadequate resources and international acceptance to power strategic plans; poor attitude & perceptions; lack of motivation; subjectivity in implementation of policies and procedures; relevant over a short period of time;</p>

awareness and life skills education	worker laziness and lack of ownership; students failure to pay fees to address the mandates; inability to live the statements – lack of adherence and lack of reminders to ensure adherence; drop them
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The interviews endorsed the role of the dense network of institutional audits, boards, committees and business units that boost and guarantee the construct's potential for high yield. Sufficient rules, regulations and policies were in place to guarantee remarkable performances and outcomes. Also, critical is the trickle-down effect through departmental statements accompanied by the capacity to utilise them in various forums. And above it all, is the need for a functioning economy: the institutions need resources and international acceptance to get the strategic plans going and less an acidic environment that induces more challenges. On the other hand, multiple public choice challenges deflate the governance. Rather than maximise the public interest, through invisible entrepreneuring, there is tendency to vest self-interests which, coupled with limited funding, weak leadership and poor attitudes from lack of motivation debunk the governance leading to confusion in the implementation of policies and procedures.

Table 5.2 Governance data from the diversity survey questionnaire (#=70)

Specifiable Indicators	Mean rating	SD	Frequency (f)			
			I/S	N/A	F/C	E/W
Overall internal governance matters	2.5	0.85	14.9	23.9	52.2	8.5
Leadership capacity	2.8	0.80	5.9	27.9	48.5	17.6
The strategic plan and related instruments	2.9	0.88	5.9	29.4	38.2	26.5
Committee system status	2.8	0.82	4.4	33.8	41.2	20.6
Conditions of service	2.2	0.76	17.6	45.6	33.8	2.9
Public/client relations	2.4	0.71	10.4	46.3	40.3	3.0
Overall institutional discipline	2.5	0.79	10.9	37.5	43.8	7.8
Human rights issues	2.6	0.75	9.7	30.6	53.2	6.5
Information reporting and disclosure	2.4	0.81	12.7	44.4	34.9	7.9
Funding	1.3	0.59	74.2	19.4	6.5	-
Procurement and supply chains	1.8	0.67	32.3	52.3	15.4	-
Average mean, standard deviation and f	2.4	0.77	18.1	35.6	37.1	9.2

Last, the diversity survey elicited data on policy/corporate matters, leadership capacity, labour practices and decent work, the committee system, rights and treatment of stakeholders, and information disclosure and reporting. Overall, the indicators were rated N/A with the exception of the I/S mean rating of ‘funding’ (1.3) and ‘procurement chains’ (1.8). The F/C rating was recorded on overall institutional discipline (44%) and human rights issues 53%. From the E/W perspective, only the status of the committee system and strategic plans and related instruments were rated fairly high with a mean of 2.8 and 2.7 or 21% and 27%, respectively. As a result, the average mean stood at 2.3 with a SD of 0.77, suggesting a strong pull towards I/S indicating a distressed circumspect community.

5.2.3 Quality Assurance data categorization

Quality assurance is guaranteeing that the higher education offered meets strict and acceptable local and international standards, free of market distortions (Materu, 2007). In the final analysis, a highly irresistible QA was the most sought-after variable. From the visions *per se*, the document sources yielded a vast spectrum of data and information emphatic on, *inter alia*, excellence, world class, scholarship, entrepreneurship, innovation, highly acclaimed graduates, commitment, teamwork, programme growth, intellectual property rights and continuous professional development, with the other sources leaving no stone unturned in the quest for absolute, clinical quality. As the ultimate measure of efficiency and effectiveness, however limited, there is a vast network of practical plans and activities to propagate the Adizes’ Prime stage for complete supply of the correct human resource pedigree at the service of the constituency.

Matrix 5.3 Quality Assurance findings from document analysis and interviews

Document indicators	Interview indicators (#=30)
<p><u>Vision-mission statements:</u> <i>entrepreneurship; innovation; excellence; world class; scholarship; commitment; teamwork; intellectual freedom; technical skills; knowledge hub/creation</i></p> <p><u>Other documents:</u> academic excellence/ intellectual freedom;</p>	<p>High infrastructure quality for quality education; venture capital for world class research and innovations (e.g., Econet); rebrand failed endeavours/institutional competencies and advantages; intentional motivation, keeps mandates in sight; <i>esprit de corps</i>/commitment by all parties; well-crafted, excellent, very wise/viable with strong merits; gives essence and meaning to institutional planning; recruitment of highly qualified staff (PhD holders); research days; protection through</p>

<p>benchmark/propel operations; uniqueness; world class output in teaching, learning, research; career guidance; publications; quality assurance office/ directorate; programme growth and intellectual property rights; quality assurance templates/best practices; awards; advisory boards; participation in exhibitions; efficiency and effectiveness; quality assurance committees; external examining; reviews; student satisfaction; seminar presentations; commitment skills; technical skills; research and development/ scholarship; a technology pedagogy; ICT revolution; patent issues; strategic partnerships; graduate enterprises; inter-library connections; ZIPO/ARIPO; Zim-Asset; staff development fellowships (Master/Doctor of Philosophy/ Technology); well-resourced libraries, information resource centres and projects incubators</p> <p><u>Challenges:</u> outdated/obsolete equipment; small IT bandwidth; limited new machine supplies; inadequate physical infrastructure</p>	<p>ZIPO (patents and commercial rights); technology diplomacy, electronic applications e.g., e-books; international exposure; special awards and commendations; evolutionary transformation of science for more praxis – mixing theory with practice; no need for change, gives integrity to science; people only need to adhere to the letter and spirit therein; capture the dictates of the time; concentrate on entrepreneurship; employee vetting for capacity to meet the vision-mission statements; continuous refresher workshops; more partnerships with industry– South African preference reflects low standards at universities</p> <p><u>Challenges:</u> shortage of resources and inadequate physical infrastructures; too much duplication of curricula; too much ‘lip service’, hence, limited actual deliverables (publications, patents, etc.) universities are judged by; too much teaching, teaching and coaching...and not how to make a computer; empirical programmes with little practical work/more textbooks than doing/practising science from labs; while theoretically equipped, lecturers must be hands-on oriented; provision of basic knowledge at the expense of technological applications; only eager to earn money than fulfil the vision-mission; always crafted to be a ‘sugar candy mountain/an expensive folly/definite <i>fait accompli</i></p>
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According to interview results, both traditional and new infrastructures were in place to support institutional aspirations to raise more and better skilled personnel, to spread entrepreneurialism far and wide while keeping the innovative capabilities of society measuring to world standards (for example, Econet) all of which enhanced the strength of the curriculum. Furthermore, there was potential to transform the curriculum towards a praxis

science education flexing a proper theory-practice mix. As a result, the statements kept the institutions on their toes and in the international higher education radar to deliver as promised all of which helps foster and ingrain the science and technology ethos that approximates the gold standard.

Table 5.3 Quality Assurance data from the diversity survey questionnaire (#=70)

Specifiable Indicators	Mean rating	SD	Frequency (f)			
			I/S	N/A	F/C	E/W
Quality assurance policy and practice	2.4	0.77	13.2	38.2	44.1	4.4
Quality of teaching/service delivery	2.8	0.62	1.5	27.3	62.1	9.1
Quality of the physical infrastructure	1.7	0.77	45.7	37.1	15.7	1.4
Quality of the academic infrastructure	2.0	0.81	30.0	42.9	24.3	2.9
Compliance to national policy specifications	2.5	0.64	4.8	45.2	46.8	3.2
Conditions for continuous improvement	2.2	0.76	20.0	42.9	35.7	1.4
The library service	2.4	0.77	14.3	32.9	50.0	2.9
The ICT support service	2.1	0.78	21.7	46.4	29.0	2.9
The examination support service	2.6	0.69	4.3	37.7	50.7	7.2
Other support services	2.4	0.67	7.6	47.0	42.4	3.0
Transfers of technological innovations and inventions	1.9	0.77	33.9	48.4	14.5	3.2
Institution's local ranking	2.6	0.88	12.3	30.8	43.1	13.8
Average Mean & Standard Deviation & f	2.3	0.74	17.4	39.7	38.2	5.2

The diversity survey QA indicators devolved around processes and practices related to both the academic and physical infrastructures. They included the programmes pool complemented by the library, ICT, examinations and other support services, compliance to national policy specifications, conditions for continuous improvement, and the transfer of innovations and inventions. Except for I/S ratings of the 'physical infrastructure' (1.7) and the 'transfer of technological innovations' (1.9), the rest of the QA indicators, including the quality of the academic infrastructure were predominantly N/A, with the 'quality of teaching/service delivery' describing a mean rating of 2.8 by 62% of the participants, followed by 'local rankings' at 2.6 (14%). From the E/W perspective, except for the local rankings, the rest of the indicators were <10%. The overall mean rating and SD were 2.3 and 0.74, respectively.

As in constituency servicing and governance, both document sources and the interviews echoed the challenges curtailing the full implementation and realisation of the QA. Duplication of curricula aside, the weak pedagogy, coupled with inadequate intakes from the school system was the most challenged passing for more theoretical models rather than practical endeavours. Again, limited funding worsened the sore thumb: responsible for obsolete equipmentation and uncompleted buildings and, therefore, rudimentarily equipped workshops, lecture rooms and laboratories as well as limited physical space for staff accommodation and leisure pursuits. The findings reflected guarded optimism.

5.2.4 Comportment data categorization

Comportment is the totality of attitudes, behaviours, personality profiles and humanely-related practices expected of the products and stakeholders. In resonating the constituency servicing and QA footprints, the document sources virtually reiterated and cemented the utilitarian strength and transformative role of the construct. Hence, the comportment footprint was the most loaded and lexically diverse multispeed courier whose lavish cargo is as close to each other as it is distant and as valid as it is priceless in its lone race towards destinations that keep receding in the horizon. The products and services must exhibit the most exacting behaviour standards of honesty, integrity/ *ubuntu*/ *hunhu*, professionalism, innovativeness, research excellence, commitment, democracy, dynamism, cultured citizenship, equity and all. A lower throughput to such perfection would not only be out of step, but very disingenuous. The grand mixture of hard and soft skills is assurance of successful leveraging of the ‘academic-productivity-humanitarian’ interface.

Matrix 5.4 Comportment findings from document analysis and interviews

Document indicators	Interview indicators (#=30)
<p><u>Vision-values statements:</u> <i>innovativeness; integrity; research excellence; commitment; equity; honesty; leadership; teamwork; diversity; entrepreneurship; professionalism; discipline; diligence; honesty; social and environmental responsibility; intellectual freedom; student centeredness; democracy; dynamism; knowledge acquisition and sharing</i></p>	<p>strong sense of equity / business values; neo-liberal policy and freedom; better work output: strong morality and social and environmental consciousness; synchronized, compatible core values–workplace culture to speak the same language; reorder core values – start with innovation then excellence</p>

<u>Other documents:</u> career guidance and counselling; discipline; customer care; ubuntu/hunhu; gender; service excellence; code of conduct; patriotism; diversity; cultured citizenship; harassment; ecumenical and counselling services	<u>Challenges:</u> unwholesome tendencies among the intellectual elite; rotten eggs that take advantage of situations; unclear policy compromising the core values; lip-service/weak commitment in the implementation of the statements; omissions
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The interviews romped in with highlights of a foundational *esprit de corps* centred on morality, equity, business ethics, environmental consciousness, a well synchronized core values-workplace culture nurtured on freedom, neo-liberalism and democratic principles. This was in light of numerous unethical practices by the intellectual elite who fail to be genuine custodians of the comportment investiture. Operations were, therefore, compromised rather than promoted reflecting limited commitment to the establishment.

Table 5.4 Comportment data from the diversity survey questionnaire (#=70)

Specifiable Indicators	Mean rating	SD	Frequency (<i>f</i>)			
			I/S	N/A	F/C	E/W
The core values	3.0	0.76	1.5	26.9	46.3	25.4
Student attitudes and conduct	2.6	0.57	1.5	38.8	56.7	3.0
Staff professionalism	2.5	0.67	7.4	33.8	55.9	2.9
Prospects for a moral community	2.5	0.72	8.8	33.8	53.9	4.4
Humanitarian services	2.3	0.72	15.4	46.2	36.9	1.5
Core values-workplace values relationship	2.4	0.70	9.0	41.8	46.3	3.0
Democracy and institution-building	2.5	0.72	6.7	45.0	41.7	6.7
Average Mean & Standard Deviation & <i>f</i>	2.5	0.69	7.2	38.1	48.2	6.7

Epistemologically, the diversity survey checked for student attitudes and conduct, staff professionalism, humanitarianism, the relationship between the core values and workplace values, democracy and institution-building. Only the core values indicator was rated F/C 3.0 while the rest were N/A. The higher-level confidence in the values was demonstrated through the F/C ratings of student attitudes and conduct (58%), staff professionalism (56%) and prospects for a moral community (54%). The big challenge was the incompatibility between the workplace and the core values (E/W 3%). The average mean rating of 2.5 and the SD of 0.69 continued the sublime but cautious idealization shown across all the footprints.

5.2.5 Evaluation data categorization

Evaluation is the systematic acquisition and assessment of information, products and services to provide useful feedback on the efficacy of the visions and missions (Trochim, 2006). Its indicators comprised reviews, audits, grading, world class, peer and student assessments, monitoring and evaluation plans, evaluation policy and related measures, the status of academic reviews, the GSIF, global rankings, and the nature of reporting/assessments. Here, the institutions reiterated standard practice which was significant confirmation on the vision statements as pointers of what should be achieved, hence, remaining the standard guide.

Matrix 5.5 Evaluation findings from document analysis and interviews

Document indicators	Interview indicators (#=30)
<p><u>Other documents</u>: reviews; audits; grading; peer and student evaluations; alumni; dynamism; assessment tools; world class; by 2025; monitoring and evaluation reports; accountability reports</p>	<p>Total achievement indicators and institutional guide; still new (3 – 5 years) and not yet subject to change; annual reports on how the strategic plan has been covered; identity to avert being radarless; regular reviews to match purpose; solid practice, e.g., research and development; annual reviews at senior management level</p> <p><u>Challenges</u>: little monitoring and evaluation– another document on the shelf; lack of continuous/constant reviews in line with the rapid changes; no scientific evaluation to support criticism of a <i>fait accompli</i>; revamp old evaluation instruments</p>

The interviews broadened and cemented the formal role of the statements whether a recent phenomenon or not. As the radar, they continue to offer the requisite guidance for practices and operations, including strategic planning and reporting. Importantly, to carry the day, they just must be pragmatic, with research and development and frequent management reviews the cornerstone to achieve this. Among the challenges was the limited monitoring and evaluation of the construct or the absence of continuous/constant reviews in line with rapid changes, hence, practically reducing the statements to just another document on the shelf, if not a fly on the wall.

Table 5.5 Evaluation data from the diversity survey questionnaire (#=70)

Specifiable Indicators	Mean rating	SD	Frequency (f)			
			I/S	N/A	F/C	E/W
Evaluation policy and related measures	2.4	0.72	11.3	43.5	41.9	3.2
Academic reviews, audits and assessments	2.5	0.73	9.5	36.5	49.2	4.8
Institution's future	3.3	0.73	1.5	11.9	44.8	41.8
The Global Sustainability Initiative Framework (GSIF)	2.6	0.83	15.6	18.8	59.4	6.3
Global ranking	1.9	0.82	39.2	31.4	29.4	-
Evaluations, impact assessments and reporting	2.4	0.78	13.0	40.7	40.7	5.6
Average mean & standard deviation & f	2.5	0.77	15.0	30.5	44.2	10.3

Subjected to the diversity survey, only the institutional futures indicator was rated F/C, with a positive mean peak rating of 3.3 – close to acknowledging that, although falling short, the vision-mission statements point in the right direction and potentially provide the necessary guidance. Still what they can achieve fails to tally with everything around – the evaluation policy and related measures and evaluations, impact assessments and reporting both at 2.4. With a rating of 2.6, and despite its high U/J rating of 50%, the GSIF and, therefore, sustainability issues, was considered adequately catered for, whereas with I/S rating of 1.9 (39%), the global ranking was considered sub-standard. Once again with the mean rating of 2.4 and SD of 0.77, the footprint was cause for concern and significant pointer to mere rhetorical rather than substantive evaluations.

5.2.6 Data categorization: support staff-student participants

Figures 4.1 and 4.2 show the verdict by both support staff and students according to the dimensions of awareness, ownership and impact (see also Appendix 3). Awareness was covered through the indicators of recognition, institutional operations, meaning, and personal applications and, therefore, whether or not the statements were necessary. The four indicators which covered ownership were the levels of internalization of the construct for total proprietorship, high levels of performance, personal guidance, and appropriate attitude change and work ethics.

Last, impact was covered through perceptions of benefits like the development of the desired moral community and a bright future inspired by the statements. As shown, 60% of the participants rated the construct favourably, with 22% strongly agreeing and 37% agreeing

while 26% were neutral and 12% disagreed and 3% strongly disagreed on its viability, which meant that the construct was well received by this category of participants.

Figure 5.1 Responses for support staff and students (#=40)

Figure 5.2 shows the findings with strongly agree and agree combined (S/A/A) and the same done with neutral, disagree and strongly disagree (N/D/SD) reduced to 'yes' and 'no', respectively. As the graph shows, 'yes' was the more dominant response across the board by fairly big margins. Except for full awareness (88%) no other indicator was as highly rated. Immediately controversial were: that the statements fully reflected the way the institution operated (65% vs 35%); that as participants they fully understood what the statements meant (70% vs 30%); and that they knew what to do with the statements (48% vs 52%). In spite of the misgivings, many felt that they did rely on the statements in addition to the job descriptions/specific subject requirements (58% vs 42%), which may or may not be normal given other factors.

Of the three variables, ownership was the most controversial across the board, with the participants quite vocal on issues of full proprietorship (42% against 58%); exceptional influence in their work/studies (42% vs 58%); and guidance and alignment (33 vs 67%). On the other hand, they felt that the statements did induce capacity to build desirable attitudes, work/study ethics, culture and values (60% vs 40%).

Figure 5.2 Responses for Questionnaires B&C – support staff and students

Additionally, the astonishing levels of disconnect from informal conversations reminiscent of social desirability or plain acquiescence were quite revealing. The mere fact that many could not recite the said visions and missions when requested to do so suggested problems of mutual pretence as well as open, suspected, and closed truths and, therefore, the construct's lack of an inherently forceful foothold in this constituency. Comments such as the following were an exception rather than the rule:

- a) while I am not fully aware of the vision-mission and core values of the University, I am guided by those of my centre;
- b) I just do my job as per job description. Not much thought is given to mission, values, etc.
- c) ...over and above the questions answered, to me it was like I was answering the university motto. The rest (honesty, integrity, etc.) are silent or are not said too often.

Overall, the results indicated that, in spite of the dilemma of a less influential yardstick, the group had positive views about the vision-mission philosophy. However, the study could not determine how the statements directly impacted personal choices or work and learning apart from the apparent reason that they were being responded to because they existed. The high neutral frequency of 26% offered supporting evidence to this conclusion.

5.3 Aggregated findings and results

Summed up, the QUAL+quan verification sources converge rather than diverge on the perceptions of the vision-mission statements. The document sources were more inclined towards E/W, although the multiple challenges softened the Utopian stance; the main questionnaire was strongly N/A; while support staff-students and interviews were equivocally N/A-F/C – not a surprising verdict given the subjective and intuitiveness of the latter. Table 5.6 read together with Figure 5.3 show the aggregated footprint ratings. Overall, the F/C rating was the most dominant at 42% followed by N/A at 34%, with I/S and E/W at 14% and 10%, respectively. To reiterate, against a possible mean of 4.0 for the set standard, all the footprints were rated N/A at an average mean of 2.4 and an SD of 0.76. Governance and QA at 2.3 had the lowest average mean ratings.

Table 5.6 Aggregated results for Q_{A1/3}

Footprint	Mean	SD	Average frequency ratings			
			I/S	N/A	F/C	E/W
Constituency Servicing (CS)	2.4	0.84	11	24	45	20
Governance (Gov)	2.3	0.77	18	36	37	9
Quality Assurance (QA)	2.3	0.74	17	40	38	5
Comportment (Comp)	2.5	0.69	7	38	48	7
Evaluation (Eval)	2.4	0.77	15	31	44	10
Average mean, SD & <i>f</i>	2.4	0.76	14	34	42	10

In terms of frequency ratings, F/C was marginally higher across all the footprints except QA at 38% F/C versus 40% N/A; comportment was the most dispersed; QA and evaluation were the most uniform, governance the most compact, and I/S spiked in all three, including evaluation. The close relationship between N/A and F/C suggests a strong pull towards the latter. Except in constituency servicing where it was slightly more competitive, the aspired E/W was a pale shadow of itself when it should be marching closely with and above F/C.

Evidently, the high SD values reflect strong satisfaction/dissatisfaction with the state of affairs with participants either equivocally supportive and, hence, marginally hopeful and giving the construct the benefit of the doubt and chance to succeed (F/C); or they discounted and dismissed it outright as a worthless pursuit (I/S). All in all, it was still a long way to go to duly

translate the substance and import of the philosophy into the choice vision of exceptional/world class and, therefore, just what the institutions want, deserve and work by.

Figure 5.3 Comparative footprint ratings (Source: Table 5.6)

From the study’s perspective, as the signal of the big gap between the reality on the ground and the target vision-mission forecasts, the N/A mean rating was sufficient evidence to accept the proposition that the statements did not play a big role in institutional mandates. Or, by deduction, the evidence was inconclusive to justify the assertion that the vision statements play a positively influential role on mandates at this point in time. While the I/S-N/A ratings were compatible with the workings of the bureaucracy, they were incompatible with the espoused singularity theorem. Challenges and difficulties clearly reduced the said aspirations to the bland N/A state of affairs.

Overall, the data confirmed the role of the broad spectrum of indicators rallying the footprints to meet the institutional mandates. Except for governance and evaluation which were largely accounted for from other sources, the other footprints, constituency servicing, QA and comportment were well articulated in the visions and missions themselves with indicators like entrepreneurship, excellence, innovation and world class, complemented by teaching, research, commitment and integrity cutting across several footprints in sync with diversity in principle, content and context.

Also, except for the core values all of which were lists, the other indicators were purposively couched. For instance, lexically, knowledge was described through the indicators of 'hub of knowledge, knowledge acquisition and sharing, advancement of knowledge and its practical application, create knowledge, and knowledge-based solutions' clear endorsement of highly esteemed and privileged scholasticism based on norms and structures rooted in experimentation and in "intangibles, fluidity and flexibility" to echo Suarez-Villa (n.d. para.4). 'World class, centre of excellence and beacon of excellence' espoused excellence, while 'entrepreneurship for sustainable development, highly acclaimed graduates equipped with entrepreneurial skills, technopreneurial leadership, and enhanced entrepreneurship' the entrepreneurship deliverable. 'Scholarship in innovation, and innovation for sustainable development' fired the innovation drive, and 'technologically-oriented research, commercialise technology through professionalism rooted in integrity, and technological challenges' stimulated the technology drive. While the strategic plans proceeded to amplify some of the indicators, the assumption seemed to be that they were generally well understood, including the values lists which only one institution briefly explained.

An additional observation was the dearth of critical indicators like impartiality, justice, liberty, rights, adaptation, accountability, transparency and the quality-quantity-time framework, extending to the more controversial like fallibility, vulnerability and morality. So, too, were the values of complexity and complication related to the technical "fix" and the myriad challenges induced, the basic attributes of 'belief, disbelief and suspension of judgment' and mandating, facilitating, partnering and endorsing all of which were less generic and fairly remote. Except that such indicators are preserves of other fields and have never been defined holistically so that they refrain across the board for the benefit of the entire constituency, there was no apparent explanation. Yet the ingraining of such skills and values among both staff and learners is a critical condition for productive nation-building.

Altogether, the variations in rating do indicate that the statements do play a purposive role to inspire and consolidate the mandates, which explains the strong emphasis on the constituency servicing, QA and compartment footprints. While the institutions have not yet achieved the desired singularity, their adoption was the right way forward to revolutionise and multiply the science and technology equity for the people and the nation. If not, then it approximated everything that they had always wanted to do to ensure positive enhancement

of their mandates – that is, premier or world class teaching, learning, research, advisory services, commercialization, consultancy, etc. extending to multiple other national imperatives and societal needs.

Accordingly, both management and the workforce needed to spend a great deal of their time and effort clarifying, communicating and confirming the construct; exhorting one another to believe in and share it. In the words of Haden (2012, para.20), this is what ‘remarkable’ employees do, since it is not enough to be “*great* employees that follow the rules/processes, but to be *remarkable* (or spontaneous) ones that are driven by the desire to find ways to make the processes even better, not only because they are expected to...but because they just can't help it.”

The CUT (2013, p.5) speaks for the other institutions in describing its mandate as the ‘development and practice of design and technology; the teaching and application of Sciences, Art and Design; the nurturing of entrepreneurship, innovation, creativity, intellectual, aesthetic and socio-moral student growth; and working for self-sustainability.’ This is echoing the Education Review Commission Report of 1999 which urged that, for Zimbabwe to architect into a mature science and technology nation, ‘Design and Technology’ must be introduced even in basic education to promote a scientific and technical culture that is the pride and envy of everyone. The technological intelligence means capacity to mobilise endeavours against the vagaries of ignorance and other disruptive physical and human forces. It is apparent that the institutions envision highly proficient constituency niches serviced along traditional and beyond orthodox lines, with science and technology the ideological strategy to, and the means behind, the practical fulfilment of the national Anthem.

As seen before, while successful with some indicators and challenged with others and, therefore, at different levels of attaining their visions-missions, the institutions were emphatically proclaiming that progress towards the technological culture was no longer a chance factor. In terms of the VAE measure, it was a practical reality at the fingertips of the nation. It was therefore a mistake if Zimbabwe was not bargaining for the best through accessing this perfect window of opportunity. In spite of the prevailing political and economic misfortunes, the exquisitely crafted statements guarantee a bright, certain journey.

Precedentially, the high profile scientifically engineered social proselytizing was the perfect plot and plan to pursue.

Problematic, however, is how as an institutional asset, the construct was stalled and frustrated by a host of internal and external factors. Portraying the troubled state of affairs were numerous, surmountable and insuperable challenges, reflected in the overall N/A ratings and high SDs (see Table 5.6) and further articulated in the interview and document sources. They included the weak funding coupled with inadequate physical infrastructures (limited physical space for laboratories, workshops, lecture rooms, accommodation, etc.), an inefficient, non-innovative leadership, poor workforce motivation, lack of continuous reviews, and the polarised national political gridlock and its aversion to the 'profit' motive. The last factor is the basic cause and source of failure towards more and better control of efficiency and incentives.

Adding to the dilemma were the weak intakes from the school system which was unable to support the institutions with enough supplies of STEM inputs, limited internet and information services (small bandwidth, old technologies/obsolete equipment and machines in laboratories and workshops), lack of resources like office space, printers, computers and photocopiers, ineffective practical lessons as a result of the large student populations, shortage of transport for industrial attachment supervision, and weak stakeholder urgency in response to issues of rebranding and accreditation of new programmes. Lastly, notwithstanding the fact that there is no lack of persistent trying and strong commitment from and by all parties, not only was there failure to 'live' the visions leading to too much lip-service or lack of buy-in, the aspirations were set too highly, while it is not uncommon for the visions-missions to occur as an afterthought when all and sundry has been put into place or settled, hence, courting employee cynicism and apathy.

This was in the face of the inherent weakness of 'flowery' language and technical jargon that left the stakeholders operating at different wavelengths, revealing not only the limited experiences most people had with the statements, but the dilemma surrounding the construct and its style of communication and marketing. The drawbacks posed the biggest challenge which negatively impacted the full implementation of the construct. The net result is the

limited rightful deliverables amid disproportionate quality standards with deep consequences on the economy and nation.

For the future, the construct will continue to provide the critical guidelines and development-oriented teaching and learning, with entrepreneurship the principal though lame focus. Programme delivery with greater emphasis on doing coupled to greater external exposure (even outside the country), as well as awards of excellence or special commendations amid a revitalised economy are part of the much-needed regenerative capacity, failing which it would be correct to pronounce the statements a definite *fait accompli* or a fad/expensive 'folly'. Importantly, first and foremost, is the call for genuine change in the leadership mind-set, supported by a synchronized core values–workplace culture to make the two compatible to speak the same language, introducing monitoring and evaluation platforms for more and better perspectives, and strongly engaging in third-stream income generation to promote self-sustainability. The subsequent interpretation of the data examines more closely the emerging opportunities and challenges subtended to the propagation of the construct.

5.4 Interpretation

Chisaka and Vakalisa (2000, p.12) define interpretation as the process in research which “seeks to make sense of the data by reaching out...for understanding or explanation beyond the limits of what can be explained with the degree of certainty.” Best and Kahn (2007) and Nithya (2011) describe it as the task of drawing inferences and explaining the meaning of the collected facts, attaching significance to the particular results, answering the *why* questions and, through multiple analytic frameworks, linking the results of the study with other studies.

Accordingly, the interpretation was linked to the development of exploratory and explanatory concepts, theories and inferences that could serve as the basis for new avenues of intellectual adventure, future research as well as greater appreciation why findings are as they were, leading to a broader understanding of their real significance. It expounded the silent principles working beneath the data-findings for significant patterns, categories, and causal relations in-keeping with grounded theory so that “the relevant audience (higher education and the teaching profession) would make sense of the study and what it means to them” (Zohrabi, 2013, p.602).

Like other processes, interpretation is confronted by numerous errors to guard against. MacCoun (1998, p.269) cautions against strategy-based errors arising from 'suboptimal cognition or mental economy' involving failure to know or to apply normative rules of inference, in particular

(a) using fallacious deductive syllogisms (e.g., affirming the consequent, denying the antecedent), (b) failing to adjust for non-independence among evidentiary items, (c) confusing correlation with causation, and (d) relying on heuristic persuasive cues (e.g., appeals to an investigator's prestige or credentials).

In line with the normative standards of discussion and inference, the pressing need is to articulate the dimensions and domains of the data-findings whether liberal, conservative or radically controversial, adversarial, inquisitional or conformable without bias and clean of promoting, ignoring, disparaging and distorting one angle at the expense of the others. The findings must be in accord with the constant refrain between the proposition, empirical observations and theoretical framework. In the subsequent exposition, the initial overview is followed by detailed discussion of the special deliverables synthesised from the main sources of verification.

From the evidence, the vision-mission statements satisfied the dimensions of the Ashridge Mission model. The excellent statements invariably included both hardware and both software elements, however reservedly. If not, then, they were good in that strategy lacked the essential behaviour descriptors – ethically, morally, honestly, etc. Events were therefore very much congruent and correspondent. Everything about the advancement of the people, nation and all is articulated with high octave and cosmic abundance. Given the self-evident truth any analysis is, therefore, an adjustment of the same expressive continuum. This is to mean that, notwithstanding challenges of self-assured paradigms, in the final analysis the institutions were pursuing the same mandate in closely identical ways. The statements are borne by the variability of, and the need to hone in, the diverse experiences arising from many people having passed through multiple systems, or having reached different achievement levels, both of which tend to increase chances of working at cross-purposes or with a false sense of knowledge and understanding.

Second, all the verification sources clearly indicated that the institutions were singing from the same hymnbook and dressing the same chickens only at separate abattoirs. Not only is

there adequate service of IT facilities for on-line registration, fees payments, local area networks and anti-plagiarism software (for example, Ephorus), the introduction of efficient information systems has reduced the glitches of bureaucratic procedures. Hence, the science and technology being talked about enjoys a growing curriculum density of about 60 programmes across the nine major disciplines shown on Figure 5.4, with further benefits from the generous dose of commercial programmes. Clearly sought after are the creative regenerative capabilities and, therefore, direct and indirect exportability of the programmes and, with the exception of sports science, much less their 'morphological and characterological correction' of individuals (Roldan, 2010). The technological infinite means prolific competitiveness that galvanises viable national self-reliance.

This is fulfilling the central theme of the mandates: to civilise capitalism as the sustainable development anchor, as there were slim chances outside it. Civilizing capitalism means making it as digestible, friendly and attractive as ever for all and sundry while civilizing the people for capitalism means tuning their mental psyche and social demeanour to ensure that they take it hook, line, and sinker and become indigenous technocapitalists themselves. To put a spin on Krueger and Gibbs (2007, p.35), as the sting process technocapitalism not only means mastering capitalism's ideological intricacies, but also acknowledging the fact that

...far from a homogeneously compatible and stable phenomenon, *technocapitalism* works against the pacification of social disruption, against the management of consensus and stability... Its concern is not with the formulation of agreements or the preservation of order, but with the invention of new and hitherto unauthorized modes of disaggregation, disagreements and disorder. (*Emphasis new*)

The institutional strategic plans bring this message out eloquently. In line with the philosophy of Instrumentalism there is overwhelming concurrence on the omnipotence of the technosciences as the correct artillery to spook the technological conversion into more and better practice. Consequently, while it is true that education cannot transform the world and the world cannot transform without it, the institutional standard is that higher education's science and technology *will* and *must* transform the nation and its people. As a super-quality instrument, its transformative power automatically buoys the economy and the society upward and forward, proverbially, fulfilling the Archimedes principle of socio-economic buoyancy. It is the celebrated construction through which everybody must see-work resources and the environment, which strengthens both official and public thinking to the fact

that the STEM approach is pre-eminently the only sensible and rational way of understanding and working the psycho-physical environment (Scott and Usher, 1999).

Today's challenges of human development, democratization, labour, industrial and agricultural productivity, rural and urban inequalities, and environmental risks and hazards require a fully-fledged technogarchy or technocapitalist expertise at the service of the nation. Naturally, the 'commercial imperative' stakes the future of the nation on the values of technocapitalism to cleanse itself of the *biggest* waste – weak science and technology – in order to 'catch up' with the rising rest. Ultimately, the people will live and enjoy better quality and more fulfilling lives; they will participate fully in the national and international affairs of their choice; and they will exercise proper ecocracy – the hallmarks of the 5Es (including emotional intelligence) and EIAA for total socio-economic emancipation. This means full affirmative action on the quality and liberty of own knowledge, skills and values to work for humanity. Finally, whether resembling an allergic drug, with capitalism either rejecting the people or the people rejecting it, without compromise, the two must exist compatibly together as in the West and in the interests of the technocapitalist world.

For good reason, then, the institutions must exude the uncompromising optimization imperative: to mean more torque pressure if the dense concentration of indicators on the constituency servicing, QA and the compartment footprints is anything to go by. This is what they were created for: to purify the products at source, hence, beneficiate the economy, the people and society and the environment at large through developing technologies and artisanship skills that suit and meet local needs and address local challenges. Through teaching, training, research, exchange and multiple community services, they deliver the core personnel of 'Thinkers, Builders, Improvers and Providers': the world-class professionals equipped with the right and correct job-entry level psycho-technics rising to higher order conceptualization skills for sustainable development.

Potentially 10 000 graduate output per annum, as a measure of the institutional proficiency the critical mass reflected a phenomenal increase of 134% between 2011 and 2014 (see Figures 5.4 and 5.5) and the graph is rising. By 2014 it was nearly 1900, about 70% of commerce disciplines with 2730 graduands. The (Applied) Sciences and Industrial Manufacturing and Engineering Technology topped the expertise list, mostly civil

engineering. However, complementary outputs from both internal sources (for example, the UZ) and external institutions (Malaysia, Singapore, South Africa, etc.) aside, the overall output is a drop at Kariba. While sports science, agriculture, and science and technology education were struggling, with medicine still at infancy, interesting developments are the introduction of the disciplines of electronic commerce and financial engineering sciences – firm grounding in technocapitalism for the imminent technological society.

Figure 5.4 Graduate output 2011-14 by disciplines
 (Source: Institutional statistics – Appendix 4)

Key:

1 – Applied Sciences; **2** – Industrial Manufacturing & Engineering Technology; **3** – Environmental Science & Health, Forestry & Wildlife; **4** – Information Science & Technology; **5** – Agricultural Science; **6** – The Built Environment; **7** – Science & Technology Education; **8** – Sports Science; **9** – Other: Electronic Commerce, Financial Engineering, HIV&AIDS

The overall disciplinary collection and its operability is a hybrid of the natural sciences and the socio-cultural infiltrations that lie behind the curricula discourses. As Roldan (2010, p.13) points out, guided by the classical theory of the human motor is the conception of the “body as a means of production (machine), of physical and mental energy as capital (organic economy) and biological strength as racial (ethnic/nationalist) vitality (eugenics).”

Figure 5.5 Total annual output 2011-14 (Source: Appendix 4)

On the other hand, the disciplinary glut reveals interest in programme diversity more than premium market competitiveness in terms of concrete, value-for-money innovations. Following market adjustments, by estimation, about half the output would likely stay in-country while the rest would engage in skills flight continuing the negative impact the national manpower need. To Gurira (2010) the dilemma of *millionaires* and *nillionaires* and, therefore, multiple social challenges, simply persists.

5.4.1 Reflections

Articulated through the indicators of academic/professional excellence, premier, world class institutions, highly acclaimed graduates, and efficiency and effectiveness, the QA footprint permeates the operations to secure the market the best options attainable. The choice indicators have strong links with the classroom to guarantee the delivery standard in terms of good teaching, academic/intellectual freedom, meritocracy, research, entrepreneurship, innovation, autonomy, and corporate social responsibility. In terms of the academic infrastructure, it means the institutions must proceed to harness and multiply all the requisite practices and processes to build perfectly sustainable relationships, styles, workflows, products and services, while reducing and eliminating all forms of defects, scarcities, discrepancies and distortions.

Furthermore, the QA clearly articulates the capacity to maximize the scientific product surpluses or profits as measured against the input-costs (materials, utilities, salaries, equipment, software), ultimately to build and sustain proper exergy and consumability values. Institutionally, the quality outcomes not only enhance alumni, but most importantly, job prospects in the market. In other words, the programme graduates guarantee maximum exchange value, or surplus value, or use-value. This means capacity to consistently satisfy the 'jobs-to-do' criteria or quality contribution to the total wellbeing of the institutional and constituency socio-economic welfare, and to national and international competitiveness when directly and indirectly compared with competitors (the HIT, 2015). This point rhymes well with Petkoski and Twose's (2003, p.1) observation that the institutions must display relentless commitment to "contributing to sustainable development, working with staff, the local community and society at large to improve quality of life, in ways that are good for the institution and for national development."

The comportment footprint is the formal prerequisite for the *bona fide* graduates as torch bearers of a humane technological society. In a nutshell, it means fusion of cultured competency with the professional morality of rational self-interest and private enterprise vital in constituency livelihoods, to governance and work, and for total quality yield. Hence, there is a deep sense of nostalgia for purity and tradition, with both esoteric and punctilious rites revealing a cultural yearning to return to roots against the rising tide of modernity, multiculturalism and vetocracy. Experience rather than experiment is considered the best way forward. Internal contradictions, therefore, exist whereby there is an outcry for strict reverence to old ways versus the call for a psychosocial revolution that is scientifically radical in its embrace of modernity and change.

The comportment further underpins powerful stakeholder engagement and responsiveness, which translated into sufficient throughput that matched the available resources (technological, financial, infrastructural, spatial and personnel) with positive constituency impact through numerous forms of feedback, in particular sustainable resource inputs and servicing. Hence, through social and environmental responsibility and other such indicators, the institutions sought to enhance community services in order to encourage and ensure greater community support, while also expected to run on a low carbon footprint – that is, low production and service costs embracing fiscal discipline, energy and water savings, and the

recycling of emissions, effluent and wastes. It was to their advantage to build an environmentally responsive and responsible reputation through supporting initiatives and establishing integrated units catering for environmentally sustainable development matters. However, from the evidence of 'appetites' gleaned from the number of SUVs in circulation, coupled with the outputs of wastes, the carbon footprint remains high and rising.

Save for the ministry statements, because of its central and very intricate role to ensure that the core functions of mandating, facilitating, partnering and endorsing were positively addressed, the governance and evaluation footprints were disproportionately absent or were very silent in the institutional visions and missions. The problem lies in indexing as both are not so easy to weave into the statements. However, all was not lost as both featured in the strategic plans and report documents. The governance, or more precisely the committee system, was critical for accrediting best management practices, for staff and student recruitment, motivation and retention under conducive conditions of caring and magnanimous institutions, for career guidance and counselling, public and international relations, student and staff welfare, and for securing funding from diverse sources. This was inevitable given that the governance is the one that formulates, administers, coordinates, promotes, reviews and executes vision-mission provisions for equitable, appropriate, accessible, affordable and acceptable quality facilities and services compatible with the rest of the (national) policy pronouncements.

The choice of the method of governance was a significant step here: whether participative, shared or corporate governance or some combination of these. Basically, it means 'involve everybody in everything', with the corporate governance modelled in the manner of private business with well-defined chief executive officers (CEOs – charismatic, energetic and outgoing) and related leadership and management techniques, much of which has been covered. The three methods seek to garner 'high involvement' and 'high performance' to boost the objectives of the corporate, targeting the cross-fertilization of ideas, underlain by the strategy that decision making does not concentrate in a few hands, but is a product of stakeholder participation from and by all forums. Clark (1986) describes the networking adjustments as involving 'adaptive generalizations' distinct from 'adaptive specialisations', therefore, ideally flexible enough to accommodate eventualities.

Writing on this subject, Olson (2006, para.9) describes shared governance as having two complementary meanings: one, giving various groups of people a share in key decision-making processes, often through elected representation; and, two, allowing certain groups to exercise primary responsibility for specific areas of decision making. To both faculty and administration it meant more than committee consensus, but ensuring the delicate balance between faculty and staff participation in planning and decision-making processes, on one hand, and administrative accountability on the other. Administration ought to accept the role of servant of collegial governance and the need to safeguard, support and encourage faculty. Reciprocally, faculty ought to exercise its teaching, research and scholarly responsibilities impeccably, in line with the administrative ideals. So, everyone has a role – hence ‘shared/corporate’ – with administration ultimately exercising overall oversight and accountability (Olson, para.11).

The shared corporate role is most important in scheduling the stakeholder complements of top academics, younger academics, established staff, and the student body. This means understanding the dynamics of each group and catering for it accordingly. In general, given their mobility, the top academics are strategically the most important followed by the younger academics or recent recruits and, lastly, established staff, the most stable. Salary, career progression and job security factors, on one hand, and opportunity to work on cutting-edge teaching and research, within state-of-the-art facilities with gifted colleagues, on the other, bear on staff mobility. The former is more critical among younger academics still starting up in life and the latter is more influential among top academics engrossed in serious business of teaching and research. Among the students, career paths and remuneration are the key drivers behind the decisions both *whether* and *where* to participate. To be competitive, the institution must be able to keep each group and, collectively, all groups focused, energetic, and in demand. In line with Olson (para.17), genuine shared/corporate “governance gives voice (but not ultimate authority) to concerns common to all constituencies and to issues unique to specific groups.”

Also very critical is the capacity to reflect proper trade-offs between correct conditions of service and appropriate physical and human inputs both institution- and market-wide. According to Hlabathi (2012), the conditions of service touch on employee morale through affording them open chances of involvement in decision making, treating them with dignity

and respect, and awarding full total rewards – cash remuneration, career opportunities, work-life balance, campus life and performance awards. The physical inputs relate to all aspects of the physical infrastructure and the human resource inputs to staff recruitment and student enrolment. The latter two must show the right energy levels, commitment and imagination, not only to teach and learn, but also to undertake and unravel the stubborn rigours of subject and management disciplines and emerge conscious competent and more competitive befitting the rigours of the technocapitalist market.

Furthermore, whatever the challenges, the governance ought to be gender sensitive and ensure gender equity across the spectrum which, for a variety of reasons, has never been easy to achieve, with countless challenges along the way. Female enrolment has always been disproportionate and, therefore, cause for concern. In a study on the retention of PhD women candidates, Rice (2012) found out that young women scientists leave academia in far greater numbers than men citing, as reasons, that the characteristics of academic careers were unappealing, that the impediments they would encounter were disproportionate, and that the sacrifices they would have to make were great. As a result only 12% of third year female PhD students wanted a career in academia. The worrisome scenario also prevails across the board with institutions eager to raise female ratios within their folds.

Last, more and better value-addition is the very basis of the evaluation footprint, expressing the magnitude of the charismatic values of 'strength, motivation and fit.' While the statements are silent on evaluation, the aspirational language implies that sooner or later some rigorous evaluations would be undertaken to ascertain the success or otherwise of the dreams, processes and practices. Therefore, evaluation is more discernible by its import and is much more forceful in the strategic plans and reports which include verifiable indicators like the scorecard, reviews, audits and accountability reports to promote a strong base-work ethic for a vibrant populace that is pragmatically robust and a perfect economic fit.

Although less apparent across the different sources of verification, institutional rankings are an important aspect of the evaluations to determine relationships, contacts and levels of reciprocal assistance, or the needed profitability and corresponding sustainable market share leading to both local and global renown. While the local rankings were favourable, it is critical to also rank among the top most institutions in the world which means at least below 500, if

not 200, lest the institution disappears in the higher education radar. This means that the rankings fundamentally converge on how to successfully inspire and engineer the footprints resulting in the acquisition of points for an award for an upgrade while failure means definite loss of points resulting in a downgrade.

5.4.2 Challenges

According to the Corporate Lifecycle model, it takes a little push for the institutions to go down 'The Fall' precipice, with both generic and external forces behind the slide into aging and decay. The high incidence of the N/A rating together with highlights from the interviews suggested the challenges have much to do with the bureaucracy or dynamics of power. A few are discussed here with further explanations under the specifiable deliverables.

While not openly declared so, at the centre of the melting pot are the two socially and ecologically challenging processes that are as close to each other as oil and water – civilizing capitalism for the people and civilizing the people for capitalism. It is general knowledge that capitalism is as good as it is ugly. Democracy, the rule of law, science and technology and a high standard of living are some of its most coveted indicators marking one end of the spectrum. Alienation, exploitation, stripping harvests, pollution, imperialism and other pathologies mark the other end of the spectrum. In between is the nice-rough terrain of opportunity, prosperity and benefits versus risks, threats, crises, poverty, vulnerability, fascism, radicalism, disadvantage, corruption and many other downgrade forces and processes that defy the might of police patrols and fire alarms in place. The challenge then is whether the institutions duly understand and have the capacity to consummately exploit and manoeuvre the technocapitalism so that the people exude its psych, failing which its destabilizing effects will continue to bedevil the national and institutional metrics, exposing both to incessant failures and attacks.

Informal conversations and tacit observations revealed that the criticism of lip-service was well founded. Although the leadership argued that it was fully committed to the letter and spirit of the statements, it was not so across the board. Both staff and students were either indifferent to, or they did not really know the vision statements, perchance a product of the proverbial familiarity breeds contempt! There were exclamations of surprise as to what was being talked about coupled with failure to recite the statements when requested to do so. As echoed in the post-fieldwork interviews, the tendency was to say 'we never thought of things

that way' and to casually dismiss the statements as the business of senior management, otherwise if it was what the leadership thought the community ought to believe and do, then, it was out of touch with the reality, which indicated strong lip-service. Hence, conditions were quite presumptuous with the core values failing to duplicate as the core workplace guidelines.

Also, taking centre stage was the dilemma of insufficient and ill-equipped personnel to run all the requisite units, coupled with financial challenges in the midst of bureaucratic complacency and inertia. Very much fraught was the need to strike the flexibility required to balance maximum participation with clear accountability to avert the downgrades of corruption and conflicts. While the governance methodology sought to solve the needed stability and balance, it had somehow become a victim of the administration gaining the upper hand, swinging the balance of power in the direction of excess control at the expense of flexibility. At the same time, values like patriotism meant that everybody must be psychosocially compliant which was not good for science where scepticism and controversy inject the necessary drive. According to Olson (2006, para.5), the challenge reduces the methodology to 'empty' or 'floating' signifiers devoid of definitive substance and import as each method takes on whatever significance a particular speaker gives it. As is always the case, once management is satisfied with the status quo and does not see the need for change, then, the symptoms of decline and aging begin to worm in which becomes a matter of time before the worst occurs as the deterioration consumes the system, only differing in the degree to which the aging problems pervade the status quo.

In addition, was mounting public dissatisfaction and concern with institutional inefficiency and ineffectiveness as a result of the mediocre product performance in higher order skill areas (the Education Review Commission, 1999), malfunctioning democratic spaces (UNESCO, 1997), and the gross socio-environmental inequities with respect to access to land, housing, income, utilities, equality, gender, disability and disadvantage (Dube, 2014; Gatawa, 1998; MoHTE, 2010; Nyathi, 2015). 'When will Africa's time come?' observes Sharara (2015) with respect to the endless socio-economic rot. Frequently checking its back and eager to protect its turf, the expertise is replete with false predictions of success where there are no sufficient grounds for it (William Easterly's *Tyranny of the Experts: Economists, Dictators, and the forgotten rights of the poor*). A refrain during the interviews was how clients were constantly told what they wanted to hear, or exactly how things 'will' be done, or 'cannot' be done, or

that they must be 'patient', only to plunge into further and deeper uncertainty and misery. Ngwenya (2016, p.B2) eloquently sums it as follows: "It is more conducive to stability to feed people illusions of unending economic growth and fairy tales of how they too can get rich. Exaggerating the positive achievements of society and seldom if ever mentioning its negative features is also the best means of attracting foreign investment." The new reality is such that agnotologism has assumed the upper hand. As defined, the culturally constructed ignorance, purposefully created by special groups working hard to obfuscate the facts and create confusion as well as suppress the truth in favour of themselves, has become the standard.

On this subject, Thaler (2009, p.133-4) cautions against the vision-mission fetishism built on rational ignorance or decadent traditional biases and falsehoods associated with optimism or wishful thinking, overconfidence, the false consensus effect, and the knowledge curse syndrome which always override other considerations. Such tendencies include the incessant happening on falsehoods and propaganda spins that are always 'bolder than they should be'. Typical are claims that a 'bright future' awaits; that 'others are just like us and will agree with us'; that since we have 'all read and learned the same, what we have learned is permanent or it enables us to think the same' contrary evidence notwithstanding, leading to the unwillingness to think differently or to realise that what we know may be less obvious to others who are less informed than ourselves. But the inability to 'apply' crowns the fetishism of the self-assured paradigm, with the constituents doing what they have always done – listening and hoping in the midst of a rigid status quo.

As Clark (1986) argues, it is a well-known fact that 'stubborn persistence', as the arch-symbol of the status quo, is the arch-enemy of disconnect, diversity, innovation and change. The combination of representative bureaucracy and punishment-centred bureaucracy holds sway to consolidate the authority of the hierarchy. As the property of all stakeholders, whether imposed or not, the common rules and procedures must be observed and followed which calls for tight supervision. As a result, the status quo frequently resorts to vesting interests and granting monopoly positions which leaves the institutions stuck in the administrative gridlock, managing the logistics to do with the 'tried, tested and trusted' undertakings much of which involves incarnating outmoded routines, as punishment-centred bureaucracy assumes the upper hand. Any departure and deviation from the rulebook invites the reading of the riot act and arraignment before the disciplinary courts for violating the standard

operating procedures. Given such a position, the statements offer the same slack and inert therapy, confusing and complicating the already bedridden. Aware of the hurdle, one of the study institutions made it a point to 'eliminate' such drawdowns in its strategic plan.

The argument being put forward here is whether the construct is simply populist rhetoric than a pragmatic tool – so much hot air unable to lift the balloon. The question is: has it become a populist slogan that is a waste of precious resources? According to Morphew and Hartley (2006), all claims that it accurately depicts institutional reality and, therefore, genuine differences in aspirations, is highly controversial. If anything, the statements suffer the indignity of copiously “unexamined presuppositions” creating a bland reality. They are adopted as the gospel truth, a good thing, oblivious of their doctrinaire stance, clothed with threadbare anecdotal evidence (Education World, 2011). Both truths and myths about them predominate, with the emerging theoretical-practical contradictions conjuring the nemesis of a fatty diet rich in cholesterol. The seemingly perfect expedition keeps approaching a lighthouse that continues to recede in the distance, inviting criticisms of vapid assignments and disproportionate investments with far reaching implications the anticipated technological society-sustainable development dividend.

5.5 Summary

Graphs, tables and matrices were used to present the data findings triangulated by method of verification, by footprint. Document sources portrayed the construct E/W but facing immense challenges; the stakeholder questionnaire was unequivocally N/A; while the interviews were equivocally N/A-F/C. Both formal rationality and substantive rationality indicators characterise the findings and results, reflecting the construct's dynamics to support and functionalise the bureaus to realise their mandates. However, numerous forces and factors spoil the engineering, increasing chances of systemic failure to work in concert. An unusual conclusion would be to describe the construct close to a Heath Robinson contrivance, absurdly ingenious and impracticable in terms of actualization, or to the spiritual trick associated with supernormal phenomena. The aspirationally market-consistent language is inordinately at odds with the stark reality of the bureaus. The next chapter examines the meta-themes or *specifiable deliverables* that emerged from the survey and, therefore, the intricacies surrounding the scope and tenure of the construct.

CHAPTER VI

6.0 SPECIFIABLE DELIVERABLES: OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES

6.0 Introduction

From the perspective of daily intercourse, the vision-mission-values statements are not talked about in terms of footprints or realisation factors. Rather, several routine indicators are used, details of which have been discussed earlier in this work. The collated data from the interviews and document review emerged with a ‘co-curriculum’ akin to Morphey and Hartley’s (2006) ‘elements’ or Opiyo-Newa’s ‘outcomes’ shown in Table 2.1. As summed up in Matrix 6.1, the institutions talk in meta-themes of ‘excellence; research-innovation-entrepreneurship; the leadership-committee system; moral efficiency; and sustainable development’ as the *nerve centre* of the construct. They coincide with the footprints, the only difference being that the building starts at the top rather than at the bottom. Last, sustainable development captures and sums up the vast demands of the constituency.

Matrix 6.1 Convergence meta-themes/specifiable deliverables

Sources of verification		Meta-themes / Special deliverables
Document sources	Interviews	
excellence, benchmark/propel operations, research, leadership, committees, innovation, service, entrepreneurship, honesty, integrity, teaching, councils and boards, programme growth, infrastructure development, teaching technologies, financial/ quality management systems, community engagement, student and staff welfare, generation, dissemination and application of knowledge, problem solving, advancement of humanity, audits, grading	excellence, world class, leadership, honesty, integrity, international best practices, entrepreneurship, research and development, identity, innovative capabilities/leadership, quality issues, stop mediocrity, good service delivery, improved academic performance, mainstreaming issues in the strategic plan, justice, awards, sustainable development, academic freedom, business units, functioning economy, consultants and committees of workers, recruitment of highly qualified staff	1. Excellence 2. Research-innovation-entrepreneurship 3. Leadership-committee system 4. Moral efficiency (soft skills of honesty, integrity, justice, identity, student centeredness etc.) 5. Sustainable development

(Source: Matrices 4.1 – 4.5)

Excellence lies at the top and, like a set of gears, reciprocally interconnects with and puts into motion the processes of research-innovation-entrepreneurship, the leadership-committee system and the moral efficiency all working towards the ultimate deliverable of sustainable development. The rest of the indicators constitute the letter and spirit of each and of all the five. Hence, they described high frequency across the footprints in the aggregation of the whole. On the other hand, both silence and dissonance themes operating undercurrent or incompatibly with the footprints did not materialise.

By all standards, the deliverables come into question as they serve as the core nuclei within the context and dynamics of the technological society, providing a compact multi-dimensional meaning and description of the construct. Reminiscent of the model footprints, singularly and together, and working like clockwork, they illuminate the organizational limelight to uncharted levels. Aspirationally, the institution can talk of having ecologically attained the “Prime’ stage market niche and other ideals in its pursuit of the HR infinite for sustainable development.

6.1 The Excellence deliverable

It is excellence, excellence everywhere, targeted as the most celebrated deliverable at the top of institutional endeavours. Taylor and Braddock, (2008, p.246) define it as an institution (especially a university) “at which teaching is of the highest order and the professors are successful researchers and genuine authorities—possibly world authorities—in their different fields.” While the definition may be misleading in the sense that it is biased towards top level professionals, it does presuppose a vibrant support base. As the interviews added, the institutional community was exceedingly passionate in its definition of excellence, reminiscing much of Figure 3.2 and partly duplicating the language of the University of Illinois although, rather than all-round, much of it was reflected in isolated successful events like graduation ceremonies, conferencing and regional training. It is the substantive equivalent of efficiency and is the watershed behind the total democratisation of the science. Hence, it induces a patriotic practical professionalism to meet the technological infinite or the high expectations of development excellence.

While not a necessary condition for excellence, world class, premier, leader, quality, fitness of/for purpose, international best practices and innovative capabilities are equivalent rhymes

or symptomatic labels. They are symptomatic in the sense that they indicate the institution's reputation and less the actual quality of its teaching, research and so on. The institutions use the fiery terms to flare up the 'blue chip' status in the culturing of the next generation of top class scientists and technologists who will make the next great scientific discoveries and inventions; who will impact research and its commercialization immensely; who will be leading personalities in business and politics; who will make Zimbabwe different and great; and who will keep the institutions world class and unique, enjoying the requisite competitive edge (Lewis, 2007). This is full stemitization or practical fulfilment of the singularity theorem – the technology-biology match and its pragmatic HR infinite. This is not to lose sight of the fact that countless renowned scientists with similarly high flying aspirations have departed the landscape, paradoxically, with *Homo simplex* expanding rather than abating.

The initiation dates back to the historical transplantation of the metropolitan establishments largely through the affiliate-associate status (for example, the University of Rhodesia (now UZ) with the Universities of London and Edinburgh). The young institutions had to measure up to the intellectual gold standard of the West, hence, "the Western university in Africa has remained Westernized, imperial and colonial in form and in content" (Mabhena, 2016b). In the process the spectre of localised adaptation necessary to be an integral part of the surrounding environment has been swept aside. Western cloning dominates the VAE measure and rankings, in some cases being a standalone, but invariably with respect to teaching, research, competitiveness, entrepreneurship and student-centeredness – which constitute the tradable profit-efficiency measurements.

World class and its equivalents cement the excellence by bringing in the idea of global belonging and participation by a prestigious ivory tower among other paragons of virtue, advancing *savoir faire* – the ability to act suitably and sustainably in any situation, and *savoir vivre* – knowledge of the world and the ways of society, including the ability to create and conduct business immaculately and sophisticatedly. This is reinforced by the notion of a special pivot, nucleus, source, or heart (centre, hub) of such priceless products, goods and services, culminating in the total symbol of academic sophistication.

The study has shown how, by its nature, excellence is a heavily loaded proposition that raises vision-mission stakes to a credible zenith, while to the less informed it may be as clear as

mud. This is because all processes and practices impact excellence however intangibly and invidiously. As spelt out before, several indicators were isolated to gauge perceptions of the excellence. Figure 6.1's jagged spectrum shows the levels of positive feedback being experienced, with some indicators more functional/commendable (F/C) than they are normal/adequate (N/A) or inadequate/substandard (I/S) and, therefore, highly weak and cause for concern, producing an average mean rating of 2.3 (out of a possible maximum of 4.0) and a standard deviation of 0.74, indicating a significant pull towards I/S, while E/W as the targeted excellence was a pale shadow of itself. Both the physical and academic infrastructures together with technology transfers were strong candidates for cause for concern.

Figure 6.1 Participant perceptions of excellence (Source: Table 5.3)

Epistemologically, supporting the excellence is the philosophy of evidentialism in terms of adequate justification for all knowledge and beliefs at a specific time provided the evidence supports believing such knowledge and beliefs. According to Fieser and Dowden (2015), evidentialism is the basis of separating fact from fancy or to justify denying sceptical claims, myths and falsehoods. From the science and technology perspective, the evidence is what confirms or refutes the models of excellence, constituting sufficient grounds for rationally deciding between the competing dimensions of the philosophy.

Therefore, inter-subjective credibility on the sources, structures, potential impact and limits of the knowledge and belief systems is the cornerstone for understanding the philosophy. This gives the system sufficient reason to interrogate the multiple *epistemic* dimensions, values and beliefs against the backdrop of the core of belief, disbelief and suspension of judgment and how excellence has come to dominate the psychosocial discourse. In short, as the philosophy fusing excellence in the vision-mission statements, evidentialism is an indispensable vaccine for comprehending the ideals of QA, details of which lie outside the scope of the study.

Thus, spurred by global precedents, the robust visions-missions galvanise the ‘academic-productivity-humanitarian’ interface to infinite frontiers, buoying operations into overdrive, while also optimally transforming the status quo. Notionally, the flamboyance stimulates perception of the most highly crowned, state-of-the-art institutions, adjectively: meritorious, exceptional, superior, savantic, and professional, enjoying high class reputations for their products, goods and services when compared and contrasted with any other. This is how the NUST Vice-Chancellor put it at the 2013 graduation ceremony: ‘A degree is the beginning of bigger and better things to come, go out and shine and remember you are a NUST family member, so think in several boxes simultaneously.’ Marketers will say, with excellence, the customer or client, and not the product, openly and willingly comes back for more which is the full essence of robotic efficiency.

The totality of the excellence means an admirably refreshing, pleasurable and exciting environment that ensures learners, administrators, teachers, facilitators, the workforce and the constituency community minimum disruptions and, in return, unparalleled performance with very high investment yields. The HIT (2011, p.1) hits the nail on the head in proclaiming its aspiration as to “enhance the institution’s brand to levels where everyone wants to be associated with it”: an institution of first ‘choice’ across the entire higher education fraternity, although fulfilling this dream is another matter altogether. The question is, does the market know what to choose; is the excellence viably evident? Meanwhile, the institutions continue to scoop top prizes for excellence like the PMR.Award which the NUST has won several times in succession.

6.1.1 Challenges

It is against this background that any discourse on excellence must be understood, and consequently, that it can never be complete, except 'to travel hopefully but never to arrive' (Morley, 2003). Given the diversity among the institutional players, contradictions ensue, generating challenges of all sorts. First, with an N/A rating of 2.3, quality assurance and, therefore, excellence, was the lowest rated footprint, evidently, with a powerful pull towards I/S. As already mentioned, 50% of the participants judged half the indicators I/S-N/A, and at best F/C. The exceptional extremes, ironically, included the quality of the physical and academic infrastructures and technological transfers which were overwhelmingly I/S-N/A versus the quality of teaching/service delivery which was rated F/C by 62% of the participants – a position to be expected.

Also, rated N/A at 2.4 was the evaluation footprint. Except for the future of the institution which was rated F/C (3.3), the rest of the indicators were rated N/A. Meanwhile, the document sources and interviews weighed in with more doubts and misgivings: the weak funding, limited internet and information services, uncompleted buildings and rudimentarily equipped labs; little monitoring and evaluation with the construct amounting to another document on the shelf; excessive subjectivity in the implementation of policies and procedures; short-term relevance; and lack of constant reviews in line with rapid changes. The perceptions and comments conjure the fly-on-the-wall dilemma and, therefore, much harder excellence's role to meritoriously nourish the divergent system-wide operations.

The dominance of the I/S-N/A ratings and related comments pointed towards stakeholder dissatisfaction with the excellence which is lower than the targeted world class standard. In spite of more visibility through the vision statements, excellence continues to elude the institutions and the nation, and the question is why? In short, in spite of the configurations, as Lewis (2007) argues, by inference, the romanticism with excellence is a prerogative that amounts to a chronic obsession. Petty (2006, p.357) would argue the extensive existence of the notorious "5Ds: denial – not that bad after all; displacement – it is someone else's fault; deference – only management can do it; despair – nothing can be done about it; and, destiny – it is all a matter of social class, genes, luck, IQ, etc." So tenuous is the deliverable, like an *ipse dixit*, it effectively derives strength from the authority of those pronouncing it.

The curtain breaks with the science and technology education *per se*, the feeder dam for the broader science and technology curriculum. Two of the study institutions had faculties of science and technology education. In one case, the programmes comprised the traditional STEM education – physics, chemistry, biology, mathematics, technology, geography and agriculture education. In the other, the curriculum comprised applied biology, applied chemistry, applied physics, applied maths, computer science, clothing textiles and fashion design, electrical and electronic engineering and mechanical and automotive engineering and several more. Epistemologically, the content has diversified following the introduction of unique modules in the applied range – micro-biology, molecular genetics, reactor technology, research in clothing, textiles and fashion, discrete mathematics, industrial instrumentation and control, microprocessors and embedded systems, plant-form and function, nuclear physics – the list goes on, to enhance the ‘technical’ effectiveness of the education mandate for both school and tertiary education graduates.

As always, the underlying challenge has been the strength of the products in terms of teacher preparedness vis-à-vis events in the school system, with the two presumably complementary so that the products are well groomed for either the teaching or the learning ahead of them. The teacher education faces serious enrolment and preparation challenges such that both approaches are strained to close the STEM gaps. The reward system in particular favours the non-teaching professions impacting enrolment to the lowly qualifying candidates who cannot find vacancies in other fields. Meanwhile, the weak infrastructure conditions of poor laboratories and training personnel add to the predicament, which makes it hard for science teaching to uplift the science and technology conditions within the school system.

The next challenge was getting the applied physics and applied mathematics more relevant and applicable at the school level. However, the recent development to drop the ‘applied’ has put paid to this, which means the science will continue to lack direct, practical applicability at the school constituency level. The argument is that the ‘applied’ does not work inside the classroom. As document sources indicated, the curricula were less about science for innovation and change (not even science fiction writing), but for more knowledge, ushering the dilemma of banking education (a position confirmed by the 200 slides lessons – evidently, the traditional textbook, content-centred and topic-oriented approach rather than process skills related to decision making and problem solving). Hence, lacking adiabatic

innovativeness, the curriculum structure and delivery have remained inflexible against a more practicable science curriculum to uplift livelihoods.

Therefore, rather than enhance STEM education or capacity for physics, biology, chemistry or general science education, in the words of the BUSE, there is broader scope for specialist 'researchers, consultants and extensionists' rather than educators – a misnomer since science education is the mandate of the institution. Indeed, its absence in the BUSE's vision statements means the science education is an ailing specie! The institution has lost out on its very mandate. In the process, the vicious cycle of the STEM gaps is perpetuated leading to weak future intakes, while the science academia products soon find themselves wading in the *Homo simplex* market. Only recently has reform to a practice-based science curriculum (Gatawa, 1998; Ministry of Education, Sports and Culture, 2015; the Education Review Commission, 1999) been heeded although largely reflecting the trappings of the status quo (the massive number of subjects) rather than genuine science education reform, driven by the practicality of, for example, a 'mathematics, energy and agriculture' curriculum for the generality of the populace.

Technically, in contradiction to the F/C rating of the 'quality of teaching/service delivery', the malfunctioning 'dual' experience has proved the gravest challenge in the face of constituency dissatisfaction and concern with the practical capabilities of the products to tackle the harmful technological dependence, macroeconomic instability/volatility, weak aggregate demand, massive unemployment and the rife corruption-ignorance index. There were many explanations to the challenge. At the practical level was the high level of disconnect hamstrung by insufficient funding, non-completed infrastructure projects, and shortage of teaching space and of high calibre personnel and facilitators in many disciplines. Frequent power outages, dysfunctional communications, examination fiascos, and other fiscal and supervisory shortcomings (pay-outs, staff-student rights, security, slack appraisal and other measurement methodologies) imploded the scene with negative prospects the excellence. Whereas the F/C rating of library and IT services was worth noting, resource constraints, coupled with inadequate and intermittent internet and web facilities limited delivery in terms of e-books and most current textbooks – with editions and versions from the 1980s still on the shelves and part of the teaching notes.

Furthermore, during interviews participants lamented the excessive textuality for examination purposes at the expense of praxis education. As they put it, ‘there is too much teaching, teaching and coaching...; we do not teach them how to make a computer, but how to use it’ – a not so unusual condition with STEM education remaining fixated on subjects at the expense of application skills. Also, explaining I/S rating of ‘technological transfers’, Phuthi and Sibanda (2011) lament the asymmetrical theory-practice relationship as posing the biggest challenge in effecting a high-impact dual experience, or artisanal scholarship, which remains a distant reality. There was hardly much coherence between the two when the reality is that one should be the practical demonstration of the theory.

In addition, ‘too much duplication of curricula’ was the norm, for example, between disciplines like applied chemistry versus chemical engineering, operations research versus applied mathematics, and applied physics versus engineering physics/industrial manufacturing which are treated as separate units when, for all intents and purposes, they are only marginally different – luxury developments difficult to justify in a developing economy. The graduates proceed to endure professional slack from exposure to demand deficient unemployment – engineers in informal and high school teaching jobs.

Basically, the banking education swamps the science and technology education in ritualistic teaching dominated by the theoretical foundations of symbolic interactionism with its emphasis on fixed facts. Not only is the bulk of the theory not found in the outside world where practice prevails, practical learning is reduced to a rare event creating the vicious cycle of disvalue education (Mnkandla, 2006). The products exude the Keynesian-Maslow poison chalice that distorts the self–community conceptualisation (Ngwenya, 2016). The expensive losses, exacerbated by the scarcity of resources, lead to some curricula being short-changed. The end result is ‘routine maintenance’ skills typical of service *providers* than *builders* in the midst of colonially inherited prodigious consumption (Nyathi, 2014).

An additional silent dilemma gleaned from some of the researches the study perused is the inherent Western corruption of reflexivity and textuality and the extent these de-contextualise local researches. Problematic are the adopted writing strategies which, in the interest of rigour and objectivity, favour the *academic realist text* and its corollary, the *readerly text*, to convey the research messages to readers at the expense of other textual modes. According

to Scott (2000, p.60), the argument is that the text “can in an uncomplicated way directly refer to the reality which their authors are seeking to describe” since language is a universal, transparent medium for describing and representing reality – a condition that is not always borne out by facts and much worse with second language speakers. He cites policy statements (like the vision-mission statements) as typical examples of this argument always meant to condition the reader or receiver to ‘unproblematically’ do as the text says they should, which then nullifies alternative interpretations rendering the research text opaque, prescriptive and unrealistic given the concealed nature of the produced account. Hence, treated as unnecessary and problematic, the reflexivity and textuality proceed to interfere with the practical scope and potential for commercialisation of the creations and innovations.

The evidence of the massive resource wastes is the wounded science and technology curriculum: dynamically and generatively inept and inert and atypically creative, inventive and of limited worth to the local scapes. The dilemma of the unsteady dual experience is not only maligned to the conundrum of technology-less science, the pragmatically low-tech scientists lack critical lab cultures and experiences for practical commercialisation of products. The statements are unravelling. Claims of ‘knowledge hub’ or ‘new knowledge’ generation are not borne out by facts, with gaps among the different disciplinary websites, coupled with aversion to e-learning platforms pointing towards external knowledge dominating the course delivery. In the end, it is endless disappointment from the science-vision rhetoric mismatch.

Largely, being reflected here are the mediocre performances in higher order skill areas necessary to vitalise technological dynamism and high-tech operations. As figures 3.1 and 3.2 showed, the Masters qualification, coupled with the limited experience of the bulk of the personnel means more Improvers and Providers than Thinkers and Builders. The total import is a stressed construct unable to pragmatically integrate theory with practice or ideology with reality producing individuals whose education borders on disvalue education (Chiwome and Gambahaya, 1998; Gatawa, 1998; Mavhunga, et al. 2009; Phuthi and Sibanda, 2011; Zim-Asset, 2013;). The conventional pedagogy of the knowledge explosion results in more deculturation and the acquisition of impertinent skills and values for local dispensations.

This brings in the debate whether universities are the correct vehicle to impart the enduring ‘hard artisanship skills’ that obtain in trade schools. Or, they should remain more open,

specialising in grooming the 'malleability' of their products to be multitalented, coachable and flexible: amenable to broader understanding of the forces at work, including the capacity to generate solutions to complex problems. The strength of the first argument is that the job market demands the hard skills which, coupled with the expenses involved, demand that the products are adequately and effectively productive from the word go. There is no prize to continue off-loading cloned derelicts or 'technically incompetent' graduates who supposedly will learn with time (Mabhena, 2016a; Nyathi, 2014). On the other hand, while the trade school approach will kill product malleability and, with it, research and knowledge generation vital for science and technology to prosper, it will expand horizontal social mobility and sustainable development. Undoubtedly, decision makers have to contend with the tenuous scenario made more complex by the plethora of foreseen and unforeseen internal and external pressures.

Meanwhile, there were no standard requirements on the workforce (new or old) for special skills that match the envisioned excellence. As participants put it, 'even new employees must be vetted in terms of their capacity to meet the vision-mission'. Otherwise, the employment is open to anyone with qualifications, however attained. Therefore, rather than motivate the employees, the statements invite cynicism since the bulk of the staff is vague about, and neither knows nor fully understands the substance and import of the excellence. Unsurprisingly, the disorientations leave the deliverable dazed, guided by the business-as-usual norm with events simply normal/adequate. No wonder, sooner rather than later, only 'lip-service' is paid to the statements, or, as Education World would argue, they become one more good intention pushed to the background.

The genesis of the problem can be found in the wholesale transplantation of the metropolitan institution which created higher education institutions that are more exotic than endogenous to their scapes. Clark (1986, p.231) observes how, ever since its inception, the African university has strived to remain high quality and high cost: aloof from the rest of the education system with highly pronounced social cleavages which uproot the students from their social backgrounds, conditioning them to Western salaries and a wealthy alien lifestyle. Research commands supremacy in the judgment of scholars, with guarded emphasis on the quality of their contribution to immediate community needs (although strenuous efforts are being made to address this). Furthermore, curricula persistently duplicate metropolitan models so closely

that, for example, right at foundation, the University of Ibadan, Nigeria, quickly developed a department of classics, while it took up to eight years to establish the department of education and more than ten years later, it still had no courses in engineering, economics, law, geology, public administration and Arabic. The copy-write has persisted.

In addition is the obsession with grading *per se*. As part of the Western package where it is reeling under intense criticism and scepticism, lack of consensus on the real purpose of grading affects the standards to be followed. The main challenge is the murky distinction between genuine versus inflated grades or soft grading, with the latter often the case to sustain public images. Together with the semesterization, the two foster banking education or learning for reproduction in examinations to achieve much more attractive grades for employment purposes, while the lessons *per se* are scarcely inter-institutionally marketable. Typically, performance is measured on the percentage grades of what the learner can remember of what other people have done or produced – a process akin to personal cloning by the teachers using routine and old methods and techniques to train their charges to work on and solve the same problems from decades back.

As the participants put it, 'programmes are still empirical with very little practical work. They end at providing basic knowledge at the expense of applications which will make them unique, especially technological information that changes the applications.' In 2003 an industrial manufacturing lecturer at the NUST remarked that he always told his students that twenty years down the road they would be recommending to their company directors technology made by their cohorts in industrial countries. This would be at a time when global developments would have brought about highly advanced changes in high-tech further complicating the conversion disability gap – developments live this prophecy.

This is why Lewis (2007) describes grading as more of an external credential that distracts rather than support learning. Claims that it has as its educational purpose the capacity to motivate students to learn more and to reward them if they do so, remain fraught. Elaborating further, he observes that, if anything, grading promotes the culture of technical rules and adjudications in place of educational values and judgements. As the discussion further illustrates, under pressure from both students and the public, and in fear of embarrassment, the institutions adopt contrary policies to ward off the damaging criticisms against their

avowed values to guide students to find direction and meaning in their lives and a sense of their place in society. To Lewis (p.257) the institutions equate to a “‘retail store’ in which orders are taken, defects papered over to get the merchandise out the exit door” – an admirably dubious outcome.

So, too, is the obsession with rankings so much that these have become an end in themselves, keenly sought for the sake of position and prestige. This is regardless of the fact that subjectivity more than objectivity characterises the methods of measurement. For instance, rankings by experts and the use of surveys are very subjective and, therefore, open to manipulation, bias or human error. According to Taylor and Braddock (2008), the criteria of Nobel winners and Field medallists, while clearly measuring excellence, appear to address the ability of the institutions to attract prestigious awardees rather than being the site where ground breaking work is performed. Hence, they can only rank a few institutions since, typical of a large number of developing country institutions, they do not have such awardees, unless the award is based on the area or field of operation and not the original institution which, even then, would more likely still come from the advanced institutions of the North.

Meanwhile, the larger institutions have more papers, citations, awards winning scientists, international students and much more all of which boost their rankings at the expense of the smaller institutions, while the enrolment of international students is a reflection of their wealth and, therefore, capacity to pay as their fees are usually higher. Also, in the interest of funding, the institutions are persuaded to maximise the paying customer tag, hence, applying less the rigour of their professional expertise for the sake of business.

Therefore, largely guesstimations given the likely prejudices, loyalties and other positive and negative gestures arising from personal experiences that come into play influencing the results, at best the rankings reflect the dilemma of copy-write. Consequently, subject to the distortions, the data are crude and unreliable symptoms rather than actualities, with the excellence debatably compromised and reduced to an overly misinformative marginal yardstick of measure (Loannidis, et al. 2007; Taylor and Braddock, 2008).

Meanwhile, sameness rather than differentiation is expanding its roots, with differences only existing in names, locations and the eyes and feelings of the institutions themselves rather

than in the perceptions of the clients who, invariably, see the institutions offering the same Grail. Typically, the one-year attachment/internship prestige model (essentially to repeat and cement the technical routines) now holds complete sway leading to exposure to the vagaries of bureaucratic monopoly already weighing heavily on the system. The freedom to experiment, to be original, to venture into the unknown, and to mix, modify and branch out (in-keeping with the core values of new networking, complexity, complication and sophistication) is lost through the voluntary imitation of the established model as if it is the institutions' very *raison d'être* (Clark, 1986). Therefore, greater congruence encouraged by both government fiat and misplaced aspirations, in the face of requisite infrastructure challenges, has become the norm.

Closely related, internal conflicts mar the visions' academic and professional summers. The weak inter- and intra-faculty and departmental relations indicate limited complementarity with the system caused to rely on the downgrade processes of the rulebook to contain tensions and conflicts. Informal observations noted open and latent conflicts within faculties and between faculties and student affairs and between faculties and the bursary, with faculties often accusing the other two of lack of touch with the primary vision of the institution. As the examples cited illustrate, among themselves faculties either duplicate curricula or offer mismatching service courses the bulk of whose content is irrelevant, excess baggage to those affected. Also, through ignorance of classroom events and wrong expectations of what students must learn, it is not uncommon for student affairs and the bursary to fail to complement academia and vice versa. Often faculties have vague, inaccurate ideas about programmes and activities at student affairs. Labelling, stigmatization and the blame-game ensue with the departments 'stereotyped' in derogatory terms, for example, finance labelled as mean and squeamish, always torpedoing faculty operations, and student affairs as the misinformed appendage, only useful as a pseudo fire brigade.

Furthermore, another inherent challenge is how excellence does not always live up to its hype. Crossroads are characteristic. According to Van den Berghe (1998), corroborated by both document sources and interviews, as a result of the complex logistics and colossal costs involved that range between US\$1000 to US\$5000 per programme accredited and US\$2million for a quality agency, it is not surprising that QA processes fall into the doldrums. The institutions are barely able to upgrade that many inadequate programmes, more so to

sustain QA for distance education and e-learning, for the latter, with respect to challenges of static versus dynamic, continuous content. In addition, the excellence does not guarantee that the products will go and replicate the system wherever they land. As discussed before, many a graduate already falls short on the critical sustainable development skills: a practicable technocracy, affable comportment with adaptive normatives, and a powerful environmental management programme culminating in the proliferation of inefficiency and corruption dogging the institutions, ironically, manned by their own highly qualified personnel.

As critiqued in Chapter 2, the devil is in the detail surrounding the teaching and learning. The dominance of secondary and consumptive education as opposed to a more primary and discovery pedagogy leaves the technological society race very much challenged. Higher education is struggling to capture the core development fundamentals of engineering science (the science and technology of engines), extending to the failure to originate capital goods like machinery, plant and equipment, automobiles, industrial oils and chemicals critical in the technologies of metallurgy, mechanical, chemical and electronic engineering and more. Rather, the learning is largely restricted to adopting and adapting the assembly line or simple fabrication and processing methodologies of intermediate and consumer goods relying on imported technology. The myriad technical complexities of the tasks involved, coupled with the sophisticated mental and physical stamina or practical rigour required, militate against the heavy engineering trades in favour of light service industries like raw material extraction, software development, fast moving consumer goods, printing and publishing, and garment manufacturing – reminiscent of Parkinson’s Law of Triviality or bicycle-shedding. Hence, the former became a heavy casualty of the land/indigenization reform and will prove a tall order to resuscitate. Mabhena (2016b) would argue that the dilemma is symptomatic of systemic ‘surrender’ of hard thinking to Western hegemony.

Closely allied were the challenges of science-fright and skills-flight, coupled with the ever-rising cost of higher education amid declining job opportunities. Science-fright means that out of fear, the majority wilfully excluded itself from acquiring the very critical science and technology skills that encourage entrepreneurship, leading to the institutional cry of weak inputs from the school system. On the other hand, ostensibly to greener pastures, but in reality, to where the skills work, skills-flight (and very minimal skills-circulation) questions the strength of the professionalism or the relevance and usefulness of the science education

qualifications. Given the wounded dualism, it is naïve to expect any better. Last, the high education costs, amid declining per capita grants, render higher education anti-social, while the stormy working conditions of low salaries and wages promote weak morale in the workforce. The aura of volatile industrial action by students and staff signifies poor customer satisfaction which compromises the excellence. In between, under the guise of the obscure 'sustainable development' agenda is the silent decimation of the science and technology infrastructure, which has added its fair share of challenges.

Aggregated, as an intangible, the excellence is easier said than done. Little by little, the challenges widen the gap to full excellence, hence, painting the construct a heavier than light burden, way beyond the capabilities of mortals. The excellence is paraded at the expense of local realities, steering and transforming the landscape into a state of severe technological dependence against the backdrop of sometimes bitter rivalry between allegiances to the 'elite league' versus the needs of the state for universal suffrage. Not surprising, the disorientations reduce the vision statements to routine fads, merely resurrecting popular orthodoxy, in Shakespearean terms, 'full of sound and fury, but signifying nothing.' Given the magnitude of the problem, it would not be farfetched that quality standards should be made a compulsory course for all final years, while Staff training ensures that the members spell out in their own terms the essence of the excellence within the context of the curriculum endeavours.

6.2 The Research-Innovation-Entrepreneurship deliverable

The research-innovation-entrepreneurship deliverable is the heart of the excellence and, therefore, knowledge generation, new discoveries and novel ideas, artisanal frameworks, improvements and inventions to meet the multi-purpose goals and targets. The HIT best captures the inner essence of exponential technology, proclaiming itself "the stimulant of scholarship in innovation through cultivating commitment towards technopreneurial leadership and commercialising technology through professionalism rooted in integrity." Similarly, at the 2013 graduation ceremony, the NUST Vice-Chancellor remarked that 'research, innovation and entrepreneurship are the key to Zimbabwe's recovery and you are at the forefront of that as young people', precisely how the trio is *the* diplomatic passport to world class status, reputation and fame. Representing the various research units, the NUST Research and Innovation Office crowns the epistemology, declaring its vision 'to be a reputable centre of excellence in research and innovation for sustainable development.'

The document sources and interviews specified several indicators centred on knowledge-based society/solutions; intellectual property rights; skilled citizens; more development-oriented research and innovation; more doing or practicing science from labs or learning-by-doing rather than textbooks; enterprise development; and greater concentration on entrepreneurship. Figure 6. 2 shows results from the diversity survey which romped in with assessment of graduate competency levels, institutional competitiveness, entrepreneurship training, employment creation, science-technology outcomes, and transfers of technological innovations and inventions, and, therefore, whether the research creates synergies with industry and answers to its needs and problems. Together, the outcome was an average N/A rating of 2.5 and a standard deviation (SD) of 0.82, with the first two and the last indicators rated F/C (3.0) and I/S (1.9), respectively, while the rest were predominantly F/C. The much coveted E/W and, therefore, the most valid measure indicating a vibrant research-innovation-entrepreneurship culture, precisely what the institutions want, deserve and work by, was a pale shadow of itself, only marginally visible in the few indicators of constituency servicing, graduate competency levels, leadership status and institutional competitiveness where it recorded an average mean rating of 3.0.

Figure 6.2. The Research-innovation-entrepreneurship deliverable

Meanwhile, as shown in the matrices, the challenges from document sources and interviews were so eloquent, virtually standing the institutions on their heads, hence, indicating significant gaps on the status of the statements, which leaves the deliverable far from the excellence to build the El Dorado that is Zimbabwe. Simply put, the mandates are struggling and failing where it matters the most – market-oriented practical professionalism.

The research-innovation-entrepreneurship is pursued across numerous fronts. First, guided by the Research Council of Zimbabwe policy goals and the related National Research Priorities, research signifies the deployment of scientific methods to innovate and entrepreneur: to strengthen capacity development in science, technology and innovation (STI); to learn and utilise emergent technologies to accelerate development; to accelerate commercialization of research results; to search for scientific solutions to global environmental challenges; to mobilise resources and popularise science and technology; and to foster international collaboration in STI (Lemarchand and Schneegans, 2014, p.101). That being the case, continuously churned out are priority themes covering national capacity: on social sciences and humanities; on sustainable environmental and resource management (climate, energy, water, land, etc.); on promoting and maintaining good health; and on safeguarding the national security of Zimbabwe in line with the GSIF. Missing very noticeably are the engineering trades and other producers of capital goods and services – the very heart of technocapitalism and the technological society.

Most crucial, therefore, is the capacity of the researcher's incisive mind to innovate: that is, to simultaneously manipulate and convert matter and energy and data and information, under correct conditions and combinations, into entrepreneurial ideas or market products, goods and services, as well as rally efforts towards successful enterprise or business opportunity. As mentioned in Chapter 2, it is the appropriate combination of 'perpetual betterising' with either sustaining innovation, or with disruptive innovation, or with both varying with market situations and conditions. In short, either the incremental and/or radical change model is the ideal generation of the constructive innovation to better human welfare failing which, and inappropriately done, is real de-innovation – destructive and rigidifying the status quo.

Meanwhile, given the deepening decline in formal sector enterprises, entrepreneurship defined in terms of the 4Es and EIAA has become the prime slogan. In line with the Black Economic Empowerment laws (BEE), it not only means reversing colonial practices, but also to provide the miracle cures to economic growth and employment equity through local ownership of the means of production, skills development and other socioeconomic measures. By putting them at the top of their visions, the institutions correctly recognise the trio as the proverbial Siamese triplets that exist and achieve more together while struggling individually. The disturbing gap is their very elusive nature across the ambient macro and micro community markets.

The technopreneurial argument is basically that, alone, technology is incapable to generate the much-desired entrepreneurship and, therefore, employment. Equally, alone entrepreneurship is insufficient for the much-needed capital goods and hi-tech businesses and projects of the 21st Century with the capacity to grow the economy and ensure sufficient employment capacity. The technopreneurship combination is, thus, the right skills-building toolkit to produce 'stemitized' *Thinkers, Builders, Improvers and Providers* rich in demonstrable *psycho-technics* to secure a prospectively interactive continuity between the scientific-technological with the productive-business worlds for better rates of return: hence, technocapitalism for life.

That being the case, strategically, in its best form the research and innovation must be capable to reduce the most abundant materials like soil-rock-mineral matter and animal-plant cellulose and fibre into numerous products mainly foodstuffs and different material ware as well as harness renewable energy resources and convert fluids like air and water into chemicals, fuels and oils to sustain national demand. Therefore, sustained practical professionalism strong in product development, coupled with ICT and market intelligence, including teacher capacity to teach in and for a technological society, must configure the research calculus (BUSE, 2013). Thus far, the limited capacity to innovate, in particular to convert the knowledge into concrete products and services, places a high premium on high value research, innovation and entrepreneurship to meet demand for commonplace and novel applications in sync with a growing technological society.

Second, the STI push has seen the establishment of research and innovation offices, centres or faculty units and science parks curricula-wide, networked and working in collaboration with local and world organizations like the Computer Society of Zimbabwe, technical and vocational education and training institutions, the SIRDC and its affiliate Institutes, the Confederation of Zimbabwe industries, extending to international governance networks like the OECD and the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO) and its affiliates – the African Regional Intellectual Property Organization (ARIPO), the Zimbabwe Intellectual Property Office (ZIPO), and institutional Technology and Innovation Support Centres (TISCs) to cite a few examples.

Alongside are MoUs/A, partnerships and collaborations maintained with world universities, technology institutes, and research organizations for quality assurance, including safe end-user consumption. The delivered research is measured in volumes of inventions and research presentations and citations in various forums, more so refereed and open source journals like *Science* and *Nature*, *Scopus* and the Zimbabwe Journal of Science and Technology (ZJST). The HEEACT, the High Impact Universities: RPI, the AHEEA, and the G-factor (Google search engine based-data) are among the leading exponents of research productivity, impact and excellence. They promote, *inter alia*, research and development, commercialization, production and manufacturing, and science and technology pedagogy, on one hand, and maximization of entrepreneurialism through development, incubation/ start-ups and transfer of results and products. The ultimate objective, as the HIT (2015, p.4) observes, is to “create a culture where students and staff are both scholars and technopreneurs”, hence, “give the nation meaning and ability to build futures which for now cannot be imagined” (HIT, 2011, pp.2–3) – a new world order never seen before.

Naturally, entrepreneurship schemes and measures continue to emerge. Examples include programmes and projects like the BUSE and NUST’s BOOST ENACTUS (to mean Building Opportunities on Student Talent and Students in Free Enterprise projects) run by the Technopark business unit; the NUST memorandum of understanding on radiography with the Parirenyatwa Group of Hospitals and STEM education with polytechnic and secondary school teachers’ colleges; the BUSE’s farm, university press, and partnerships with the Grain Marketing Board, Exhort and Pannar (the latter for the growing of special crops); the HIT’s Capstone Design projects and the Centres of Excellence: the Technology Centre, the

Technopreneurship Development Centre, the Technology Education Centre, the Environment Management, Renewable Energy and Climate Change Research Centre, and the Institech Holdings for partnerships with the Dairy Marketing Board, Energy Resources and Varitech (Pvt) Ltd.

In addition are the state's Graduate Entrepreneurship and Employment Programme (GEEP) to promote school leaver-teams mainly artisans, agriculturalists, engineers and accounting and banking graduates through state-loans seeded projects, coupled with the Tech@school programme – a technology-business forum targeting appropriate selections of relevant subjects for university entry, the school upgrade programmes, constituency engagements or participation in community and national committees, and community health awareness campaigns on HIV and AIDS and other disease disorders. Overall, the schemes are meant to expose and enhance student proficiency to translate scientific concepts into commercializable innovation, entrepreneurship and other creative outputs, while simultaneously augmenting institutional finances. As they put it, the transformative agenda is geared towards renewed investment in ideas and people, summed up in graduate capacity to stand their own in industrial, commercial and informal sector markets.

Pivotal to, and lying at the forefront of, the innovation are research fields like materials technology, design research, service design and market research the backbone to technocapitalist corporatism, to leverage the supply-demand relationships to ultimately ensure real equity in the provision and delivery of products, goods and services, free of downgrade factors and processes: through experimental design and development of products, services, and programs – materials technology and design research; through multi-disciplinary creation of more useful, effective, and efficient services – service design; and through optimizing financial value from market and consumer leverage points – market research. Given the Schumpeterian effect that ideas and models do expire when they reach the end of their entrepreneurial lifespan and when this happens, the socio-economic systems are left at the mercy of 'creative destroyers', often external agents (or looters) and proxy businesses, the research fields continue to plug such gaps.

Hence, through the Medici Effect the research exploits cross-cultural diversity to generate practicable solutions from the diverse experiences, ideas and entities; through cynectics, it

brings together experts from various backgrounds to generate technical solutions; through abductive reasoning, it pools lay ideas and concepts and vets them for their commercial value; through digital technology, it engineers and rebrands models of new and old products, goods and services; and through predictive analytics (Big Data), as Hesseldahl (2013) observes, it defines the actionable intelligence embedded within the vast troves of data that businesses and governments gather which, when subjected to analysis, can be useful to forecast future probabilities with an acceptable level of reliability and efficiency for application by different units in the *econogram*. As the basis of the stemitization, there is vast potential in the last two methods simply awaiting further initiatives and product and service diffusion.

Briefly, reduced, the generated utility value comprises, *inter alia*, solar dryers for farm produce, egg and fruit incubators, moringa products, tobacco grading technology, vermiculture technology for waste management, use of activated carbon granules in gold extraction, sanitary pads, solar power plants, the biochar stove, solar-powered robot technology (for railroad crossings), synthesis of silica gels, a DNA testing service, a farm humidity-pH sensor, an expandable bending machine for the construction industry, the optical coherence tomography (OCT) surface imaging system to name a few, extending to information technology and myriad incubation platforms, accelerators, kick-starters, new prototypes, tech-hubs, applications and inventions for patenting. The massive outpouring of creative ideas across disciplines sustains. In the words of Lee (2012), the significance of the 'generated utility value is developing better ways for people to access the services they need from the most mundane (like commuting to work or SME vending stalls) to the most life-altering (like accessing quality healthcare and international jobs)' in the most economical and efficient way practicable. By expanding human needs, the deliverable's throughput constitutes the *bona fide* base for inventions and new solutions guaranteeing the exciting technological breakthroughs that enhance institutional renown espoused in and by the vision-mission statements.

In comparison to the incredible leap forward through the GRIN technologies, the local innovations essentially amount to appropriate technology. Measured against the Ford assembly plant, industrial farming, and 3D (additive) manufacturing, quadcopters, drone technology, brain stimulating devices, the Drinkable Book (for water purification) and developments in medical physics and genetics, they amount to no more than mere

replications, leaving the Technopark a pale shadow of the intended business hub. The 2015 Research and Intellectual Outputs: Science, Engineering and Technology Expo (RIO-SET) revealed the magnitude of the adoptive and adaptive configurations among the bulk of the technologies and innovations on display. It can be argued, though, that this is a normal development in science and technology, since there is really nothing new, but diversity in discoveries and improvements on what already exists. What is needed is full mastery of the psycho-technics entailed in the bio-physical properties of the materials or in engineering, information, marketing and environmental technology. As ideas, the technologies represent a potentially significant starting point in line with the STEM drive!

On the main, the products are significantly secondary than primary inventions and innovations which indicates the nascent tendency to substitute, modify, recreate, remodel, readjust and repackage rather than clear-cut breakthroughs into uncharted high capacity high-tech domains. Their field frequency to meet the jobs-to-do criteria resembles a meteorite in the dark sky, the challenges of venture capital notwithstanding. The peak–trough of disillusionment see-saw is typically characteristic, while the high school boosts flavour the diversity of operations rather than deep curricula integration. With events more third rather than world class, the landscapes are prone to domination by foreign technology to the most basic levels, sustaining the dictum of developing countries producing what they do not consume and consuming what they do not produce.

Global experiences reveal a complex research-innovation-entrepreneurship interplay. Writing about company executives in Forbes Magazine, Sniderman (2012) concluded that broad-based high technology innovation is much more than an individual piece of art. Rather, it is a combination of several categories of expertise comprising ‘Movers and Shakers, Experimenters, Star Executives, Controllers, and Hangers-on’ in that order. He defines the Movers and Shakers as the highly passionate leaders, always up-front, wielding influence and pushing on others to get things done driven by the desire to create a legacy. The Experimenters, on the other hand, are the persistent perfectionists and workaholics open to all new things, highly dedicated to duty and always eager to push through an idea or initiative. The Star Executives are the brilliant, all-round managers, virtually good at everything, seeking out and cultivating the right mentors, identifying colleagues’ best talents and putting them on their best use. The Controllers are the more insular executives who like to focus on

concrete, clear-cut objectives more inclined to greater control of everything around them. Last, the Hangers-on executives bring everyone back to earth by tethering them on the actual reality, reminding all of process limitations.

Sniderman notes that there is no special, purest entrepreneurial group, but that all are critical parts of the puzzle: Movers and Shakers to inject the necessary drive; Experimenters, the vision and energy to implement; Star managers, the leadership and strategy forward; Controllers, the execution; and Hangers-on, synergy and reality, variably in sympathy with the age and size of the organization. While the much younger organizations will need more Movers and Shakers, the matured will do with all the categories of innovators. Like a piece of drama, it is crucial to have the whole cast of characters on board to bring an innovative idea to successful fruition. From this perspective, innovation is scarcely a singular function as it needs the input and support of many expert variables to succeed and impact the technological culture. This is how technocapitalism works with respect to the character mix of researchers and innovators for entrepreneurial practice.

The colossal constituency drawbacks are the result of limited research, innovation and entrepreneurship, creating societies that are more consumptive than productive; that are more dependent than creative; and that remain perplexed by the inner spirit of science and technology in this day and age. The indicators of commitment, strategic partnerships, teamwork, dynamism, intellectual freedom, technical skills and professionalism echo quite succinctly the thinking to propel the research, innovation and entrepreneurship to foster the stemitized culture of creative problem solving. A deep technocapitalist culture involving intensive skills mixtures is what comes into focus to harness opportunities and ventures while stemming gross challenges.

Historically, notwithstanding the meagre national investment of about 1%, institutional research has contributed immensely to propel vibrant socio-economic activity. According to document sources, there was a total output of 197 science and technology research papers in 2013 alone, funded from local and international investment grants totalling about \$1million, representing 0.6% of the total institutional expenditures. This was commendable output which, very often, as a result of insufficient funding, goes uncommercialized or is transferred elsewhere only for it to come back as (expensive) useful products or services. As the HIT

puts it, developments rest on the 'seeding' in terms of the capacity building being undertaken with success realisable when patents (or IPs) begin to roll out. Also, the introduction of 'Open Access' in the institutional library repositories has enhanced public science communication and, therefore, the visibility and affordability of the researches to improve their usefulness and harness their potential for socio-economic impact. However, as noted above, Scott (2000) has a point in arguing that issues of reflexivity and textuality demand that other textual modes like the *confessional* and *writerly texts* be incorporated if the researches are to assist readers make more useful judgments on the functionality of the constructed accounts.

6.2.1 Challenges

Olivier's (2010) critique cited on page 9 sums up the dilemma confronting the research-innovation-entrepreneurship deliverable. As evidence is the dominance of challenges of outdated/obsolete equipment; excessive duplication of curricula; small IT bandwidths; limited new machine supplies; inadequate physical infrastructures; too much 'lip service', hence, limited actual deliverables (publications, patents, etc.) universities are judged by; too much teaching and coaching on how to use than to make a computer or highly empirical programmes with very little practical work summed up in the N/A ratings across the bulk of the indicators. It is hard for the deliverable to firm strong roots under proxy capitalism outside the Rostow model stage of mass consumption. Powerful forces rightfully and wrongfully induce open and latent diminishing returns, hence, subjecting the elite function to misinterpretation and pejorative criticism.

Powering the intrigue is a curriculum that is epistemologically not only 'international in focus, but is continuously kept in tandem with changes in the global environment' (the HIT, 2011, p.4). To Mabhena (2016), this is confirmation of the dilemma of the 'Western university in Africa'. While making it easy to benchmark with global institutions, the prime challenge is the level of freedom from or subservience to the powerful institutions, resulting in limited control and mere followership of global curricula trends, a condition that blunts and distorts the deliverable. In a nutshell, the dilemma of content and context simply traps the research in the anachronisms of adoption and adaptation of foreign technologies (mostly, what has been done) at the expense of local design and service for a quasi-cybermarket. Hence, to fit the test mark, the research must pass the international test first before it can be accredited locally, which translates into American technology being the most suited to the Zimbabwean institutions and scarcely for, about, and by themselves.

Consequently, the distinction between necessary and unnecessary research becomes blurred – for example, products research versus rocket science, astrophysics or weapons research, with products research further facing the dilemma of idle capacity. Typical of this dilemma is agricultural equipment given the physical reality of small pieces of land among the smallholder farmers, the potential market. It is vital that market research develops new strategies relevant to all parties. Equally, with the advent of open access, corporatism's invasive pathologies have entered academia. Superficial writings and critiques reflecting vested interests, secrecy and topic-based biases and prejudices have become the norm. To echo Lewis (2007, p.9), it is not an overstatement that inflating numbers of publications with junk science has become easy. As he observes, the pressures for quick, rapid publications “make academic writing duller, less adventurous, and more technical, since junior faculty members opt to write what they know to be acceptable to the journals and academic presses”, linearly, “leading to the production of much more nonsense.” Academic litter peddling quasi-plagiarised parallel presentations or copy-writes is the norm.

Indeed, if products, goods and services were directly proportional to the volume of research undertaken, the massive ideological tie to, and material dependency on, foreign technological outcomes would now be a thing of the past. Instead, much of the evidence points towards the research as purely for purposes of academic qualifications and certifications, staff promotions, and institutional visibility rather than the tool for broader socio-economic progress along the lines of the vision-mission of the University of Illinois. Nothing of much substance takes place once the study objective is achieved.

Tacit evidence calls into question the progressively pedantic research, with the Further Education pedagogy more concerned with technical adjudications while averse to philosophical experiences it is unaccustomed to. As a result, such studies are potentially reduced to the usual copy-write rather than deep, clinical searches for innovative models compatible with the evolving realities. Mabhena (2016a, para.8) puts it eloquently arguing that “Intellectually we are really not exerting ourselves hard enough; we keep allowing quality and rigour to remain a preserve of whites and Europeans”, hence, justifying the maxim that ‘blacks are lazy’ or are of low intelligence. Scholarship is more fastidious about conventional cosmetics rather than socially functional researches that can withstand the pressures of both

public scrutiny and demand. Observing further, he (para.9) challenges such naivety which expects more and better results when “researchers in our universities know by now that the theories and methodologies that guide our researches are still the rusty colonial relics that lead us back to the findings and conclusions of intellectual imperial masters.” Ironically, the cloned research still struggles to commercialise findings that have always been known and applied in other contexts.

Therefore, besides the keen interest on the trio, there are limited formations and metrics to stimulate a cross-wide innovation culture – that is, how staff and students are nurtured to think, act and symbolise innovation, in much the same way they communicate with one another for innovation. In fact, monodisciplinary research predominates, with the Sniderman model nowhere nearby (not even in projects). Furthermore, poor public science communication isolates the institutions from their hinterland causing the bulk of the researches to disappear into oblivion. Meanwhile, consumerism induces mass desertions among the skilled, condemning the country to global marginalization and dependency. Equally, the habit factor strengthens the economic–work places spectre. As such stakeholders are least eager to ruffle the status quo and stand the institutions on their heads all for the sake of research and innovation. Hence, varying with the fortunes the researches encounter, threats of enclaving, resocialization or termination always loom high (If at all, they are not even accorded air time in their own institutions) generating conflict between the naïve, populist politics and proletariat versus the intellectual elite with its quasi-concordant research.

In strangling the research, the absence of a powerful science fiction tradition is only paralleled by the stifling neoliberal dense network of specifications enshrined in the WTO and WIPO’s IP policy systems which, essentially, close rather than open up the research-innovation-entrepreneurship space. Room for cooperation is strongly countered by the rigmarole of rules and conventions, (patents, trademarks, industrial designs and copyright) that amount to what Karl (2002) calls ‘sophisticated mechanisms of disguised protectionism at the very gateways’ to the industrial markets. Briefs like the ‘rules of origin’ policy simply continue to promote the technological exports of the North at the expense of the South. At the same time, inherent restrictions and stipulations associated with the IP system like the dearth of local examiners pose big problems to access patents as well as enforce copyright locally. In the final analysis, the IP system amounts to technological imperialism the institutions can scarcely generate

maximum benefit out of to realise the 'mythical catch up' to the industrial North and/or East. What bears fruit is complicity and compliance as the nature of the game, flirting with dim hopes and false victories.

In one of his informative articles, Chulu (2014) of the Bible School Business School (BSBS) strongly criticises Africa's gross naivety in succumbing to the 'Goliath' development agenda of the West as opposed to the 'Davidian' approach of small, simple, affordable, alternative technologies that 'betterise' with time (the zhing-zhong philosophy). But then what technologies are being talked about is not clear. Rather than cling to traditional rules, like what Japan and the other East-Asian Tigers did, Africa should change the rules and adopt much more aggressive, unorthodox methods of harnessing the needed technology, even if it means espionage, pirating or hacking. Writing on the US's accusation of China for economic espionage, the New Yorker (2014) observes how throughout the ages such espionage has been the ball game, by the USA itself, by Japan and today, by China, without exception. As he puts it "When you are not yet generating a lot of IP on your own, you imitate. The tactic of using piracy to leapfrog ahead (technologically) is an idea China stole from us (the US)." It is an open secret that Africa bonded fiercely against colonialism, but failed the crucial war of economic espionage, instead, preferring worthless Blocs, Summits and Agreements. While efforts will be made through the WTO to stop China, she would have registered commendable success guaranteeing her economic independence.

Africa's historically soft, genteel 'catch up' mantra, now cast as 'technology diplomacy' involving elaborate institutional research infrastructures and third party technology transfers, is but a recipe for prolonged slavery to technocapitalism. Indeed, visions like '... professionalism rooted in integrity' mean that reverse engineering and similar alternatives lie outside the institutional scope. The trials and tribulations of the politics notwithstanding, it was time for a paradigm shift to interfere with the so called 'rules of fair play' that close rather than open up research space against the continent and its institutions. Such wisdom remains embroiled in the power politics to see the light of day any time soon, if ever.

Much more specifically, Lewis (2007, p.18) chides the logic of economic competition to which the institutions have virtually become slaves rendering the research-innovation-entrepreneurship their Achilles heel, always up against red robots and powerful headwinds.

The research-entrepreneurship is a seed that has fallen on hard ground, given Zimbabwe's dismal rating of 125 out of 140 countries according to the 2015/16 Global Competitiveness Index Report. It is difficult for it to flourish, with the institutional products reduced to informal employment. This is exacerbated by weak and erratic funding which leaves the institutions running on quarter-empty but with the 'Prime' estate still the fancied target. The challenge has witnessed erratic student enrolment, strained service delivery and staff-student body industrial actions, with multilateral and bilateral support in limbo. Hence, the Zim-Asset (or is it the misnomer!) laments the institutional inability to successfully usher the desired competitiveness, an indication how, given the highs and lows in institutional intrigues, the punctured research-entrepreneurship barometer is unable to sense that much pressure change in the deflating technocapitalism balloon.

Still cause for great concern are the rising levels of unemployment even among higher education graduates, suggesting serious exaggeration of the philosophy of entrepreneurship, least hamstrung by acidic, inconsistent and non-transparent policy making (Akinola, 2015). Crucially, to restate the algorithm, the mismatched blending of broad learning and skills training means the students exit the institutions ill-equipped in terms of optimal labour market skills. But, arguably, the lack of start-up resources aside, many regard entrepreneurship as disguised unemployment, only suitable for the informal sector, hence, opting to be employed rather than to start their own businesses. Recounting his experience, an undergraduate at a NUST seminar in 2014 argued that it was much easier to go through formal employment before starting an own business venture. If anything, then, the new entrepreneurs descend to the informal sector out of necessity from which they skip out as soon as better opportunities present themselves elsewhere. In other words, they would rather have a stable job than be self-employed which they regard a menial practice (Philipp, 2010). Also, it is common cause that, while necessary, because of their nature and the huge capital outlays entailed, some disciplines like the atmospheric sciences, aeronautics engineering, astrophysics, medical nursing, and science and technology education do not readily lend themselves to entrepreneurship, worse in a decimated economy.

This is against the argument whether universities are the best vehicle to impart the requisite hard skills previously offered through apprenticeship and in-house training methodologies by sector-specific Associations, Institutes and Societies. The schemes did a better job in terms

of sunken skills with great entrepreneurial potential, plus the products did not easily and readily succumb to vices like inefficiency and corruption. While the school-based education compensates the 5–8 years education and training with one year industrial attachment, the product has never been the same. Hence, many are persuaded to agree with the argument for students to ‘stop out’ of university, since, chances are they are more likely to achieve entrepreneurial breakthroughs on their own than with more formal education (Grasgreen, 2013; Thiel Institute, 2011). As Grasgreen observes (para.3), a point echoed by Wright (2013), “the traditional model needs to be totally rethought and resurrected as something different.” In other words, what needs to be interrogated the most is not whether entrepreneurship is ‘nature or nurture’, but our capacity to envision and to critique the concept beyond the level of a *fait accompli* which it has become, incidentally now equating to skills, further confusing the education outcomes (Akinola, 2015).

On that score, the entrepreneurship lobby overlooks the fundamental issues surrounding the perspiration-inspiration or perception–reality gradient and, therefore, critical to managing a business successfully, *inter alia*, the capitalist spirit and the related traits of risk awareness, attitudes, discipline, attention, political-cum-business climate, financial support, capability, safety, experience, and handling failure (Philipp, 2010). Apart from the fact that the skills take time to ingrain, master, transfer and deliver, with beginners the least qualified to handle them, many people just do not have the ‘instincts’ for entrepreneurship.

Writing in the Telegraph, Wright (2013, para.8) argues that entrepreneurship is a ‘nature than a nurture’ cause. As she puts it, true to fact, the operations and mechanics of business management can be learned. The challenge is converting the learned idea or ideas into ‘a well-run, sustainable operation’ – a feat not everyone is capable of undertaking. In her view, ‘instincts’ come into the equation as the “key skills of sparking somebody’s imagination of creativity, boldness and the desire to take risks.” This is why “some people will be more suited to entrepreneurship than others”, which boils down to the fact that there are ‘exceptional’ people and not everyone is ‘exceptional’ for business (Robertson, 2015). In short, not everyone has capacity to balance correctly the enduring perspiration-inspiration gradients. According to Philipp (2010), the culture of the extended family compounds the problem further as it makes employment a big obligation to the clan. The pressure hampers job creation causing many to retreat from starting businesses in fear of the burden.

As things stand, even graduates well-schooled in entrepreneurship find the practice hard, tough and even not worth the effort (Wright, 2013). Writing in Forbes, Schramm (2013) of UP Global argues that even undergraduate courses are not producing star entrepreneurs. Among some of the reasons she advances are that the programmes are business-centred rather than entrepreneurship oriented, with the latter just one of many courses in business management. The bulk of the teachers lack the entrepreneurship qualification, often with the generated ideas too simplistic and half-baked. Further, given the usual right-wrong grading approach, the students are in it for the wrong reasons of good grades rather than genuine entrepreneuring based on creativity and effort. To add to the injury, special prizes are awarded for distinction passes than other initiatives. The last reason is the lack of incentive to launch the entrepreneurship plans upon completion. If, then, well established institutions of the American system are unable to deliver genuine entrepreneurs, it is unlikely that, given the difficulties, the Third World scapes will fare any better.

In a nutshell, if things were as easy as the classroom puts it and as readily applicable as politics says, then the over 2000 graduates selling airtime, coupled with the collapse of businesses virtually at the Adizes' Courtship, Infancy and Go-Go stages would not be such a colossal challenge as is currently the case. With the advent of robotics increasing joblessness, entrepreneurship is up against a very steep incline. In the end, as Philipp argues, entrepreneurship or self-employment is an 'out-of-necessity' drive rather than an opportunity building measure; an alibi for failed educational and socio-economic policies, with even middlemanship or self-dealing, arbitrage, tenderpreneurship, resource pillaging and other venal jobs labelled entrepreneurship.

Adding to the dilemma is the contradiction among some of the entrepreneurship measures which, while meant to generate employment, are anti-employment creation. World class manufacturing's automated interventions that replace human labour and contribute to expanding the unemployment labour pool, including among higher education graduates, is well known. But more at stake, as critics argue, are the dynamics of the 'Indigenisation policy'. Notwithstanding its noble cause, it continues to devour whatever is left of the economic carcass, "damaging the economy, fuelling capital flight and keeping investors at bay" (Mangundhla, 2014, p.13). According to Robertson (2015), the silent killer 'disempowers

anyone who displays ability and ambition under the illusion that anyone can run a business'. The 51% equity hype is but a manipulative gimmick for political rule rather than solid economic thinking, alternatively, a new version of the donor syndrome and easier way out of the unemployment quagmire, but certainly neither the right nor best way. A relic of the BEE programme, critics argue that there is little entrepreneurship worth talking about as all the new entrepreneurs do is dip into government tenders, hardly generating much business and industry for their unemployed compatriots. Mangundhla describes the policy's violent aura as equivalent "to racketeering by regulation", if not legalised plunder by the elite. Riddled with inconsistencies and lack of transparency, it has proceeded to ruin existing businesses, reducing gains in employment (Bloc, 2014). Even following the mooted Production Sharing Model for extractive industries (mining, agriculture, tourism) and the Joint Empowerment Investment Model, targeting manufacturing and services sectors, the model has failed to inspire confidence towards profound structural reforms that transcend the narrow, tactical changes to attract foreign direct investment (Bloc, 2014; *Zimind*, 2015).

Two models have emerged to accommodate the controversy and criticisms:, however controversial. The two are said pragmatically to meet the ideological, legal and policy dictates of indigenization and empowerment. Critics argue, though, that the policy shift is simply another way of tightening the screws and rigidifying the status quo. The shift has barely

Furthermore, the massive output of research papers is largely for appearances and immediate gratification than anything beyond. The papers are guilty of naïve realism and failure to demonstrate the practical functions of the researches as tools to work the environment and promote the social wellbeing through the frames and understandings of the ambient populations, increasingly feeding more rational ignorance and related decay and redundancies. Through conscious and unconscious competence and incompetence is the massive imposition of colossal categories of fixed facts of dubious value rendering true Sachs' (1992) criticism of fascination with myopia, if not the axiom of 'dumping ground of obsolete ideas.' It all starts and ends with the excess paperwork, while on a dim note, the decline in investment research in key sectors like rural agriculture and forestry cast murky prospects for the future. Epistemologically, the statements reincarnate the dilemmas of exaggeration, manipulative sophistry and Utopianism, symbolising the proverbial

management pie advancing technological tokenism. Currently higher education is overwhelmed by this problem whose narrative is the endless blame games.

Additional negative spin-offs lead to nebulous and erroneous policy formulations and decisions that are responsible for wasteful expenditures and administrative excesses, abject protectionism and propaganda spins. Scarce resources are diverted away from more productive uses, while products and services are wilfully discounted and input costs doctored, in the process, destabilising both the institutional and national economies. Stealthily, headquarters uses such evidence of decay to gain the upper hand, entrenching centralism and greater control to achieve its agendas, negatively impacting sustainability and quality standards and, ultimately, the strength to foster the technological society.

In conclusion, the research-innovation-entrepreneurship deliverable is the springboard for the technological infinite. It is inconceivable for the institutions to work without it if they are to 'guarantee Zimbabwe as a leader in the creation and use of new and existing knowledge, skills, attitudes and resources' (MHTE,STD). Curtailing efforts to leverage the deliverable is the extent the institutions work more with excellence as the watershed mark or prime value and less with efficiency which is more pronounced in the market. Driven by the traditional catch up myth, the deliverable is pursued with much vigour but, inadvertently, weak in what Lee (2012) calls the catalytic 'deliberation and process formalization' which then limits its utility value. Primarily, through externalization, the 'adopt and adapt' approach re-entrenches the dictates of Capital natively, which renders the deliverable more exploitative than facilitative, stolen to benefit outside regions, while also remote and beyond the oral worldviews of the local populations.

Both radical critique and radical solutions have become imperative to tackle the existential risks. It behoves the institutions to ingeminate more forceful but safe processes and mechanisms that deepen science (distinct from plain numerical expansions or duplications) to translate Furukawa's philosophy of 'Fusion of Knowledge' into a spontaneous uptake in order to leverage the multiple researches, innovations and entrepreneurships to contribute in the crafting of effective solutions.

6.3 The Leadership-Committee System deliverable

The leadership-committee system defines the roles top, middle and grassroots positions of power, authority and responsibility in charge of units and sections play in the system. As noted in Chapter 2, a host of defining models influence the behaviour of the deliverable, ultimately converging on leadership: as influence, as change, as service, as character, as development, and as culture and tradition impacting the systemic processes and practices however openly, intangibly and assiduously (Ambler, 2013).

At the institutional level professors, senior scientists, the deanery and chairpersons constitute the academic leadership, while the chancellery, registry, bursary, library and directorates constitute the administrative and departmental leadership, culminating in section heads. While the professorial and doctoral experts occupy top management, overall deployment is strictly by discipline, for instance, mathematicians are responsible for the leadership of the mathematics schools, scientists and engineers the leadership of other science and engineering departments, and the same obtains for chemists, computer science and so on, notwithstanding the attended challenges. Cross-breeding and mixed categories are very limited, mainly to the administrative divisions and occupations. As Yizengaw (2003, p.13) observes, profoundly important is the way the leadership foregrounds

...the fundamental question of accountability [which] revolves around who is to be held accountable, for what, to whom, through what means, and with what consequences. Putting in place mechanisms for accountability helps avoid trappings of arbitrary power and corruption, while raising the quality of performance by forcing critical reflection on operations and it raises the legitimacy and autonomy of the institutions.

Inevitably, the distinctive skills of effective mandating, facilitating, partnering and endorsing stand supreme. According to Bennis and Goldsmith (2010), this means leadership efficiency and effectiveness to cope with and promote visioning and change; to set direction, align people and provide support and recognition; and to motivate and inspire the workforce beyond self-interests to reach the highest expectations, if not the improbable: a capacity whose final product is Effective Action. Or, as management, capacity to cope with complexity, planning and budgeting, organizing and staffing, controlling, problem solving and a productivity drive (or operations orientation): a capacity whose final product is Efficient Action. Whether defined or not, efficiency and effectiveness have always regulated the levels of assiduity entailed in the total quality-quantity sustainable development narrative. The

resulting protocol is the leadership-management integer involving a repertoire of skills that are consistent with the Seven Nolan Principles of Public Life or life-work situations and the problems these create – a difficult proposition and one dogged by a plethora of challenges and problematic gaps (Pipim, 2013).

Committees and boards constitute the heart of the governance. Varying with institutional size, including Council and Senate, the number of boards/committees varies between 20 and 40, and the phenomenon keeps growing through intra- and inter-university councils/sub-committees to resolve issues and questions at different levels and moments in time. In short, just about every aspect of university life is dealt with through either an established/standing committee, or an *ad hoc* (sub-) committee of one form or the other comprising multiple expert leadership brands. Without doubt, the ‘more issues–more committees’ cycle is taking after the ‘more problems–more organization’ cycle of the formal bureaucracy (Jaffee, 2008).

Figure 6.3 shows the several indicators that were isolated to verify participant perceptions of both phenomena. The frequencies describe a jagged but compact spectrum. Only ‘funding’ and ‘procurement and supply chains’ were strongly rated I/S-N/A, while E/W was a pale shadow of the targeted leadership-committee excellence.

Figure 6.3 Participant perceptions of governance (Source: Table 5.2)

Although still so much lower than the targeted world class standard, the predominance of the F/C rating reveals stakeholder tacit commendation of the leadership-committee system's levels of assiduity. However, the N/A rating spike on variables like information reporting and disclosure, public/client relations and conditions of service means more challenges can be expected and, therefore, more work still to be done.

According to Leithwood, Louis, Anderson, and Wahlstrom (2004, p.5) the strong leadership is required to

set directions – charting a clear course that everyone understands, establishing high expectations and using data to track progress and performance; develop people – providing teachers and others in the system with the necessary support and training to succeed; redesigning the organization – ensuring that the entire range of institutional conditions and incentives fully support rather than inhibit teaching and learning.

Yizengaw (2003, p.12) echoes this viewpoint arguing that it is extremely difficult to provide education of satisfactory quality without the adequate and efficient system of leadership and management as the prerequisites for reforms and change in such a way that the two complement each other as opposed to being allergic to each other. This then puts a high premium on “creative, visionary and committed leadership, transparency in the working system, and the ability to up-grade skills of the leaders and managers, the committees and the whole workforce, to bring them into a process of renewal and transformation.” The totality is the numerous leadership dimensions reflecting Ambler's genre quoted above, executed through Petkoski and Twose's (2003) collective responsibilities of mandating, facilitating, endorsing and partnering.

The basic guiding principle behind the committee system is to involve everybody in everything. Clark (1986, p.202) maintains that “the ability of staff to meet and discuss strategy and policy and be appropriately involved in decision making is a strength of the university system that needs to be maintained and nurtured”, albeit conscious of the need to keep the efficacy of the system vibrant and clean of slack, sleaze and interference. Echoing the benefits of the 'high involvement', Leithwood, et al. (2004, p.52) further observe how it helps accomplish several objectives, mainly, 'bureaucratic compliance and loyalty to the leadership and system; fostering cooperation, confidence and support from the feeling of being professional decision-makers; to build human relations from enhanced job satisfaction, high morale and feelings of professional self-efficacy, while eliminating feelings of powerlessness

and workplace alienation, hence, reducing energy drain; and to foster organizational learning through more and better utilization of the institution's entire intellectual capacities culminating in better, and better coordinated, decisions'. In inspiring greater staff and public indulgence, the system is, *par excellence*, assured of bright prospects for growth and development.

Followed through, the committee system is the basis of the vital institutional autonomy and/or legitimate disorder, for the advancement of knowledge and academic freedom, and for the dynamic pursuit of careers and mandates. Hence, the impetus is towards participative and corporate governance so that decision making comes from multiple sources instead of having one set of policy makers responsible for all the decisions. Through the committees, the system avoids the dangers of the authoritative decision making of the civil service while upholding self-governance. Therefore, as Clark (1986) explains, rather than go for 'adaptive specialisations' such as more powerful planning units, the system is more comfortable with 'adaptive generalizations' in terms of multiple and overlapping committees.

The literature is awash with models invariably explaining the leadership brand or 'action logic' which Rooke and Torbert (2005, para.1) define as "the ways in which the leadership interpret their surroundings and react when their power or safety is challenged." As mentioned in Chapter 2, common practice is to categorise the leadership by generic functions of instructional, democratic, transactional and transformational leadership, etc: to mean and suggest that there are special leaders whose sole duty and responsibility is to carry out each one of such functions – an unusual phenomenon. Leithwood, et al. (2004, p.5) observe that by description

Instructional leadership encourages a focus on improving the classroom practices of teachers as the direction for the institution. Transformational and moral leadership, on the other hand, draws attention to a broader array of institutional and classroom conditions that may need to be changed if learning and behaviour are to improve. The strategic, democratic and participative leadership are especially concerned with how decisions are made about both institutional priorities and goals and how to pursue them.

For decades, this approach has influenced leadership design and deployment, with instructional leadership cursory dominating: faculty and teaching units; transformational and moral leadership, student affairs and sub-sections of administration; and the strategic leadership, head office, top administration and core departments, with all types sometimes, but not necessarily, democratic and participative. As mentioned above, the OECD (2011, p.3) endorses the importance of the deanery as it "interfaces between the institution's

decision making bodies and teachers on the job, hence, encouraging the cross-fertilization of strategic approaches, building and supporting communities of practice and nurturing innovation in everyday practice in the classroom.”

Apparently, for effectiveness, the vision-mission statements demand all the different forms of leadership style and/or action logics, a difficult proposal to install under the circumstances. On the whole, it was difficult to tell the range of action logics operating on the ground. On one hand, transformational leadership was the most envied given its ideological and revolutionary appeal, as well as the capacity to communicate the vision effectively and foster performance beyond expectations. On the other hand, variants of opportunist, diplomat and achiever leaderships, cultured around expert leadership, emerged and merged, however, not so ideally, given the complexities in the institutional footprints. On the main, Ambler’s leadership traits were subsumed in the *in-situ* expertise and authority models.

In the midst of the standard models, home-grown initiatives that include the IIAG, the Africa Leadership Initiative (ALI), the AAU’s Leadership Development series (LEDV) the ‘Prospective Commitment’ model, the NEPAD, and the Africa Leadership Studies (ALS), coupled with local brands like the Zimbabwe Leadership Forum (Zimlef) and the ‘Total Leadership’ model, to cite a few, dot the landscape. Prospectively, the designs seek to bolster and bring about more resolutely progressive anchors and changes in the leadership-management architecture: the Ibrahim Foundation, through advocacy and incentives for good governance; the NEPAD, through the specified joint responsibilities complemented by peer reviews and assessments; and all the others, through further education and training, research and innovation in endogenous leadership frameworks equipping participants with skills that are commensurate with the demands for more and better institutional governance.

But, as Leithwood, et al. (2004, p.5) observe, sometimes the leadership by ‘adjectives’ approach works, but more often than not, it “masks the more important underlying themes common to successful leadership, regardless of the style being advocated.” Rather, the ideal is to develop leaders with a large repertoire of practices and the capacity to choose from that repertoire as needed – leaders who keep their eyes on the entire institutional “ball” rather than leaders trained in the delivery of one “ideal” set of practices.

On the same vein, Groysberg and Slind (2012, para.10) argue that, in its oversight function, the leadership must exhibit 'outlook and practices' that enable it: to get closer to subordinates; to promote dialogue as opposed to monologue; to engage subordinates by allowing them to become active participants in the institution; to foster rigorous agendas that align the action logics with organizational strategy; and, to put a premium on ensuring that the people in the organization talk and work *with* each other, and not just *to* or *about* each other, let alone *against* each other. In line with Naim (2013), the social 'revolutions' progressively lead to the rejection of authority in position, in favour of synergy, consultation and participation. Hierarchies and their usual label of the 'other' who can be a superior, a peer or a subordinate do not sell anymore. The target is pro-social power associated with achievers versus personal power common with opportunists and autocrats. Contributing to a great working experience where everyone matters, everyone grows and everyone benefits, such leaders garner most support because of their truly servant-hearted natures: putting others and the institution first and displaying a strong, but humble spirit and willingness to listen to diverse points of view of which personal power is the opposite.

Clark (1986, p.276) buttresses this viewpoint, observing that "higher education needs a fair amount of discontent for people to speak up about what they think is going wrong, in a system where arcane knowledge can hide error from generalists" without the leadership feeling bad about it. Often, the absence of 'rights' as an enshrined value system compromises this important point. Authority works best when it is earned and leadership earns respect when it works 'among' rather than 'over' or 'under' the 'others' for there is never a time when the vision, knowledge and judgments of others are irrelevant and inappropriate to its endeavours. The local models strongly target the pro-social power brand, only they fail in rigorous critique to enhance their market value.

Therefore, team involvement in charting the way forward produces prime institutions that are more flexible and adaptable. The leadership gradient strives to foster the 'leaders for leaders' and 'managers for managers' continuum which does not mean a leadership that is everything to everybody, but one whose action logic *works* and achieves robotic efficiency for the institution and constituency. As always said, theory will always be convincing against hard practice which is as problematic as the number of leaders and practitioners in the equations.

6.3.1 Challenges

'A camel is a race horse designed by a committee'; or, 'a high finance burn rate is the standard of the bureau'; or, 'a pushcart is a lorry recommended by a committee'; or, 'if you want to kill it, form a committee', are some of the inferiority taunts on the leadership-committee system, reflecting challenges confronting both forums. As the spinal cord beneath the accomplishment of the footprints, from the survey the governance system was rated N/A at a mean rating of 2.3: specifically, 2.6 for the status of the leadership; 2.8 on the functional capacity of the leadership; and 2.8 for the committee system, albeit, showing a powerful pull towards F/C, but still inferior to the world class standard. In short, the compact rating in Figure 5.3 reflects the bureau model: everybody knows and follows the norms and rules, or do they?

The dilemma with the committee system is whether it achieves more to justify its relevance and adequacy, or else, it is just as lethargic as the formal bureaucracy it has replaced (Jaffee, 2008). The alarming N/A rating shows how governance as an investment of immense proportions should never be taken for granted. While participants approved the 'high involvement' and 'high performance' for maximum cross-fertilization of ideas and information, the leadership-committee system remained problematic in spite of the high-profile vision-mission statements. In its attempts to meet the demands of management and decision making, the system is confronted by a fair amount of challenges no amount of immunity can shield it from criticism, with both faculty and administration, on one side, and external partners, on the other, blameworthy allies.

First, the interviews described the leadership as challenged, problematic and falling short in several respects and expectations:

- (i) lack of innovative leadership which is always apologetic about its inefficiencies
- (ii) lip-service and lack of buy-in, hence, limited actual deliverables (publications, patents, etc.) universities are judged by
- (iii) little monitoring and evaluation/lack of constant reviews in line with the rapid changes – another document on the shelf
- (iv) aspirations are too high and are further let down by poor national (political) policy and strategic initiatives – which are not in harmony with the reality on the ground
- (v) too much subjectivity in implementation of policies and procedures
- (vi) lack of leadership and finances turn the statements into a pipe dream, at least for now

- (vii) inability to live the statements – lack of adherence and lack of reminders to ensure adherence
- (viii) drop them.

The excerpts reveal the dilemma to effectively and efficiently sustain the vision-mission pulse. The criticisms rhyme with an observation at a study seminar in 2014 which singled out leadership as the weakest link responsible for many a failed programme or project. The bureaucratic tendencies of qualified intelligence or rational ignorance prevail, with the leadership doing and undoing itself in many ways. The regularised and institutionalised behaviours and processes repeat the formalism of the bureau, rather than the post-bureaucracy ethos of self-rationalization.

Echoing this position, Clark (1986) observes that where leadership is an institutionalized 'sacred' cow and, therefore, a personality cult with the leader the soul and breath of the institution, and given the extent freedom of expression, creativity, empowerment and diversity are effectively stifled, it becomes the source of disaffection and dissent, consequently igniting tensionally stressful workplace values. Not only does the leadership push autocratic tendencies as both effective action and efficient action, risks and threats of lip-service, manipulation, politicization and inefficiency result in frustrations and disgruntlements leading to disengagements, instability and conflict – not ideal resources for a world class status (Mabhena, 2016). Equally perverse is the economy of protectionism as sensitivity to public scrutiny increases, with the strongly guarded courses of action impacting the essentials of academic freedom, in particular reporting, transparency and rights, etc.

Again, the critique echoes Clark's (1986, p.202) classical observation that, often

faculty governance is dogged by proximate forces of academic oligarchy displayed through deeply entrenched personal power, producing a closed system around the chancellery, or deanery, or chairs, hence, walling off external scrutiny and localising privilege which goes with abuse of power.

In other words, the colossal leadership burden induces hegemonic apparatuses controlled by quasi-authoritarian oligarchies vesting self-interests. Rather than spur it into active duty, it is as if the assembly-line mentality induces a morbid transformational agenda: professionally and politically cowed into submission, with the old retiring while the up-and-coming lack sufficiently robust skills to carry the flag forward. Translating forward are what

Manion (2011, p.19) calls faults and breaks characterised by “the accelerating levels of ambiguity and uncertainty; workforce issues; diversity in the workforce; turbulent business and regulatory environments; and, the leader’s energy drain.” This is to say, the leadership has to endure the constant vagaries associated with rapid, uncontrollable changes, unstable staff mosaics (tenures, shortages, unionization, demands), protectionism/rigid controls, escalating costs amid declining funding, and endless migraines dealing with myriad matters that never seem to end, or to gel together, or to progressively get right with time. The catharsis for the unacceptable affects is nowhere nearby.

In short, so much the nemesis of the leadership is the state of the body politic that is at various levels of industrial action over fees, salaries and conditions of service, staff relations and corruption. Nearly permanent battle lines are always drawn between management versus the student body, versus staff unions, versus headquarters, versus the constituency, fuelled by one degenerative factor after another. Equally, developments point towards unhealthy committee bureaus marked by shortcomings reminiscent of the above taunts, but largely reflecting the hazards of the Adizes’ ‘Bureaucracy’ stage. In diluting the bureaucracy dictionary, the committee system finds itself caught in the economy and practices of the same, with the neo-patrimonial legacy contributing quite significantly to the dilemma: on one hand, endorsing and, on the other, *ultra vires* Western leadership models, contributing to the high incidences of weak oversight marked by confusions, irregularities, *ad hoc-ness* and confrontations – fulfilling the negative slur of ‘what else can be expected!’ (Kagame, 2015).

In his remarks on a study on the relevance and adequacy of the committee system in Nigeria’s Benue State Universities, studentobserver.com (2010, para.7) indicates that out of four Null hypotheses, the Study rejected three and accepted one. Of significance is the way the respondents endorsed the alternate hypotheses (H₁) “that the committee system will significantly: lead to the participation of a higher number of staff in university management; improve the decision making process in university management; and instil greater confidence in the university as a whole.” Meanwhile, and surprisingly out of sync with the confidence shown in the committee system, the Benue Study accepted the Null hypothesis that “the committee system will not significantly influence university management” – where it matters most. The sudden change in outlook is not hard to explain. The first three hypotheses resemble assumptions building on to the reality on the ground – expressed by the last

hypothesis, which entails senior management and headquarters effecting important governance functions from committee/board decisions and recommendations.

The respondents' perception reveals deep concern that, in spite of being a vital tool for university governance, the committee system is least effective where it is expected and must matter most – influencing university management. As the Study proceeded to note,

This is because the respondents agree that committees do not provide effective advisory services to Vice-Chancellors, and that committee recommendations will not influence opinions of the university council and senate. There is no confidence that university administration will really implement the recommendations of committees.

The research did not go on to verify the situation among the case-study institutions. Suffice to say the conclusion can only point either to lack of trust between the parties or to the bureaucracy simply failing to gel together. Cases exist where committee recommendations are either changed or completely thrown out by higher authority confirming fears of a *fait accompli* if what they decided was unacceptable and other interests prevailed.

In addition, the Benue Study argues that, in some cases, the creation of Vice-Chancellor 'management boards' has perfected monopoly decision making with wide sweeping powers that, not only erode even the authority of the Senate, but engender situations whereby 'views or decisions of committees are ignored if they are in conflict with those of administration.' The long and short of the argument is that committees pale into insignificance in the face of vested interests that are in sympathy with the status quo. As Clark (1986, p.203) observes, power struggles arising from the "vested interests which are strongly guarded by structurally entrenched practitioners richly equipped with ideologies that justify traditional practice and political *allegiance*" (*emphasis added*) are the basis of the problems confronting the leadership, exacerbating institutional dysfunction and malfunction. The Benue Study concludes with the observation that, "although universities teach about democracy and are quite vocal about the need for popular participation in decision-making, their administrative structures and key policy-making bodies are most undemocratic." It is not uncommon for boards and senior management to abuse the governance system and run roughshod over the interests of other groups, even at the expense of faculty.

The field observations revealed that the 80:20 rule prevailed. This is to say 80% of the committee membership is shared among 20% of the staff mostly the deanery and senior

administration to decentralise decision making. At stake is the breath of fresh air allowed for positive results and/or with adverse implications the dynamics of the committee system as, more often than not, it is the same personnel across the spectrum of committees. The trivial many versus vital few is a replication of the monolithic practices of the formal bureau which, according to Jaffee (2008, p.122), ignores the impact of the rule as a result of inequality in the distribution of resources "...inequality in skills and knowledge, inequality in rewards, and inequality in authority" whose cumulative effect results in "alienation, disaffection, and weak commitment among those lacking or denied the resources", with unintended consequences.

In addition to the risks of rational ignorance are the overly fixed and frequently unstable committee structures (especially, intermittent inquoracy), as well as numerous and too frequent meetings sharing and recycling agendas, swamped in mountains of paperwork, and whose only motivation are deadlines, to name a few. Hence, high instances of AWOL and of other events failing to take place, squeezed out by meetings. Rather than controversial debates that build, are challenges of mere acquiescence or rubber stamping; or the opposites of wilful contradictions, sabotage and conflicts with negative consequences the governance.

Further, specialisation induces the risk of rational ignorance, revealed through unequal and inadequate knowledge of the issues at hand among the attendees leading to erratic contributions, while incendiary decisions are not uncommon among controllers eager to veto than to build the issues, rendering committing both impertinent and impotent. At worst staleness, stalemates, argumentation, recriminations, obsessions and excessive referrals of decisions to individuals or other committees are additional committee burdens at the expense of the discharge of vital business. Hence, decision making becomes convoluted as committees not only usurp decision making away from appropriate units, but take decisions on routine maintenance matters which, effectively, individuals held properly to account can do better, and certainly more quickly. Meanwhile, the plague of disproportionate delays in making appointments that take years while headquarters is searching for the politically correct candidates complicates scenarios further.

As the Corporate Lifecycle model puts it, the dilution of responsibility and accountability culminates in more centralization: "with no inclination to change, everyone's day is filled with systems, procedures, forms, and rules", but on the main, 'meetings' and 'minutes' whose

raging debates give the impression of serious business when, in fact, very little real action is taking place. Beyond talk and records of talk shows, the meetings assume unparalleled supremacy to constitute the very reason for the committees without much cutting-edge business reflected. The phenomenon of management-by-minutes or memoranda has been a noticeable spin-off, ushering the risk of issues being constantly either overtaken by events or emboldening the bureaucratic tendency to park them awaiting the next tabling of the agenda and minutes.

Sharing on the phenomenon of the bureaucratic red tape and slow decision making the pliable committee trees engender, Clark (1986, p.203) observes how “the political aspects of direct coordination share with bureaucracy and oligarchy the tendency for deliberately organised social forms over time to vest self-interest, accumulate tradition, and fix on routines.” While professing to put the interests of the institution ahead of self-interests, individual rationality fails collective action to the point where the committees are never taken seriously. The benefits of high versus low returns on investment that go with the 80:20 rule remain coincidental, with the file room/dump-bins the biggest beneficiary from the stockpiles of resource wastes.

If anything, then, the committee system does spread faulted decision making across the wide spectrum of endeavours as a result of the leadership having assumed immortality from amassed authoritarian power for itself and its ilk, while lack of research personnel in both the chancellery and registry-bursary further rigidify the status quo. According to Clark (1986, pp.271-2), central authority’s dictates and directives that everything must be run under one roof for ease of oversight, inspection, and dissemination of personnel and control instruments (circulars, budgets, finances, appointments) prevails, leading to the concentration of power in a single or few hands. Diversity, change, variety and other differentials are dismissed as evidence of redundancy and, therefore, the effectively unnecessary, needless, risky and costly excesses of poor management. Soon, central authority finds itself saddled “with the messy, chaotic ways of departments, faculties, students, and individual staff members at the expense of the much broader policy fundamentals.” The directives from headquarters are as sweet as they are sour. In the process, decision making and institutional activity are scuttled and herded towards defective consensus and stability, harmful to the very competitiveness that is the aspiration of the vision-mission thesis.

The challenges disable the accretion of the requisite decision making variables and, therefore, the capacity to engender clear decisive judgement with more and better spread effects. In the process, the Adizes' 'Bureaucratic' stage is re-entrenched: real time spent behind the desk generating and replying (headquarters) emails; following instructions to the letter; pushing as much paperwork as possible; and arranging or attending countless routine meetings leading to meetings fatigue – with the personnel inaccessible because of meetings. As the participants commented, 'there are inefficiencies in the system especially the time it takes for most meetings. They are unproductive.' While demonstrable measures of work, the duties are barest measures of value addition. Instead of rigorous appraisals to enhance fewer but effective deliberations, premised on reviews like: why is this meeting necessary; what will be done differently if this meeting succeeded; do the meetings animate the goal of the team/system? prevalent is the oligarchic tendency for accumulated tradition and fixed routines.

In conclusion, reminiscent of the Western university-college system, the leadership-committee system deliverable is one other archetypal example of the P-AIUG's 'addressee–consignee–copy-write' infamy. The shifting governance paradigms and the old and new challenges they generate render operations cumbersome, complicated and over-bureaucratic, with the leadership unable to tell the signal from the noise: romanticising with whoever and whatever promises a future with prospects greater than anything the constituents have ever imagined.

This brings into focus Pipim's chicken mentality and its characteristics of 'leadership incompetency and corruption; relishing disguised stupidity as being administratively savvy; pricing routine motions as indicators of success; hype on degree qualifications, pedigree and blind agreement to determine individual worth, ability, and position; pushing more activity than productivity as the backbone for respectability and acceptance; splashing endless excuses to justify failure; glorifying self-pity as humility; entertaining consciences that hardly catch fire on matters of principle' and other victimhood/predatory instincts (*Leadership nuggets: Chicken Leadership vs Eagle Leadership*).

In the interim, the curriculum trends continue to exhibit a leadership education and training deficit. As such, the products exit the system foggy about the leadership institution: for some,

to be painfully learned in the next 20 to 30 years, while others engage in continuing education to boost the skill, but the dye would have been cast. As the key strategy, leadership commissioning is still to receive the requisite attention and boost.

6.4 The moral efficiency deliverable

The document sources summed the target of the moral efficiency deliverable as to 'prioritise the development of a complete graduate who is patriotic, smart, hardworking and tolerant of other people's views and above all, a graduate who has *Ubuntu/Hunhu*' (CUT, 2013). It is what the *esprit de corps* of discipline, leadership, student centeredness and the whole gamut of the Technocracy- Equity- Rights- Integrity- Liberty- *Ubuntu*-revolutions, including the Engineer's Pledge and the Hypocritical Oath, are all about. The immediate challenge is the extent the non-market decisions are driven by 'morphological and characterological correction' of individuals against the pressures of self-interest and other negative affects. In other words, the profit-power-VUCA dilemma must be handled, among many yardsticks, with clinical moral efficiency – that is, with certainty, transparency, morality and predictability befitting all behaviours.

This is procedural power whereby all stakeholders across the hierarchy (top-bottom) exercise full power in all that they do. However, reality is not as easy and straightforward as this. Crossroads are characteristic, with the culture of arms' length driving the profit motive diluting humaneness more than ever before. In its place, 'Liberalismo' or Western individualism, to culture an independent individual centred on the superior ego of the 'I': an exceptional Object that is always in front and ahead of others and denigrating other cultures to the social margins, is the ordained target.

This is to say, self-actualization for a totally gratifying identity through new and special ways of knowledge, whose acquisition is both the means and end, is the hallmark of the perpetual struggle (Streck, 1996; Mnkandla, 2006). To be schooled is to escape and never surrender to both natural and social shackles – damn the consequences. Socio-culturally, at great risk are the conservative Christian and traditional *ubuntu* values from the emerging loose cannons. Aware of the ulcer, the science education espouses strongly humanitarian standards in an effort to turn the promising freshmen and women into mature products well-groomed in value-chains centred on self-mobilization, moderation and dialogue and

projecting self-understanding, judicious judgments and humanistic resource mobilization, hence, reflecting “confidence in their own principles which are the key tools of educated citizens and leaders to champion and represent the best of humanity” (Lewis, 2006, p.267). The former UN Secretary General, Ban Ki-moon (2016), would canvass for “a world where dignity is respected, diversity is celebrated, and peace is permanent.”

This brings in the controversy discussed in Chapter 2 whether a Theo-technocracy or ‘spiriton-science’ culture should be the essence of the pragmatism, or else, existentialism (or secularism) should be the lead philosophy. On the other hand, by creating a level playing field between economies of scale and opportunity costs, nanotechnologists argue that technology will deliver the moral efficiency prerequisite fully and completely, ushering a well-knit, like-minded moral citizenry (McCarthy, 2012). Whether such a scenario will materialise or remain elusive much longer is another matter. For now, the catch-cry is how to uphold the moral efficiency against behaviour disorders bedevilling the constituents.

Therefore, the technological society needs a more versatile and forthright morality dividend. This means modelling highly discerning character and personality profiles steeled in humanitarianism and, therefore, able to distinguish between the various psycho-technical spread and backwash effects. Alongside the Seven Nolan Principles of Public Life, the pedagogy must highlight emotional intelligence, duty to care, democracy, role modelling and incorruption among other *esprit de corps* affects. Or, according to Lewis (2007, p.266), as the foundation stone for rational persons, the scholarly excellence must embody the values of “self-understanding, maturity, strength of character, and compassion and empathy for others.” Enough to say it is the battle of the ages.

Epistemologically, morality’s class-based nature and related ambiguities, coupled with human fallibility induce the social tendency to reflect the culture and worldviews of the dominant group. From a constituency perspective, this means harmonising the different sector-moralities – grassroots, middleclass and the leadership. By its culture, the first one is characteristically aboriginal according to the prevailing laws of natural existence, whereas the latter two show a strong Western influence, whereby the moralities have been variously diluted, learned, adopted and adapted in line with global moral regimes and laws of

rationality. While always in a state of flux, the moralities are also in constant struggle for supremacy generating multiple perspectives.

Meanwhile, as a result of its links with Christianity, colonialism, globalization, modern law, environmentalism and humanitarianism, Western morality exercises a vast and thorough influence. In the absence of powerful notions, aboriginal morality reflected in *ubuntu* is a severely weakened heap of confusion. Hence, in order to get the morality mixture rolling, it is a must that the majority internalises it which the institutions have proceeded to do. While differing in terminology, as Table 1.1 and Matrices 4.1–4.5 show, there is greater accent to absolute, unquestionable norms and behaviour standards whose absence and/or violation, it is feared might not only destroy the individual persons, but, more seriously, disintegrate the constituency order as well.

Therefore, evidence from the fieldwork revealed total embrace of the letter and spirit of moral efficiency and sufficiency or the principles of a humanely-based moral community and all that it stands for. In terms of practice, the institutions have adopted multiple noble strategies that include the ‘Peace, Leadership and Conflict Management’ (PLC) and the ‘Communication and Public Relations’ curricula, peace projects like the NUST Campus Dialogue Peace Project, guidance and counselling, life skills and community service platforms, social clubs, sporting and other competitions, chaplaincy and facilities for worship promoted through numerous media platforms, including security and the social media to enhance campus life and with it, moral efficiency. Highlighted was institutional capacity to ‘model’ the values through dialogue and consultations around team-building. The absence of the public choice discipline, however, is a revealing gap.

As Table 5.4 shows, while the core values indicator was rated F/C, the N/A compartment mean rating signified dissatisfaction with events on the ground. This means that, while the participants endorse the values statements, they are altogether unhappy with the supporting variables as the cross-stats revealed. They are dissatisfied with the democracy in place, student attitudes and conduct, the professionalism of the staff, and the *in-situ* levels of humanitarian services all of which reflect skewed conditions of social capital. This raises Lewis’ (2007, p.xi) argument that the institutions are barely able to help “the young grow up, to learn who they are, to search for a larger purpose for their lives, and to leave institutions

as better human beings.” Rather, it is like they are cloned into adults, only to emerge social misfits further down the road, unable to merge and foster a vibrant moral community. Wary, critics lament the paradox of wild ignorance of the ‘educated persons’ (Mabhena, 2016).

Without doubt, this calls for capacity to reconcile the eternal rivalry between the laws of morality and those of the market with the latter, according to Ridge (2015), engaging more the values of ‘respect, recognition, belonging, autonomy, personal growth and meaning’, or in terms of Olson and Stewart’s (2011) ‘micro-traits’, or Koestenbaum’s (2001) ‘social contract’ referred to in Chapter 2 (see pages 38 and 120, respectively). For the leadership, this means a culture of connection that allows the workforce ‘to thrive for sustained periods of time’ distinct from merely ‘focusing on operations and financials’; a leadership that “must not be merely smart and accomplished and skilful and experts, but be wise and mature and good people” (Lewis, p.266). Whether or not the key embodiment of the challenges, the argument of self-interest, reflecting individual differences, continues to unsettle the moral efficiency crusade.

6.4.1 Challenges

Chapter 2 discussed the myriad unacceptable affects bamboozling humanity and virtually turning the institutional metric upside down. From the fieldwork, expressions of poor attitudes and bad perceptions, lack of motivation, laziness, and failure to take ownership and weak commitment in the implementation of the statements, coupled with the 2.5 N/A rating of the comportment footprint expressed the mixed impasse of the moral efficiency framework between success and struggle. The invisible hand of negative affects continues to rattle the moral fabric against the run of play. In Chapter 2 it was argued that the *Cartesian* view is responsible for the separation of the intellect and emotion, yet the two are expressive modes of the same domain. More so is the mystery emanating from the overbearing contradictions in the pronounced *normative-virtues* canon with the conflicts tearing communities apart. The concurrent interest in emotional intelligence in an attempt to close the gap still fails to successfully romp in the opposites of emotional distress, social woes and broken morals. In spite of countless sources be it stubborn experiments, or product development, or hormonal complications, the emotional opposites are reduced to fancied counselling sessions.

Several other forces further complicate the morality breakdown. Reference has been made to the students–faculty interest dichotomy with Stein’s (2014) observations discussed in

Chapter 2 worth noting (see page 113). Among the students, excellence is the capacity to win the 'certificate' game versus faculty's desire to keep jobs, raise funds and keep reputation and rankings high. For both groups, then, but for different reasons, interest is more on 'getting it right' at the expense of life-skills education and the need for a strong foundation for a stable future life. Effectively, the science and technology plays a peripheral role in the upbringing and maturing of the students into adulthood, leaving many struggling to come to grips with the basic questions of life. As Lewis (p.18) further observes, tensions often leading to conflicts ensue emanating from the differences "between what the bright, ambitious, talented, but otherwise ordinary students want and what the faculty think they should want", encouraging endless mind games which generate loose morality, with students bunking lessons, or 'over assisting' each other in their work, while more than ready to cheat in examinations and other areas of their work.

Clearly, technocapitalism is stronger than foundational rationality with the language of production and consumption dominant as product futures are evaluated for potential productivity rather than what it means to be a human being in the 21st century. According to Lewis (2007), this means stronger pursuit for means and ends to achieve world class status rather than concern to explore the broader / wider social, economic and political contexts of the education. Consequently, the liberalismo induces the tragedy of reconceptualization pronounced through the phenomenon of mental slavery which, according to Chiwome and Gambahaya (1999, p.101), "is far more destructive than the slavery of the body, for it demeans the people creating individuals who are more useful to others than themselves; schooled in ways that scarcely advance their cause making them their own enemies." Developments among professional bodies reveal how these now function less to protect the public from impostors, but from the greed and avarice of the professionals themselves.

At the wider market level, Morley (2003) and Lewis (2007) argue that the passion for scholarly excellence renders the institutions slaves of the same. The cut-throat competition to address the financial considerations of salaries and research money virtually overshadows everything. According to Morley (p.9), the fact is that "higher education has become a product one buys, rather than a process one enters", hence, creating a student-institution relationship of a "consumer to a vendor of expensive goods and services." Taken as customers first and foremost and learners next, the imperative is to satisfy their interests and those of their

families in response to the fees they pay. Consequently, the values are constantly reduced to vendible commodities pushing disparate and contradictory promises and assurances that proceed to cultivate weird mind-sets. The products proceed to justify the “high purchase price...on the basis of even higher future returns” leading to rising moral degradation and the rest is history (Lewis, p.4).

Similarly, multiple processes like technical rationality, the tenure system, lack of back-up literature and a weak chaplaincy are at odds with the weak foundational rationality. As seen, the demand for technical rationality means that, in the spirit of technopreneurship or robotic efficiency, the products have little choice but to accept the norms and attitude-value complexes that come their way. According to Lewis, a point echoed by Dale and Hyslop-Margison (2010), the problem with technical rationality is that it deems all learners and the contexts in which they live uniform across the economy. Its heavy demands not only leave little room for advisory learning, but reduces higher education to a mere job or business than, as Lewis (p.257) goes on to observe, a “deep conviction and calling revealing mature understanding of causes and effects, smart about students, and reluctant to risk teaching the wrong larger lesson by quick decision that might be expedient in the short run administrators have been renowned for.” In the end faculty no longer does the good job of helping students grow up into mature, capable adults, a gap that is further compounded by the vanished status of education administrators whose new role of ‘student service professionals’ and, therefore, information conduits and paper pushers, is a far cry from the ‘providers of perspectives on deep and enduring problems of life’ (Lewis).

Likewise, rated N/A (2.5), staff professionalism was found inadequate in spite of the presence of the core values of honesty, integrity, etc. within the body politic. Characteristic were the multiple scandals involving examination shenanigans, pilfering of institutional resources, harassment and improper associations, while cases of fraud and abuse of the workforce were reported. To the study, the delayed responses and instances of half-filled questionnaires, coupled with the excessively U/J responses which had to be rejected was an indication of professional inertia and ineptitude. The vision statements were substantively peripheral to the staffs’ daily business: they were not worth the extra effort and time in their busyness schedules. Furthermore, on the main, the answers were substantially unbecoming the expected levels of professionalism and scholarship.

But more telling is the way tenure, faculty hire and promotion are given for research, teaching and community service, but never to help students become mature adults. In the process, life skills education has diminished since it is of scant value to the personnel. This is against official rhetoric that continues to chime the adage that professors are the true mentors and source of guidance of values and ideals to the young and confused: teachers, yes, but guidance and counselling mentors, question mark; while grading imperatives continue to witness the axiom of the tail wagging the dog. As Lewis (p.74) sums it, “typically, the weak social inputs in the teaching and learning deny the development of an all-round comportment on the part of both teachers and students” with the outputs at odds with the cherished ethics, principles and standards.

Closely related is the extent deliberative classroom critiques and debates on curricula and visions, missions and core values, in light of possible alternatives with greater potential for the moral imperatives befitting the technological society, were few and far between. The 2014 Victoria Falls conference on the Professionalization of Student Affairs was quite an eye opener on the peripheral role the vision-values statements play in moulding the foundational curriculum to promote the ideals of the envisaged institutional society and its communities. This is compounded by the shortage of locally produced standard literature readings for support. To echo Lewis (2007), consequently, there is absence of serious dialogue about student development into people of a sound mind who feel indebted to society for the privileged education they have received and are more than ready to deploy it for the uplifting of the same society. Instead, external values prevail which casts the proclaimed core values as merely vendible cosmetics for special occasions with speeches, again as Lewis (2007, p. xiv) observes

...flooded with the world's problems, the pursuit of knowledge, success and hard work. Rarely will you hear more than bromides about the soft socio-institutional good character values (personal strength, integrity, kindness, cooperation, compassion) and how to leave the world a better place than the students found it.

Even the chaplaincy service is pressured for lasting solutions to the challenges. The multiple counteracting forces linked to existentialism make it hard to sustain robust religious principles, with the ‘constructive’ and ‘destructive’ forces typical of atom and cell repeating with spiridon. The biblical principles are severely stretched by escalating dehumanizing

practices (Satanic and demonic forces!) which further frustrate and cripple the moral efficiency building efforts.

Beyond the classroom, staff and student politics add to both the loopholes and the dilemma to plug them. Under pressure to stave off stakeholder militancy and keep politicians and professors satisfied and students happy so that they remain attractive, with the all-important skills and survey rankings staying high and funding promising, it is not unusual for the institutions to resort to fire fighting measures. Lewis (2007, p.16) laments the resulting *ad hoc* decision making soon conditioned to “appearances and immediate gratification” such as the use of peer groups and hiring of specialists to fill training gaps and the matching of concessions to student complaints. In the process, students abuse the ‘discordant views and clashing and inconsistent messages’ with weird agendas some of which border on curricula and administrative moral hazard.

As variously discussed, worst are the diverse criminal pathologies – hard and soft (cyber) crime – the systems have to endure. Driven by self-interest, the products scarcely take the skills learned as the basis for honest productivity, but more as the passport to wealth (the rags-to-riches syndrome). It is no surprise how, as Woods and Grant (2003) observe, while many immoral values like usury, bribery, gay marriages, homosexuality, alcoholism, abortion, pornography, gambling and the desecration of the environment were cardinal sins, today they are open practices however controversial, in virtually all fraternities – professional, government, religious, legal, civil society. This leaves the institutions and their constituents consumed by unprecedented pathologies perpetrated by their very own stakeholder alumni (merchants of shame), visions-core values notwithstanding.

To illustrate the point further, according to Woods and Grant, the reality is one of rampant materialism, propelling an epidemic of scandals concealed behind a screen of hypocritical moralising about sin, right and wrong, duty, integrity/*ubuntu*, stewardship, patriotism, honesty, innovativeness, dynamism and the whole gamut of core values. (Even Pope Francis has lamented the global sickness and ruin – Chronicle, October 16, 2015) The massive looting of public resources and stakeholder assets seriously compromises the acclaimed integrity and prudence with the perpetrators often going scot-free (Magaisa, 2016).

Hence, barring the good intentions on paper, the argument is that the curriculum products simply match the promises of technocapitalism, especially its power to render what is: a downgrade a stepping stone; weak, strong; unproductive, prolific; and immoral, innocent and perfect. As Woods and Grant (2003) observe, police patrols and fire alarms or not, at work is the real artillery of finance capital (clever, ruthless, rapacious, invasive) which has overpowered the capacity of the morality crusade to deliver. Echoing Woods and Grant, Magaisa (2016) and Ngwenya (2016) argue how the elite deliver grandiose lectures and public teachings on the virtues of moral uprightness, holiness, sensitivity to the dignity of every human being, thriftiness, sacrifice, peace and goodwill, to name a few ethics, while practising rape, paedophilia, human trafficking and committing (ritual) murders; while awarding themselves massive salary increments and prestigious properties with workers losing jobs or going unpaid for months and burying everything under liquidation via judicial management; while looting and externalising national resources, including plunging the national currency into chaos for personal gain; while stockpiling food and energy supplies for themselves and their kith and kin, as well as murderous weaponry to fan unrest or to suppress the poor; and while demolishing shelters for the poor and pushing a pacifism built on shedding of innocent blood, broken bones and mass graves. In a nutshell, the spectre of moral efficiency is at crossroads rendering it attainable more in word than in action.

Whereas all the institutional values evoke a strong moral efficiency dynamic that defines and nurtures humanized action logics across the larger constituency action spaces, apparent, though, is the infinitesimal role of moral education, with social critiques peripheral in the teaching and learning. Unlike the other deliverables discussed so far, the faulted humanization-materialism and organism-organization relationships are proving hard to reconcile to culture a vibrant moral community leaving the systems confused, burdened and exhausted physically, emotionally and morally, apparently with the immorality debacle heading further north than showing signs of abating. Can it be by raising the values bar so highly, higher education flies over the bulk of its constituency, including its own products, hence, missing the very essence of cultivating and ingraining the skill-values in the learners and the publics? Or, is the steady marginalisation of the institutions through the incessant erosion of their autonomy at the behest of more control and monopoly negatively impacting their true potential to grapple with the moral efficiency debacle (Lewis, 2007)? The questions call for further research than has been offered here.

Such, then, is the impact of the education paradox of transforming the product of the culture of the extended family into a self-centred individual well-groomed in narcissism and arms' length relationships and meant to exercise selflessness and other principles of public life. The institutions argue that they are doing their best but the open world eventually spoils everything. In the midst of the cosmopolitan, neo-patrimonial culture the net impact are the confusions and related behaviour orgies confronting the constituents. In the intermediate, higher education has no answers to these challenges, except more inertia across the board. Among the consequences, the weak moral efficiency fundamentally kills that very critical industrial building block – teamwork – as the divisive self-interests dissuade the teambuilding spirit vital for business start-ups and management. In hindsight, during the entire period of de-industrialization (2000 onwards) academics and students could not form teams targeting take-over of specific industries in order to save them for the good of themselves and their communities. Some of the institutions actually dispatched teams to study the phenomenon as if that was the solution.

In conclusion, the vision-mission statements push for greater public indulgence to promote stronger liberal, conservative and traditional values. The target is to ensure that learners acquire the best attitude-wise and, therefore, proceed to live and work intelligently and accountably. Affectively, the public engagement attest to arrest and stave off the dehumanizing morality breakdown – crime, injustice, vulnerability, victimhood and other downgrade vices. Ironically, the morality impasse is interred in the market driven curricula that profusely articulate and assertively preach the technological infinite as the hallmark of the greatest good, which plainly indicates how the total loss of a moral community has inevitably become a question of time. From the ensuing impact gaps, both the classroom and the market are robbed of the most critical inputs in the fostering of the science-technology culture, leaving society at different stages of disintegration. So much is happening against, or is not happening for, life skills education and the logic of a humane commonwealth. Consequently, the unstable mandates drive rising radicalisation amid a rigid status quo at the expense of a well cultivated and cherished moral efficiency.

6.5 The Sustainable Development deliverable

As the final melting pot, sustainable development is the most idyllic but problematic and controversial deliverable. While all indicators ultimately converged on it, the transfer of technological innovations and inventions, employment creation, the GSIF, impact assessments and reporting, and democracy and institution-building were among the many indicators that directly tested it. As already reported, the I/S-N/A rating characterised them all and, therefore, that the sustainability buzz fails to clinically interface the higher education-constituency servicing composite, with applause echoing in all directions. What this means is that, as the brains to mastermind the localization and indigenization of all adopted dynamics, higher education must make sure that sustainable development works both intrinsically and extrinsically, within and beyond its walls, touching the constituency and its properties sustainably.

To the IIAG, the LPI and the REI, narrowed down, sustainable development is the graded, macroeconomic performance engendering purposeful human transformations reflecting Africa's ability to deliver on the Indexes or the HDI. It is the climax of the overriding idealism, progressivism and pragmatism, on one hand, with industry enjoying high-value technological transfers or competitive manpower supply and the populace, on the other, total supply and demand, including environmental democracy and justice. To the Zim-Asset (2013), a buoyant technocapitalist state is the *sine qua non* for an 'Empowered Society amid a Growing Economy' or development excellence.

In line with Yizengaw's (2003, p.16) admonishing cited below, higher education should prosecute, withstand and fight-off the sustainable development contests, engagements, struggles, etc. This means active conversion of the learned science and technology as the springboard to realise the cherished dream. From the institutional statements, the Singaporean ethos has found way into the visions to push the cultural and ideological homogenization of the nation through redesign of curricula programmes and staff training. Hence, Further Education is witnessing the training of more Masters and Doctors of Technology personnel, complemented by senior personnel sorties to the Far East, to spearhead and rollout the Zim-Asset cluster programmes and projects (the HIT, 2015).

Socio-environmentally, the technocracy must emerge with a sustainability architecture that ensures full sustenance of functioning programmes, projects and ecosystems or the up-keep of prime physical and academic infrastructures, as well as pristine biodiversity and landscape patterns free of exponential growth, ballooning crises, hazards and catastrophes (Shumba, 1993; Mnkandla, 2011b). In response, the system has adopted a variety of curriculum, legal and policy measures, audits and laws, land and disaster management agreements, conventions and movements, including the ISO14000 family of Environmental Standards, as well as the new global Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) as part of the arsenal to firm the sustainable development dividend.

This is in line with the GSIF / GRI, although both reflected very thinly in the statements and other source documents. Nonetheless, sustainability is no longer just a lobbying slogan, but a critical market point, requiring institutions to manage the processes of identifying, acting upon and disclosing opportunity and impact indicators related to socio-environmental cohesion details of which were described in Chapter 2. What is still outstanding is the practical renaissance to transform the sustainability into a concrete mechanism readily accessible to everyone to bring about a more secure development superstructure and other related configurations. Conflicts and contradictions notwithstanding, as the key theme, sustainable development is the very *raison d'être* for institutional survival and progress, reflecting the capacity to diminish both tame and wicked problems and all manner of crossroads hampering the posthumanity journey.

6.5.1 Challenges

In their study, Rafael, et al. (2016, p.412) observe that while the mission statement is meant to reflect “institutional reality about sustainability, Brazilian universities do not necessarily have sustainable indicators on their mission statements.” They conclude that

Just 6.6 percent of institutions explored the environmental management system indicator in their mission statement. It seems possible that this result is due to the difficulty of inserting these subjects in statements and promoting the minimizing of the negative impacts of activities and operations, energy savings, resource conservation and efficient environmental management.

As so far indicated, the same obtains locally where sustainable development as an indicator was mentioned in only one statement. The tacit conclusion is that among the rest, it is assumed and is covered and dealt with in the course of duty. However, external pressures render the sustainable development ethos hotly contested. Leading the challenges is the

false infinite (Verhelst, 1990) compounded by the vagaries of conspicuous consumption, the chicken mentality (Pipim, 2013), the corruption-ignorance disease, technophobia, the marginalization of the poor, run-away fiscal deficits, domestic and external debts, cybercrime and other opportunistic behaviours and illegal vices which dog the institution-constituency spaces (Gundani, 2015; Ngwenya, 2016; Olivier, 2010).

In part, the contradictions arise from the ambiguity surrounding sustainability which appears to mean different things to different people, as what is sustainability to some is not necessarily sustainability to all. As a result, varied technological, ideological and socio-political interests and interpretations have assumed ascendancy, including policy exaggerations that even label moral hazards like tenderpreneurship, arbitrage, self-dealing, middlemanship and fraud forms of business acumen for sustainable development. As Sharara (2015) argues, the euphoria that 'Africa's time has come' is slowly receding into the dustbin of history as the continent's nakedness intensifies.

The first confrontation is rationalizing the political imperative that the institutions must 'serve development' with the state-institutions relationship both complementary and conflictive on the matter, imposing strains and stresses to be grappled with. According to Clark (1986, p.232), the requirement "leaves a generic imprint on all who follow" and the related "risks of emphasising particularism at the expense of universalism" often with negative consequences the epistemology and faculty personnel leading to the loss of the scarce talent who quit and join more attractive destinations with more open conditions for research, contacts, scholarship and teaching. In short, not all the professionals subscribe to the development imperative as the backbone to relevance, with negative impact institutional and national programmes and projects.

Next, is the challenge of rising levels of unemployment even among higher education graduates and, therefore, whether the institutions are the best vehicle to convey the much sought target of entrepreneurship as always claimed, or else, other routes might yield better results. As pointed out elsewhere, the graduates regard the advocated 'necessity entrepreneurship' as disguised unemployment only suitable for educational and economic misfits, which strengthens Philipp's arguments of the gridlocked mind-sets. The irony though

is how the less intelligent are meant to be the economic builders as the intelligentsia is less inclined to plough its hands.

Therefore, surrounding the challenge is building a technological society founded on SMEs, a system, according to Rudzuna (2014), dogged by more disadvantages than advantages. Invariably the SMEs project is a notorious instrument, victim and perpetrator of fraud, misrepresentations, and pathologies of all sorts. As Rudzuna further notes, not only is it riddled with ignorance disguised as entrepreneurship, it is the hub of venal activities like tax evasion, money laundering, contraband, and entrepreneurial bundling (registration, licensing, labour conditions and standards, accounting, and insurance), while scarcely contributing much towards growing the economy let alone substantive tax receipts to the national fiscus. Therefore, given that the concept is outmoded with the level of mediocrity reminiscent of subsistence production, it is the wrong foundation, if not a myth upon which to re-brand a modern economy. On its part, it would appear the sustainability lobby overlooks the fundamental issues critical to nurturing the technology culture.

Funding pressures also complicate the sustainable development capacity challenges rendering very fragile the management of core processes and practices. According to Gurira (2010), funding is the worst nightmare for virtually all institutions of higher education. Estimates indicate that 80% of budgetary support is from the national fiscus, 15% from fees, and 5% from other sources, a not so rosy picture given the sick state of the Zimbabwean economy. As evidence, rated I/S at 1.9, the institutional budgets reflected severely unfavourable variances of between 55 to 90% between the expected grants/cadetship funds versus the actual funds received, culminating in operational deficits of 10–12% of income (NUST, 2013).

Indeed at 74%, participants were unanimous on the challenge funding poses – a condition Clark (1986, p.220) long observed as very detrimental to research, institutional or faculty operations as long as the survival budget is precariously tied to, and dependent on, “a long-standing part of a national budget, fixed in perpetuity in some bygone day and so much as unconsciously accepted as part of things that no one asks why, or does so only by way of idle speculation.” According to Gurira, the weak infrastructural development impacts low staff morale, massive brain-drain and inability to deliver the mandates. It is no surprise that the

grossly under-funded GEEP has been quietly abandoned without the acclaimed employment breakthroughs having materialised.

Overall, graduate output reveals huge disproportionate variations as Table 6.1 shows. Outputs from other sources notwithstanding, according to the 2014 statistics, against the national population of 13million, the output averaged one graduate for every 7000 people, which translates into an infinitesimal ratio of 14/00000. The unhealthy ratios stood at: 3.8 for the (Applied) Sciences and 3.0 for Industrial Manufacturing and Engineering Technology; 1.7 for Science and Technology Education, and <1 for most of the other disciplines. Crucially, what does the 0.3 ratio mean for agriculture which, for all intents and purposes, ought to be the highest; and whether land and wildlife degradation and other environmental outbreaks can be controlled with the output ratio of 1.8 environmental scientists, or more and better shelters with an output of 0.7 architects and quantity surveyors, or health and disease with a doctor-patient ratio that staggers between 1:250 000? Whereas to the institutions the figures signal 'profit' and 'efficiency'; to the market, the skewed ratios mean shortage of expertise which, coupled to skills flight, exacerbates capacity challenges across the economy and the distant technological society dream. The future is no rosier with the subdued intake of science and mathematics at the school level.

Table 6.1. The 2014 Graduate output ratios per 00000 of the population

Disciplinary category	'00000	Disciplinary category	'00000
(Applied) Sciences	3.8	The Built Environment	0.7
Industrial Manufacturing & Engineering Technology	3.0	Science & Technology Education	1.7
Environmental Science & Health, Forestry and Wildlife	2.3	Sports Science	0.4
Information Science & Technology	1.5	Other: Electronic Commerce, Financial Engineering, HIV/AIDS	0.9
Agricultural Science	0.3	Overall output ratio	14.5

(Source: Institutional statistics, 2014)

Meanwhile, institutionally, as Materu (2007) sums it, the inverse capacities mean insufficient numbers of adequately trained and credible professional staff to manage QA processes with consistent integrity across institutions and programmes, to conduct self-evaluations and peer reviews, while imposing strain on senior academic staff to support both their own internal

quality systems and the external QA processes of their national agencies. The trials and tribulations of the PhD programme are just one classical example. Further afield is the colossal scale of uncompleted and poorly maintained physical infrastructures and projects dating from the 1990s. Hence, given the inadequate funding and requisite expertise, sustainable development will remain the pseudo slogan by the politically emancipated.

The sustainable development call is certainly on overdrive with virtually no stone left unturned. Socio-economic indicators reveal how, reflecting the false infinite and as a product of the 'catch-up' myth, it is as presumptuous as it is illusory (Verhelst, 1990). 'Human security' is yet to touch the bulk of the population (Sharara, 2015; Tandon, 2008). While entrepreneurship and innovation have been around for thousands of years, the rapid expansion associated with the recent revolutions has virtually turned them into a Western fetish peddling more forceful external waves with neo-colonialism and technological imperialism the only recipe, riding piggyback on the shoulders of the construct, with local initiatives standing little chance (Mabhena, 2016a).

Meanwhile, institutionally, is the intellectual hubris that entrepreneurial innovation is a recent discovery no one knew about, let alone taught it, until the institution came along, with vision-mission statements feverishly competing heads over heels to outclass each other. This is despite the common tragedy of the 'Gartner hype cycle' with regard the behaviour of innovations and how the innovation wave is atrophying in most populations exhausted by the endless ploys to enslave the people to culpable consumerism. Therefore, what goes for innovation amounts to symmetric improvisation, but silently assisting external markets refine their prototypes and brands.

This is the dilemma confronting the science and technology drive as humanity's most celebrated gift versus this adversary image of an assault weapon masquerading as a gift or false light to the future. The magical transformation creates a false mind-set of a new being freely bonded to the state and the market, but otherwise drifting towards greater cultural entropy. As Verhelst (1990, p.68) puts it, "freedom and creativity are reduced to economic entrepreneurship which for the majority means the freedom to be marginalized, a condition typical of Western materialism." The conditions resemble the debt 'Laffer curve' in economics, whereby the larger educated stocks are associated with lower probabilities of

investment growth (Mnkandla, 2006). Eventually, no matter the levels of increase in the numbers of the educated labour force, the overall contribution of the excess manpower to sustainable development is relatively marginal. This will be the greatest challenge confronting the STEM education hype to successfully duplicate the market model.

Complicating the scene further is the technological society-*Homo simplex* nightmare referred to in Chapter 2. The gap is proving intractable to close down. Instead, it is widening and confounding the new social and economic reality. As indicated before, the technological society manipulates events and conditions for the benefit of itself and its offspring for which it neither seeks permission nor informs the Other. Meanwhile, those unable to escape *Homo simplex* are simultaneously pushed to the margins generating divisions and conflicts in the process (Olivier, 2010; Roy, 1999; Verhelst, 1990). Whether a direct problem of science and technology or of its outcomes, as argued previously, always at stake are issues of how much science and technology should be fostered; how much investment resources must be allocated to it at the expense of which social imperatives; which outcomes should find utilization in the face of which environmental disasters and other challenges; or, which ethical concerns related to its applications deserve intense scrutiny and control, and what are the costs and implications for science?

Furthermore, in coalescing the transformations, sustainability inadvertently generates further insecurity. Numerous events reveal how both philanthropic gestures and human atrocities are committed to promote 'sustainable utilization of national resources' or to achieve 'sustainable development' – with the spectres of the resource curse and debt-based monetary slavery bedevilling Africa coming into mind (Burgis, 2015). Providing the massive evidence is the plethora of measures that are democratic to some but non-democratic to others, friendly to some and hostile to others, nationalistic to some but acts of terrorism to others, voluntary to some and involuntary to others. Failure of more positive answers means more wicked problems for the constituency, paradoxically, which the vision-mission statements promise to resolve.

In conclusion, thus far, the sustainable development road has proved rough, foggy and slippery with no massive, tangible results appealing to all players, in particular the political leadership eager to conquer VUCA stressors and stabilise the society and economy. As

physical laws remind us, motions have overt and subtle transformational impacts at source and upon landing, naturally demanding utmost refinement, more so against extremes in externality. Apart from gambling with the market model, sustainable development is under immense challenge, with Furukawa's Fusion of Knowledge and Geisler's *Homo technicus* visions still a distant dream. In spite of the vision-mission avalanche, the nation is choker-bloc with risky vortexes in varying magnitudes of acceleration, reflecting accidents waiting to happen, happening, having happened or still unknown but certain to happen. Progress to counter the escalating human insecurity remains haphazard, riddled with downgrade impacts, including enduring kulakazation of the peasantry. In the meantime, as the institutions put it, they are still undergoing capacity building and will not be stampeded into action, however pressing the challenges. On its part, sustainable development has survived the contradictions, coalescing and strongly shaping and influencing multiple interests, including the curriculum-management policy discourse.

6.6 A Critical Overview

Notwithstanding the extensive critique given so far, a more overarching view is fitting to consolidate the research questions whether, having chewed and chocked, how much of the philosophy deserves swallowing and how much to spit out. The baseline challenge is: what are we to make of it? It is back to Adizes' (2015) and the participants that, for the statements to live up to the expected hype, the institution must 'walk the talk' and live them, which means "truly inspiring and channelling the energy of every employee in the same direction" (Smit, 2006, p.164), failing which they are worthless, empty rhetoric. Nationally, in line with neo-liberal thinking, they must spur capacity to salvage the Zim-Asset economy.

But, on the downside, as repeatedly pronounced, the infrastructures are rocking: distorting and misrepresenting the institutional reality – a bland reality strained and stained by the degenerative bureau and expanding *Homo simplex* conditions, with the institutional products struggling to come to grips with the practical realities of the ambient challenges (Gundani, 2015; Parliament of Zimbabwe, 2011; Sharara, 2015).

Quite conspicuous is the fact that vision-mission statements are not new; that they depict smooth flowing, nice sounding utopian frames; and that they leverage convergent thinking or positive stunts about the status quo in contradistinction to the high-handed policy

fundamentals of conservatism, centralism and an acidic environment. In total envy of the gold standard, they persuade all to rally behind “‘the pursuit of excellence’ or ‘the discovery and transmission of knowledge’ and, in the end, they resemble ‘rhetorical pyrotechnics’ – that is, nice, melodious audio of little structural consequence, except to lay claim to important terrain even where the institutions enjoy qualified competence to serve their normative adventures” (Morphew and Hartley, 2006, p.459).

Operationally, multiple pros and cons continue to trip the system. The one-size-fits-all definition means that what the NUST and the CUT do must not only be identical, but must also be identical with the University of Cambridge or the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT). Further, what they do to each other, they must do likewise to Cambridge or MIT and vice versa. There are no shortcuts and therein lies the trappings of the QA footprint. Locational and developmental conditions do not matter. The newcomers must adeptly match the well-established institutions. Hence, on a day to day basis, the statements are of bland significance, merely to inspire idle aspirations or to rekindle lost glory. The institutions relive the delusion of the catch-up myth subjecting themselves and their constituencies to the drain and strain of a mischievously uncompromising optimization imperative whose complexities implode the vicious cycle of ‘disvalue education’. To reiterate, the knowledge explosion, coupled with resource scarcities accelerates the flood of theoretical knowledge whose conventional pedagogy generates more impertinent skills, escalating challenges which, ironically, the statements promise to resolve.

In legacy terms, Clark (1986, p.20) states it well that the “severe effect of the simplified definition of purpose is that the statements mislead those who believe them, raise expectations that will be dashed and promote quarrels that cannot be resolved.” Life’s more realistic and controversial ideals of global and local intrigues, the psycho-ethnic revolutions, the Africa disease syndrome, and the unsustainable reverse food chains, to name a few, do not feature in the visions-missions story. Hence, coupled with difficulties of measurement, the statements flourish uncontested, difficult to prove that the institution is on course or is migrating way off its vision, or is fictitiously operating at business-as-usual, pure and simple.

It would appear institutional behaviour is influenced more by the mathematics of congruence coupled to the doctrine of sameness, which belies the tendency to emulate prime institutions

hook, line, and sinker. The irony is, whether West or South, despite the identical design of the learning operations the resulting affects or ultimate perceptions and conceptions are markedly different, gravitating towards the sub-standard grade in the South. Utopianism rather than extropianism dominates the mind-sets entertaining high-heaven dreams that are hard to achieve: perchance, way beyond local capabilities at this point in time. In the process, save being politically correct, the institutions are blinded and made untrue and unrealistic to their situations and populations.

This is to say the grand plan to civilise capitalism sustains but, in the process, breeding the false infinite or proxy capitalism and its lopsided infinities outlined in chapter 2. Clearly, the benumbed vision-mission jargon degrades, substitutes, demeans, confuses, changes, transmogrifies and destabilizes the human condition and the people's socio-cultural conceptions of themselves, fostering pseudo-capitalist natures, with the traditional lying alongside the modern in convoluted relationships. In spite of all the bombardment, the utopian emancipation shows greater capacity to know rather than to apply, to consume rather than to build, to maintain rather than to capitalise, and to sell the labour to the next willing buyer. The people are for capitalism for its coveted benefits but not necessarily to acquire its inner spirit and ethics, hence, they soon relapse to their traditional milieu when the stakes rise, as the state grapples haplessly with a broadening and deepening MPI.

Furthermore, the technocapitalism is materially at odds and socially and culturally at cross-purposes with the vernacular cultures. Echoing Tung (1999) and Gwatidzo (1999), Mnkandla (2006) and Pipim (2013) observe how the civilizing is responsible for the ruinous psychological atrocities reflected in the 'identification crisis' and 'philosophical dilemma' across the entire educational pyramid. The educated elite find themselves more of imitation Englishmen or Frenchmen well versed in Western technology and culture but challenged in terms of pertinent skills for leadership and management of the development of the Zimbabwean society. It is as if education for the ambitious is a preparation for a destiny in England, Europe, or the USA and certainly not in their own village, or their own country, or any other African country other than South Africa, ironically, with the latter progressively perceiving themselves less African.

To Sachs (1992, p.285), the *Homo simplex* dilemma is an indication of how the psychosocial

changes have been both seductive and traumatic, disembedding and alienating the people from their roots, subordinating them to unaccustomed life ethics and time rhythms, forcing them to value arms' length relations higher than family relations; to "experience increasing tress and to regard it as normal, to accept jobs without motivation and under conditions of poor wage labour and commodity fetishism, and to define the competitive struggle of all against all as the correct social synthesis." For the liberated citizenry, disembedded from its concrete contexts, contemptuous of vernacular values and bewildered by modernity, it willingly rationalises its own oppression: reduced to perpetual *job-seekers* in the labour market, *contract workers* in farms, industry and commerce, socio-economic *vendors* and diaspora *migrants*, and *pawns* for politicians in the midst of grave threats and risks to livelihoods. In short, the *Homo simplex* gap sustains and continues to torpedo the development efforts, ironically, with both traditional and modern livelihoods progressively beyond the reach of many, while simultaneously spawning the dilemma of lost future generations. Such is the aging and deterioration following the shallow diagnoses the applications and implications of technocapitalism.

American progress is in concert with the vision-mission statements of the Universities of Illinois, the VU and other dynamics of that system. Through massive, diverse information, profit and power are successfully reconciled, whatever the challenges, to master the technology exponential syndrome. From the vision-mission statements of the science and technology institutions, Zimbabwe ought to be a hi-tech *guru* on the African continent. On the contrary, substituting the de-industrialization is a plethora of foreign technologies that parade and command the economic space, spawning economic dependence, technological imperialism and cultural confusions. The research prefers robot technology to affordable health care devices and environmental appliances, while value addition is less a constant to expand investment, but a new fetish masquerading as an economic strategy. The 4Es–EIAA platform continues to under-perform much to the under-empowerment of that most exposed constituency – poor urban and rural women. Whereas the Singaporean experience succeeded at the expense of the politics, it is unlikely to repeat locally given the rigidity of the status quo. Ultimately, the host of challenges arising from slack in conversion efficiency render the economy dependent on, and vulnerable to, external sources for multiple intermediate and high-tech resources, equipment and installations (Gundani, 2015).

By extension, from the vision-mission statements of agricultural institutes, agricultural productivity anchored on a sound ecocratic culture ought to be extensively widespread (taking after the status of the SADC food basket). On the contrary, food imports and food aid have become the norm in the face of mounting hunger and starvation amid faminogenic practices, while environmental degradation is responsible for the desertification and expanding wastelands across the physical landscape – the eloquent vision-mission statements notwithstanding.

Also, from the commerce units of the universities and colleges, in conjunction with the Institutes of Chartered Accountants, of Secretaries and Administrators, and of Bankers, etc. efficient, competent administration of public offices, accounting, insurance and banking services, institutions and organizations, with stimulating entrepreneurial innovations, ought to be the shared, popular vision and gold standard across the economy. On the contrary, regardless of the constitutional provisions such as the ‘No Conflicts Rule’ and the ‘No Profit Rule’, among many forms of cybercrime and reigning supreme are incompetence, inefficiency, opportunism, corruption, fraud, externalization, looting of enterprise assets and escaping accountability, among many tricks, through denial, impunity, creative accounting and liquidation via judicial management (Magaisa, 2016; *Zimind*, 2015). The predatory shadowy state continues its gainful supremacy prejudicial to the formal state, while in larger numbers, students swam humanities and commercial programmes to manage an economy they have neither built nor created and, ironically which, through middlemanship, they proceed to plunder.

Therefore, whereas moral efficiency ought to be the *in-situ* pedigree, the challenges reflect how, on the contrary, the various shades of immorality, ranging from deliberate and conspiratory human deprivation and exploitation to environmental injustice and abuse, reign supreme across the psychosocial scapes. In spite of the curriculum displaying the appropriate compassion and other humanitarian skills and, therefore, the grooming of full thoroughbreds, the disturbing trend is the extent the moral decadence is gaining more ground than losing it to a technological society espousing positive emotional intelligence.

Such are the implications of the shallow diagnosis on the workings of technocapitalism. Called into question (confirmed in the post-fieldwork interviews) is how the states of affairs

are not as visionarily concretized as the statements would allow us to believe. What exists on the ground is a long wish list, a catalogue of good intentions still to see the light of day. This leaves the vision-science outlook somewhat threadbare unable to reconcile the profit-power-uncertainty motive through building the critical middleclass mass to support the technocapitalism. From a philosophical perspective, it resembles a bundle of 'paradigm shifts' still to undergo reforms that never reform; a complex, zero sum-game fixated on the status quo and at varying stages of decay as the aging and deterioration both broaden and deepen (Robertson, 2015).

The predicament is not exclusive to the institutions. Even business, the owner of the philosophy, is reeling under the miscarriage, causing Kwaramba (2016) to conclude that the statements are now 'useless'. According to Nwagbara (2011, p.85), an observation shared by Pipim (2013), all this is sufficient evidence of the ravages of the Theory of Learned Helplessness defined as the condition when an "organism learns that its reinforcements are independent of its responses (to mean that it lacks control over its responses), and this learning undermines the motivation to initiate further instrumental responses." To echo Ngwenya (2016), not only does the negativity reduce the motivation to positively respond to similar situations to reverse the disorder, through carrying the experiences of defeat, conquest, domination and repression to new environments, the socialization indoctrinates the people to accept their own oppression as rational destiny.

Given the high amplitude of constituency matters, what kind of a philosophy must the institutions employ? There are no known state-of-the-art models to perfect the constructions, and those that exist are of Western origin and taste, hence, the incompatibility dilemma. The systems are, therefore, left to bargain on measures as if to say 'probably it can work and even if it fails we would have tried our best'. The future can only be fancied with history playing an uncertain role, if any at all. Yizengaw (2003, p.16) best captures the dilemma facing higher education, maintaining that it

has to constantly change and adjust to the wide variety of situations...be they political, social, economic, cultural, etc; it should never lose ground and speed and fall behind whatever the situations...It should continue to guide the future of development, being the cornerstone and instrument of hope, and the centrepiece in the national capacity building, sustainable development and poverty reduction endeavours of any government.

Besides the myth that given enough resources government will do good work (Hill, 2009), the coercive validation exposes higher education to festering philosophical and ideological dust storms. Given the macro engines, the statements breed misconceptions that brand the institutions a compact social mass advancing combatively and continuously towards a renewed future. But, in sync with Streck (1996), contrary to the view that the statements are *the* most valued catalyst galvanising the pulsating institutional profiles, the investigation reveals institution-building as a non-epic linearity but contradictory and ambiguous process reflected in the historical processes of struggle and liberation. You need not spell status quo in order to smell the arguments it uses to propagate its interests in order to secure itself a buffer, while the bureaucrats use the vested monopoly positions to enlarge their own parochial interests.

Strongly compromised is the condition of Prime, with the institutions even suspicious of any freedom that occasionally comes their way. For instance, to echo Clark (1986), rather than 'experiment, wander and diversify', they voluntarily gage themselves and succumb to the heuristic persuasive cues of the prestige syndrome, with the NUST Industrial Attachment (Internship) programme a good example, and now adopted by virtually all. Whereas full efficacy in terms of the core psycho-technics is suspect given that the courses of study are yet-to-be-completed, the programme is most cherished for its financial and other windfalls. Meanwhile, the impotence of the vision-mission model against the hardening status quo, which marches on oblivious of the initiative, invites further scepticism on its prospects.

Such are the embedded costs the people have to endure in the drive to access Capital's technology. The inherent malfunctions render the construct guilty of the 'spiritual trick': that perceptual mode that simultaneously offers visions of the truth, good and evil from everywhere and nowhere, equally and fully; a narrative of the universal truth that both cripples and denies others their rights, privileges and interests to boost human existence. The ensuing epistemological and cultural confusions are euphemistically justified as cultural dynamism breeding crude understandings and mundane misconceptions on the trials and tribulations surrounding struggle and liberation.

To round off, the jury's explicit verdict about the vision-mission philosophy is clear between a momentous construct and an expediency, verbally world class but functionally normal/

adequate, reflecting evidentialism as the missing link at inception. It was difficult to tell the direct impact of the statements distinct from endogenous changes which would still occur with or without them. Hence, the proposition disclaims the view that the vision-mission statements are *the* default yardstick propelling and revolutionising higher education's technology–sustainable development dividend. So far, they have registered no enduring impact the mandates, except to shore up a mock bureaucracy and its brand of uncertainties. It is an acknowledged policy standpoint no one is taken to task for failing to fulfil it. Any echoes across corridors and classrooms hardly carry the ideal strength, motivation and fit to unmask the robust web of relations and succession of happenings befitting a nation yearning for change amid throes of awkward transitions.

6.7 Summary

Special deliverables comprising excellence, research-innovation-entrepreneurship, the leadership-committee system, moral efficiency, and sustainable development were identified and explicated. Emerging was how the construct was as much the basis for inter- and intra-institutional engagements as it was the premise for heterogeneous management-curriculum matters. However, both old and new operational challenges, with the system both challenged and failing where it mattered most, reduced its efficacy to fascination with myopia. As the technocapitalism unfolds, the complexities of sustainable capitalist development continue to vex the institutional metric which has become as intriguing as visioning the visions themselves. The next chapter consolidates the rich discussion to this point towards some more befitting conclusions and recommendations.

CHAPTER VII

7.0 SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

7.1 Introduction

This chapter consolidates the multiple issues raised in the various sections of the study. It gives a fuller insight and foresight into the main research question, and the emergent strengths, gains, losses and weaknesses encountered. Following the summary review of the literature and fieldwork, it synthesises the conclusion according to the research questions highlighting the aspired benefits, concerns and reservations the participants expressed about the statements, before proceeding to theoretical implications, the study recommendations, and wraps up with suggestions/recommendations for further research. Summed up, the study was a scholarly aggregation-disaggregation of the vision-mission philosophy as a subject of public interest designed to fire up the institutional portfolios to prominent levels.

7.2 Summary

The study investigated the rationale for the vision-mission statements as the default policy yardstick driving the institutional mandates. At the forefront is whether, injected as rocket fuel into institutional practice, it proceeds to induce the dynamic thrust to the potential learning product easing access, realisation and achievement of the much sought after technological society goal the backbone to sustainable development. In the absence of local empirical literature, specifically in the context of science and technology education, evidence was inconclusive to justify the construct's wholesale adoption. Now a ubiquitous phenomenon across higher education, the statements constitute the springboard to the technological infinite, that is, infinite production, infinite consumption, infinite growth, and infinite development, and other critical pressing goals to usher the technological society. In that vein, it is fitting that the institutions constantly question their strategies and the wisdom to maintain, adopt and adapt particular philosophies, worldviews, practices and experiences.

By definition, the vision-mission statements are the foresighted and farsighted construct that reduce the intangible visionary persona into tangible, public platforms accessible to everyone, powering the academy forward towards high expectations in terms of development excellence emulating the gold standard. As a response signal, they portray the manner social

actors react to particular power plays, discourses, locatedness, environments and time and how they proceed to construct, understand and manipulate their world. It is one of the long list of emancipatory theorems representing different types of truths, designs and plans to strengthen institutional theory that an organization such as a university succeeds when everyone both inside and outside agrees that it is a university sufficiently equipped to spearhead human advancement (Morphew and Hartley, 2006).

Structurally, excellent and/or good statements incorporating the two hardware and two software elements of the Ashridge model to ground and buoy the mandates to new levels never experienced before, are the standard. An import from business, higher education mulls the philosophy to emulate or duplicate the market model and, therefore, stimulate creativity, innovativeness, knowledge acquisition and sharing, professionalism, team work and diversity, equity and much more. Hence the nuclei of terms pivoted on 'excellence, world class, premier, hub' on a mission to 'provide, contribute, enable, cultivate and produce' innovative solutions to scientific, technological and socio-environmental problems dominate the narrative. With technocapitalism or globalization-business, profit-power initiatives and complexities strongly behind the emulation of the market model, wholesale proselytising has ensued, with the statements impacting multiple institutional undertakings.

Ontological, epistemological, methodological, and normative ideals configure the statements. As the dynamic motive force galvanizing institutional operations, the construct advances the multi-philosophical dialectics of strategic studies, idealism, pragmatism, continuous improvement, and systems thinking and the related inputs, outcomes and impacts critical in advancing the human skills and organizational growth and development. In sum, the statements are the front for the paradigm of technocapitalism rooted in pristine entrepreneurial psycho-technics whose focus is the uncompromising optimization imperative to mastermind the 'academic-productivity-humanitarian' interface towards full autarky, with the SADC Industrialization Strategy a case in point.

To bolster the paradigm, the statements strategically position the core footprints of constituency servicing targeting issues of the development superstructure, entrepreneurship and community service; governance, involving the faculty-administration oversight roles of mandating, facilitating, endorsing and partnering; quality assurance, aimed at the academic

infrastructures of teaching and learning, research and innovation, resource supplies, and protocols and specifications; comportment, the instilling of the values-standards of technocracy, the normative-virtues/ethics canon, and environmental justice; and, lastly, through grading, reviews, audits, accreditation, the GSIF and other self-check and monitoring mechanisms, the evaluation footprint. The footprints constitute technocapitalism's stock-in-trade, the prime goal and emblem when fulfilled. The challenge is how far the institutions understand this and work to achieve it.

As defined, the problem was, given such an overarching role, does the all-purpose, purpose role render the statements the most ideal instrument for non-market rationality to promote more and better, mutually acceptable, Pareto efficient, life-work behaviour outcomes? In the footsteps of McDonalidization, the spectrum exudes the bureaucratic principles of efficiency, calculability, predictability and control for super services transforming the human motor towards AI or robotic efficiency. Internal and external audiences are well informed on the intentional purposes, cognitive purposes, motivational purposes, etc. that amount to intellectual catharsis and other educational designs and aspirations. Not only does it seemingly pull together management and curricula matters, it further unlocks ideal behaviour and process changes reaffirming technocapitalism in the institutional metric. But, given the scant literature to ascertain its efficacy and to support the wholesale global hype, it is possible the institutions have inadvertently imported a philosophy that causes them to incur known and unknown social costs more likely to escalate people misery rather than abate it. The study sought to understand the authoritative voice behind the acclamation.

Vigorous proselytising to motivate, shape behaviours/product malleability and cultivate high levels of commitment, ultimately, to positively impact employee and learner performance, has ensued. This is both to persuade and convert all stakeholders to simultaneously believe in and make the statements their working habit in pursuit of excellence. The goal is to achieve a fulfilling technocratic culture through the teaching, research, entrepreneurship and community services fulfilling the fancied HR infinite – the engine that drives government and private enterprises, utilities and projects for the state, rural and urban communities. At this point, the products can stand their own in the industrial, commercial, informal and global markets, although both graduate unemployment and local IP output decry the claim.

Playing out in real time is the singularity theorem or techno-progressivism and the great passion for STEM and GRIN technologies education as the way to go, with a lower throughput considered disingenuous. As its basis is the premise to resolve the cultural-fit versus universal-fit theory divide, hence, ridding science and technology of the plethora of fears and restrictions that cripple its generation, conduct and implementation. The scalability of the mandates needs the intellectual, persuasive power of the robust statements to prospectively leverage scientific fact and action to reconcile human intrusions for desired breakthroughs for and by a satisfied populace. The management-curriculum dexterity induces sensitivity to the fact that higher education must and will transform the technocratics of the people and nation.

For only a fully-fledged technogarchy is able to resolve human problems: to control the paradox of progress and arrest the see-saw irony of opportunity versus loss of opportunity, of growth prospects versus foreclosure brakes the science and technology goes through. From the empirical evidence, suffice to say several deliverables highlighted subsequently constitute the backbone to the technocapitalist aspiration. In the mould of a steroid, the statements inspire the brainpower critical to nurture the products' intelligence, power of observation and creative imagination to harness the consciousness energy particles of atom, cell and spiriton, un-observed by the accidents of personal habitat and culture.

Based on the vision-mission statements of 34 institutions, the study built the footprints conceptual framework as the basis for the interrogation of the problem. The post-positivist paradigm decomposed through research questions and the mixed method approach comprising document analysis, the diversity survey, and interviews was the basis of the investigation on the market status of the vision-mission statements. Using heterogeneity sampling, a class of 110 participants drawn from the multiple-case of four science and technology universities, according to the institutional hierarchy, participated in the study. Enumerative content analysis and survey questionnaires were used to solicit, elicit and record the data, the former for document sources and interviews and the QCA program for the survey data. The latter was a four-point ordinal rating scale comprising: inadequate/sub-standard (I/S), normal/adequate (N/A), functional/commendable (F/C), and exceptional/world class (E/W) ratings. Tables, matrices and graphs were used for data presentation and analysis, pending aggregation and interpretation.

However, legendary is the immense potential for both forced and unforced errors as a result of a host of factors the bulk of which have been discussed in the critical overview in the last chapter. Briefly, among them are the rational ignorance effect, the special interest effect, and the short-sightedness effect, generating limitations that impinge and stifle the envisioned dream, hence, echoing Morley's (2003) viewpoint that, rather than a forceful response to existing conditions and problems, the constructions are more a discourse in which both problems and solutions are created, with unintended consequences. Apart from the obsession and naivety of an exciting innovation, there is little evidence of the electrification or rocket propulsion fuel galvanising greater prospects for the Heaven scenario and/or greater resilience against the growing Hell scenario in the face of extractive politics, the calamitous economy and other aspects of VUCA. Acutely toxic are the bureaucracy dictionary and external pressures and the psychosocial contradictions both induce, signifying the heavy burden the bureaucracy-globalization elephants continue to inflict on the institutions and their beneficiaries.

Top most are the soft and hard infrastructural constraints which have rendered the construct unable to sustain the much-coveted pivotal emblem of excellence and/or world class status. The overly competitive conditions, often perceived as hostile or apathetic, generate immense anxiety which triggers the survival mode as the best way to go. Doing well is therefore a function of self-preservation rather than one's capability to pursue higher critical and creative frameworks fulfilling social imperatives. Hence, the nation remains challenged in terms of capital goods, especially enginery creations and adaptations that are the backbone for sustainable development. The Zim-Asset touched a raw nerve on the traditional theory-practice mismatch, with the ailing economy "still facing a challenge of a curriculum that does not match the developmental needs of the country (p.22).

The institutions, though, argue that such demands for spontaneous results on a process which cannot be dictated to are responsible for derailing the delivery of the visions. As everything that matters most, thinking and efficiency are constrained inviting criticism of the bandwagon-drag effect symbolised by the gridlocked mind-sets fanning the dependency syndrome. In the process, the construct reduces to plain everywhere statements resembling the proverbial half-full/half-empty glass devoid of professional justification. Rather than

disruptive innovations in the footsteps of Western materialism, the technocapitalism borders on the usual routines that barely go beyond the statements' everydayness.

Meanwhile, representing the 'principal', headquarters is often at odds with, and nervous of institutional diversity, differentiation, variety, redundancy and other forms of market disorder to which it responds with dedifferentiation and other bureaucratic manoeuvres. Typically, the bureaucratic inertia vests preference on simplicity and routines (management by minutes/memoranda), punishment, uniformity, popularity, loyalty, consistency, monopoly, patronage, obedience, and rigidity in order to promote more order, predictable efficiency, stability and happiness, with both hidden and open perverse effects. Scientifically, the linguistic levels and uniformity struggle to carry product research beyond adoption and adaptation. Expanding Clark (1986, p.132), the manoeuvres presage a decision making whose very forte is to advise, recommend, confer, draw up budgets, testify, develop plans, write rules, procedures and guidelines, report, supervise, propose curricula, assist, meet, argue, train, consult, reprimand – 'but *decide?*' (*Emphasis original*) – on the main, skills and ethics averse to the critical techno-values of complexity, practical rigour, complication and sophistication.

Last, adding to the challenges are the crippling effects of resource shortages, balancing the three-statement status quo, and the dilemma of the institutions as cultural museums, work places, custodial centres and centres of political and economic activity for the outside world. And, additionally, is the dilemma of rankings with the institutions paying more attention to rankings and the tendency to gloss over inherent problems to achieve upgrades rather than the hard realities which catapult them to junk status. Ultimately, the envisioned technocapitalism largely offers the learners crutches when they can walk on their own, disproportionately off-loading more elites and/or dead weight and derelicts, hence, serving as fertile ground for rent seeking behaviour while giving greater credence to lopsided industrialism enslaved to adoption and adaptation of foreign technologies. In the process, the statements pose as a supernova for some and a black hole for others, with both the institutions and the nation left vulnerably exposed.

The euphoria is equivalent to fascination with myopia, or to the ecological fallacy of the whole being greater than the sum of its parts, wormed by Morley's (2003, p.6) elements of moral panic: "mounting tension, concern, powerlessness, hostility, consensus, volatility and

anxiety” generating bland prestige, false dawns and a naive worldliness. To echo Kwaramba (2016, p.2), it is proving hard to conjure up time when the institutions “stop playing around with cute slogans and tag lines and start living the statements.” Unable to withstand the onslaught, the institutions resign fate to the bureaucracy fort, constraining and crippling the needed buoyancy and intellectual forte, and misdirecting than fervently addressing the intricacies of the technological society in the face and amidst the plight of the rising volumes of *Homo simplex* and the attendant people misery.

Contrasted, there are more challenges than opportunities confronting the vision-mission philosophy. Weighed against the odds, the narrative revealed a background of a very much challenged constituency servicing; a distressed, circumspect governance; a highly fraught quality assurance; a cautiously sublime comportment; and more rhetorical than substantive evaluations. The high incidences of both tame and wicked problems portray the statements as a mixture of multiple manoeuvres that are merely Messianic than they are fundamentally endogenous attempts at education change and reform. As the conclusion drawing proceeds to show, against the elusive and resistant technocapital ailment, the philosophy amounts to a weak, expired palliative, psychosocially generating both optimism and pessimism to soothe than to treat the chronic condition.

7.3 Conclusions

From the standpoint of the central question: how does the vision-mission rationale galvanise the institutional mandates to foster the technological society for sustainable development? Put another way: practically, what do the institutions seek to achieve from the vision-mission policy arsenal? The average mean rating of 2.4 and standard deviation of 0.76 revealed N/A as the most dominant rating, while the acclaimed E/W was the lowest across all the footprints, dropping from 20% in the CS footprint to 5% in the QA footprint (see Table 5.6). On average, 14% and 34% of the variables were rated I/S and N/A, respectively. The cause for concern was further confirmed by document sources and interviews, much of whose optimism was instantly countered by the deteriorative wrecking of the system from the plethora of problems and challenges. This strengthened the study’s proposition that the vision-mission statements do not play a buoyantly transformative role in the institutional mandates. Among the support staff and students, except for full awareness, the rest of the indicator variables were relatively

mixed, more so ownership which was quite controversial and equivocal about the role and status of the statements.

The open conclusion is that there is an element of naivety about the capacity of the vision-mission statements to generate and inspire the dreams and aspirations being proclaimed. The stubborn roadblocks render them limited, undoable, negligible rhetoric, neither adding much value to, nor discounting anything within, the institutional metric, marked by weak strength, motivation and fit. Given the equivocation, it was just one of the usual burdens the institutions must carry; a marginal rather than a dynamic template inspiring the all-embracing uncompromising optimization imperative and other pragmatic endeavours. It was still a long way to go to duly translate the parameters of the philosophy into the choice E/W and just what the institutions want, deserve and work by.

The following syntheses sum up participant views on the wherewithal of the construct, that, having tested it, whether it tastes like spring wine, or dead wine, or tap water, or some lukewarm combination, sourced from Tables and Matrices 4.1 – 4.5.

7.3.1 Justification for the adoption of the vision-mission philosophy as the default policy yardstick by higher education institutions in Zimbabwe

First, the evidence pointed to the philosophy as the backbone to the constituency servicing meta-themes of excellence, research-innovation-entrepreneurship, moral efficiency, the leadership-committee system, and sustainable development. Despite the predominantly N/A rating the construct was not only a viable proposition marketable across all spaces, it was the masterstroke to the teaching, research, internships and rankings, to transform labour skills, to develop endogenous technologies, to transfer and adapt exotic technologies, and to adopt and indigenise the economy towards greater competitiveness that measures to the gold standard. Its adoption was no longer an option but, officially, a critical requirement as the following excerpts portray:

- (i) good statements of intent (if only they were more personalised) to ensure that the institution does not lose sight of its mandate, and through strategic plans, is working to achieve it.
- (ii) give essence and meaning to institutional planning and links directly with strategic plan.

- (iii) to know who we are, otherwise we are radarless; very valid, capture the dictates of the time.
- (iv) to mainstream many issues in the strategic plan; well crafted, people only need to adhere to the letter and spirit therein.
- (v) very wise with strong merits and promising if reviewed regularly to match their purpose.

This is in-keeping with the aspirations of the potential learning product. The exhortations echo Clark's (1986, p.20) observation that such constructs always emerge as a result of the rapid "expansions and fragmentations of knowledge causing academics to seek reassurance in formulations that promise to pull things together again and provide some overarching meaning", resulting in the proliferation of "purportedly new statements" packed with alteration phrases of dubious distinction. Therefore, not only do the statements serve to constantly goad the institutions to up-grade and maintain attractive facilities, amenities and teaching-learning spaces at world class standards in order to attract the best minds from everywhere across the globe, it is through them that the prime base-work principle, as the cornerstone for the desired expertise, performance and lifestyle, can be realised.

Specifically, the technological society vision-mission is premised on the ideology that science works: it makes things work; it is talents and wisdom that produce practical results and products; things are done right and rightly, correctly and precisely, ensuring maximum resource appropriations. The technologically powered intelligence, both human and artificial, induces capacity mobilization to generate robotic efficiency against the vagaries of *Homo simplex* and environmental disorders. The launch of the 'STEM' education programme has added further impetus to the science-technology cultural drive. Indeed, given the massive scientific-technological advances there is no reason why such a position should remain untenable and eluding the bulk of the people.

Viewed actively, through propelling human advancement or development excellence, the construct engenders the dynamic modification in-keeping with civilizing capitalism for the people and by the people themselves. The impact is better understood institutions, well poised to be identified with, and to leverage the much-sought technology society for sustainable development. Barring the challenges surrounding the transfer of sustainability to the constituency at large, the construct is politically and bureaucratically apt.

However, in the midst of the accolades, and outstanding, is how, despite international acclaim, the educated workforce skills continue to be of marginal consequence locally, mostly ideal for routine maintenance, repair and service functions rather than the springboard for vibrant domestic growth, development and sustainability. Defining the N/A rating is how the HR standard is numerically and physiologically fragile (a drop at Kariba or across drought-prone Zimbabwe); weak in diversity; limited in knowledge, skills and values; infinitesimal in ideas, inventions and innovations; vitiating in productivity, entrepreneurship, consumption and governance; and is riddled with fractious communications and conspiracies – not ideal resources to spark vibrant national inspiration.

Not only has the core value of scientific controversy become a rare breed, substituted by the ideals of fixed knowledge facts now the boon and bane of the teaching and learning, on the increase are the spectres of more non-usable, blind usage, misuse, abuse and redundancy of the acquired knowledge, skills and values (conscious incompetence). Functionally, the commodified product knows: it knows all the theory there is to know, and it does not know the vagaries of empty knowledge as it gropes to commercialise findings that have always been known and applied in other environments *ad infinitum*. Suboptimal cognition more than unqualified intelligence contributed to the adoption of the philosophy.

7.3.2 Practical steps to enhance the productivity of the construct.

There was empirical evidence of practical steps to enhance the construct's productivity or its curricular strength. Behind the technocapitalist push is the dense network of conventional and novel academic-physical infrastructures of which, in addition to the 60 programmes, equipmentation, research days and exhibitions, are research and innovation offices, MoUs on STEM and health education, industrial parks and agro-investments (institutional farms and industries), coupled with research output of products, services and workflows to address local challenges. With the expansions of the STEM programme involving Doctoral and Masters Degrees in Technology, there was potential to rejuvenate curricula to new heights to witness expansion of the Sniderman model of Movers and Shakers, Experimenters, Star Executives, etc. if not locally engineered cluster models.

Further, quality strategic plans incorporating results-based management (RBM) were in place, while through parallel progressions, the institutions recognise the long-term goal of recruiting and retaining top academics as well as attracting gifted young academics and researchers to plug turnover gaps. On the social front is commitment modelling through environmental clean-up campaigns, staff-student (financial) contributions to infrastructure development, as well as physical publicity and inclusion in multiple documents like reports, handbooks and websites. Last, the statements make up the bulk of the triumphalism typifying official speeches, with additional putsch from oversight bodies like ZIMCHE, all of which enhance competitiveness.

By 2014, the total annual output stood at 1900 skilled professionals and intellectuals who, technocratically, exude appropriate stamina and perfect strength, motivation and fit to address the demands of the development superstructure. They possess the critical aptitudes of initiative, creativity, new knowledge, modern culture, politics, and business acumen and must proceed to demonstrate the intellectualism surrounding the franchising. In more detail, the foot-troopers are imbued with: scientific, medical, technological, engineering and technical rationality skills; mathematical and statistical techniques and predictive analytics skills; computer-ICT/digital proficiency and infographics (creations, processing, editing, contracting and reporting) skills; critical thinking, decision making, problem solving, commercial entrepreneurial and legal rationality skills; leadership, patriotism, influence and relationship-building skills, as well as integrity, accountability, altruism, and community service skills. This is the intellectual engine whose immense potential diffuses the national philosophy of a technological society for a sustainable future.

However, the challenge is how much of this is true positive and/or false positive. From events on the ground, the envisaged workforce competitiveness remains hard to fathom. Furthermore, although even challenged in these, at best the products exude Haden's (2012) nominal qualities of 'great' employees: reliable, dependable, proactive, diligent, good leaders and great followers. Resembling a needle in a haystack and hard to fathom are the 'remarkable' employee qualities of 'operating beyond job descriptions; being both eccentric and serious about work; the drive to prove others wrong beyond the desire to do a good job; and always fiddling for the best ideas that work.'

Operationally, challenged is the capacity to stimulate the ‘uncompromising optimization imperative’ befitting the superintelligent technological society sufficiently grounded in the technocapitalist mould. The Masters qualification among the bulk of the personnel, coupled with the limited working experiences of 10 years and below bolsters Providers than even Improvers let alone Thinkers and Builders, with greater focus on paper pushers in the mode of ‘officers, researchers, consultants and extensionists’ than typical GRIN technologies and STEM trades. Debasingly, with the workforce more concerned to earn money and rarely to fulfil the vision-mission mandates *per se*, made worse by slack monitoring, images and reputations continue to be tarnished.

Accolades aside, STEM education and its ilk is never the purest and safest proposition. For one, the localization drive not only faces the dilemma of insufficient capital and infrastructure resources to enable it to work perfectly and precisely, just what the doctor ordered, practically, the Western summer it promises amounts to an endurance platform to contend with Africa’s perpetual wintry-drought conditions. If anything, therefore, it is the visa to re-entrench, through official fiat, technological dependency, corruption and subjugation to the might of technological and imperialist hegemony.

7.3.3 Stakeholder views on the efficacy of the vision-mission construct

The lavish praise was tempered by concerns on the utilitarian value of the construct. On one hand, its perceived influence runs deep and wide: energising hopes, uplifting expectations and crowning aspirations following in the footsteps of global success stories achieved through such robust vision-mission statements. Not only was it a very marketable proposition, it was long overdue to replace the old, non-achieving frameworks, in particular to inject vigour and vitality to address the basic need for definition and direction on issues of purpose, strategy, values and work-ethics, crowned with benchmarking with world class examples. Taken more literally than seriously, the utopia bonds everybody and everything together, providing the roadmap to steer and guide the ship forward.

To its credit, it inspires the LEADERSHIP acronym or bandwidth and action logics related to: Legacy, Exemplary, Accountability, Decision making, Ethics, Responsibility, Significance, Hard work, Integrity/Intelligence, and Pursuit of praxis and enlightenment at all times. The

variables complement the construct's default policy yardstick further. For example, the legacy principle avers that by the end of the leader's term of office, the system must display a collectively and singularly remarkable legacy, rich with teams of self-motivated and empowered colleagues, stakeholders and customers, all capable of concrete decisions that meet the universal wellbeing of the institution. In addition to which are the moral efficiency adaptation hallmarks of thoughtful action, tolerance, fairness, the rule of law, as well as criticism, prudence and care at all times, making it the basis for clinical leadership and other apex conceptualization skills. Notwithstanding the drawbacks of public science communication, the construct was destined for a long shelf-life, ultimately impacting the *Techno sapiens* transformation of society through science.

On the other hand, concern and dissatisfaction were just as stinging. Among the rampant errors of omission and commission, they cited issues of an expensive folly, elitist emblems/ sugar candy mountain; *laissez-faire* and lackadaisical attitudes and perceptions, wormed by lip-service, bribery, cynicism, endless excuses and the tendency to sweep things under the carpet; hard line, injudicious leadership and management that leaves the statements merely aspirational rather than something that must be lived, with the values of commitment, integrity and honesty not fully enforced, hence, the prevalence of rotten eggs with fuzzy commitments that take advantage of the situations, threatening the entire fabric of the institution.

Furthermore, the management transformations were conspicuously morbid than proportionate with the Waitely maxim and the shift from hierarchy and control to synergy, self-mobilization and teamwork. Given the aging, decay and a variety of other causes, virtually all the footprints were unravelling, more so governance, QA and comportment at great expense to the nation. From the ensuing dereliction of duty, coupled with the philosophy's sub-marginal benefits, it was most apposite to drop the statements.

7.3.4 The role of the vision-mission statements in the transformation of science and technology education

Beyond the compass helping track relevance and progress, to their credit the statements are the steppingstone behind the casting of the human motor–technocapitalist template. They inspire greater strength and capacity for innovative scientific practices to muster the

localization and indigenization of all generated dynamics. This is to say that they not only promote but inspire the technological fix theory as the veritable standard and determinant of the ground rules within which the games of human civilization get played out, hence, ingraining the knowledge and skills befitting the science-technology exponential drive. Accordingly, they prime institutional rationality with concentrative science and technological vigour ideal for industry and public space. Through the Doctor and Master of Technology programmes and in line with global trends, they are the vehicle to usher and diffuse globalization in general and the East Asian ethos in particular.

That the construct was weighing down local initiatives including a more endogenous science curriculum was out of the question; rather, the science and technology methodology given the constant criticisms. Potentially, it cements the demand for a more edupreneurship and technopreneurship curriculum comprising lecturers, researchers and students who are less theory minded; who, while theoretically equipped, are more hands-on oriented beyond the mathematics-physics chicken-egg scenario. To configure the frontiers of science more effectively, the statements need to be taught to avoid people going in all sorts of directions. Evidence from the revised statements shows just how the virtuosity has sustained becoming even more robust to scale up a sophisticated market niche (see Appendix 1).

Still the challenges of the false negative sustain. Excessive theory in the teaching and learning, coupled with rare evaluations restricted to isolated audits spoils the 'Applied' as the cornerstone of the epistemology, with the practitioners resorting to the propagation of fixed facts dictated to by authoritative sources (mainly the knowledge explosion) in the vain hope to be applied later. The curriculum is verbosely redundant than it is practically equipping in the propagation of the technology exponential syndrome. Equally, not only is mono-disciplinary research the standard, post-graduate studies are more seized with the cosmetics rather than socially functional researches that unravel the skills and ethics of complexity, practical rigour, complication and sophistication in the public space.

All this has increasingly fed more rational ignorance or the technology regression syndrome and related decay and redundancies. Currently higher education is overwhelmed by this problem whose narrative is the endless praise/blame-games. Epistemologically, the statements reincarnate the fly-on-the-wall image and dilemma for purposes of exaggeration,

one-size-fits-all (*bambazonke*) and manipulative sophistry which portray the philosophy as the proverbial management pie (*high in the sky*) advancing technological tokenism.

Put together, over thirty years down 'independence highway', rather than talk the full language of a technological society and, therefore, a Zimbabwe that is on the 'brink' or has 'taken-off' (Sharara, 2015), the nation is still reminiscing Gwatidzo (1999) and raising the same concerns and questions on the trials and tribulations of higher education. On one hand, is the dilemma of the cemetery of indigenous frameworks and, on the other, through the pervasive rags-to-riches syndrome, the promotional stigma of technocapitalist slavery. From the empirical evidence, the institutional politics has not done enough to interrogate the policy and ideological pros and cons the philosophy espouses. Since its launch in early 2000, the veto politics has been incorrect to embrace globalization's vision-mission ramifications. Instead, it has been eager to experiment with ultra-nationalism to audaciously achieve the ambitious autarky drive.

Like the rest of Africa, the target has been to uproot settlerism but never to embark on the alternative of economic espionage even when invited to do so (witness the countless nationals both studying and working abroad, and the disinclination to advance the Rhodesian regime import-substitution initiatives and its potential for reverse engineering). Ironically, reverse espionage has become the norm multiplying fake qualifications and fake degrees. Meanwhile, the high costs and elusive benefits the corporatist hegemony espouses render hard institutional capacity to break the bureaucratic stranglehold and land the right comportment investitures, visions-missions notwithstanding. More a coolant than a fuel, the statements emasculate the desired emancipation perpetuating the anaemic condition.

Aggregated, a host of factors and conditions lie behind the vested interests in the philosophy of vision-mission statements and, reminiscent of studies by Morpew and Hartley (2006) and Muzondo (2012), accounting for and impacting its diversity and adoption, revealing profound pros and cons on the statements. The higher education institutions adopted the vision-mission market model to stimulate rapid and profitable growth befitting their mandates. Through it, and in a manner never witnessed before, the model articulates and champions the message of purpose into a realistic, credible and attractive future state that is much better in all respects than obtained before. The target is to secure much more pragmatic stakeholder

engagement and involvement in sync with the organizational principles and values vis-à-vis who they serve, what should be received, and the ultimate significant socio-economic impacts consistent with the technocapitalist transformations of the human motor.

Without doubt, the construct's agenda has become a conundrum, if not an aporia leaving anyone grappling with it saddled with contradictions and paradoxes. The ultimate perceptions and conceptions reflect an inferior theoretical professionalism that is practically handicapped. Rather than concretise capitalism, the systems hatch new forms of consumptive than productive education, pushing more disruptive social cleavages. From the magnitude of opportunity costs, downstream internal and external challenges continuously scuttle the full realization of the desired dream, limiting the capacity of the statements to inspire the cherished optimization imperative that is the hallmark of their domain. Forced and unforced errors predominate peddling the traditional strictures of bureaucracy, hierarchy, alignment and extrinsic motivation that have repeatedly failed the system, but now resurrected under the obscure philosophy of vision-mission statements.

The scepticisms resurface the usual criticisms of a *fait accompli*, fad, or fly-on-the-wall; of insipid, paper tigers full of hollow platitudes and unsubstantiated suppositions barely able to effectively boost institutional portfolios to the satisfaction of all parties. The *bambazonke* nemesis stalks the construct exposing it to the all too familiar threats some of which ruined its predecessors, prompting the critique that its adoption reflected the frailties of the false infinite, Learned Helplessness and copy-write in the jaws of a rigid bureaucracy so much that, even with the inspirational surgery, the patient still dies of shock.

Hence, the claim that the statements revolutionise and enable higher education to rediscover itself, or that they are the solution *absolutus*, was not borne out by facts. Given how the science-technology yield continues to fail to function as the doctor ordered, not only is the continuous improvement rhetoric difficult to decipher, the philosophy is equivocal than it is resolute about institutional reality. Its formless generalities render it internally impotent to fire up realistically tenable positions, while advancing the East Asian ethos to diffuse through is a non-starter. Clearly evidentialism was and continues to be the missing link, with the global copy-write struggling to match local terrain. This is not reckless conservatism as it is never the intention of the critique to merely oppose or praise the status quo for all it is worth. In

vogue is the extent criticism has become unacceptable, well-nigh vulnerable to derogatory and pejorative commentary. How appropriate the observation that often, despite the Rashomon effect, truths and myths are polished into super Concords culminating in the think-alike stigma averse to other perspectives.

7.4 Theoretical implications

Like all social constructions, the statements can only be as powerful as the brains and stamina behind them if they are to overturn the tables, which the personnel have purportedly set out to demonstrate, although events speak otherwise. Still, the criticisms do not take away the need for a philosophy to herald what the institutions aspire to be and how to get there which remains paramount, but which they have gone about wrongly. First, constituting new knowledge, the body of literatures reviewed has added to present knowledge in the field of higher education in general and science education in particular. Conceptually, the footprints model offers opportunity to crystallise the multiply complex patterns and processes influencing the higher education mandates. Currently, the lack of such an anchor renders the statements too ethereal and murky to implement.

Complemented by the 'potential learning product' construct, through the footprint pillars of constituency servicing, governance, quality assurance, comportment and evaluation, cross-examined for productivity, marketability, curriculum strength, and transformative role, the model as outlined in Figure 2.1 supplemented by other models (for example, Figure 3.2 and the Sniderman model) calls for new thinking and alternative scaffolding among academic managers and curriculum developers in the furtherance of their respective fields.

Secondly, despite its existence since the late 1990s, the deeper essence and impact of vision-mission statements remains unfamiliar and poorly understood by the bulk of the practitioners and stakeholders in higher education and the research has filled this gap. I, therefore, hope that the study findings will attract other researchers, in particular to study the inroads of the philosophies of technocapitalism and transhumanism and the pending role of academia in their futurization across the Zimbabwean education institutions.

Thirdly, and most importantly, the research offers suggestive evidence for the *pracademic* philosophy to inject the aspirations and imperatives of the mandates to roll out more and better *praxis*-oriented education. The *pracademic* philosophy reflects in the clinical integration of practice and theory in such a way that the practice superintends the theory functionally. Its central thesis is that, given that the bulk of the learned skills, especially decision-making and problem-solving are seldom general and universal, but are situational and occupationally driven, the teaching and learning must ensure better teacher-student adaptation to the practical realities of local conditions and circumstances which can only be forged through practice. Focus is therefore on practice and the immediate and long-term development of that practice (involving the 5Es), rather than plain theory expected to lead to the eventual attainment of the footprint objectives.

Contextually, the *pracademic* name rallies the ‘practice-beyond-theory’ paradigm shift for informed, committed, conscious competence individuals bring to work and learning situations consistent with the evolution of these situations and the problems they create. With the corporatization agenda adding so much complexity to the culturing, both at one and at odds with technocapitalism, like service learning, the *pracademic* culture’s *modus operandi* is: start with the physics or field operations to show how the mathematics or chemistry works, which coalesces favourably with the reality to culture pools of morally efficient *Thinkers, Builders, Improvers* and *Providers* with the requisite psycho-technics to competently solve 21st century African problems.

Central to the *pracademic* model is the ‘m-theme’ to blend the skill frames of the methodology (m) with the lesson themes or psycho-technics so that the products simultaneously acquire and learn how-to: do, generate, develop and apply socio-economic and scientific practices and ideas unperturbed by compulsions, exploitive schemes and curricula pathologies. As the basis for institutional rebranding there is immense potential for edupreneurship for staff and job and entrepreneurship abilities for the learners, simultaneously enhancing practical professionalism. This is echoing Cooper’s (2013, para.5) eloquent observation on the need for curriculum teachers who are always busy

turning old-school curricula on their heads; experimenting with incentives and the demand-side of the education equation; rethinking recruitment, development, and retaining of top education talent, etc. They are showing exactly the boldness, creativity, and impatience with stale truisms that our students need and deserve.

Worley (2015, p.15) strengthens the advantage with pracademics indicating that they “can speak the language of practitioners and community work to help industry put theory into practice; to blend the technical with the behavioural side of the organization, and to teach both the hard and soft skills and help achieve the proper balance” of high-impact dual skills. Since it is a redundant exercise to know all the theory there is, paramount are the practical skills mixtures that influence and re-engineer the concepts, principles and constructs with a bearing on well-baked artisanship skills and other pracademics to nurture individuals and groups that are culture participant within their places and spaces in the context of the societies and cultures the institutions serve and service.

By participating in organized pracademic activities that meet identified community needs, the curriculum simultaneously broadens appreciation and application of the discipline while enhancing learner understanding and comprehension of the course content. Far from being perplexed by the inner spirit of science and technology, the teachers and learners are enthralled by, and resonate with, the technological culture around them to transform the *econogram* for the benefit of all. Meanwhile, there is potential for one of the most desired aspirations: to capacitate key institutional units like the Technopark to work and generate more business for the institution. Perspiration and inspiration are properly matched.

Alongside, drawbacks are characteristic, with power the basis of the inherent opportunity costs that spawn “the intractability of schools to reform” (Torres, et al. 1996, p.19). As Clark (1986, p.203) argues, “where new interests are forces of change in one decade, they become, according to their success in achieving power, sources of rigidity in another”, reflecting the irreconcilable struggle between the divergent forces of power education reformers have to grapple with. With the personnel least exposed to such models, in the midst of the tribulations of material constraints and unsatisfactory conditions of service, implementation challenges always loom large. Coupled with this is the criticism that such curricula models potentially ignore critical democracy and human development issues and, therefore, are likely to escalate potential abuse of learners as experimental guinea pigs and sources of cheap labour. While the bureau-pathology risks the re-entrenchment of Western hegemony and its coterie of challenges as the only known model, in line with the Africa Must Think paradigm, strategy is to dismantle the stultifying bureaucracy in favour of acclimatizing the endogenous models.

7.5 Recommendations

In the face of the challenges, a recommendation that would incorporate both curriculum and management issues would not be an easy proposition. Be that as it may, the study recommends the '*pracademic* sense of mission' conceived both at the wider institutional and personal levels, synthesised in a single statement (word, phrase or sentence) advocating the practice-theory paradigm, cascaded to the product level. The idea is to take advantage of one rather than several statements to work with in line with Campbell and Yeungs' (1991) original idea which makes it easier to administer as well as motivate and direct the stakeholders to cultivate a level of attachment, commitment and accountability not easily attainable across the three statements format. Unlike business which lives the statements 24/7, the institutional position is more intermittent which complicates the three statements approach. Short constructs or frames like 'value addition, practical professionalism, or full employment' ideally integrate and align the host of issues and factors with the national educational philosophy to the satisfaction of all parties.

The personalisation is best secured through individual mottos or *nom de plumes* to inspire and enhance commitment towards productive frameworks. Drawing from the Zimbabwe liberation war, fighters were given 'war' names which served as their (*pracademic*) sense of mission for the effective execution of the war. They inspired sacrifice and solidified teamwork which enhanced commitment. Similarly, straight at entry students identify and 'personalise' their *pracademic* missions in line with the 5Es, while also relating with one another for problem solving. The HIT's 'cause and calling' are along these lines to nurture personalities with appropriately blended psycho-technics for practical enterprise, hence, being more culture participant within their places and spaces. Given the status of the current visions-missions, they are unlikely candidates for the personalization.

From the mission, *nom de plumes* are then distilled in tandem with the philosophy of knowledge fusion. As in trade schools, the target are *skills mixtures* or appropriately blended psycho-technics in terms of well-baked practice-based skills to tackle the technical debt consistent with shifts in singularity – competences that go beyond the mere entrepreneurship rhetoric. From the perspectives of Figure 3.3, the appropriate questions to ask are: what skills mixtures should students learn; how does the theory go with them; and which practical

instructional approaches integrate the two effectively, to ingrain the competences, with group/team projects a useful starting point.

Moving forward, the *pracademic* mission is poised to leverage the requisite skill-frames that advance pragmatic product mandates – significantly engineering applications – to manoeuvre the tough climb the exergy–consumability plateau, a position that continues to elude the institutions by some very wide margin. Each school leaver must have acquired responsible psycho-technics grounded in the 5Es. Stochastic programming and heuristic algorithms hold immense promise. Vision-mission statements or not, curriculum literacy demands a transgressive fortitude undeterred by convention, the fetishism of self-assured paradigms or the dictates of globalisation, etc. It is only when society is so rationally equipped that the principles of the *pracademic* curriculum can be fully realised. The massive waste from intellectual failure to ‘originate’ for the benefit of the country has gone on for far too long.

Aggregated, the knowledge aim was adequately articulated, the results of public policies and programmes measured and accounted for, and the dynamics of *praxis* education and related benefits and concerns understood and strengthened. Accordingly, the research questions were answered and the objectives met, and the overall significance fulfilled. From the evidence, the interpretive scrutiny and insights into higher education management and curriculum issues has contributed empirical literature on the philosophy and science of vision-mission statements in non-market establishments, stakeholders should find a forceful, additive roadmap in their endeavours.

7.6 Recommendations for further research

Given the diversity of the vision-mission philosophy, the study could only be highly selective in its suggestions for further research. Some special and interesting issues stood out which further research can follow to establish validated proofs or otherwise of the philosophy. Among them is the ‘entrepreneurship disconnect’ whether or not it has become a *fait accompli*. Quite common is how it is the bull’s eye for the status quo and for all seeking recognition. Next is the ‘practical applications of the *pracademic* mission model’, especially how the different school levels cater for the 5Es to bring out the best opportunities as well as expose any hidden flaws the original study was unable to fathom, for possible adoption.

Thirdly are 'the dynamics of the bureaucracy dictionary'. It is neither well understood nor publicised as the best or worst operating standard in the whole spectrum of institutional endeavours. It is common knowledge that the octopus has impaired systems more than meets the eye and, yet, scholars continue to shy away from duly cataloguing it. A compilation of its inner dynamics would help unmask its benefits and devastating inroads into higher education management and curriculum matters.

Last, is the 'Proficiency of Africa's Further Education', which, perchance has gone astray or is misdirected! For instance, how much of a mischaracterization is William Easterly's tweet that 'A typical African is more likely to have an advanced degree than to be a victim of famine...', or, Pipim's criticism of the 'gridlocked mind-sets' and the crude insinuation that 'if it is bad, it can only come from Africa' as a result of pathological curricula investments? The fertile ground is crying to be explored.

With so much at stake, scholarly searches would certainly be an advantage to the new thinking and way forward for the Zimbabwean institutions.

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Appendix 1: Samples of vision-mission-values statements 2011-16

Institution	Vision	Mission	Values
Ministry of Higher & Tertiary Education, Science & Technology Development	Guarantee Zimbabwe as a leader in the creation and use of new and existing knowledge, skills, attitudes and resources through the local mobilisation and provision of quality higher and tertiary education	To provide an effective system for the production of patriotic and competent high level manpower through the provision and accreditation of higher and tertiary education programmes and institutions for sustainability and global competitiveness	Patriotism, professionalism, creativity, integrity/hunhu/ubuntu, entrepreneurship, innovativeness, industry, and multicultural tolerance (Source: mhtestd.gov.zw).
Bindura University of Science Education (BUSE)	To be a hub of knowledge and a beacon of excellence in teaching, research and extension services.	To contribute to the advancement of knowledge and its practical application to social, economical, technological, cultural and scientific challenges; to produce innovative, highly acclaimed graduates equipped with research, entrepreneurial, social and technical skills for the benefit of the nation and the international community.	Knowledge Acquisition and Sharing; Teamwork and Diversity; Integrity; Innovation and Excellence; Student Centeredness; Commitment and Discipline (Source: BUSE, Annual Report, 2013)
Chinhoyi University of Technology	To be the world class centre of technological innovation and entrepreneurship.	To produce innovative graduates, create knowledge, enhance entrepreneurship and provide community service through quality teaching, training and technologically-oriented research.	Integrity; Excellence; Dynamism; Entrepreneurship; Democracy; Culture (Source: Chinhoyi Annual Report, 2013)

Harare Institute of Technology	To be the stimulant of scholarship in innovation.	Cause: To cultivate commitment towards technopreneurial leadership; Calling: to commercialise the technology through professionalism rooted in integrity.	Innovation; Leadership; Integrity; Commitment; Professionalism (Source: HIT Annual Report, 2013)
University of Zimbabwe (UZ)	To be (and be recognised by others as) a leading University working for prosperity, peace and dignity in Zimbabwe and beyond	Enabling our clients and customers to make meaningful contributions to sustainable development in Zimbabwe. To this end we provide high quality education, training and advisory services on a needs oriented basis. We guarantee the above by maintaining excellence in Teaching, Learning, Research and Service to the Community.	Knowledge, Diligence, Integrity (Source: uz.ac.zw).
Women's University in Africa	To be the best African university in the promotion of gender equity and equal opportunities in tertiary education.	To provide quality tuition, research and service to the community to empower students for leadership and developmental roles.	Gender Sensitive; Equity & Diversity; Academic Freedom; Creativity & Innovation; Integrity & Honesty; Social Responsibility; Transparency & Accountability (Source: wua.ac.zw)
<i>National University of Science & Technology (2016 Edition)</i>	<i>To be an international centre of excellence in science & Technology & entrepreneurship for sustainable development by 2025</i>	<i>To spearhead human capital development for industrial and socio-economic transformation through science and technology based solutions</i>	<i>Integrity – trust derived from honesty; Innovativeness – developing a culture of creativity by all; Equity – fairness; Excellence – best service; Corporate citizenship – responsiveness to environmental needs; Client-focus – client centeredness</i> (Source: Strategic Plan 2015-20)

<p>Mlezu Agricultural College</p>	<p>To be a leading provider of relevant entrepreneurial graduates, products & services in a responsive manner</p>	<p>To be responsive to the needs of the Zimbabwean agricultural sector through the provision of relevant high quality graduates and services in an innovative, cost effective and sustainable manner. <u>Core Purpose</u> – Production of high quality, self-reliant agricultural graduates; to produce at optimum levels highly marketable products; Engaging in community service delivery to facilitate entrepreneurship in the agricultural sector. <u>Main Objective</u> – The main contributor in the provision of relevant, responsive, entrepreneurial graduates; Operating a thriving and profitable agricultural enterprise that shall be the epitome of the commercialization of agricultural institutions in the country.</p>	<p>Social and national responsibility, Cost consciousness and profitability, Diversity and equal opportunity, Continuous learning and growth, Entrepreneurship and innovation, Team work and collaboration. (Source: mlezuagriccollege.ac.zw)</p>
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Appendix 2. Survey Questionnaire: Q_{A1&2} Senior Academics/Administration

National University of Science and Technology
Faculty of Science and Technology Education
Department of Science, Mathematics and Technology Education

My name is Vincent A Mnkandla. I am a PhD candidate in the Faculty of Science and technology Education, Department of Technical Teacher Education, NUST. I am carrying out a study thesis on **vision, mission, and core values statements**. As you may be aware, the statements are an integral part of policy critical in both the teaching and management of the institutions. It is therefore fitting that institutions constantly question their strategies and standards to maintain, adopt and adapt particular worldviews, practices and experiences. I hereby request you to complete the following questionnaire with respect to your institution's vision-mission statements. You have been selected because of your expertise and potential for day to day interaction with these statements. Your assistance is valued very greatly in that regard.

Instruction: Please, mark the appropriate box and feel free to make additional information/ comments as indicated. Kindly complete by return e-mail to vmnkandla@gmail.com. Your contribution will be treated with the utmost confidentiality for the express purpose of the research and nothing more. Once more, thank you for your assistance, it is greatly appreciated.

Before proceeding to answer the Questionnaire, kindly complete the following details:-

Your gender: Male..... / Female.... Your position/status:.....

Your highest qualification:..... Your duration at the
institution:.....years

The questionnaire consists of a total of 45 statements each to be verified against the following qualitative indicators/criteria:

1. **inadequate/sub-standard** (S/I) to mean that the descriptor or indicator variable was a poor/ invalid measure of the footprint (1);
2. **normal/adequate** (N/A) to mean that the descriptor was a weak and bland measure of the footprint (2);

3. **functional/commendable (F/C)** to mean that the descriptor was a valid measure and positively equated with the footprint (3); and
4. **exceptional/world class (E/W)** to mean that the descriptor was a strongly valid measure that actively boosted the footprint; precisely what the institution wanted, deserved and worked by (4).
5. **Unable to Judge (U/J)** to mean the statement is unusually weak, unknown, irrelevant or difficult to rate.

PLEASE MARK THE APPROPRIATE RATING

Ratings

<i>Constituency Servicing</i>	Inadequate/ Sub-standard	Normal/ Adequate	Functional/ Commendable	Exceptional/ World class	Unable to Judge
1. The institution's mandate to service its constituency is					
2. The graduate competency levels are					
3. The status of leadership is					
4. Entrepreneurship training is					
5. Employment creation is					
6. Human resources development is					
7. The capacity to meet the needs of the constituency/market is					
8. The institution's competitiveness is					
9. The <i>science-technology</i> outcomes are					

<i>Governance</i>	Inadequate/ Sub-standard	Normal/ Adequate	Functional/ Commendable	Exceptional/ World class	Unable to Judge
10. Overall, internal governance matters are					
11. Overall leadership capacity is					
12. More specifically, the strategic plan and related instruments are					
13. The status of the committee system is					
14. The conditions of service are					
15. Public/client relations are					
16. Overall institutional discipline is					
17. Issues of human rights are					
18. Information reporting and disclosure is					
19. Funding is					

20. Procurement and supply chains are					
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<i>Quality Assurance</i>	Inadequate/ Sub-standard	Normal/ Adequate	Functional/ Commendable	Exceptional/ World class	Unable to Judge
21. Quality assurance policy and practice are					
22. The quality of teaching/service delivery is					
23. The quality of the physical infrastructure is					
24. The quality of the academic infrastructure is					
25. Compliance to national policy specifications is					
26. Conditions for continuous improvement are					
27. The library service is					
28. The ICT support service is					
29. The examination support service is					
30. The level of other support services is					
31. The transfer of technological innovations and inventions is					
32. The institution's local ranking is					

<i>Comportment</i>	Inadequate/ Sub-standard	Normal/ Adequate	Functional/ Commendable	Exceptional/ World class	Unable to Judge
33. Aggregated, the core values are					
34. Student attitudes and conduct are					
35. Professionalism among staff is					
36. Prospects for a moral community within and outside the institution are					
37. Humanitarian services within the institutional community are					
38. The relationship between the core values and the workplace values is					
39. Democracy and institution-building are					

<i>Evaluation</i>	Inadequate/ Sub-standard	Normal/ Adequate	Functional/ Commendable	Exceptional/ World class	Unable to Judge
40. The policy on evaluation and related measures is					
41. The status of academic reviews, institutional audits and assessments is					
42. Given its vision-mission and values, the future of the institution is					

43. The status of the Global Sustainability Initiative Framework (GSIF) is					
44. The institution's global ranking is					
45. Evaluations, impact assessments and institutional reporting are					

Additional information/comments:

Thank you for your contribution

Appendix 3. The Interview Guide Q_{A2}: Senior Academics and Administrators

Instruction: Kindly complete by return e-mail to vmnkandla@gmail.com. Your contribution will be treated with the utmost confidentiality for the express purpose of the research and nothing more. Once more, your participation is greatly appreciated; thank you for your assistance.

Answer the following questions (with explanations) in the spaces provided.

- 1 What was/is the justification for adopting the current vision-mission-core values statements? (What lay behind its adoption)
- 2 What practical steps enhance the workings of the statements?
- 3 What are your personal views on the viability of the vision-mission-core values statements?
- 4 Vision-mission statements are criticised as a 'fad' or '*fait accompli*', what is your take on this?
- 5 What challenges hinder the implementation of the vision-mission-core values statements?
- 6 Do the vision-mission-core values statements play a role in the transformation of science and technology education?
- 7 If you were to change the vision-mission-core values statements of the institution, what would you add or subtract or what alternative would you propose? Explain.
- 8 Is there some additional information about vision-mission statements you would like to bring to the attention of the study?

Appendix 4. Graduate output data 2011-2014

Disciplinary category	2014	2013	2012	2011
(Applied) Sciences	524	383	300	174
Industrial and Engineering Technology	395	222	274	193
Medicine		1		
Environmental Science and Health, Forestry and Wildlife	260	188	75	108
Information Science and Technology	198	113	30	18
Agricultural Science	45	118	87	40
The Built Environment	84	116	50	72
Science and Technology Education	220	139	63	73
Sports Science	53	16	5	13
Other science and technology disciplines (Electronic Commerce, Financial Engineering, HIV and AIDS)	111	151	69	74
Totals	1890	1447	953	765